

IMMERSIVE VIRTUAL REALITY AS A
PEDAGOGICAL TOOL IN HIGHER EDUCATION:
A STUDY OF USER ATTITUDES AND LEARNING
OUTCOMES

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*For Mum, Dad, Andrew,
and Meghan*

*“In the long run, the secret of study resides in our ability to bathe our thought, our task,
our lesson in the stream of interest.”*

Francis Lockwood, 1913.

DECLARATION

This thesis is the result of my own work and includes nothing, which is the outcome of work done in collaboration except where specifically indicated in the text. It has not been previously submitted, in part or whole, to any university or institution for any degree, diploma, or other qualification.

I confirm that this thesis conforms to the UWS Doctoral College Code of Practice, as well as Chapter 4 of the Regulatory Framework for Research Degrees.

Signed

A solid black rectangular box redacting the signature of the author.

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ABSTRACT

The introduction of virtual reality (VR) technology has the potential to challenge the very conceptual definition of what constitutes an educational experience. Allowing students to embody the first-hand perspective of another person, or experience environments and situations outside of the traditional everyday gives an insight into its pedagogical potential. Despite this, applied research into the practical and logistical considerations associated with VR implementation has been lacking. Although experimental research has demonstrated that VR has the potential to facilitate knowledge acquisition, these have tended to be confined to isolated laboratory studies with little insight as to how the technology can be successfully integrated in higher education (HE).

This thesis presents a multiphase design consisting of six original studies exploring the pedagogical application of VR in HE. The first study is a comprehensive systematic review that evaluates the effectiveness of educational VR interventions, and the attitudes of students towards them. The following two qualitative studies investigate the practical considerations associated with applying VR among instructors experienced and inexperienced with the technology. After determining the feasibility of integrating VR in HE, two subsequent qualitative studies explore the perception of students towards its applied application. The final study is a mixed-methods experiment comparing learning outcomes and attitudes between two competing modes of VR presentation, experiential and non-experiential/didactic, based on preceding results and implications.

The thesis aims to achieve a deeper understanding of the potential benefits and limitations of VR in HE. It provides insights into the practical considerations and perceptions of both instructors and students towards VR as a pedagogical tool. Additionally, it investigates the effectiveness of different modes of VR presentation, providing implications for future VR design and implementation. Overall, this thesis provides a comprehensive and multifaceted exploration of pedagogical VR, providing both theoretical and practical insight for educators and researchers.

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All Digital Supplementary Material referenced in this thesis is available to download as a ZIP File from the Open Science Framework:

https://osf.io/zpxws/?view_only=78b5f8f09f2e4bd48e6b53b9f3fc0903

1 INTRODUCTION TO THE THESIS

1.1 An Educational Revolution?

Lecture theatres will be built from code, not from bricks and mortar. Students will be transported through time and space to undergo experiences deemed unimaginable just a few years ago. Virtual learners, separated by oceans and continents will collaborate as if they were next to one another. Yes, the “metaverse is virtual, but the impact will be real” (Meta, 2022). Indeed, such claims might lead many to believe the halcyon days of education are upon us. No longer constrained by traditional pedagogical environments, VR represents a seismic shift in how education can be offered to students and is changing the very definition of what constitutes a learning environment. The disruption caused by the COVID-19 pandemic has only accelerated the innovation in developing new and exciting technologies to engage learners in novel educational experiences. Reporting from Davos in 2022, the World Economic Forum announced that VR constituted a “force of change” in the educational sector, and would reshape how teaching is delivered on an unparalleled scale.

Companies like Meta have unquestionably invested significant capital, expertise, and research in pursuing pedagogical VR (Dincelli & Yayla, 2022; Han et al., 2022). Undoubtedly, this has bolstered the view that we stand on a technological and educational precipice, with immersive technologies set to revolutionise how we

conceptualise and define education. However, is technological advancement in graphical fidelity and sophistication sufficient for widescale adoption of such technology? If the hype is to be taken at face value, it almost certainly is. Video advertisements show groups of educators and students seamlessly interact with VR applications through collaboration, embodied experience, and novel visualisation (see, Meta, 2022; Microsoft, 2021).

Not only does VR promise to be a vehicle for driving pedagogical innovation in terms of providing novel education experiences. As Rospigliosi (2022) suggests, VR will also be the “gateway” to accessing the Metaverse, an interconnected virtual world facilitating interaction and collaboration every bit as salient as reality. Here, the boundaries that separate individual brick and mortar establishments will cease to exist. Millions of students and teachers will be able to share ideas, collaborate, and learn on an unprecedented global scale through virtual interaction (see, Hedrick et al., 2022; Lin et al., 2022). Perhaps even the idea of distinct or individual institutions will become redundant, as educators and students join a universal pedagogical community. Needless to say, this would constitute the greatest shift in educational provision in human history.

As a consequence of this new educational paradigm, the role of both students and instructors could fundamentally change. As already alluded to, students may no longer be required to attend in-person classes, but rather have the freedom to access high-quality material from anywhere they choose. Indeed, hybrid VR lectures in the metaverse have already been conducted by UK universities (see, Queen Mary University, 2022). In response to this change, the roles and responsibilities of educators would also fundamentally shift. With less emphasis on traditional didactic means of academic delivery (e.g., lectures, seminars), instructors would instead become facilitators of learning, using the novel toolsets to encourage inquiry. The question of whether traditional didactic lecture still have a place in HE was brought sharply into focus during the COVID-19 pandemic (e.g., Teichgräber et al., 2021), and technical innovation in the field of education will do nothing to quell this scrutiny. Could VR be the catalyst for this change?

If indeed VR is set to revolutionise education, instructors will want to know precisely *what* it can provide to them and their students. The work of Veronica Pantelidis gives even the most unacquainted an insight into VR's possibilities. In fact, she remarks that the potential applications are almost limitless. Exploring inaccessible locations, interacting with virtual avatars, and manipulating abstract variables will offer students unparalleled opportunities for learning in the here and now. However, there is a glaring issue that should now be raised. This imminent promise of a new educational tomorrow was first touted over thirty years ago (Pantelidis, 1993). Since then, multiple generations of school, college, and university students have passed through the doors of academia without having ever touched a VR headset. Are the contemporary promises of VR companies today any closer to fruition than they were in the early 1990s? Or is VR once again destined to rouse the imagination, yet never gain a foothold as a pedagogical mainstay?

Ultimately, media hype must give way to an honest investigation and scrutinization of VR's place within education. This means a thorough examination of the willingness of both educators and students to adopt such technology, and for what purpose. The many practical considerations too must be realised as potential impediments and barriers to successful integration. Indeed, flashy advertisements seldom show the less glamorous realities of obtaining funding to buy headsets or solving the logistical nightmare of room bookings or timetabling to accommodate VR lessons. However, an investigation of such factors and the practical recommendations that come with it are essential aspects in obtaining a balanced perspective of such technology.

Does this concerted drive towards VR adoption represent the start of a pedagogical revolution as so many have promised (see, Hedrick et al., 2022; Lin et al., 2022; Rospigliosi, 2022)? It very well might. But such assertions must be based on a careful examination of the evidence, and not on media hype. It must account for the attitudes and perspectives of those who will eventually facilitate its use, the teachers and students. And finally, it must make practical and applied recommendations to help accommodate the

seamless integration of such technology into the education sphere. Ultimately, these are the factors that this thesis endeavours to investigate.

1.2 Thesis Aims and Objectives

In the evolving landscape of contemporary education, the integration of VR technology emerges as a pivotal area of exploration which could redefine and revolutionise how education is delivered. This thesis aims to critically evaluate the ambitious assertions made by many VR companies, which herald VR as a revolutionary force in education. Such claims, often characterised by their optimistic portrayal of VR's potential, raise pertinent questions regarding their empirical substantiation and pragmatic feasibility. This inquiry is particularly relevant in the context of HE, where the integration of novel technologies must be balanced against logistical considerations and the readiness of educational institutions to embrace change and innovation.

The primary objective of this thesis is to provide a comprehensive examination of VR's applicability and effectiveness as a pedagogical tool in HE. To achieve this, the research is structured around a multiphase design, comprising six original studies that collectively address the pedagogical deployment of VR. An integral part of this thesis is the critical evaluation of the enthusiastic pronouncements surrounding VR's impact on education. It seeks to discern whether these claims are grounded in evidence or are merely a consequence of media hyperbole. In addition, it seeks to examine whether the expectations of VR's integration are realistic, or overlook the complexities of applied practice. By engaging with these questions, the research aims to contribute to a more grounded and critical discourse on the adoption of emerging technologies in education, emphasising the importance of empirical evidence over speculative enthusiasm.

Moreover, this thesis endeavours to bridge the gap between theoretical research and practical application. It is predicated on the belief that the value of academic research lies not only in its contribution to theoretical knowledge but also in its ability to inform and improve practice. Consequently, a significant aim is to translate the findings from

theoretical and empirical research into actionable recommendations for educators, policymakers, and VR designers. These recommendations are intended to facilitate the purposeful integration of VR into HE, ensuring that its deployment is pedagogically sound and aligned with educational objectives. By adopting a mixed-methods approach, the research combines qualitative insights into the perceptions and experiences of educators and learners with quantitative evaluations of learning outcomes. This methodological eclecticism enables a comprehensive examination of VR's educational role, encompassing both its potential to enhance student outcomes, and the practical considerations and challenges of its implementation.

1.2.1 Theoretical and Empirical Contributions

By investigating the pedagogical implications of VR in HE, this thesis makes a range of theoretical and empirical contributions to knowledge. Across six studies, this project undertakes a thorough examination of VR's pedagogical applications, its effects on learning outcomes, and the perceptions of both students and instructors. Furthermore, it delves into the distinction between contrasting modes of VR presentation and experience. A key theoretical thread that runs throughout this work is the consideration of both student *and* instructor attitudes in tandem. This thesis represents the first time that an integrated theoretical framework examining both groups has been considered within a larger multiphase design. Indeed, the Educational VR System Model (see, Alfalah, 2018; Alfalah et al., 2017, 2018) allows for this project to consider the symbiotic relationship between students and instructors in the context of utilising VR in HE. Consequently, this thesis is able to provide specific recommendations for applied practice that consider the perspectives of both groups.

From a methodological standpoint, this thesis represents a considered effort to reframe the conversation around how educational VR is evaluated and conceptualised. Specifically, it recommends moving beyond simple media comparison studies, and instead exploring integration strategies that emphasise the value of concepts like embodiment in providing novel insights for students. From an early stage in the research process (i.e., the systematic review in Chapter 4), it became evident that the main contribution of this thesis was not to substantiate whether VR *should be used*, but rather, explore *how* it can be used. Consequently, a fundamental recommendation of this

research is to employ VR to complement existing modes of education. This is particularly prudent in subjects where direct experience or deep reflective understanding is crucial (e.g., psychology). By using VR, students had the opportunity to embody the lived experience of another person, giving them unprecedented insight into topics such as clinical and mental health. Not only did students demonstrate that this could facilitate better learning outcomes, but it also encouraged holistic and tangential motivation in a way that traditional methods of education did not.

In addition, this thesis also stresses the essential role of educators in the successful integration of VR. Indeed, these more practical and logistical concerns have often been neglected in previous applied research (see, Smith & Southgate, 2017). Specifically, this thesis gathered a diverse range of attitudes, opinions, and perspectives ranging from enthusiastic endorsement to cautious scepticism. These findings suggest that the effectiveness of VR is contingent upon its careful integration as a supplement to existing methods, rather than a standalone educational “panacea.” Such an endeavour requires a concerted effort at all levels of the educational hierarchy, from individual lecturers and instructors to policymakers and management.

This research delves into the factors influencing educators’ willingness to adopt VR, such as its perceived educational value, logistical hurdles, and institutional challenges (e.g., financial barriers). By carefully considering the prerequisites for successful VR integration in HE, this thesis provides valuable insights into technology enhanced learning. It makes applied recommendations for implementation that focuses on curriculum alignment, accessibility of technology, and facilitator support. This strategy aims to create an environment conducive to VR teaching methods, ensuring that its incorporation is both educationally advantageous and logistically feasible. Overall, the theoretical and empirical contributions presented in this thesis represent progress in examining and assessing the role of VR within HE environments and beyond.

1.3 Thesis Structure

In the proceeding chapter, a background to the research area is provided. The aim is to equip the reader with the foundational and fundamental knowledge necessary to engage with the later empirical chapters. Chapter 3 provides an in-depth exploration of the various methodological considerations that informed the research approach taken throughout this thesis.

Chapter 4 introduces the first empirical study, assessing VR's impact on learning outcomes through a comprehensive systematic review. This examines both quantitative learning outcomes, and qualitative perspectives relating to student attitudes. Chapter 5 and 6 present qualitative explorations of instructors' attitudes towards VR integration. These utilised both semi-structured interviews and online focus-groups to gain a deep and nuanced understanding of how educators conceptualise VR's place within educational settings.

In Chapters 7 and 8, the focus shifts to investigating the attitudes of students towards educational VR. By implementing practical suggestions from the preceding studies, VR was integrated into two predefined psychology modules. This allowed for a natural evaluation of how students engaged and conceptualised the technology in an applied setting. The final empirical contribution in Chapter 9 features a mixed-methods study, comparing experiential and non-experiential VR modes and their effects on learning outcomes and student attitudes.

The concluding chapter synthesises the overall research findings, offering a critical reflection on VR's pedagogical implications and its potential to transform educational practices.

2 BACKGROUND

2.1 A Brief History of VR

The ability to define and conceptualise the origins of VR is an elusive and challenging one. As far back as the 1830s with the invention of the first stereoscopes, there has existed the capacity to provide viewers with depth cues in static images (Parker, 1983). This primitive technology allowed for the illusion of immersion and presence in an environment where hand-drawn images and static photographs were presented as imitations of reality. It was not until 1962 that Morton Heilig created one of the first multisensory VR simulators. The technology which was initially entitled “The Experience Theatre” became known as the “Sensorama” when it was constructed and exhibited in the early 1960s (Mazuryk & Gervautz, 1996). The simulator displayed a wide-angle perspective of a motorcycle ride through New York City in three-dimensions and full colour (rare, since colour displays did not become common until at least the mid-1960’s). Additionally, the Sensorama tracked the on-screen display to tilt and manipulate the body of the participant, whilst also providing surround sound and jets of air to simulate wind (Rheingold, 1991). This proprioceptive and tracking ability would not become common place in VR for almost another half-century (Kardong-Edgren et al., 2019).

One of the most ubiquitous and instantly recognisable features of VR is the use of headsets, or head-mounted-displays (HMD), to display stereoscopic 3D imagery. Although the development of HMDs can be traced back to the early 1960s, the “Sword of Damocles” VR system invented in 1968 by Ivan Sutherland is widely considered the most important and influential predecessor to modern HMD systems (Boas, 2013). Although Sutherland’s HMD could only display simple wireframe graphics, its use of early computing technology, head-tracking, and innovative display system was instrumental in demonstrating that three-dimensional images could be manipulated in real-time depending on the actions and movement of the user (Sutherland, 1968). In the decades that followed, the production and application of HMDs focused almost exclusively on the potential training benefits of utilising VR. For instance, The Visually Coupled Airborne

Systems Simulator (VCASS) was developed in 1982 as a HMD-based flight simulator to assist US Air Force pilots. In addition, The Virtual Interface Environment Workstation (VIEW) was used by NASA in aeronautical training of its astronauts (Mazuryk & Gervautz, 1996).

It was not until the early 2010s that the first HMDs started to become commercially viable for consumers and educators (Lyne, 2013). Until this point, the cost of HMDs and the associated computational hardware required to run it was beyond the scope of most individuals. However, with the release of the Oculus Rift Development Kit (DK1) in August 2012, households, small businesses, and educational institutions could acquire powerful VR headsets *en masse*. Early adoption tended to be centred around medical and surgical simulations that allowed students to practice procedural skills without harm to themselves or others (Li et al., 2017). However, other subjects and domains such as engineering, mathematics, and biology also realised that VR could offer a degree of novel visualisation that would assist student comprehension (e.g., Barahimi & Wismath, 2014; Lartigue et al., 2014).

Since then, there has been an influx of HMDs, each offering unique specifications and features such as hand tracking, motion detection, and haptic feedback. This has ranged from accessible low-cost mobile headsets like the Google Cardboard (see, Lee et al., 2017), to powerful untethered options such as the Oculus Quest 2. Although these products have generally been geared towards the gaming and entertainment market (see, Grand View Research, 2017), there has also been an increased interest in how these new technologies and features can be integrated in education (Jensen & Konradsen, 2018). Consequently, it is imperative that such educational application is justified and guided by sound research and evidence, ensuring that VR's application is evidence-based and informed.

2.2 Core Principles and Affordances

Just as the ability to define VR's origin is a challenging one, so is the capacity to authoritatively characterise its key features and components. Although it can be argued that VR can trace its origins back to the early stereoscopes of the 1800's, it was not until 1987 that the philosopher and computer scientist Jaron Lanier coined the term, "virtual reality" (Satava, 2008). As Jensen and Konradsen (2018) highlight, the interdisciplinary nature of VR research and application has resulted in a poorly defined taxonomy and nomenclature of key terms. In the decades before and after Lanier's coining of the phrase "virtual reality," researchers have used a myriad of terms to describe similar or wildly divergent applications: "virtual reality", "virtual world", "three-dimensional experiences", "artificial environments", and "simulations", to name a just a handful (Mazuryk & Gervautz, 1996). The result is a confusing and muddled literature where disparate technologies, applications, software, and hardware are all grouped under the same umbrella term, "virtual reality," despite often sharing little in common. The fast moving and multi-disciplinary nature of VR research has often resulted in the technology being coarsely defined in research, and this necessitates that researchers are more explicit in how they define and conceptualise the technology in future. As a result, a conscious attempt has been made throughout this thesis to concisely define what is meant by "VR" and its associated experiences. The proceeding sections introduce some of the core principles of VR technology, before an explicit conceptual definition of the technology is offered for the purposes of this thesis.

As a result of the diverse nature of the terminology, researchers have attempted to standardise and define the core tenets of VR. Kardong-Edgren and colleagues (2019) attempted to examine and review how the technology has been conceptualised in previous research, thus making recommendations for future published work. The review identified more than 15 different definitions of VR and its associated factors (e.g., presence, immersion). These range from antiquated descriptions about rendering depictions of reality on 2D computer monitors (see, Sheridan, 1996; Steuer, 1992), to contemporary definitions associated with "immersive, highly visual, 3D characteristics that allow the participant to look about and navigate [with] head-mounted-displays" (Lopreiato et al., 2020, p. 40).

As these previous definitions exemplify, VR has often been associated and conceptualised with its mode of presentation (e.g., desktop computer screen, HMD). However, there are several issues with taking this broad approach. Firstly, the fast-moving nature of VR development can render a conceptual definition obsolete in a short space of time. For example, few of the concepts that Steuer (1992) and Sheridan (1996) define as “VR” stand-up to much scrutiny today (e.g., using Cathode Ray Tube [CRT] computer screens). Secondly, as researchers have started to realise (e.g., Jensen & Konradsen, 2018) a constant need to define and redefine novel technology can lead to a muddled and confusing literature with little agreement in terminology or specifications. A prime example of this very issue is contained within this thesis. Specifically, over 9000 original articles were examined as part of the systematic review in Chapter Three to ensure comprehensive capture of the literature.

2.2.1 A Contemporary Understanding of VR Principles

What is needed is a contemporary definition of VR that covers the myriad of disparate applications, systems, and technologies. Fortunately, work by researchers such as Miller and Bugnariu (2016) and Kardong-Edgren et al. (2019) has attempted to do exactly that. Rather than defining VR primarily through its mode of presentation, they have instead defined VR by its two primary core principles: “presence” and “immersion.” Although these two concepts are often used interchangeably, they do in fact represent distinct and separate domains of the virtual experience. It is important to recognise both ideas as separate concepts, whilst also understanding how they interact with one another. “Immersion” is a technical term, and relates to the features of a particular system (e.g., 360° visuals in a HMD) that gives the participant the illusion that they are in a virtual space (Kardong-Edgren et al., 2019; Miller & Bugnariu, 2016). On the other hand, “presence” is a psychological and experiential concept that relates to how subjectively present the user feels in that given environment (Wilkinson et al., 2021). High levels of immersion (the technical component) should therefore result in the psychological feeling that the participant is “part of” the environment, often with a reduced awareness of the real-world around them (Mestre & Fuchs, 2006; Slater, 2018). A diagram illustrating this relationship between technical immersion and psychological presence can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1

Relationship between immersion and subjective presence

2.2.1.1 Immersion in Virtual Environments

The works of both Kardong-Edgren et al. (2019) and Miller and Bugnariu (2016) are instructive when trying to understand the principles of “immersion.” Rather than seeing these concepts as predefined or static, Miller and Bugnariu (2016) have tried to position them on a continuum, comprised of numerous factors or aspects. According to Miller and Bugnariu (2016), there are five technical aspects that can be grouped under the overarching principle of immersion. These are: (a) inclusiveness; (b) extensiveness; (c) surrounding; (d) vividness; and (e) proprioception matching. Each technical aspect can either be defined as being either low, medium, or high in immersion. For example, *extensiveness* (b) is an immersive aspect that relates to how many modalities the virtual

system targets. A Desktop-VR simulation that can only be viewed on a 2D screen would be classed as providing a “low” level of immersion (targets only the visual modality). On the other hand, a HMD that provides 360° visuals and sound, limb proprioception, motor cues, and haptic feedback would be deemed to be very extensive (multiple-modalities), and would therefore be classed as providing a “high” level of immersion. These same ideas can be applied to different aspects of Miller and Bugnariu’s (2016) classification.

The idea of defining VR on the continuum of its constituent factors (e.g., immersion) seems to be gaining traction in the scientific community (see, Slater, 2009). For instance, writing in the *British Journal of Psychology*, Slater (2018) dispensed with the notion that there can be a one-size-fits-all definition of VR. Rather, concepts like immersion must be evaluated by the degree in which it “support(s) natural sensorimotor contingencies for perception” (Slater, 2018, p. 432). Simply, VR systems that can more accurately replicate natural cognitive inputs should be regarded as more immersive than those that do not. Therefore, the immersive component of VR can be defined as a system that utilises its technical specifications to replicate normal sensory input. The degree to which it achieves this feat will ultimately determine whether its technical immersion is either low, medium, or high.

2.2.1.2 The Illusion of Presence

According to Draper et al. (1998), presence (also referred to as “telepresence”) is a psychological and mental state where the participant feels physically present and involved in a computer generated environment. More contemporary theories have attempted to expand on this early conceptualisation. For instance, Roettl and Terlutter (2018) described the phenomenon of presence as the subjective appraisal of being in a virtual space as opposed to a real one. And both Slater (2018) and Wilkinson et al. (2021) refer to the common trope of presence being the illusion of “being there” (in the virtual environment), whilst at the same time acknowledging that you are not. What these definitions have in common is that presence represents a psychological and experiential dimension where a participant will feel actively and presently involved in the artificial environment (see, Pan & Hamilton, 2018; Slater, 2018; Wilkinson et al., 2021).

However, these rather coarse definitions may fail to provide an appreciation of the complex nature of presence in VR. Specifically, they say little about the affordances of VR technology itself, and how the psychological phenomenon of “being there” can facilitate such experiences. The work of Mel Slater and colleagues is instructive in providing a more nuanced understanding of the role of presence in VR, and how the continually evolving nature of the technology facilitates ever more sophisticated experiences (see, Slater, 2009; Slater et al., 2022). Namely, this theoretical insight focuses on two components contributing to the sensation of presence: Place Illusion (PI) and Plausibility Illusion (Psi). PI refers to the feeling of being in a real place, whilst Psi involves the illusion that the scenarios being depicted are really occurring. Slater (2009) argues that both PI and Psi are essential for user to respond realistically in VR, despite the awareness that they are not actually present in that environment. Furthermore, subsequent work by Slater and colleagues (2022) builds upon this understanding by presenting a multifaceted construct influenced by VR’s ability to support sensorimotor contingencies and the credibility of its scenarios. Specifically, in the decade since its original inception, Slater’s perspective has evolved to consider a more integrated view of presence, accounting for technological advancements and their impact on the user’s psychological and behavioural responses. This evolution signifies a shift from defining presence through specific illusions to a more holistic understanding of how various elements interact to create a convincing and impactful VR experience (Slater, 2009; Slater et al., 2022).

PI is more specifically concerned with the spatial aspect of presence – the convincing sensation of being located in a different place from one’s physical location. Achieving PI involves a complex interplay of technological fidelity and psychological factors (see, Skarbez et al., 2017; Slater, 2009; Slater et al., 2022). From a technical standpoint, high-quality visual and auditory rendering, responsive and naturalistic interaction mechanisms, and accurate motion tracking are foundational (Skarbez et al., 2017). These elements work together to mimic the natural sensorimotor contingencies that humans experience in the real world. For instance, the visual field should change seamlessly as the user rotates their head, and sounds should shift in accordance with one’s movements in the virtual space. On a psychological level, PI is enhanced when the virtual environment aligns with the user’s expectations based on their real-world experiences. This involves

creating environments that adhere to real-world physics and logic. Additionally, the inclusion of interactive elements that respond in a realistic manner further strengthens the illusion.

Next, it is crucial to understand why PI is central to the notion of virtual presence. Primarily, PI amplifies the impression of immersion, which is pivotal to the evaluation of VR applications irrespective of domain (e.g., entertainment, education). Once users perceive themselves to be truly “transported” to a different environment, their engagement and emotional reactions tend to mirror those seen in genuine situations (Škola et al., 2020). For instance, Kisker et al. (2021) demonstrated that the integration of environmental and haptic signals could stimulate physiological responses akin to those experienced during real-life interactions. Secondly, solid PI often results in elevated user satisfaction coupled with more intense experiences. In the context of entertainment, for instance, a convincing PI can change an ordinary game or virtual tour into a powerful, engrossing, and emotionally salient event (e.g., Bujčić et al., 2020; Herrera et al., 2018).

Previous empirical research has examined the role that PI plays in the subjective evaluation of VR experiences. For example, VR environments characterised by elevated levels of sensory authenticity and congruency generate a higher perception of PI. A study conducted by Kim and Lee (2022) examined the relationship between audio-visual cue correspondence and cognition within VR contexts. Their findings suggest that harmonious integration of multisensory inputs significantly amplifies participants’ sensation of presence and immersion in VR. Furthermore, research in fields such as psychology and education demonstrate that heightened PI is associated with more effective learning outcomes and therapeutic results. For instance, in exposure therapy, VR environments that successfully create a robust sense of PI can elicit reactions similar to real-life exposure, aiding in the treatment of phobias and anxiety disorders (e.g., Gromer et al., 2018). In addition, empirical data derived from psychophysiological measures (e.g., heart rate and galvanic skin response) during VR exposure substantiate the link between PI and the corresponding emotional engagement (see, Dey et al., 2020; Diemer et al., 2016). These results underscore the importance of designing VR

environments that are not merely visually interesting, but also align with the subjective anticipations and experiential backgrounds of users.

Place Illusion focuses on the proverbial “where” aspect of the virtual experience. Its concern is in making the user feel as if they are occupying a different plane of reality. Conversely, Psi focuses on ensuring that what happens within this virtual environment is consistent and believable. While PI can be achieved through technological means like high-quality graphics and effective sensory input systems, Psi requires a deep understanding of human psychology and meta-cognition. This concept is crucial for creating a deeply engaging VR experience as it influences how users emotionally and cognitively engage with the technology (see, Slater, 2009; Slater et al., 2022). Psi plays a pivotal role in various applications of VR, especially when the effectiveness of the experience is predicated on the viewers' belief in its plausibility. This notion of Psi finds its foundation within theoretical paradigms associated with immersion, suspense of disbelief, and cognition. Consequently, fostering a sense of Psi becomes essential for VR developers striving to optimise the impact and utility of their experiences.

The concept of Psi is rooted in several theoretical frameworks. One key underpinning has already been covered extensively in this chapter; namely that of “presence.” Presence is a precursor to Psi, as a user must first feel present in the virtual environment before finding it plausible (Slater et al., 2022). For example, Rovira et al. (2009) and Slater et al. (2013) conducted a series of studies in VR where participants watched a fight erupt in a London bar between opposing football supporters. However, in early versions of the study, participants commented that they did not feel that the decorations and interior of the virtual bar were congruent with the type of establishment that football fans would frequent. Consequently, they did not feel that the virtual space was a realistic representation of a “football bar,” impacting the believability that such a scenario would occur within that specific space.

Another theoretical framework is the “suspension of disbelief,” which is borrowed from the field of literature and film. Just as audiences willingly overlook the unrealistic aspects

of a book or movie so as to enjoy the narrative, users in VR must suspend their disbelief to fully engage with the experience (see, Böcking, 2008; Muckler, 2017). This is closely tied to Psi, as the more plausible the environment and its events are, the easier it is for users to suspend their disbelief. This is especially pertinent in the realm of VR due to its locomotion and movement aspect. A review by Holland (2007) underscores the neurological importance of motor activity in “reality testing”. When watching a film requiring no explicit locomotion, this “reality testing” is bypassed, allowing the audience to momentarily believe in the plausibility of the events unfolding. However, many VR experiences are not static in nature, and require active and engaged participation on the part of the user. Consequently, these findings highlight the importance of creating a plausible and believable virtual world for the participant to interact within.

Finally cognitive psychology is essential in comprehending and understanding Psi. Cognitive processes influence how users view, comprehend, and engage with the virtual world. To produce a credible VR experience, components such as interactive feedback, logical consistency, and narrative coherence must match the user's cognitive expectations (see Slater, 2009, 2018; Slater et al., 2022). In reality, these cognitive aspects support fundamental affordances of VR technology, like embodiment and empathetic elicitation, which will be discussed in more detail in the proceeding sections.

The interplay between PI and Psi is crucial because it significantly influences the user's sense of immersion and engagement. If a virtual environment excels in PI but lacks Psi, the user may feel present in a space that is otherwise lifeless or artificial due to an unconvincing narrative. On the other hand, high Psi combined with low PI might result in a plausible environment that the user does not feel a part of (see to Slater et al.'s [2022] analysis of Rovira et al. [2009]). To persuade users that the virtual environment is authentic—both in terms of its physical depiction and the way interactions and events unfold inside it—both of these concepts must operate in tandem. As such, equal consideration should be given to both theories to achieve a genuinely immersive and effective VR experience.

As the technical specifications of VR systems continue to advance, the levels of presence possible will only increase (see, Shu et al., 2018; Slater, 2018; Vesisenaho et al., 2019). Again, this supports Slater (2018) and Kardong-Edgren et al.'s (2019) conceptualisation of VR as non-static and dynamic. Ultimately, any collection of systems that attempt to elicit an experience of “being” in a virtual space can conceivably be categorised as VR. Consequently, the plethora of divergent terms or taxonomies may not be the central problem. Rather, it is how coarsely these definitions have been described and presented in previous literature that has resulted in confusion. As Kardong-Edgren and colleagues (2019) allude to, this necessitates that researchers are far more deliberate and methodical in how *they* define VR in future. Indeed, a detailed conceptual definition of VR within the context of this thesis is provided later in the chapter.

2.2.2 Embodiment and Body-Ownership

In the previous sections, this thesis has provided a comprehensive overview of the contemporary understanding of immersion and presence in VR. Specifically, the work of Slater and colleagues (see, Slater, 2009, 2018; Slater et al., 2022) has demonstrated the complementary nature of PI and Psi in creating the illusion of being physically present in virtual environments. Not only should the implications of body-ownership be considered in relation to the subjective appraisal of presence, but also what the experience of embodiment itself can facilitate.

Embodiment is a phenomenon where a user feels that a virtual body or avatar is their own (Slater et al., 2022). This is typically achieved through the integration of multisensory information, where visual, auditory, and haptic feedback are aligned with the user's movements and interactions (see, the "Bodily Self-Consciousness Model" proposed by Blanke et al., 2015). Specifically, when viewers inhabit a virtual body from a first-person perspective, and observe it move in synchronicity, they begin to perceive it as their own (Petkova & Ehrsson, 2008). An intriguing affordance of VR technology is that it can facilitate this illusion of body-ownership even when the embodied avatar is significantly different from the viewer. For instance, Slater and colleagues (2022) highlights that VR can facilitate strong ownership even when the users is of a different racial background (e.g., Banakou et al., 2016), age (e.g., Banakou et al., 2013), or gender identity (Slater et al., 2010) than the embodied character. Further, research conducted by

Osimo et al. (2015) demonstrated that subjective body ownership in virtual environments is not significantly influenced by the visual congruence between participants' actual physical appearance and their virtual avatar. The study compared levels of subjective ownership of a virtual body that closely resembled the participant's real appearance with that of an avatar that was markedly different. No significant differences in subjective ownership levels were observed across contrasting virtual embodiments. These findings suggest that a diverse array of avatar designs can successfully induce a sense of body-ownership, allowing users to experience the lived reality of another (see, Döllinger et al., 2022).

It is also important to understand why embodiment represents such an intriguing utilisation of immersive technologies by considering its psychological and cognitive impact. In scenarios where adults embody a diminutive virtual form, such as that of a child, they perceive their environment differently. For instance, Banakou et al. (2013) found that adults in child-like virtual bodies perceived their surroundings as larger, approximately twice the size than when in an adult-sized equivalent. This suggests that it is not just the physical dimensions but the overall configuration of the embodied form that alters perception, pointing to a deep cognitive integration of virtual and physical selves.

Embodiment and body-ownership in VR also has profound implications for psychological and behavioural responses. For example, Caucasian individuals embodying a darker-skinned virtual avatar exhibit diminished implicit racial bias after a VR intervention (see, Banakou et al., 2016; Bedder et al., 2019). Furthermore, research by Hasler et al. (2017) demonstrated that these experiences could also facilitate changes in social and cognitive processing by influencing real-world behaviours and attitudes. These findings have been replicated in numerous studies examining VR's ability to facilitate socio-cognitive change through body-ownership. For example, Seinfeld et al. (2018) demonstrated that male perpetrators of domestic violence changed their perceptual processing through embodiment of a female avatar. Similarly, Neyret et al. (2020) found that men exhibited reduced aggression towards virtual females after experiencing virtual sexual harassment. These findings suggest that VR embodiment can be a powerful tool in modifying social

and emotional cognition in a variety of diverse domains and applications. The novel representation afforded by embodiment has the potential to trigger a shift in bodily self-consciousness, affecting both conscious perception and the underlying cognitive processes. This complex interplay between virtual and physical identity highlights the potential of VR as a tool for psychological and educational interventions designed to foster a deeper understanding of lived-experience.

2.2.3 VR: The “Ultimate Empathy Machine”

As discussed in the previous section, research has already concluded that the experience of embodiment can facilitate socio-cognitive and behavioural change (e.g., Banakou et al., 2016; Hasler et al., 2017; Neyret et al., 2020). Consideration should now be given as to how these attitudinal shifts and insights can be achieved using VR. Researchers have commonly attempted to use the concept of presence in VR to elicit an empathetic response on the part of the user (e.g., Herrera et al., 2018; Martingano et al., 2021; Schutte & Stilinović, 2017). The conceptualisation of VR as the "ultimate empathy machine" has garnered significant attention within the academic community, particularly regarding its capacity to induce attitudinal change and transformation in a multitude of domains (Hassan, 2020). This concept, first articulated and popularised by the film critic Roger Ebert (see, Bollmer & Aldouby, 2020), posits VR as a powerful tool for the elicitation of empathy on the part of the viewer. Indeed, this characterisation has been subject to a range of diverse interpretations, serving as both a form of commendation and detraction in the discourse surrounding VR and its associated technology.

First, it is important to provide a conceptual definition of what “empathy” is. Indeed, as this thesis transcends the boundary between psychological, educational, and even technological research – the terminology used to describe similar ideas can be diverse. However, the work of Martingano et al. (2021) provides a robust contemporary understanding of the idea, building upon the earlier work of researchers such as Mark Davis (1983). Specifically, empathy can be thought of as an overarching, multidimensional construct comprising of two primary types: cognitive and emotional. Cognitive empathy, sometimes referred to as "perspective-taking," is the intellectual ability to understand and identify with others' thoughts, feelings, and attitudes (Davis, 1983). It involves a conscious and deliberate effort to comprehend the mental and

emotional states of others, akin to putting oneself in another's shoes. In contrast, emotional empathy, often termed as "affective empathy," is an instinctive and automatic response to others' emotions (Herrera et al., 2018). It is thought of as a more primal reaction that involves resonating with or being affected by the emotional state of another. The key difference between the two lies in their nature and execution: cognitive empathy is a learned, conscious process of understanding. Conversely, emotional empathy is an inherent, automatic response to emotional stimuli. For a more in-depth discussion of these varying types of empathetic response, the works of both Perry and Shamay-Tsoory (2013) and Smith (2006) are instructive.

The debate on the effectiveness of VR to elicit emotional and cognitive empathy is complex and multifaceted, with various studies providing insights into its effectiveness, limitations, and areas of controversy. Indeed, not only does this controversy involve methodological issues, but also wider moral, ethical, and philosophical concerns associated with the technology (e.g., emotional manipulation). VR's capacity to evoke emotional empathy has generally been acknowledged, with a comprehensive meta-analysis conducted in 2021 by Martingano and colleagues finding a small to medium effect size. Yet its ability to foster cognitive empathy remains less clear. To examine this point further, each facet of empathy should be examined within the context of VR.

VR has been increasingly recognised for its ability to improve emotional empathy by allowing users to viscerally feel and respond to emotional stimuli in a virtual environment (Martingano et al., 2021). For example, Ingram et al. (2019) used a VR experience of bullying and peer-victimisation to elicit emotional empathy; a factor that has been demonstrated to decrease bullying behaviour in school students. Similarly, Herrera et al. (2018) used an emotionally charged scenario of homelessness to increase levels of emotional empathy, and this was associated with tangible and positive behavioural change. As aforementioned, VR's influence on cognitive empathy – the ability to understand and imagine others' perspectives – is less clear. The same meta-analysis (Martingano et al., 2021) concluded that VR did not significantly enhance cognitive empathy. This suggests a disparity between feeling compassion (emotional empathy) and

understanding the innate perspective of another person (cognitive empathy) in VR settings.

An explanation for the discrepancy in emotional and cognitive empathy may reside in the innate cognitive processes involved. Cognitive empathy is a deliberate skill that involves understanding and reasoning about others' thoughts and feelings (Perry & Shamay-Tsoory, 2013; Smith, 2006). It requires a higher level of mental engagement and effortful processing; skills that are not automatically triggered in the same way as emotional reactions in VR (Martingano et al., 2021). Indeed, disparity and differences in VR design means that many experiences are created with the primary aim of eliciting strong emotional reactions, rather than encouraging users to actively consider and understand different perspectives or complex emotional states. Although this is not necessarily a criticism or weakness of the technology itself, it should prompt VR users and facilitators to think about how the technology should be used or integrated. For instance, by providing the viewer with an opportunity for deeper introspection and reflection (perhaps through group discussions), it is possible that cognitive empathy could be more effectively fostered.

Finally, research has examined the technical specifications and levels of immersion required to generate empathy in VR. The meta-analysis conducted by Martingano et al. (2021) concluded that levels of immersion and interactivity in VR experiences do not correlate with increased empathy elicitation. Specifically, they remarked that although high-end VR systems are known to facilitate more “psychological engagement,” it “did not have a larger effect on empathy” (Martingano et al., 2021, p. 10). Consequently, the authors suggest that less expensive and immersive options such as Mobile-VR headsets and 360° video could be utilised to elicit empathy among users.

2.2.4 Categorisation of VR Mediums

VR can broadly be broken down into two main sub-categories: non-immersive, and immersive. Since the widespread integration of HMDs, the terms “VR” and “immersive VR” have tended to be used synonymously. Consequently, it is becoming progressively rarer to see non-immersive technology (e.g., a 2D simulation on a computer screen) being

referred to as “VR” in the literature. However, as has already been alluded to, there tends to be a poorly defined taxonomy of terms when it comes to categorising these technologies. As a result, it is worth flagging up that the simple phrase “VR” can encompass both of these very different modes of presentation.

2.2.4.1 Non-Immersive VR

Non-immersive VR most commonly refers to Desktop VR where a HMD is not used, and the participant will be controlling and manipulating the virtual environment on a computer screen with a keyboard and mouse (Lee et al., 2010; Merchant et al., 2014). Desktop VR has traditionally been utilised as a teaching aid in schools and universities due to the wide availability of affordable desktop computers that are still able to display visually complex and interesting graphics (Boulos et al., 2007; Burgess & Ice, 2011). A popular example of Desktop VR is Second Life, a cooperative and interactive virtual world that allows users to build and construct virtual environments (Wang & Burton, 2013). These environments can contain interactive puzzles and games, as well as visuals to teach abstract or conceptual problems in a range of disciplines including chemistry, nursing, and health (e.g., Boulos et al., 2007; Merchant et al., 2012). Despite its rudimentary nature when compared to fully immersive modern VR environments, virtual worlds like Second Life do have the potential to encompass and encourage both constructivist and experiential learning by allowing students to be proactive in their education (Wang & Burton, 2013). Desktop-VR has also been used in a myriad of other educational applications as diverse as virtual anatomy dissections, and construction safety lessons (see, Bockholt et al., 2013; Lee & Wong, 2008).

2.2.4.2 Immersive and HMD Based VR

In contrast with Desktop VR, Immersive VR is typically multimodal in nature by providing a sense of immersion in the environment. This is achieved through 360° visuals using a HMD, auditory stimulation through the use of earphones, and the proprioception of limbs by way of controllers and tracking (Freina & Ott, 2015; Howard-Jones et al., 2015; Murcia-López & Steed, 2016). As the technology has continued to advance, additional hardware and accessories have added to the sense of immersion in the environment. For example, VR gloves can track the movement of individual fingers, allowing participants a degree of dexterity completely unimaginable just a few years ago (Wilkinson et al., 2021). In

addition, full-body VR suits can replicate visual/haptic cues in real life through targeted electro-stimulation and constriction of the material (see, TeslaSuit VR Electronics, 2022). For example, it will soon be possible for VR suits to replicate the feeling of rain falling on a user's shoulders, or the sensation of being struck by an object.

Although VR has become synonymous with high-end and advanced HMDs, there are a range of other systems that are important to consider. Mobile-VR is a technology that allows users to experience virtual environments using portable devices, typically their own smartphone. These devices often utilise cardboard or light plastic HMDs, where a mobile phone is inserted into the headset to serve as the central display and processing unit (Minocha et al., 2017; Poppe et al., 2017; Powell et al., 2017). Distinct from high-end or "real VR," Mobile-VR is characterised by its accessibility, affordability, and portability, making it particularly suitable for institutions to purchase and use *en masse* (see, Lee et al., 2017; Olmos-Reya et al., 2018). As has been discussed, Mobile-VR allows for the "democratisation" of access to immersive technologies, allowing consumers, businesses, students, and teachers to leverage its benefits with just a smartphone and a simple VR viewer like the Google Cardboard (see, Lee et al., 2017; Powell et al., 2017). The scalable nature of Mobile VR (owing to the widespread availability of smartphones) makes it easier to implement in larger setting where ease of access and portability are paramount (Boel et al., 2021).

Both Mobile-VR and high-end systems typically utilise the same underlying principle of "stereoscopic" imagery. By presenting the user with two slightly different images for the left and right eyes, it creates a sense of three-dimensional depth perception, mimicking how the human visual system works (Skulimowski et al., 2019). Despite the similarities of the "stereoscopic" principle, the ways in which Mobile-VR and high-end systems achieve this technical feat are distinct in their nature. Mobile-VR relies on the smartphone's built-in sensors, screen, gyroscope, and computing power to deliver immersive experiences to the user. Ultimately, the experience of each viewer depends on the idiosyncrasies of their own device, meaning that differences in graphical fidelity, screen resolution, screen size, and sound quality are unavoidable (Minocha et al., 2017; Poppe et al., 2017). In addition, Mobile-VR typically limited support for additional

hardware such as advanced controllers and haptic feedback devices (Sherman & Craig, 2018). In contrast, high-end VR systems like Oculus Rift and HTC Vive are powered by robust processing units, facilitating a more immersive experience thanks to higher resolution, better tracking, and advanced graphical capabilities (Freina & Ott, 2015; Moro et al., 2017). Despite the intrinsic differences in hardware capability and sophistication, research has demonstrated that low-cost Mobile-VR systems can be just as effective as high-end HMDs in delivering “isolated” educational experiences (Moro et al., 2017, p. 1). For example, although Moro et al. (2017) found that high-end systems produce better visual acuity than Mobile-VR, there was no significant difference in their educational effectiveness. Similarly, Rupp et al. (2019) concluded that despite the Oculus HMD producing significantly higher levels of subjective “place illusion,” it did not contribute to more pronounced learning compared to a Google Cardboard headset. As Boel et al. (2021) intimates, the decision to use simple Mobile-VR or sophisticated high-end systems is contingent upon the individual design-elements and task properties. However, for simpler activities, Mobile-VR has been shown to “provide acceptable levels of immersive user experience” (Papachristos et al., 2017, p. 477).

Ultimately, the user experience in both types of VR systems varies. Mobile-VR offers a more accessible and portable solution but often at the cost of immersive depth due to limitations in processing power and sensor accuracy (see, Boel et al., 2021; Minocha et al., 2017). High-end VR systems, with their advanced head-tracking and room-scale technology, afford a deeper level of immersion, making them more suitable for applications requiring detailed and interactive environments (Sherman & Craig, 2018). However, their relative cost and steeper learning curve make them less accessible than their Mobile counterpart.

It is important to highlight that immersive VR is not restricted to HMDs (although this is its most common modality). For example, immersive VR can also incorporate projection-based systems such as the Cave Automatic Virtual Environment system (CAVE). This technology uses a series of projectors that superimposes high-fidelity visuals on cuboid walls. This provides a fully immersive environment without the need for a HMD, and also allows multiple participants to share the same space (Manjrekar et al., 2014; Mestre,

2017). However, the financial feasibility of implementing such technology is beyond the scope of most educational establishments or private buyers, with even low-cost systems costing around £20,000 (Juarez et al., 2010). When contrasted with the relative affordability of HMDs, it is not difficult to see why they have become synonymous with the term “immersive VR.” (Lee et al., 2017; Powell et al., 2017).

2.2.5 The VR Experience

The term “VR” encompasses a broad spectrum of immersive technologies, each distinct in its nature and application. For example, the phrase can refer to a range of devices from sophisticated HMDs to basic cardboard headsets, and even expansive projector-based systems like the CAVE. Similarly, the variety of “VR experiences” also mirrors the diversity in hardware now available to users. Analogous to Miller and Bugnariu's (2016) “sliding scale” of illusion, VR can be positioned on a continuum of low to high immersion. Consequently, it is challenging to definitively define the constituent factors at each point on this scale. Rather, congruent with the implementation methods employed within this thesis, an overview of “real VR” and “360° video” should suffice in providing a conceptual understanding of the main attributes and differences between these two types of experience.

2.2.5.1 “Real VR”

“Real VR” offers a fully immersive virtual experience, primarily through computer-generated environments that allow users to interact and manipulate virtual assets. This technology has evolved to become a crucial tool in education, training, and various other domains, offering unique opportunities for learning and engagement (see, Jensen & Konradsen, 2018; Radianti et al., 2020). This virtual setting is often a simulated reality, but it can also represent real-world places, albeit in a virtual format. For example, locations of cultural or historical importance have often been rendered virtually, allowing users to explore the environment and interact with items within it (e.g., Häkkinen et al., 2019; Maach et al., 2018; Moesgaard et al., 2015). These environments are designed to be highly detailed and interactive, providing users with the illusion that they are occupying a different physical location.

Interactivity is a central feature of real VR, allowing users to engage with the virtual environment in a dynamic way (Pirker & Dengel, 2021). This could involve manipulating virtual objects, navigating through virtual space, testing variables, or even interacting with other users (Scavarelli et al., 2021). While real VR presents significant opportunities, it also comes with challenges and limitations. These include the risk of cybersickness, technical complexities, and the need for high-quality content creation (see, Jensen & Konradsen, 2018; Yildirim, 2019). Furthermore, as real VR typically requires more advanced hardware than other forms of immersive technology, the practicalities of cost and accessibility are important considerations. Educators and developers need to balance the immersive and interactive benefits of real VR with these logistical constraints. Indeed, this consideration is a focal point of the current thesis.

2.2.5.2 360° Videos and VR

Typically utilising omnidirectional cameras, 360° videos capture and project real-world scenes in a comprehensive, panoramic view (Pirker & Dengel, 2021; Snelson & Hsu, 2020). By using the inbuilt gyroscope present in the HMD (whether as a standalone system, or a Mobile-VR headset), users can control their perspective by moving or tilting their head to focus on a particular aspect of the scene. Unlike “real VR”, which often relies on computer-generated environments, 360° videos are typically (but not always) grounded in real-world footage, offering a unique blend of reality and virtual experience (Alamäki et al., 2021). For instance, immersive 360° video has been used to give tours of the International Space Station (Rupp et al., 2019), show students a real operating theatre (Harrington et al., 2018), or allow viewers to see inside a Syrian refugee camp (Schutte & Stilinović, 2017). Although immersive 360° video typically employs real-world footage captured from specialised cameras, there are some examples of computer-generated or animated 360° videos. For instance, animated graphics have been employed to give the user the experience of what Bipolar Disorder might feel like (WebMD, 2018).

When comparing immersive 360° video with “real VR”, several key differences emerge. “Real VR” typically offers a higher level of interactivity, allowing users to manipulate and engage more dynamically with the virtual environment. As already mentioned, this might include the use of sophisticated controllers, tracking, or haptic feedback (e.g., Johnston et al., 2018). In contrast, immersive 360° video is more focused on observation and

exploration within a predefined and structured environment (colloquially referred to as being “on rails”). The technological requirements for 360° video are also generally less demanding than those for real VR, making it more accessible to a broader audience (Minocha et al., 2017; Ray & Deb, 2016). In terms of content creation, producing immersive 360° video content is often simpler and more cost-effective than creating fully computer-generated environments. This commonly involves filming real environments with specialised cameras and stitching the footage together using editing software such as Adobe Premier Pro, as opposed to the complex environmental and physics modelling required for interactive or “real VR” (Alamäki et al., 2021).

Despite the relative simplicity of immersive 360° videos, researchers and practitioners have exalted its potential benefits, especially in the field of education. A comprehensive review conducted by Pirker and Dengel (2021) found that 360° videos offered substantial benefits in terms of accessibility, ease of content creation, and the ability to deliver immersive experiences. These have been shown to benefit learning processes in terms of performance, motivation, and level of pedagogical engagement. Indeed, this topic will be explored further within this chapter.

2.2.6 Conceptual Definition within this Thesis

As has already demonstrated, the plethora of divergent terms has made a clear and concise definition of VR challenging (see, Jensen & Konradsen, 2018; Makhkamova et al., 2020; Radianti et al., 2020). Consequently, it is necessary that this thesis makes a precise statement defining how VR will be conceptualised. As already discussed, these definitions might deviate from how others choose to categorise VR in their own work. However, if researchers adopt the suggestion of Kardong-Edgren et al. (2019) and explicitly define the meaning of VR in *their specific* context, the reader can use this to frame their own understanding of the associated work.

Unless otherwise stated, hereafter, the terms “virtual reality” and/or “VR” refer to experiences that participants view with a HMD. The HMD can range from a low-cost mobile setup like the Google Cardboard (see, Amin et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2017), through to high-end systems like the Oculus Quest, Rift, or HTC Vive (Moro, et al., 2017). The

important feature is that a headset is placed over the face, and a stereoscopic image is relayed to the participant. Consequently, the Desktop-VR or CAVE projection systems previously mentioned will not be classified as “VR” in this thesis. When these applications are mentioned, they will be referred to by their full name for the avoidance of confusion.

The second conceptual definition that should be explicitly outlined is the nature of the VR experience itself. In the context of this thesis, a “VR experience” is one where the participant can view an environment in 360°. This environment can either be computer generated such as those experiences that use animated graphics to relay visual information (e.g., Babu et al., 2018; Johnston et al., 2018; Sankaranarayanan et al., 2018), or be a 360° video that uses recorded footage (e.g., Harrington et al., 2018). In addition, the experience must allow for the user to alter and manipulate the perspective by performing bodily movements and actions (e.g., participant can look behind them, or look up and down because of head movements). As a result, non-immersive videos that are simply projected on a 2D plane and watched on a HMD will not be considered as a “VR experience.”

2.3 VR as a Pedagogical Method

In this section, a brief overview of VR’s most common educational applications will be presented. A far more detailed analysis of the pertinent literature will be explored in the systematic review in Chapter Three. Consequently, to dispense with as much repetition as possible, the current section will give only a general overview of VR’s pedagogical application in three broad categories: (a) VR to teach procedural skills; (b) VR to teach information; and (c) VR to encourage behaviour change. As Jensen and Konradsen (2018) propose, these three domains encapsulate the most common uses of VR technology in cotemporary education.

2.3.1 Teaching Procedural Skills Through VR

Procedural skills training can be defined as the ability to teach specific actions or psychomotor responses that pertain to a certain activity (Bloom et al., 1956). Traditionally, these hands-on activities used to be facilitated through models, practice

dummies, or large simulators. VR and HMDs now offer an accessible means of harnessing procedural skills that can then be applied in real world scenarios. This has generally been termed “procedural skills transfer,” or the ability to practice an activity in a virtual environment, and then perform the task in real life (Freina & Canessa, 2015; Schmidt et al., 2021).

There is no shortage of studies that have used university and college students in procedural VR training. However, as a comprehensive literature review by Mallam and Nazir (2021) highlights, students are often used in *proof-of-concept* research that aim to show the effectiveness of VR in non-applicable domains. For example, Elbert et al. (2018) recruited university students to test a procedural VR intervention aimed at personnel working in logistics. However, these students simply tested the intervention, and are not the intended benefactors or end-users of it. As a result, when medical applications are discounted, there are limited instances of student-specific procedural applications. However, the current section aims to highlight some of the ways in which the technology has been utilised for procedural training in school, college, and university settings.

A 2015 study by Bharathi and colleagues used VR to teach engineering students how to perform a functional analysis task by disassembling and then reassembling an electronic device. The purpose of the intervention was to allow students to become acquainted with the inner workings of specific electronic devices. The research found that students performed the task quicker in VR compared to a non-immersive alternative, and also tended to agree or strongly-agree that the medium helped them visualise the procedure better than a 2D simulation. The principles of VR visualisation and procedural training have also been combined with gamification elements to help educate students. For instance, computer and PC assembly is a constituent part of many Computer Science degrees and associated programs. Checa et al. (2021) created a simulation and assembly game aimed at teaching students how to construct and install PC components. By comparing several presentation methods, the study demonstrated heightened levels of knowledge and satisfaction compared to a traditional lecture and Desktop-VR alternative.

One of the biggest benefits of using VR for procedural skill acquisition is that detailed statistics and metrics can facilitate improved feedback. For example, a rather unique application of VR technology was to help train music students how to conduct an orchestra (see, Orman et al., 2017). The VR intervention tracked the eye-gaze, head movement, and torso position of students whilst performing the task. After four-weeks, the study demonstrated that those students who participated in the VR intervention showed greater conducting skill and knowledge than those who did not undergo the training. In addition, by assessing real-time performance metrics, students had a detailed understanding of their own strengths and weaknesses when performing the task.

Most procedural VR research has been conducted in the fields of surgical and dental education. Beyond this, general educational settings have yet to implement the technology to the same extent to teach psychomotor skills. One obvious reason for this is that most college and university degrees are focused on scholastic or academic endeavours, as opposed to practical ones. Consequently, VR is more likely to be used in teaching cognitive or declarative information, as opposed to practical *hands-on* skills that are the hallmark of surgical or vocational trade professions.

2.3.2 VR for Acquiring Cognitive Information

Based on a series of reviews examining VR's place in pedagogy, its most common application in general education is to teach cognitive information (see, Concannon et al., 2019; Jensen & Konradsen, 2018; Radianti et al., 2020). As opposed to using VR to hone procedural or psychomotor skills, cognitive knowledge acquisition involves using VR to imbibe specific information about a given topic.

2.3.2.1 Visualisation of Abstract Concepts

One of the most common justifications for using VR to teach cognitive information is that it facilitates a degree of visualisation unattainable by traditional means of education (Jensen & Konradsen, 2018). This allows students to gain a novel perspective of particular phenomenon or concepts. Often these topics are highly abstract, making their respective intricacies challenging to impart using didactic means of delivery (i.e., lectures or presentations). For example, Johnston et al. (2018) used a VR experience that allowed students to shrink to the size of a human cell, and visualise the inner biological processes

that govern them. By doing so, students displayed significantly higher levels of knowledge acquisition and understanding than those who did not undertake the VR intervention. Indeed, the fields of health sciences, biology, and anatomy have frequently employed VR to successfully help students visualise the inner workings of the human body. For instance, VR has been employed to help students visualise the cardiopulmonary system (Maresky et al., 2019); the human brain (Stepan et al., 2017), and spinal column (Moro et al., 2017). Again, the overarching justification for using VR in these contexts is that these perspectives would either be challenging (e.g., the need for surgical dummies) or impossible to replicate in reality (e.g., actively exploring a human cell).

Apart from the biological sciences, VR has also been used as a tool for representing completely theoretical or conceptual topics. For example, many theoretical principles in physics and mathematics do not have concrete or applied examples that can be easily visualised using either traditional or multimedia means. For instance, the theory of “relative motion” is not one that can be pictured using conventional techniques. However, a study by Kozhevnikov et al. (2013) used VR to allow students to interact with objects on a virtual plane. Through interaction and manipulation of the object’s relative position, the student could gain an understanding of the theoretical principles that governed their movement. In fact, students who interacted with the VR application scored significantly higher on a knowledge questionnaire than those who only viewed the intervention on a 2D screen. Similarly, Matsutomo et al. (2017) created a simulation that allowed physics students to visualise magnetic field distribution in 3D space. Although the research did not specifically examine learning outcome metrics (e.g., test scores), it was cited as an example of how VR can be applied to teach cognitive information through intuitive visualisation and interactivity. Many of these same principles have been successfully applied to teach theories and concepts as varied as photoelectric (Tarng et al., 2018) and spatial physics in VR (Katsioloudis et al., 2017; Molina-Carmona et al., 2018).

2.3.2.2 Novel Insights and Perspectives

VR offers an exciting opportunity to visualise and experience highly abstract or conceptual topics. However, the technology can also facilitate novel insight by allowing students to visualise tangible objects in a new light. For instance, VR has been applied as a means of boosting understanding of art and associated fields of study through unique

visualisation experiences (González-Zamar & Abad-Segura, 2020). For example, Mu et al. (2022) created an experience that allowed participants to traverse and explore abstract canvas paintings on a 3D plane, facilitating a novel perspective of its creation and composition. Far from integrating such experiences merely within the cultural heritage sector, educational institutions have also applied the technology to increase understanding among students. In one such example, Chiu et al. (2022) conducted a quasi-experimental study in which art students were assigned either to a conventional learning activity, or a VR intervention. The VR intervention allowed students to visualise paintings and artwork from a variety of angles and perspectives (e.g., being able to zoom in on interesting details). Not only did the VR group display increased motivation and engagement, but also displayed higher levels of conceptual and applied understanding.

2.3.2.3 Virtual Fieldtrips and Immersive Learning

As has now been discussed, VR has the potential to facilitate knowledge acquisition through visualisation and novel insights. However, the technology has also been shown to be an efficacious means of allowing students to experience locations or scenarios that would otherwise be inaccessible. By actively exploring and experiencing these virtual worlds, students can imbibe new knowledge and perspectives that would have otherwise been impossible to realise.

A prime example of this application can be found in a study by Markowitz et al. (2018). Students were able to take the first-hand perspective of a scuba diver and explore the floor of the ocean to gain insight into the effects of climate change and acidification. Not only did students report an increased understanding of climate change theory, but also remarked that they were more engaged and interested in the topic as a result. In a similar vein, Schott and Marshall (2018) virtually transported university staff and students from New Zealand to the Pacific island of Fiji. The VR experience had users interact with virtual avatars who explained the impact of tourism on sustainability endeavours in the Pacific Islands. Participants remarked that they were given a holistic and immersive experience of what it was actually like to “be there” on the island. Again, this underpins the unique attribute of VR to transport users to a place that would otherwise be impractical or completely impossible to visit.

One of the most intriguing pedagogical interventions in the field of immersive learning is allowing students to experience historical locations. Indeed, many of these historical environments are now no longer accessible, and can only be appreciated through pictures, photographs, or scale models (Çalışkan, 2011; Hodgson et al., 2019). However, the advent of high-fidelity VR has allowed these archaeological sites to be regenerated and revisited through computer-aided-design. Although these types of simulations have been implemented in the cultural heritage sector (e.g., museums, visitor attractions) for members of the general public (see, Häkkinen et al., 2019; Petrelli, 2019; Schofield et al., 2018), educational establishments have also realised their potential as a pedagogical method. For example, Checa et al. (2016) had undergraduate history students explore a reconstructed version of the city of Briviesca, Spain in the 15th century. Students could explore the architecture of the environment, as well as gain an insight into medieval life. On evaluation, students remarked that their understanding of historical theory improved owing to the simulation, as well as intimating that their conceptual knowledge of urban environments had increased. These same overarching ideas have been applied to areas of historical religious importance, such as allowing history students to visit the Ka'bah in Mecca, Saudi Arabia (Yildirim et al., 2018). As these studies exemplify, VR has huge potential in allowing students to imbibe knowledge by actively experiencing environments first-hand. This can be especially beneficial if the topic of interest features environments or situations that would be impossible or impractical to experience in reality.

2.3.3 Affective Learning Perspectives

The final area of pedagogical application to explore is VRs use as an affective learning method. Affective learning is a challenging concept to define, but it is commonly conceptualised as the ability to change attitudes, behaviours, or mental states (Jensen & Konradsen, 2018). Indeed, ever since the trope of VR being the “ultimate empathy machine” was coined, researchers have investigated its potential to facilitate attitudinal change in educational contexts (Hassan, 2020). It is worth bearing in mind that affective learning is rarely studied in isolation. That is to say, concepts like empathy, perspective taking, or behaviour change are typically investigated in conjunction with more common approaches like cognitive learning. However, this section aims to examine how the

affective and behaviour change components have been studied and examined in pedagogical literature.

2.3.3.1 VR to Foster Attitude Change and Empathy

One of the most intriguing applications of VR technology involves allowing a participant to embody the lived experience of another person and perceive the world as they see it. By facilitating this type of *experiential learning*, the viewer can be prompted to change their attitudes or behaviours towards a particular phenomenon or group of people. For instance, studies by Schutte and Stilinović (2017) and Bujic et al. (2020) demonstrated that VR experiences could foster more positive attitudes towards the plight of refugees. Similarly, Herrera et al. (2018) implemented a VR experience that allowed participants to experience what it was like to be homeless. Not only did the VR intervention increase long-term empathetic response towards people who were homeless, but its application also led to demonstrable behaviour change. Specifically, those participants who viewed the VR experience were more likely to sign a petition calling for a change in homelessness policy than those who simply imagined the consequences of living on the streets. These studies demonstrate that VR has the potential to increase empathetic response, positive attitudes, and behaviour change. However, these research endeavours tend to be associated with *proof-of-concept* studies, as opposed to being tied to a particular educational domain. In the context of this thesis, it is therefore imperative to highlight how such experiences can be practically applied to predefined learning objectives.

In terms of educational application, affective VR has been used to educate students about various health conditions. For instance, Formosa et al. (2018) conducted a study that gave students the perspective of what it is like to suffer a psychotic episode (within the context of schizophrenia). Specifically, the viewer experienced auditory and visual hallucinations such as distorted lighting and shadowy figures. Not only did the simulation increase levels of knowledge about psychosis (pre- vs post-test), but also led to affective changes such as increased empathy and a decrease in negative attitudes towards sufferers. Qualitative research by DePape et al. (2020) also substantiated the idea that VR can lead to an increase in affective learning and empathetic concern. In the study, 41 students underwent a VR experience called Brain Stories where they took the perspective of three people suffering from autism, schizophrenia, and Alzheimer's disease. Students remarked

that immersive learning contributed to increased understanding about the respective disorders, as well as increasing empathy towards sufferers.

As has already been discussed, a tantalising benefit of VR is that it has been shown to confer transferable benefits in procedural learning. This same overarching principle has also been applied in affective learning tasks to help improve applied practice. As Li et al. (2021) highlights, there has been a downward trend in empathy levels amongst medical students and other healthcare trainees. Consequently, the development and application of tools to increase empathy, compassion, and sensitivity in frontline health workers is imperative. For instance, nurses have used VR as an educational tool in order to improve their interaction with patients in real healthcare settings. Specifically, Campbell et al. (2021) found that a VR experience of Alzheimer's disease significantly increased levels of awareness, sensitivity, and empathy towards patients they encountered in their everyday practice. A short study by Dyer et al. (2018) also found that VR could successfully enhance empathy in medical students, and help them understanding age-related deficits in their patients. Indeed, a comprehensive literature review conducted by Hirt and Beer (2020) found that Dementia related VR interventions tended not only to improve general knowledge and competency, but also increase levels of awareness, empathy, and attitude change among students and trainees.

Wan and Lam (2019) found that improvement in affective outcomes such as sensitivity and empathy seemed to be dependent on the applicability to applied practice. Those students who underwent a VR experience directly related to their studies or future career (e.g., trainee nurses or doctors) showed more pronounced increases in affective learning than those studies that sampled from the general population (e.g., Jütten et al., 2018). Consequently, VR seems particularly effective in increasing affective outcomes relating to applied future practice such as helping nurses understand patients' perspectives and lived experience. This bodes well for the current thesis as most of its studies are linked to specific teaching or learning outcomes. Consequently, both staff and students might be more likely to perceive the affective benefits of such technology as it directly relates to scholastic activities within their domain.

3 METHODOLOGICAL CONSIDERATIONS

3.1 Chapter Overview

The purpose of the following chapter is to give consideration and justification to the methodological approaches applied in this thesis. Each study conducted as part of the research is presented within its own self-contained chapter. Therefore, the precise method and procedure of each individual study is discussed within these chapters. However, the current section aims to provide an overarching description of the philosophical underpinnings that have directed the research project in its entirety.

3.2 Research Aims and Background

Good research practice is predicated on proper consideration being given to the specific aims and objectives of the project. Therefore, a set of well-defined research questions are invaluable for focusing the attention of the researcher in devising an appropriate strategy.

Fundamentally, this thesis is concerned with the attitudes of higher education instructors and students as they pertain to using VR as a pedagogical tool. Using a sequential approach (i.e., the findings of one study naturally informs the direction of the next), the thesis makes a novel contribution to literature by addressing several fundamental aims:

- i. To assess how VR has previously been utilised in experimental and educational contexts and identify oversights or limitations therein.
- ii. Examine how VR experiences can be evaluated in terms of learning outcomes. This includes methods of formal and informal assessment.
- iii. Understand how both students and facilitators conceptualise VR's place within higher education, with a specific focus on how, why, and when it should be used.

- iv. Evaluate how specific modes of VR presentation can influence student learning outcomes, motivation, and subjective appraisal.
- v. Make practical suggestions and recommendations for future applied practice in education.

These five overarching objectives are addressed through a systematic literature review (Chapter 4), preceded by a further five original studies (Chapters 5 – 9). Finally, a general discussion chapter (Chapter 10) re-examines these aims in the light of new findings, drawing conclusions from the six study chapters, as well as existing literature. In the next section, a general overview of each of the six studies is provided, although a more detailed summary of their purpose, justification, and novel contribution are contained within their individual chapters.

3.2.1 Summary of Empirical Studies

This PhD thesis comprises six individual studies that addresses the research questions set forth in the previous section. This consists of a systematic literature review examining both quantitative and qualitative components of educational VR application. Subsequently, three primarily qualitative chapters utilise semi-structured interviews and focus-groups to understand student and staff attitudes towards VR. The final empirical study utilises a mixed-methods approach to examine student learning outcomes, motivation, and subjective appraisal with educational VR content.

Study One addresses the first of these research questions (research aims *i and ii*) by conducting a systematic review of previous literature. Unlike a traditional literature review, the systematic nature of the chapter explores specific facets of VR research and identifies areas that warrant further investigation (Boland et al., 2017; Sampaio & Mancini, 2007). In addition, the completion of a comprehensive review gives the researcher a strong grounding in the area and allows them to make informed decisions as to subsequent exploration (e.g., choosing to focus on subject-specific applications of VR). Studies Two and Three are primarily concerned with exploring how HE instructors conceptualise VR's place within education (research aims *ii, iii, and iv*). By conducting interviews and focus-groups with lecturers both experienced and inexperienced with VR,

these studies provide a theoretical and applied contribution to research. Studies Four and Five examine student attitudes as they pertain to using VR as an educational tool in psychology (research aims *iii* and *iv*). In the first of these studies (Study Four), *post-hoc* interviews are conducted to examine student attitudes towards using VR to teach mental health concepts. In the subsequent chapter (Study Five), asynchronous VR activities are fully integrated into an existing Environmental Psychology module, and student perceptions of motivation, engagement, and learning are collected at predefined intervals. Finally, Study Four and Five raised questions as to the effectiveness of different modes of VR presentation to impart knowledge and information. Therefore, Study Six addressed the two key research questions (*ii* and *iv*) by conducting a mixed-methods, within-subjects experiment to evaluate different modes of presentation (i.e., experiential VR versus didactic approaches) and their effect on learning, motivation, and appraisal.

All empirical studies are underpinned by the notion that this thesis must have a practical application by offering recommendations for applied use of VR in HE (research aim *v*). Therefore, each study explicitly and implicitly makes recommendations for ameliorating barriers and impediments to successful integration. For example, the barriers identified in Study Two prompted the researcher to opt for a low-cost and accessible VR solution that can be practically applied in educational institutions.

3.3 Overarching Research Approach

The following section gives an account of the ostensibly mixed-methods approach that was employed in this thesis. Although the majority of the empirical contribution comes from qualitative data (in the form of semi-structured interviews and focus-groups), a pragmatic approach to research also justifies the use of a quantitative component where necessary. It is therefore important to address and define the mixed-methods approach, before providing a justification for its use in this research project.

3.3.1 Defining Common Mixed-Methods Designs

A mixed-methods research design is one in which both qualitative and quantitative data strands are collected to address a similar set of research questions (Fetters et al., 2013;

Hanson et al., 2005). As Leech and Onwuegbuzie (2009) underline, the collection of these complementary forms of data do not necessarily have to be utilised within the same study. Rather, they can be used interchangeably across numerous studies that all investigate the same underlying issue. First, it is prudent to address the commonalities that underpin the two strands of the mixed-methods approach. All quantitative and qualitative approaches necessitate the development and guidance of an overarching research question, aim, or objective. Further, both components involve the collection of data commensurate with the approach being utilised, as well as its subsequent analysis and interpretation (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017).

When utilising mixed-methods, there are several designs that can be employed depending on the nature of the phenomenon being researched (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017; Leech & Onwuegbuzie, 2009). Although the nuances of mixed-methods projects can be complex, Fetters et al. (2013) were able to identify three fundamental designs: (a) sequential exploratory approaches; (b) sequential explanatory approaches; and (c) convergent designs.

A *sequential exploratory approach* typically starts with the researcher conducting and analysing a set of qualitative data (Fetters et al., 2013). This could be in the form of interviews, focus-groups, or diary entries. This initial qualitative exploration can be used to identify factors and constructs that can then be subsequently measured using quantitative methods (Onwuegbuzie et al., 2010). For example, a researcher might want to understand how online learning during COVID-19 has impacted students' motivation in HE. First, the researcher explores the phenomenon by conducting a series of focus-groups or interviews to collect qualitative data. Thereafter, the researcher uses the themes and ideas collected as part of the qualitative data to design a novel questionnaire to measure the phenomenon quantitatively.

The *sequential explanatory approach* can be thought of as the *exploratory approach* in reverse. Here, the researcher first collects quantitative data before using these findings to inform subsequent qualitative exploration (Fetters et al., 2013; Onwuegbuzie et al.,

2010). For example, whilst conducting quantitative analysis, a researcher might identify a small number of significant outliers. Rather than dismiss these participants outright, the researcher might attempt to *explain* these results by conducting a qualitative negative case analysis by way of follow-up interviews (Athens, 2015; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017).

The final mixed-methods approach that Fetters et al. (2013) identifies is the *convergent design*. A *convergent mixed-methods design* is one in which qualitative and quantitative data complements each other in investigating a specific research question (Creswell et al., 2011). In its simplest form, both data strands (i.e., qualitative and quantitative) are collected in a predefined window of time (e.g., during a single academic semester). These data stands are analysed separately before being synthesised, compared, and interpreted. In doing so, the researcher can rely upon the requisite advantages of each method in order to produce a nuanced understanding of the phenomenon under investigation (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017).

3.3.2 Choosing a Mixed-Methods Design

Despite Fetters et al. (2013) providing a simplified taxonomy of mixed-methods designs, none of these satisfactorily align with the methodology employed in the current thesis. For instance, both the *exploratory* and *explanatory sequential designs* necessitate that the researcher gives initial priority to either the qualitative or quantitative strand (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017). However, the current project did not place an initial emphasis on one method or the other. Rather, an early systematic review examined both quantitative and qualitative outcomes concurrently to provide a foundational understanding of the research area. Further, the current thesis did not employ a naturally *sequential* design that sought to explain prior quantitative results, or measure preceding qualitative findings. Rather, each study informed the direction of the next, using a pragmatic approach when selecting appropriate methods. In addition, a *convergent design* would also not adequately describe the mixed-method approach undertaken in this thesis. A *convergent design* typically consists of the collection of both data strands at the same time or in a single predefined phase (e.g., during a single university semester) (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017). As this project sampled multiple populations (students

and lecturers) over several academic years, it would not strictly meet the criteria for a *convergent design*.

Rather, the *multiphase design* as described by Creswell and Plano Clark (2011) gives the most accurate reflection of the approach taken. In *multiphase designs*, alternating strands of qualitative and quantitative data are collected over an extended period of time to understand a particular phenomenon. *Multiphase designs* are predominantly suited to projects that require the need for multiple studies to address an overarching research objective (e.g., explore and evaluate the effects of VR in higher education). As Creswell and Plano Clark (2011) illustrate, the findings of one study will naturally “inform” the direction of the subsequent one (p. 70). For example, an initial mixed-methods study might inform the need for a subsequent qualitative investigation of an identified phenomenon. Thereafter, a proceeding quantitative measurement of said phenomenon could follow. As a result, each study will stem from, and then build upon the findings of the previous one. By doing so, each smaller study contributes to a holistic understanding of the particular aspect under investigation. Keeping with the principles of the *multiphase* approach, this thesis gives explicit justification as to how each study informs the direction of the preceding/proceeding chapter. Figure 2 provides an illustrated example of the *multiphase design* that best represents the approach adopted in this thesis.

Figure 2

Illustration of the multiphase design employed in this thesis

3.4 Reflections on Research Approach

As has already been intimated, the designation of a specific research method often hinges on the researcher's own worldview and philosophical underpinnings (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017). This philosophical worldview is determined by the researcher's position on several fundamental issues. In her book, Killam (2013) identifies three main concepts that ultimately shape how a researcher views the world and subsequent research: (a) ontology (what is the fundamental nature of reality?); (b) epistemology (what is the nature of knowledge itself?); and (c) methodology (how can we go about obtaining this knowledge?). It is imperative that researchers reflect upon their worldview, and how this might influence the practical applications of project and study design.

There are a multitude of paradigms and worldviews that can guide and influence a researchers' approach (Killam, 2013). Consequently, only those paradigms that were initially considered appropriate will be discussed here. Several worldviews were considered and ultimately rejected as unsuitable or not wholly satisfactory. These are briefly defined and critiqued first before a description of the adopted paradigm is presented.

Both strands of the mixed-methods approach (i.e., the quantitative and qualitative component) have typically been associated with two different worldviews. Namely, that of *post-positivism* and *social constructivism*. *Post-positivism* is based on the idea that an objective reality does exist. However, *post-positivists* assert that reality cannot be wholly deduced by reason alone, and therefore cannot be fully understood (Killam, 2013). The axiology of *post-positivist* research is typically driven by attempting to establish cause-and-effect relationships through experiments and measurement (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017). Importantly, *post-positivists* recognise that researchers' individual values can ultimately bias what they observe. As a result, there is a strong endeavour to prevent idiosyncratic differences in values, backgrounds, and biases from influencing results. *Post-positivism* is therefore associated with the quantitative strand of the mixed-methods design. However, as Kurki (2007) intimates, this means that it may not be a suitable paradigm for research that incorporates a qualitative component. This point is even more important when considering the precise analytical methods incorporated in this thesis.

For instance, Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA) is used to analyse data in several chapters. By its very nature, the “*reflexive*” component actively encourages the researcher to draw upon their background understanding or personal experience when interacting with the data:

“Reflexivity involves drawing upon your experiences, pre-existing knowledge, and social position (such as ethnicity, gender, class, etc) and ‘critically interrogating’ how these aspects influence and contribute to the research process and potential insights into qualitative data.”

(Braun & Clarke, 2021, p. 5)

It is precisely the insistence on reflexivity that stands in direct contrast to the *post-positivist* endeavour to prevent researcher influence. As a result, the adoption of a single *post-positivist* worldview would not have been suitable in the current thesis and was therefore rejected.

Social constructivism has generally been employed in qualitative research, and is predicated on the ontological assumption that individuals are the architects of their own reality (Burr, 1995; Schultheiss & Wallace, 2012). As Kukla (2013) succinctly expresses, *social constructivists* believe that individuals create reality as opposed to discovering it. As a result of this ontological subjectivity, Barbosa da Silva (2008) affirms that qualitative methods such as interviews and focus-groups are the only way to record these experiences. Importantly, *social constructivists* understand that this ontological subjectivity is not only experienced by participants, but also by the researcher as well (Barbosa da Silva, 2008; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017; Sullivan et al., 2012). As reflexive thematic analysis demands the researcher examine data in-light of their own subjective experience, the *social constructivist* worldview fits well with many of the methods employed in this thesis. As Byrne (2021) remarks, RTA should dismiss any positivistic interpretation and instead use the researchers’ construction of reality as an asset in qualitative analysis.

Although a *social constructivist* philosophy is compatible with much of the qualitative analysis undertaken in this thesis, it would still be inappropriate as a “single” worldview. For instance, learning outcomes are generally examined through the quantitative measures associated with the *(post-)positivist* approach. In theory, a researcher could incorporate multiple worldviews into a single overarching project (Greene, 2007). Quantitative data could be examined through the *post-positivist* lens described, whilst the qualitative data could be informed by a *social constructivist* approach. This is commonly described as the *dialectical perspective* (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017). However, the assimilation of diametrically opposing worldviews are likely to give rise to conflicting ideas and contributions (Greene, 2007; Greene & Hall, 2010). As Creswell and Plano Clark (2011) state, these contradictions could lead to strands of research becoming completely irreconcilable. Therefore, it was important to adopt an approach that would: (a) represent a single overarching worldview; (b) be free from contradiction; and (c) address the aims and objectives of the thesis.

3.4.1.1 Qualitative Research, Analysis, and Generalisability

The discussion of reflexivity necessitates a short digression to examine the applicability of this thesis across domains. Simply, if methods of analysis such as RTA spurn the idea of (post-)positivist objectivity, then just how generalisable are the findings presented in this thesis to other disciplines, institutions, or topic areas? As Smith (2018) states, one of the biggest misconceptions surrounding research is that it should always strive to produce *universally* generalisable findings. This is especially true when the concept itself is viewed through the single lens of “statistical-probabilistic generalisability” (Smith, 2018, p. 2). This is established on the fundamental quantitative principle that if a sample is deemed representative of the population, then this representativeness allows for wider inferences to be made (Polit & Beck, 2010). However, in qualitative research, the idea of generalisability is more complex and necessitates a greater degree of nuance in considering the epistemological assumptions that underpin it.

Braun and Clarke (2021) are instructive in this regard by identifying two related but distinct concepts: namely that of “generalisability” and “transferability.” Generalisability in qualitative research refers to the potential relevance of findings beyond the specific context of the study itself. In contrast, “transferability” focuses on the applicability of

these findings to other contexts. Importantly, the subjective appraisal and evaluation of a study's "transferability" is contingent on the breadth of information provided by the researcher/writer, and the subjective appraisal of the reader.

Reflexive Thematic Analysis can be "softly generalisable", meaning it can have relevance beyond the studied contexts (Braun & Clarke, 2021b, p. 146). Researchers are encouraged to reflect on how their research context may influence the findings and conclusions drawn. Researchers should discuss how their results might be generalisable, drawing on conceptualisations of generalisability that align with their philosophical assumptions. In the realm of applied research (i.e., pedagogical VR), it is incumbent upon the researcher to exhibit reflexivity and clarity regarding the scope and nature of the potential generalisability of their findings. This necessitates a consideration of both the idiosyncratic attributes of their research and the overarching philosophical and methodological footings. Adopting such a methodology warrants a nuanced and critically informed comprehension of the extent to which research outcomes may be extrapolated further (see, Polit & Beck, 2010; Smith, 2018).

Braun and Clarke are not the only people to have considered the ideas of "generalisability" in the context of qualitative research. A 2017 paper by Brett Smith conceptualises "generalisability" as a spectrum of distinct concepts as opposed to a discrete, overarching idea. Namely, he introduces four ways in which qualitative research might be "generalisable" to wider contexts. First, there is *naturalistic generalisability* which is based on the recognition of similarities and differences in the results with which the reader is familiar. It occurs when research resonates with the reader's personal or vicarious experience. Next, there is *analytical generalisability* which concerns the generalisation of findings to a theory or concept, rather than a population. It is concerned with applying the results to broader theoretical constructs. Less pertinent to the objectives of this specific thesis is that of *intersectional generalisability*, which focuses on engagement with often marginalised communities, populations, or groups. Finally, Smith (2017) covers the idea of "transferability." Transferability specifically refers to the idea that qualitative findings can be relevant beyond the contexts and settings of a particular study (see, Braun & Clarke, 2021b, 2021c). Transferability in qualitative research is richly

contextual, allowing the reader to judge whether and to what extent they can safely transfer the conclusions to their own context or setting. Indeed, this requires the researcher to exhibit “sensitivity to context” in describing how their research is conducted (Yardley, 2007, p. 295). Consequently, a sufficient description of the background, participants, environment, and circumstances surrounding the study must be provided. It is only by doing so can a reader appropriately evaluate the degree of transferability to their own domain.

As a fundamental aim of this thesis is to make applied recommendations for VR in educational practice, the concepts of transferability and generalisability are salient. For example, when examining VR's impact in a particular pedagogical domain (e.g., psychology), transferability allows for an evaluation of how these findings might be relevant in other settings. Therefore, this thesis has endeavoured to provide the necessary contextual information to support readers' ability to appropriately evaluate the degree of transferability.

3.4.2 Employing the Pragmatic Approach

Ultimately, it was deemed that the *pragmatic approach* was the most appropriate worldview to adopt for purposes of this project. *Pragmatism* is a commonly utilised approach in mixed-methods designs, and is particularly well suited to larger projects such as a doctoral thesis (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017; Greene & Hall, 2010). Whereas philosophical approaches to research are generally underpinned by specific ontologies (e.g., *social constructivists* believe that reality is created), *pragmatism* is generally less concerned with this (Creswell, 2014; Killam, 2013). Rather, *pragmatists* see the consequence of the research itself as being of utmost importance (Morgan, 2014). In practice, this means that the researcher should employ the method or methods (e.g., qualitative, quantitative, mixed-methods) that best addresses the research question being posed. As Creswell and Plano Clark (2017) propose, the researchers' primary interest should be on “real-world practice” and ultimately “what works” (p. 89).

There are several justifications as to why the *pragmatic approach* was deemed the most suitable for this research. It is worth reemphasising that the defining feature of

pragmatism lies in its concern for the end-result of the project being undertaken (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017; Morgan, 2014; Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2010). As previously stated in Section 1.2., one of the fundamental aims of this thesis was to make recommendations for applied practice. By implementing a variety of qualitative (e.g., interviews with lecturers) and quantitative (e.g., comparing learning outcomes) techniques, a key objective can be fulfilled by influencing “real-world practice” in education (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017, p. 89). In addition, the *pragmatic* approach does not constrain or limit this process to any one method (Morgan, 2014). Rather, the researcher is free to implement the methods best suited to address specific objectives (i.e., the multiphase mixed-methods approach used here). The methodological freedom that *pragmatism* affords can be liberating, and this has been especially true when conducting research during the COVID-19 pandemic.

3.4.3 Reflections on Pragmatism During COVID-19

It is important to stress that a *pragmatic approach* was not adopted *because of* COVID-19. However, the approach has been instrumental in allowing for the continuation of data collection. This section will provide not only a reflection on the research process, but will also serve as a concrete justification as to why the *pragmatist approach* was most suitable.

As previous stated, the established research design that best matches that used in the current thesis is the *multiphase approach*. As Creswell and Plano Clark (2017) imply, this means the individual study objectives and associated methods are informed by that which precede it. Ostensibly, the findings of one study will naturally inform the direction of the next. For instance, if face-to-face interviews were found to be an appropriate and effective way of collecting qualitative data in one instance, this would likely inform its application in proceeding studies. However, the start of the COVID-19 pandemic coincided with the end of data collection for Study Two (face-to-face interviews with HE lecturers who had previously used VR). This had several ramifications. The first was that the previously utilised method of qualitative face-to-face data collection was no longer going to be possible for the foreseeable future. Secondly, initial plans to integrate VR into on-campus classes (e.g., in seminars or workshops) were abandoned as HE moved to a purely distance learning approach. Finally (and relatedly), unless staff and students had

access to their own VR headset, this project could no longer fulfil its key objective of investigating VR use in an applied manner.

However, by employing a *pragmatic approach*, this thesis was not constrained by the rigidity of other research perspectives (see, Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017; Greene & Hall, 2010). Therefore, primary focus could be given to understanding “what works” in order to continue answering the research questions laid out at the start of this chapter (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017, p. 89). Consequently, interviews and focus-groups were switched to an online format allowing qualitative data collection to resume. Further, previous research suggested that the quality of data would not be compromised by employing an online method as opposed to conducting them face-to-face (e.g., Woodyatt et al., 2016). Following the cessation of on-campus teaching, the issue of VR integration in an exclusively online environment had to be addressed. It was therefore decided that VR should constitute a form of asynchronous learning that students could access through their VLE. As a result, VR research could still be conducted as part of specific and predefined modules, albeit at a distance. Not only would this approach address the purely pragmatic concerns associated with data collection, but also expand the scope of the research contribution by encompassing asynchronous and online learning.

The final and most pressing concern raised was that of VR hardware. Due to repeated lockdowns (March 2020, November 2020, January 2021), university closures, and health and safety issues (i.e., cross-contamination with shared use of headsets), the use of traditional VR devices was ruled out. A novel solution based upon both a *pragmatic approach* to research design, as well as the findings of Study Two had to be implemented. A collection of Mobile-VR headsets were acquired that could be operated using nothing but a participant’s own smartphone. This fulfilled the pragmatic criteria by; (a) allowing VR headsets to be posted to a participant’s own residence during lockdown; (b) reducing cross-contamination as participants could retain the headsets; (c) being fully integrable with common VR platforms such as YouTube; and (d) allowing for student recruitment and data collection at a distance. As Creswell and Plano Clark (2017) have alluded to, adopting this *pragmatic approach* allows researchers to find a solution that simply “works.” However, it is worth reiterating that this approach was not exclusively a

response to COVID-19. Findings from Study Two highlighted the need for an accessible and low-cost means of delivering VR material to lecturers and students. Therefore, Mobile-VR was a natural direction of travel (as informed by the *multiphase approach* forementioned) and would have likely formed part of this thesis regardless.

3.4.4 Positionality in the Research Process

The final methodological consideration concerns that of positionality. As Coghlan and Brydon-Miller (2014) outline, positionality refers to the stance that a researcher employs concerning the social and political context in which the project is carried out. The epistemological, ontological, and axiological lens in which the researcher views his or her reality will directly influence how they position themselves in the research process (Ormston et al., 2014). As Marsh and Furlong (2002) memorably allude to, these philosophical positions are not merely a “sweater” that can be cast-off on a whim. Rather, these factors are analogous to a “skin” that permanently enshrouds the researcher, influencing their decision making at every turn. This overarching positionality ultimately influences how research questions are devised and explored, as well as how data are evaluated and actioned.

The works of both Savin-Baden and Howell-Major (2013) and Holmes (2020) are instructive in identifying and defining the ways in which an individual researcher adopts and identifies their positionality. First, a researcher must identify and acknowledge how personal positions and circumstances influence their framing of the subject matter. Next, they must attempt to understand the relationship they have with their participants (and vice versa). Thirdly, a researcher should possess an explicit awareness that they will invariably influence the research process, either consciously or not. Finally, Holmes (2020) adds a temporal dimension: time. The process of reflection is one that is not merely instantaneous. Rather, it is a drawn-out process of reflexivity and reflection that can change and evolve over extended periods of time. As Holmes (2020) remarks, it is vital that researcher explicitly articulates their positional approach as these will ultimately shape the entire research journey from inception to fruition.

3.4.4.1 Positionality Statement

There are no standardised methods or reporting criteria for expressing and articulating positionality. This presents an immediate challenge. Namely, a researcher must identify *what* information is relevant, and *how* to articulate this to the reader (both being a subjective endeavour surely influenced by positionality). It was decided that examining the three major influences identified by Savin-Baden and Howell-Major (2013) would ground this process in a predefined method of enquiry.

3.4.4.2 Philosophical and Methodological Reflections

As already alluded to, a *pragmatic* approach to research was adopted in this thesis. Although this was in-part necessitated by the intrusion of the COVID-19 pandemic, this approach would likely have been employed regardless. Therefore, it is important to reflexively examine the philosophical lens through which this research is conducted. Interestingly, this lens seems to be influenced by an ontological and epistemological contradiction pertinent to the project. In previous work (both at undergraduate and postgraduate level), the researcher had always employed quantitative methods underpinned by a positivist or post-positivist perspective. This influenced a theoretical belief that the holy grail of the scientific endeavour was to identify cause/effect relationships through quantitative analysis. Simply, an objective reality exists, and this can only be understood (or theoretically understood) through numerical information and inferential statistics. In fact, qualitative methods and their associated philosophical assumptions were completely alien prior to the commencement of the PhD. This had two effects. The first was that qualitative approaches were almost entirely dismissed because of a lack of experience and general ignorance of their applications. The second was a bias concerning the employment of such techniques being “unscientific” or unnecessary. After all, personal philosophical assumptions were established on the idea that attitudes are the product of deterministic factors (and therefore understandable through positivist means). Consequently, at the inception of the project, it was believed that this thesis would constitute an entirely quantitative endeavour informed by a positivistic philosophy.

It was not until becoming entrenched in the background literature that these attitudes started to shift. Studies that examined learning outcomes tended to be congruent with the researcher's own positivistic outlook, utilising quantitative methods of inquiry. However, a second permeating strand were those studies that attempted to understand the subjective appraisal and attitudes of VR users. Although these typically employed quantitative methods (e.g., surveys and questionnaires), there was scepticism as to whether these provided the nuanced insight required to truly understand the subject area. For instance, many studies simply adapted older technology acceptance questionnaires to the fit the novel area of VR (e.g., Chang et al., 2018; Hussin et al., 2011). Consequently, it was challenging to identify *what* made VR different from previously means of pedagogical technology (e.g., computers, tablets, smartboards). Simply, average item scores and standard deviations were wholly insufficient in attempting to understanding the subjective attitudes of students and educators towards VR. Only then did attention start to shift towards understanding the value of qualitative methods when investigating something as intricate as subjective phenomenological meaning.

Importantly, these more receptive attitudes towards qualitative methods coincided with a shift in philosophical lens and positionality. Simply put, continuing to hold a purely positivistic outlook whilst investigating attitudes and meaning through a relativist or social constructivist lens would have been contradictory. As others have noted (e.g., Creswell, 2014; Morgan, 2014), the chosen approach of this thesis, *pragmatism*, makes no explicit overture to ontological and epistemological assumptions. Rather, the researcher is simply concerned with implementing the most appropriate method to answer his research question(s). This, in theory, solves the methodological issue. However, it still necessitates a more explicit explanation of the philosophical one. Ultimately, even if a single objective reality exists (the positivist position), the interpretation of this reality and the meaning ascribed to it is still constructed in consciousness, and subjectively relayed using language. Therefore, it is wholly unimportant whether the participant constructs their own reality as in the social constructivist position (Creswell, 2014), or experiences a single objective one as in the (post-)positivist position (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017). Ultimately, as long as language is believed to be an accurate and reflective medium in which to convey such information, then the qualitative

method allows for a richer and more nuanced understanding of attitudes than quantitative methods can. This realisation came as a consequence of the extended nature of the PhD process, and the entrenchment and immersion in literature that it facilitates. Unlike an isolated study, this thesis allowed for an in-depth understanding of the theoretical and philosophical principles that underpin research, paving the way for a fundamental shift in methodology and positionality.

3.4.4.3 Relationship to Research Area

Both Savin-Baden and Howell-Major (2013), and Holmes (2020) state that a researcher must be aware of how their attitudes surrounding their subject area influence the research process. Indeed, it is almost impossible for any researcher to approach a project with a proverbial *tabula rasa* or blank slate. Rather, researchers will invariably bring their own preconceptions to the table, and this will likely influence how they approach the project.

For all intents and purposes, this doctoral research was conducted from the perspective of an “educational traditionalist” (see, Carr, 1998; Kelly et al., 1985). Through his own experience of education, the researcher places a strong emphasis on didactic teaching methods, explicit instruction, and quantitative learning outcomes. As a result, there was a general scepticism of more progressive teaching practices such as technological integration, and peer-learning. Consequently, a degree of conservatism regarding the pedagogical utility of VR integration and application was present from the inception of the project. Far from seeing this as a disadvantage, this position is congruent with the rigours of scientific research and enquiry. By adhering to a traditionalist perspective of education, the researcher believes that an evidence-based case for VR must be made, as opposed to seeing pedagogical innovation as intrinsically good in itself.

The second way in which the researcher’s experience and relationship with the subject matter may have influenced the project were his preconceptions of VR itself. Prior to undertaking the current PhD project, the researcher had no experience with VR technology in any meaningful capacity. The major drawback this presented was that it took time to become familiar with the terminology and intricacies of operating the

headsets and associated hardware. On the other hand, this also meant that the researcher did not feel as if he had a vested interest in the ultimate success or failure of the technology as a pedagogical medium. Consequently, the theoretical and applied contributions of this thesis are drawn from findings and evidence, as opposed to an overt attachment or promotion of VR itself.

3.4.4.4 The Insider-Outsider Debate

The final aspect to scrutinise is how the researcher understands his relationship with participants. As Holmes (2020) describes, this relationship has typically been conceptualised in two broad ways: the “insider,” and the “outsider.” As Merton's (1972) longstanding definition describes, “insiders are the members of specified groups and collectives” whilst “outsiders are non-members” (p. 21). Simply put, insiders are privy to intimate knowledge and information about the participants through their own experience or circumstances, whilst outsiders are not (Bukamal, 2022). This raises the question as to whether there are distinct advantages or disadvantages by occupying either position.

Researchers have argued that being an insider allows one unprecedented insight into the lived-experience of their participant (Holmes, 2020; Kusow, 2003). This can be done as the researcher can ask more targeted questions, build rapport with their participants, and build a nuanced understanding of the phenomenon under investigation (Holmes, 2020). Conversely, many of these “advantages” would be seen as impediments or pitfalls by an outsider. Specifically, outsiders question whether an insider can remain sufficiently detached from what they are studying to maintain a degree of objectivity. In addition, an insider might not question, challenge, or explain phenomenon that would be obvious to them (from an insiders’ perspective), but would be completely unfamiliar to someone outside of their experience (Bukamal, 2022; Merton, 1972).

However, when reflecting upon these considerations, a simple binary *insider* versus *outsider* perspective presents a false dichotomy (especially within the context of this research). Indeed, many theorists have come to the same conclusion, questioning whether these emic and etic distinctions are even useful (see, Herod, 1999; Holmes,

2020). Rather, the researcher's own view aligns closest to that expressed by Mercer (2007). Here, being an insider or outsider is not a fixed positionality. Rather, it exists on a continuum that is influenced by a myriad of temporal factors that can change and evolve over the course of an extended research project (e.g., participant demographics, nature of the study, time, location). This is pertinent to the current project as the researcher does not see himself as either an "insider" or "outsider."

As Mohammad (2001) succinctly alluded to, collecting data during a PhD traverses the boundary between a student and researcher. Whilst interviewing lecturers in studies Two and Three, the researcher was at once an "insider" (had gained teaching experience through his PhD programme), as well as an "outsider" (not being a faculty staff member). Although this might have allowed the researcher to lean on his personal experience of teaching practices (the "insider" perspective), lecturers might still have been unwilling to share more critical or personal attitudes with the interviewer (seeing him as an "outsider"). The same issue exists in the proceeding studies whilst interviewing undergraduates about their perceptions of VR. The researcher was an "insider," in that he was still technically a university student and could relate to the prominent attitudes expressed. Simultaneously, he also occupied an "outsider" perspective by being a doctoral researcher, and therefore could be viewed as distinctly different by an undergraduate.

The work of Holmes (2020) is instructive in providing a detailed discussion about the plethora of advantages and disadvantages of occupying either position. However, for the sake of this project, the researcher hopes he has now conveyed why holding either a fixed insider or outsider position would neither be possible, nor appropriate. Like Mercer (2007), throughout this project the researcher has recognised that his position and relationship with participants is bound to change and evolve. Consequently, it was never the intention of the researcher to occupy a binary *either-or* perspective. Rather, by taking Herod's (1999) idea of an insider/outsider continuum, it is envisaged that the impediments of being part of one group would be offset by the advantages of belonging to another. As a result, a rich tapestry of phenomenological insight would still be allowed to emerge, whilst not explicitly adhering to one overarching position or another.

3.5 Chapter Summary

Chapter Two outlines the methodological considerations associated with the research conducted in this thesis. Specifically, the various designs associated with mixed-methods approaches were described, before justifying the use of a *multiphase design*. Subsequently, the chapter summarised some of the most common philosophical approaches utilised by researchers in the field of psychology. Thought was given as to why many of these were generally deemed inappropriate given the research objectives and the methods employed. As a result, *pragmatism* was deemed as the most suitable overarching approach to conducting research as part of this thesis. The researcher reflected on the benefits of this approach in-light of the COVID-19 pandemic, and the many challenges associated with conducting studies during this period.

In the following six chapters, each study conducted as part of this PhD thesis is presented in-turn.

4 STUDY ONE - IMMERSIVE VIRTUAL REALITY IN EDUCATION: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

A version of this chapter has been published in the *Journal of Computers and Education*, and can be found in Appendix 1:

Hamilton, D., McKechnie, J., Edgerton, E., & Wilson, C. (2021). Immersive virtual reality as a pedagogical tool in education: a systematic literature review of quantitative learning outcomes and experimental design. *Journal of Computers in Education*, 8(1), 1–32. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40692-020-00169-2>

4.1 Chapter Overview

The proceeding chapter presents the first empirical contribution of this thesis. It describes a comprehensive systematic review that addresses some of the most fundamental questions raised in the field of pedagogical VR. A description of the justification, research questions, and methods is described. Thereafter, a detailed overview of the key findings, as well as their implications and ramifications are outlined. Finally, weaknesses and opportunities that warrant further investigation are addressed; many of which form the basis of future research within this thesis.

4.2 The Present Study

The adoption and implementation of any novel educational technology hinges on two fundamental assumptions. First, it must be shown to confer an advantage in terms of learning outcomes, and secondly, those using the technology must be receptive to its implementation. Previous research examining VR's place in education transcends various academic disciplines, subjects, and domains. Further, the precise evaluative method of each study has ranged from one-off laboratory-based interventions (e.g., Maresky et al.,

2019) to longitudinal and naturalistic classroom settings (e.g., Ray & Deb, 2016). At the time of writing this chapter, a thorough and systematic examination of the implications of these disparate research paradigms has not been attempted. Therefore, this chapter presents the findings of a systematic review examining learning outcomes, experimental design, and user perceptions in educational VR.

4.2.1 Justification for Review

The justification for the systematic review is two-pronged. First, a description of *why* a systematic review (as opposed to a literature review) was identified as being the most suitable method for synthesising literature is needed. Secondly, it must outline *why* a systematic review was necessary, and what it adds to existing research on the topic.

The inherent strengths of conducting a systematic review have already been briefly outlined in the Methodological Considerations chapter. But to reiterate, systematic reviews offer a more robust and comprehensive evaluation of existing literature on a given topic (Boland et al., 2017). This is done by having a predefined evaluative process guided by a set of overarching research questions and objectives (Sampaio & Mancini, 2007). By doing so, systematic reviews are less prone to bias, such as the exclusion of findings that do not fit the prevailing narrative outlined by the author. In addition, the systematic review process considers the intrinsic quality of each included study. This helps form a more detailed understanding of the included literature as well as the conclusions drawn (Reed et al., 2007; Sampaio & Mancini, 2007).

The next objective is to justify why an updated systematic review examining pedagogical VR was required. At the time of writing, the last major review was conducted by Jensen and Konradsen (2018). Although their paper was published in 2018, it only included articles up until 2016. As a result, more than 70% of papers included in the current systematic review were not included in preceding ones. Therefore, an updated examination of relevant literature was necessary to account for new publications and findings.

The second reason an updated systematic review was necessary concerned the previous narrow scope of research questions and objectives. For instance, although preceding reviews have examined the effectiveness of VR and associated technologies (e.g., Berntsen et al., 2016; Jensen & Konradsen, 2018; Kavanagh et al., 2017), they do not tend to examine the methods or research design employed. As a result, definitive claims about one method being more effective than another are hard to validate. Therefore, the current study restricted quantitative studies to experimental or quasi-experimental designs. By doing so, alternate methods of delivering education could be *directly* compared with VR.

A second oversight in previous reviews is that they seldom investigate *how* conclusions regarding the effectiveness of VR are evaluated. For example, what was the nature of the assessment instrumentation used to inform their conclusions? Therefore, the current study set out to address the methodological and design elements of each study in order to form a more comprehensive overview of past research, and exactly how conclusions as to VR's efficacy were being drawn. These findings will inform how future research undertaken as part of this project is considered and conducted.

4.3 Aims and Objectives

As already outlined, one of the distinctive characteristics of a systematic review is that it is guided by a predefined set of research questions and objectives (Boland et al., 2017; Sampaio & Mancini, 2007). In doing so, a specific criterion of inclusion and exclusion can be formulated to ensure that only material relevant to the overarching objectives of the review are included.

There were several core research aims identified as part of this systematic review, and these are outlined below:

- i. To identify the subject areas, disciplines, and learning domains that VR has been previously utilised in.
- ii. Identify where and when the use of VR confers a benefit in terms of quantitative learning outcomes over non-immersive methods of instruction.

- iii. Assess the experimental design of included studies, with a particular focus on intervention characteristics, and the nature of the assessment instrumentation.
- iv. Evaluate the subjective attitudes and perceptions of students towards using VR as a means of knowledge acquisition.

4.4 Methods

4.4.1 Protocol

As already alluded to, unlike traditional narrative reviews, a systematic review must adhere to a strict set of procedures and processes (Boland et al., 2017). In doing so, the entire review from inception to conclusion is *systematic* in nature (Sampaio & Mancini, 2007). Although there are subtle idiosyncrasies in how different researchers approach the process, there are generally several agreed-upon stages that all reviews must adhere to (Todhunter-Brown & Berge, 2017):

- i. The researcher must identify the research questions, aims, and objectives for conducting the systematic review.
- ii. Next, the researcher must identify and collect relevant literature. This was done by conducting an initial scoping review to formulate a comprehensive search strategy.
- iii. The amassed articles must then be subjected to a strict set of inclusion and exclusion criteria. First, titles and abstracts are examined, before a review of the full-text.
- iv. Data is extracted from each of the included articles in-line with the initial set of aims and objectives.
- v. The final set of included studies are subject to quality appraisal using a predefined tool.
- vi. The included research is synthesised into a coherent structure for presentation.
- vii. Finally, the results are interpreted with an overview of the most pertinent findings, and suggestions for future research.

4.4.2 Search Strategy

An initial scoping review identified seven databases that could be utilised in a comprehensive literature review, as well as associated keywords and search terms. These included: Web of Science (Core Collection), Science Direct, Sage, IEEE Xplore, EBSCO, Taylor & Francis, and Google Scholar. These databases encompass a mixture of general, social science, and technological literature. Each of the seven databases were searched using a series of keywords based on the following Boolean logic string:

("Virtual Reality" OR "Virtual-Reality" OR "Immersive Virtual Reality" OR "Head Mounted Display" OR "Immersive Simulation") AND (Education OR Training OR Learning OR Teaching)

Due to the scope and parameters of the research objectives, only peer-reviewed literature published between January 2013 – December 2018 was included for final analysis. Early access articles due to be published in 2019 were also included if these were found using the database searches. Date criteria was based upon an initial scoping review that found a substantial growth in relevant VR literature from 2013 onwards. The scoping review searched a subset of relevant databases to understand trends in VR publications by year. As seen in Figure 3, there is a consistent upward trend in publications with the phrase “immersive virtual reality” in the title from 2013 – 2019. A major contributing factor was the release of the Oculus Rift Development Kit 1 (DK-1) in early 2013, which is regarded as one of the first economically viable and high quality HMDs (Lyne, 2013).

The literature search across the databases yielded more than 12,000 references from a variety of sources. After the removal of duplicate records, 9,359 unique references were included for the title and abstract screening stage of the review. A full breakdown of the databases searched can be found in Digital Appendix 4.1.

Figure 3

Prevalence of the term "immersive virtual reality" in publication titles

4.4.3 Selection and Screening

An anticipated concern that might be raised is the fact that a large number of publications were returned from the initial search. This might lead some to suggest that the initial search terms were too vague, or not refined enough. However, as Jensen and Konradsen (2018) already alluded to in the last major review, VR research transcends various academic disciplines. The result is a lack of a clear taxonomy of definitions and terms. This means a wide net must be cast to ensure comprehensive capture of relevant material. This review defined VR as either a completely computer-generated environment, or the viewing of captured 360° video using a HMD. Studies that utilised surgical or dental simulators and trainers such as the da Vinci Surgical System (see, Intuitive Surgical, 2022), were excluded as these represent a separate domain of both technological and pedagogical application. For example, surgical simulation based VR typically combines computer generated visuals with simulated surgical tools, haptic feedback, and robotic components (see, Li et al., 2017). This type of technology would therefore not be applicable for general pedagogical application. Additionally, references

were excluded if they: (i) focused on using VR as a rehabilitation or therapeutic tool; (ii) were not in English; or (iii) where the full-text was not available.

After title and abstract screening was performed, 197 articles remained to be included for full-text review. Each article was assessed against a set of inclusion and exclusion criteria depending on whether the quantitative or qualitative component of the paper was being examined. This process is detailed in Figure 4. In addition, a full list of reasons for exclusion can be found in Digital Appendix 4.2. After full-text screening, 30 references passed all stages and were included in the systematic review. This included 25 quantitative studies, four mixed-methods studies, and only one purely qualitative article. See Figure 5 or a full summary of the step-by-step selection process.

Inter-rater reliability checks were conducted at the title and abstract screening stage to assess the agreement of included studies. There were four individual evaluators that assessed the suitability of each paper based upon the predefined set of inclusion and exclusion criteria. Due to the large number of included references, each of the three supervisors were given a random subset of 10% of the total number of articles to check. Their evaluation (i.e., to include or exclude) was compared to that of the principal researcher, and an agreement percentage and Cohen's Kappa score were subsequently calculated. The percentage of agreement between the principal researcher and the reviewers were: Reviewer 1 – 95.6%; Reviewer 2 – 94.2%; and Reviewer 3 – 98.7% ($M = 96.2\%$). To improve the description of the screening process, a Cohen's Kappa score was also calculated. As the percentage of agreement for each reviewer has already been stated, some might question why this is necessary. However, an average agreement percentage gives the reader only an indication of the overall consensus. It does not take into account whether the principal researcher and the reviewer agreed or disagreed on the *same* or *different* papers (see, Landis & Koch, 1977). The Cohen's Kappa (κ) scores ranged from 0.75 – 0.82, indicating a “substantial” to “almost perfect” degree of interrater reliability (McHugh, 2012). Where any disagreement existed, the paper was discussed

among all assessors until a unanimous decision was reached as to its suitability for inclusion.

Figure 4

Flowchart detailing the inclusion and exclusion criteria for systematic review

Figure 5*Step-by-step screening process for systematic review*

4.4.4 Quality Assessment Tools

An issue that had to be immediately addressed was that this systematic review included both quantitative *and* qualitative data. Although this provides a comprehensive overview of the research area, it does raise several problems for quality assessment. Namely, many quality assessment tools are specifically designed for quantitative *or* qualitative data; not both. Where mixed-methods tools are available (e.g., Crowe & Sheppard, 2011; Hong et al., 2018), these tended not to address the most pertinent aims outlined in this review (e.g., an in-depth assessment of the intervention characteristics and assessment measures). As a result, an alternative strategy was used. As Lorenc et al. (2014) has already demonstrated, separate quality assessment tools can be used for each type of included data. For example, Lorenc et al. (2014) used the Hamilton Assessment Tool (EPHPP, 2010) to assess quantitative studies, and a modified version of Hawker's Assessment Tool to examine qualitative data (Hawker et al., 2002). As a result, it was decided that the most prudent course of action was to utilise two domain-specific quality assessment tools in the current review.

4.4.4.1 Quantitative Assessment Tool

To assess the quality of the quantitative studies, the *Medical Education Research Study Quality Instrument* (MERSQI) was used (Reed et al., 2007). Although this tool was primarily designed to examine the quality of studies in the field of medical education, it can be used across domains. As the MERSQI assesses not only the quality of experimental design and outcomes measures, but also the assessment instrumentation used, it was viewed as a suitable and comprehensive tool for quality appraisal. Other assessment checklists such as the Crowe Critical Appraisal Tool were considered (Crowe, 2013). However, the appraisal categories did not adhere as closely to the predefined aims and objectives set out in Section 4.4. Therefore, these were dismissed in favour of the MERSQI. In addition, the same instrument has been previously employed and validated in other reviews that have examined VR's place in education (e.g., Jensen & Konradsen, 2018).

The MERSQI tool covers six quality assessment domains. This includes: (a) study design; (b) sampling; (c) type of data; (d) validity of evaluation instrument; (e) data analysis; and (f) outcomes. Each domain is scored out of three, with a maximum overall score of 18. Unlike Jensen and Konradsen (2018), the current review gave full points in the *study design* category for experimental trials with participant randomisation, as well as appropriate pre-intervention measures. This decision was made as true randomised control trials featuring random sampling is unrealistic in pedagogical VR research, as the participant sample can only be drawn from an educational establishment. A full copy of the tool can be found in Digital Appendix 4.3.

4.4.4.2 Qualitative Assessment Tool

The qualitative data was examined using a modified version of the quality assessment tool created by Hawker et al. (2002, p. 1296). The original tool comprised of nine domains, but upon reflection, this was reduced to four for the purposes of the current review. The four included domains were: (a) methods and data; (b) sampling; (c) data analysis; and (d) results. The assessment tool required that each category was rated as either "good," "fair," "poor," or "very poor" depending on a set of key criteria listed in the original publication (see, Appendix D of Hawker et al., 2002, p. 1296).

The five removed domains were, *abstract and title*, *introduction and aims*, *ethics and bias*, *implications and usefulness*, and *transferability and generalisability*. The first four domains were removed as they did not form any part of the previous quantitative quality assessment. As a result, there was little utility in investigating only these domains in a comparatively small number of qualitative papers. Ostensibly, the main purpose of this review was to investigate the methods and intervention characteristics of included studies. Therefore, this review included those of Hawker et al.'s (2002) domains that aligned most closely with the predefined aims and objectives set out in Section 4.4. A full copy of the assessment tool can be found in Digital Appendix 4.4.

4.5 Results

The following section outlines the most pertinent findings of the systematic review derived from the initial aims and objectives identified at the start of this chapter.

4.5.1 Quality of Studies

In this section, the results of the quality assessment stage are described. To increase readability, this is broken down into the requisite quantitative and qualitative articles.

4.5.1.1 Quantitative Studies

The first domain examined for quality was the *study design* of the papers. There were 20 studies (69%) that featured an experimental design with stated random allocation of participants between control and experimental group. The review featured nine studies (31%) that were quasi-experimental in nature, meaning there was non-random allocation of participants into experimental groups.

Only one of the studies featured participants being studied at more than one institution (Yoganathan et al., 2018), with most of the studies included (N=28) only sampling from a single establishment. Again, this is not surprising given the nature of the pedagogical VR research. All studies produced response rates of over 75%, which means they were given the highest score in that domain.

In terms of the type of data presented, all included studies featured an objective measure of learning outcomes such as test scores or completion times. No studies used self-assessment on the part of the participant to gauge learning outcomes.

The most pronounced weakness of the quantitative studies included in the review was the validity of the evaluation instrument used to assess learning outcomes. This domain pertained to the physical assessment instrumentation such as the quiz, test, or questionnaire that was given to the participant. Only six of the included studies (21%) reported the internal structure sufficiently through dimensionality, measurement invariance, or reliability using the criteria set down by Rios and Wells (2014). In addition, only 10 studies (34%) stated how the content was validated, with the majority (N=19) not reporting this information at all. Three papers (Kozhevnikov et al. 2013; Makransky et al. 2017; Molina-Carmona et al. 2018) appropriately outlined both the internal structure and validity of evaluation content, although the vast majority of studies (N=16) did not report either item.

Of the 29 quantitative studies in the current review, 26 scored full marks on the data analysis domain with both an appropriate and sufficiently complex analysis and reporting of the findings (i.e., the use of inferential statistics). Three studies scored lower than this due to reporting descriptive statistics only (Angulo & de Velasco 2013; Babu et al. 2018; Ray & Deb 2016).

Overall, the average quality score of a study in this systematic review was 12.7 with a range of 10.5 – 14.5 (SD = 1). This was 1.8 points higher than the review carried out by Jensen and Konradsen (2018), which could in part be due to differences in study design criteria which was previously outlined. A full summary of the MERSQI scores for each study can be found in Digital Appendix 4.5.

4.5.1.2 Qualitative Studies

As already outlined, qualitative studies were examined using a modified version of the quality assessment tool constructed by Hawker et al. (2002). Studies were generally of

poor to fair quality, with few excelling across domains. The most pertinent issues are identified here, along with an overview of how this influenced the future direction of this thesis.

The description of the *methods and data* was generally of poor or fair quality. Where interviews or focus-groups were conducted (e.g., Farra et al., 2018; Fogarty et al., 2017), limited information as to the precise questions or prompts were provided. This made it difficult to ascertain exactly what questions were being asked, or what information the researchers were trying to garner. Other studies simply utilised free-response questions to gather qualitative data (e.g., Allcoat & von Mühlenen, 2018; Greenwald et al., 2018; Kozhevnikov et al., 2013). Although these studies generally stated what questions were asked, there was no justification as to *why* these were chosen as a means of collecting qualitative data. There was also no information provided as to average length or detail provided by participants on free-response questions.

As four of the five studies included utilised mixed-methods, they were generally of adequate sample size in terms of participant numbers (Allcoat & von Mühlenen, 2018; Fogarty et al., 2017; Greenwald et al., 2018; Kozhevnikov et al., 2013). However, where these studies revealed pronounced weaknesses was in their *justification* of the qualitative sample. For example, only Fogarty et al. (2017) attempted to justify *why* a subset of nine participants were chosen to partake in the interviews. In this instance, it was to ensure that a representative sample was interviewed in terms of quantitative performance on learning outcomes. The other studies failed to justify their qualitative sample with reference to previous research, or data saturation. The sole qualitative study (Farra et al., 2018) provided a detailed description of the focus-group sample-size, distribution, and participant demographics. However, once again, there was little indication that previous research or a predefined protocol had influenced their sampling strategy.

Data analysis and results were two of the most pronounced weaknesses in the included qualitative data. It is worth noting that this is not a deliberate attack on the adequacy of the studies. For instance, many, if not most of the qualitative data was collected as a

means of user-evaluation, and not as a rigorous scientific study. But it does still have implications for how findings are interpreted, and how this thesis will proceed. Many included studies make a vague reference to qualitative “coding” of the analysis (Fogarty et al., 2017; Greenwald et al., 2018; Kozhevnikov et al., 2013), without a clear definition of what this meant in practice. In addition, these studies often failed to explicitly mention precisely what method of analysis they were using (e.g., thematic analysis). Even when explicit reference to a method of analysis was made, the requisite steps from data collection to interpretation were typically lacking detail. For instance, although Farra et al. (2018) remarked that they used “content analysis,” there was little information as to how their final codes or themes (referred to as “categories” in their paper) were arrived at. Again, many of these studies were conducted in the field of computer-science as a means of evaluating specific HMDs, experiences, or products. As a result, the lack of qualitative rigour might not be surprising.

As a result of the quality assessment process, it is the finding of this review that a far more rigorous approach to qualitative research is needed in pedagogical VR. Researchers need to be explicit in their justification for collecting qualitative data, as in many instances, it appeared to be an *extra* or *add-on* to quantitative research. In addition, most qualitative data did not provide a sufficient depth of enquiry or investigation. Most studies provided only a shallow description of basic codes or categories, without ever truly attempting to understand the pertinent attitudes or perceptions that shape the VR experience. As a result of identifying these key weaknesses, this thesis can improve upon previously employed methods and analyses to provide a thorough understanding of the topic.

4.5.2 Subject Areas and Learning Domains

Table 1 provides a summary of all 30 articles that were included in the review. Studies were first categorised by the population that was sampled. Most VR studies took place in a further or higher education establishment using undergraduate or postgraduate students (N=26). A smaller number of studies used high school pupils (N=2), or adult education students (N=2) such as those in vocational or work-based programs.

Each of the included studies were then examined for the topic and subject area they pertained to. This was based upon the nature of the VR experience, participant pool, and intervention. In total, six main subject areas were identified. These included: medicine, nursing, and healthcare (N=5), science (biology, chemistry, and physics) (N=13), geography (N=1), computer science (N=2), engineering and architecture (N=7), and safety education (N=1). One of the included studies (Molina-Carmona et al. 2018) did not neatly fit into one of the predefined categories as it utilised VR to teach abstract spatial concepts to multimedia engineering students. It was therefore categorised as “*other*.” An overview of the studies included can be found in Figure 6.

In addition to the subject area, the learning outcomes were also categorised into three specific domains based upon the findings of previous systematic reviews (e.g., Jensen & Konradsen, 2018), as well as the taxonomy of learning developed by Bloom et al. (1956). The first domain is *cognitive knowledge* which relates to studies that intend to teach specific declarative information. The second is *procedural skills* which intends to teach the user how to perform a specific task or action that pertains to a psychomotor activity. Finally, the third learning outcome is *affective skills* which can be defined as a growth in areas relating to emotion, attitude, or behaviour change. Most of the included studies concentrated on the *cognitive* domain, with two studies focusing on purely procedural and psychomotor skills (Bharathi & Tucker, 2015; Yoganathan et al., 2018). The remaining studies were a blend of two domains with Sankaranarayanan et al. (2018), Smith et al. (2018) and Farra et al. (2018) examining both cognitive and procedural skills,

and Gutiérrez-Maldonado et al. (2015) utilising both cognitive knowledge and affective awareness in psychiatric diagnosis training. An overview can be found in Figure 7

Figure 6

Proportion of included studies by subject area

Figure 7

Proportion of included studies by learning domain

Table 1*Table of articles included in the systematic review*

Study (year)	Learning domain	Method	HMD(s) used	Comparison variable(s)	Findings
Akbulut et al. (2018)	Cognitive	Quantitative	Mobile VR	Lecturers and lab sessions	Test scores were significantly higher in those who used the VR platform compared to those who learned through lectures and lab sessions alone.
Alhalabi (2016)	Cognitive	Quantitative	Oculus Rift	Traditional methods	VR was shown to produce significantly higher attainment in engineering content than traditional educational methods. Furthermore, HMDs produced better results than a CAVE based system.
Allcoat and von Mühlenen (2018)	Cognitive	Mixed-methods	HTC Vive	Textbook 2D Video	Those who used VR performed better on a test than 2D control group. The VR group performed better on <i>remembering</i> questions than those in the textbook group, but no difference in <i>understanding</i> questions.
Angulo and de Velasco (2013)	Cognitive	Quantitative	Other	3D physical model	Higher appraisal of architectural spaces designed with VR than physical model.
Babu et al. (2018)	Cognitive	Quantitative	HTC Vive	Desktop VR (tablet based)	Although VR and D-VR produced similar post-test scores, VR was shown to improve retention of knowledge learned.

Study (year)	Learning domain	Method	HMD(s) used	Comparison variable(s)	Findings
Bharathi and Tucker (2015)	Procedural	Quantitative	Oculus Rift	Desktop VR	Functional analysis task was carried out significantly faster in VR condition compared to D-VR.
Farra et al. (2018)	Cognitive and procedural	Qualitative	Oculus Rift DK2	Desktop VR	Students reported that VR was a fun and engaging way of learning, although some people participants reported physiological symptoms.
Fogarty et al. (2017)	Cognitive	Mixed-methods	Oculus Rift	No VR (lectures only)	At pre-intervention the participants performed significantly poorer than the control group. At post-intervention, this difference disappeared showing improvement in cognitive knowledge.
Greenwald et al. (2018)	Cognitive	Mixed-methods	HTC Vive	2D system	Study found no difference in test-scores or number of moves between both mediums. One session was slower in VR compared to 2D.
Gutiérrez-Maldonado et al. (2015)	Affective and cognitive	Quantitative	Oculus Rift DK1	Stereoscopic desktop VR	Both immersive and non-immersive mediums produced similar results in psychiatric interview training.
Harrington et al. (2018)	Cognitive	Quantitative	Samsung Gear VR	2D video	No difference in information retention between both mediums.
Johnston et al. (2018)	Cognitive	Quantitative	Oculus Rift	No VR (lectures only)	Those participants who underwent the VR experience performed better on final exam question than those who did not use VR.

Study (year)	Learning domain	Method	HMD(s) used	Comparison variable(s)	Findings
Kozhevnikov et al. (2013)	Cognitive	Mixed-methods	nVisor SX60	Desktop VR	Performance in understanding relative motion concepts were significantly higher when participants used VR compared to D-VR.
Lamb et al. (2018)	Cognitive	Quantitative	HTC Vive	Lecture Serious game Hands-on activity	VR produced a better test-score than a traditional lecture. No difference between VR and educational game or hands-on activity.
Liou and Chang (2018)	Cognitive	Quantitative	HTC Vive	Traditional didactic teaching	VR was shown to produce significantly higher levels of learning in anatomy and chemistry tests than those who did not use the technology.
Madden et al. (2018)	Cognitive	Quantitative	Oculus Rift	Desktop VR Ball-and-stick method	VR was no more effective than D-VR or a traditional model demonstration when learning about astronomy.
Makransky et al. (2017)	Cognitive	Quantitative	Samsung Gear VR	Desktop VR	Knowledge test score worse when using VR. No difference in transfer score.
Maresky et al. (2019)	Cognitive	Quantitative	Oculus Rift	Independent study	Those who used VR to learn about cardiac anatomy scored significantly higher on post-test than a control group who used independent study.
Molina-Carmona et al. (2018)	Cognitive	Quantitative	Mobile VR	Desktop VR	VR was shown to improve the spatial ability of those participants who used it, compared to those that used D-VR.

Study (year)	Learning domain	Method	HMD(s) used	Comparison variable(s)	Findings
Moro et al. (2017)	Cognitive	Quantitative	Oculus Rift	Desktop VR	VR and D-VR were shown to be equally effective modes of learning on an anatomy skill test.
Olmos-Raya et al. (2018)	Cognitive	Quantitative	Samsung Gear VR	Desktop VR	Those participants who learned about geography using VR demonstrated significantly higher learning gains and medium-term retention than those who used D-VR.
Ostrander et al. (2018)	Cognitive	Quantitative	HTC Vive	Instructor lesson	In 6 out of 7 lessons, VR was no more effective than a lesson delivered by an instructor.
Parong and Mayer (2018)	Cognitive	Quantitative	HTC Vive	Slideshow	VR was demonstrated to cause significantly poorer results on a cell biology test than those who learned using a traditional PowerPoint.
Ray and Deb (2016)	Cognitive	Quantitative	Google Cardboard	Slideshow Lectures	Over the course of 16 sessions, those who learned computer science through VR tended to score higher on test scores than those who did not.
Rupp et al. (2019)	Cognitive	Quantitative	Google Cardboard Oculus CV1 Oculus DK2	2D video (on phone screen)	Significantly better learning outcomes were demonstrated on test scores when VR was used compared to non-immersive condition.
Sankaranarayanan et al. (2018)	Cognitive and procedural	Quantitative	Oculus Rift	No VR (written material only)	Using VR produced higher learning gains in procedural activity and transfer test. There was no difference in MCQ test-scores.

Study (year)	Learning domain	Method	HMD(s) used	Comparison variable(s)	Findings
Smith et al. (2018)	Cognitive and procedural	Quantitative	Oculus Rift	Desktop VR Written instructions	No difference in test score or completion time between VR and other methods.
Stepan et al. (2017)	Cognitive	Quantitative	Oculus Rift	Online textbook	No difference in test score at pre-test, post-test, or 8-week follow-up.
Webster (2016)	Cognitive	Quantitative	Sony HMZ	Lecture	VR produced significantly higher test scores than a lecture.
Yoganathan et al. (2018)	Procedural	Quantitative	Unspecified	2D video Face-to-face training	VR produced higher scores in knot tying skills. No difference in completion time.

4.5.3 Experimental Design

A thorough understanding of the role of VR in pedagogical practice can only be fully appreciated when consideration is given to the assessment instrumentation and outcome measures used to assess its utility. Therefore, this section outlines how the included studies were designed.

4.5.3.1 Outcome Measures

As previously mentioned, when analysing the quality of the included studies, it was the evaluation instrumentation itself that was shown to have the most pronounced weakness. To assess the evaluation instruments being employed, the measures were broken down into two broad domains: (i) outcome measures, and (ii) assessment instrumentation. Outcome measures can broadly be defined as how learning outcomes were quantified (e.g., by comparing test scores or reaction times). Assessment instrumentation is the evaluation tool itself that was used to measure learning outcomes (e.g., multiple-choice questionnaire, long-form answers, procedural checklist). There were 27 studies that used test scores to assess learning outcomes, with the majority using this as their sole method. There were four studies that used completion time as a metric of learning outcome, although only one study (Bharathi & Tucker 2015) used this method exclusively. For procedural skills, Sankaranarayanan et al. (2018) used a checklist to examine whether a task was completed in the correct, predefined order. There were three papers that utilised other outcome measures that could not be easily categorised. For instance, Greenwald et al. (2018) counted the number of moves needed to complete a task; Webster (2016) examined performance on a virtual jigsaw puzzle; and Angulo and de Velasco (2013) used a mixture of scores and evaluations of an architectural space.

4.5.3.2 Assessment Instrumentation

In terms of the direct assessment instrumentation used to examine outcome measures, there was a heavy reliance on the multiple-choice questionnaire (MCQ). There were eighteen studies that utilised this method of assessment, with the majority of those using it as their sole evaluation instrument. Only five studies used extended-answer questions (long or short form) to probe for a deeper understanding of the educational content. This

was typically done in combination with MCQs. The studies that included the teaching of procedural skills used marking criteria and checklists to assess whether the correct order has been followed. For instance Yoganathan et al. (2018) had an expert assessor use marking criteria to assess the knot tying skills of students. Similarly, Smith et al. (2018) had evaluators observe students with a decontamination checklist with grading based upon predefined actions being fulfilled.

There were a smaller number of studies that used more novel instrumentation and methods for evaluation, such as the utilisation of labelling and identifying parts of a 3D model (e.g., Babu et al. 2018; Moro et al. 2017; Stepan et al. 2017). Fogarty et al. (2018) probed spatial and conceptual understanding in their assessment instrument by having participants draw shapes based on their understanding of structural engineering concepts. Additionally, Alhalabi (2016) used quizzes on both mathematical knowledge, and the appropriate understanding of graphics and charts as an assessment measure for engineering students.

There were three studies (Liou & Chang 2018; Madden et al. 2018; Ray & Deb 2016) where the nature of the assessment instrumentation could not be definitively ascertained from the description. This was reflected in the requisite MERSQI scores for each of these studies.

Most included articles utilised the pre/post-test design by comparing the test scores pre-intervention with those after the VR experience. The remainder of the studies tended to assess post-intervention scores only, usually by comparing the difference in learning outcome between VR and one or more control groups. Less conventional means of post-intervention comparison included Johnston et al. (2018) who compared scores on a specific end-of-module exam question between those who did, and those who did not undergo a VR intervention.

Only four articles examined the short to medium term retention rate of information and learning through follow-up assessment. This ranged from as soon as one day after the

initial VR experience (Babu et al. 2018), through to six months post-intervention (Smith et al. 2018). Olmos-Raya et al. (2018) and Stepan et al. (2017) had follow-up assessments at one-week and eight-weeks respectively.

4.5.4 Intervention Characteristics

In addition to having appropriate assessment measures, it is also important to examine the nature of the VR intervention itself. The most popular HMDs used were those under the Oculus branding (N=15), or the HTC Vive (N=7). There were seven studies that used a form of Mobile-VR headset such as the Google Cardboard or Samsung Gear-VR. Mobile-VR headsets allow students to watch 360° content by inserting their own smartphone into the front of the device, as opposed to having an integrated display (Lee et al., 2017; Powell et al., 2017). In one study (Yoganathan et al. 2018), the exact model of HMD used could not be ascertained, and therefore could not be included in the analysis.

Most studies featured a single intervention with the VR experience, meaning that the students were exposed to the technology only once. There were a few exceptions to this, with Ostrander et al. (2018) having seven individual VR interventions in their manufacturing lesson, as well as Ray and Deb (2016) utilising Mobile-VR over 16 sessions. Other studies allowed a greater degree of freedom in the number of interventions or times that a student could interact with the material. This was usually a result of time being dedicated to the technology through scheduled classes or labs (e.g., Akbulut et al. 2018; Alhalabi 2016; Molina-Carmona et al. 2018). Despite this, the VR intervention was usually a single and isolated one.

As well as most research featuring a single intervention, the exposure duration was also typically short, ranging from 6 – 30minutes. The average predefined intervention time for those studies with a set-limit was just 13–minutes. Generally, the only exception to this was when the VR intervention lasted as long as it took the participant to complete a specific task or objective (e.g., Babu et al. 2018; Bharathi and Tucker 2015; Greenwald et al. 2018; Sankaranarayanan et al. 2018). Molina-Carmona et al. (2018) supplemented the limited intervention duration by allowing participants to take the HMD home with them, so they could access the educational content for two weeks outside of the classroom.

Most studies utilised VR as the sole method of learning and did not combine the technology with additional pedagogical practices or materials. A limited number supplemented the VR lesson by providing additional aids that were designed to complement the educational experience. For example, Smith et al. (2018) and Stepan et al. (2017) both had participants use web-based modules and textbooks in addition to the VR intervention before testing them on learning outcomes. In addition, some utilised lecture based instruction or scheduled class time to operate in tandem with the VR environments (e.g., Akbulut et al. 2018; Fogarty et al. 2018; Johnston et al. 2018; Ray and Deb 2016; Sankaranarayanan et al. 2018).

4.5.5 Theoretical Framework Employed

A fundamental component of any educational tool or activity is to ground its use in learning theory or educational paradigms. Learning theories can broadly be broken down and defined by proposals regarding how student imbibe, process, and retain the information that they have learned (Pritchard 2017; Schunk 2011). When applied to educational VR, these theories should provide a pedagogical framework and foundation as how best to design interventions. Papers were examined for explicit statements regarding the theoretical basis for the study. Those papers that only mentioned theoretical approaches as part of the introduction or literature review were not deemed to have explicitly stated them. The majority of studies (N=24) made no mention of a theoretical approach underpinning the intervention. There were two studies that applied a *generative learning* framework (Makransky et al. 2017; Parong & Mayer 2018). This can be defined as an approach where the learner will actively integrate new knowledge with information that is already stored in the brain (Osborne & Wittrock 1985). Webster (2016) employed Mayer's (2009; 2014) *Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning* (CTML). CTML proposes a dual channel approach where visual and auditory information is actively processed, organised, and then stored in the brain. This is contingent on neither channel (visual or auditory) becoming overloaded with information. Smith et al. (2018) and Farra et al. (2018) used the *NLN Jeffries Simulation Theory* as their theoretical basis. This theory, most commonly employed in nursing education, is where students learn information as part of a simulated experience (Jeffries et al., 2015). For the teaching of vocational skills, Babu et al. (2018) stated that their approach aligned with *situated*

learning. Situated learning employs a constructivist approach in that students learn professional skills by actively participating in the experience (Huang et al. 2010).

However, as evidenced by the findings of this systematic review, previous research has often negated to explicitly inform the reader of the overarching pedagogical theory instructing their research.

4.5.6 Cognitive Learning Outcomes

For VR to gain wide-spread acceptance as a reliable pedagogical method, it must be shown to confer a tangible benefit in terms of learning outcomes. There were twenty-four studies that fell into the *cognitive* domain by aiming to teach specific declarative information or knowledge through VR interventions. Most studies demonstrated a significant advantage to using VR over non-immersive alternatives, whilst a smaller number of studies found no discernible difference between the comparisons. Only two studies found that VR led to significantly poorer learning outcomes than the competing method (Makransky et al., 2017; Parong & Mayer, 2018).

To increase readability, a description of the cognitive learning outcomes has been broken down into individual subject domains.

4.5.6.1 Science Based Cognitive Studies

The review demonstrated that VR can enhance cognitive learning activities that require a high degree of visualisation and experiential understanding. For example, VR has been found to be more conducive to anatomical learning facilitated by complex 3D visualisations of the human body, as compared to traditional learning or independent study (Liou & Chang, 2018; Maresky et al., 2019). Additionally, Lamb et al. (2018) used a virtual environment that allowed for the manipulation and movement of strands of DNA, which produced better learning outcomes in content tests than a lecture or a serious educational game.

Johnston et al. (2018) found that participants who underwent a cell biology VR experience scored 5% higher on the related exam question compared to those who did

not. In contrast, those who did not undergo the VR intervention scored on average 35% lower on the same question. Similarly, Rupp et al. (2019) found that participants who watched an educational 360° video about the International Space Station (ISS) using an HMD scored significantly higher on a multiple-choice questionnaire than those who used a 2D mobile phone screen.

However, not all learning objectives can be learned equally well with VR. For example, Allcoat and von Mühlénen (2018) found that VR conferred a benefit over video or textbook learning when questions required remembering, but not when pertaining to the understanding of the material. The novelty of VR environments could have contributed to the lack of an obvious benefit in the latter domain. Similarly, Kozhevnikov et al. (2013) found that participants in the VR condition performed significantly better in two-dimensional problems than their desktop counterparts, although there was no significant difference between groups in problems featuring only one spatial dimension.

Some studies have shown no obvious benefits to using VR over traditional pedagogical methods. For instance, Greenwald et al. (2018) and Moro et al. (2017) compared student attainment whilst using VR, a desktop simulation, and a 2D video. These studies demonstrated no significant difference between the three methods of instruction, suggesting that VR did not confer an obvious pedagogical advantage. Similarly, Stepan et al. (2017) found that VR was no more effective than online textbooks for the teaching of neuroanatomy.

A few studies have even shown a detrimental effect of VR on learning outcomes. Makransky et al. (2017) used a VR simulation to teach laboratory skills to university science students and found that the VR condition resulted in significantly poorer assessment scores than when the same simulation was viewed on a 2D screen. Parong and Mayer (2018) found that students who used VR during a biology lesson scored significantly lower than those who learned using a PowerPoint. Both studies cited Mayer's (2009; 2014) Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning as a possible explanation for the poorer VR performance, suggesting that high-fidelity graphics and animations

could have significantly increased cognitive load, detracting from the learning task at hand.

VR has shown to be an effective tool for enhancing cognitive learning activities in science education, particularly for tasks requiring visualisation and experiential understanding. However, VR may not be equally effective for all learning objectives, and the design of VR experiences should consider cognitive load by avoiding excessive graphics and animations.

4.5.6.2 Engineering and Architectural Based Cognitive Studies

VR was demonstrated as being an effective tool in engineering and architectural education, especially as a method of visualising key concepts and ideas. For example, Fogarty et al. (2018) allowed students to volunteer for an VR experience who were struggling with the comprehension of spatial arrangements in structural engineering. Before the intervention, those students who volunteered scored significantly poorer than their non-intervention counterparts. At post-test, not only did those students who underwent the VR experience score significantly higher than they did at pre-test, but they also eliminated the significant difference between the non-intervention group. This would suggest that VR could serve an important function in supplementing or assisting learning in those students who are struggling to grasp complex problems relating to their discipline. Angulo and de Velasco (2013) used many of these same spatial and visualisation principles in a more applied setting. Their study split students into groups who were tasked with designing an architectural space (a health clinic waiting room), either with the assistance of a VR design tool (experimental group) or a physical model (control group). The study found that those architectural spaces conceptualised and designed with the aid of the educational VR tool had higher appraisal than the control group.

Webster (2016) created a graphically rich immersive environment which combined active and passive media with elements of gamification and interactivity to teach corrosion concepts to US army personnel. The study found that although both the VR environment and a traditional lecture were effective pedagogical methods for teaching

these principles, it was the VR condition that produced the highest gain in knowledge acquisition.

There was also some evidence to suggest that VR interventions could assist in short-term retention of information in engineering related activities. Babu et al. (2018) found that although participants performed similarly in a mechanical labelling task using either VR or a tablet computer immediately post-intervention, the VR group had better retention of information when the test was re-administered one day later. Furthermore, those participants in the VR group were also less likely to wrongly recall information compared to the non-immersive group on the retention test.

Ostrander et al. (2018) examined cognitive learning outcomes over seven separate manufacturing tasks utilising VR in one group, and a traditional class environment in the other. The study found that in six of the seven tasks, VR was no more effective than a traditional class where students could interact with the instructor or the physical models that they were accustomed to.

4.5.6.3 Medical Based Cognitive Studies

Although papers featuring surgical simulators did not form part of this review, there were several applications of VR in the field of general medical education. Harrington et al. (2018) had medical students watch a ten-minute 360° video with slides containing surgical information superimposed over it. This was viewed either on a large television screen, or through a Gear-VR headset. The study found no significant differences in knowledge retention scores between those who viewed the information through a HMD, or a traditional television screen. Despite not showing a distinct advantage in cognitive learning outcomes, the authors did suggest that the 360° surgical experience may facilitate a better understanding of how teamwork and interaction takes place within an operating theatre. This type of learning may be more difficult to measure using assessment instrumentation such as the MCQ, but nevertheless it could be that the experiential nature of VR may facilitate an understanding of interactions and communications. Smith et al. (2018) split participants into either a VR or desktop simulation group to teach decontamination protocols and procedures to students. The

study found that VR was no more effective than the desktop version either immediately after the intervention, or at six-week follow-up when examined using an MCQ.

4.5.6.4 Computer Science Based Cognitive Studies

Two studies demonstrated a significant advantage in using VR to teach computer science information. For instance, Akbulut et al. (2018) found that students who underwent an VR experience that focused on software engineering principles scored 12% higher than students who did not undergo the intervention. In a study by Ray and Deb (2016) that ran over 16 sessions on microcontrollers in computing, the VR group performance lagged behind that of the control group who used slideshows for the first four sessions. It was only on session number five that the VR group outperformed the control group, and this performance enhancement remained relatively stable in the majority of the remaining 11 sessions. In effect, it took the VR group some time to *catch-up* with the control group, but once they did, they tended to outperform them in the remaining lessons. The authors propose that this may have been due to the novelty of the VR equipment which participants took time to become comfortable and competent with.

4.5.6.5 Other Cognitive Studies

VR was used by Molina-Carmona et al. (2018) as a means of spatial ability acquisition and visualisation. The study showed that learning outcomes as assessed by a spatial visualisation test were higher among those who undertook the task in an immersive, compared to a non-immersive environment. There was only one study in the field of social science that used VR to teach cognitive information. Olmos-Raya et al. (2018) used either VR or a tablet-based system to educate high-school students about human geography. The research found that VR produced significantly higher learning gains on an MCQ than the tablet-based system. Further, those who used VR performed better than the non-immersive group on a knowledge retention quiz when administered one-week later.

4.5.7 Procedural Learning Outcomes

Three of the four studies that attempted to utilise VR as a means of teaching procedural skills showed a distinct advantage over less immersive methods. Bharathi and Tucker (2015) found that engineering students were faster in assembling a household appliance

in a virtual functional analysis activity using VR compared to a desktop simulation. Yoganathan et al. (2018) also found that medical students were more accurate in knot tying practice when using VR as a training tool as opposed to a control group who learned via a standard video. Medical and surgical residents were also studied by Sankaranarayanan et al. (2018) who used VR as a teaching tool for emergency fire response in an operating theatre environment. This study found that 70% of those who utilised the VR training were able to perform the correct procedure in the correct order. This was 50% higher than the control group who were exposed to a presentation and reading material only and did not participate in the VR intervention.

One of the studies found no significant advantage to using VR as a learning tool. Smith et al. (2018) split nursing students into a VR group, a desktop simulation group, and a written instruction group to learn about appropriate protocols for decontamination. The study found that there was no significant difference in performance between the groups as measured by a decontamination checklist, or the time taken to complete the task. Furthermore, reassessment six months later showed that VR conferred no advantage in procedural knowledge retention (accuracy and speed) compared to less immersive methods.

4.5.8 Affective Learning Outcomes

Only one of the studies attempted to use VR as a pedagogical tool to teach applied behavioural and affective skills. Gutiérrez-Maldonado et al. (2015) used VR in the field of diagnostic psychiatry in an attempt to improve interview skills when assessing patients for an eating disorder. Participants were exposed to a series of virtual patient avatars in either a VR, or desktop condition (using stereoscopic glasses). Results demonstrated that both conditions were equally as effective, and no significant differences were shown in the acquisition of skills between the two groups. Nevertheless, this was a novel study as it traversed the boundaries between traditional cognitive skill acquisition and applied behavioural and affective change.

4.5.9 Qualitative Methods and Student Attitudes

As part of this review, the attitudes and perceptions of students towards VR education were also investigated. Similar to the quantitative inclusion criteria, this section includes

studies where researchers compared the subjective appraisal of VR with a non-immersive or traditional pedagogical method. By following these criteria, each study has a *point-of-reference* by directly comparing attitudes pertaining to VR with an alternative learning tool. In addition, each included study had to make explicit or implicit reference to the qualitative method of analysis they were using to arrive at their findings. Where uncertainty arose as to whether this was done or not, it was discussed among all reviewers until a unanimous decision was reached.

In total, five studies fulfilled the criteria. Four of these studies were mixed-methods, and their quantitative components have already been discussed in this review (Allcoat & von Mühlenen, 2018; Fogarty et al., 2017; Greenwald et al., 2018; Kozhevnikov et al., 2013). A fifth included article by Farra et al. (2018) was purely qualitative in nature; however, the quantitative elements of the study were already published in a separate publication by Smith et al. (2018).

4.5.9.1 Data Collection Methods

Three of the five studies (Allcoat & von Mühlenen, 2018; Greenwald et al., 2018; Kozhevnikov et al., 2013) used written questionnaires or long-form responses to gather information from participants. For instance, Greenwald et al. (2018) used a questionnaire that had a series of free-response questions directly concerned with comparing the immersive and non-immersive experience. Similarly, Allcoat and von Mühlenen (2018) used an online questionnaire that gave participants the option as to whether they wanted to leave written feedback. Fogarty et al. (2017) used a combination of written survey responses and a series of semi-structured interviews with a subset of nine participating students (featuring three participants who scored better, the same, or worse after the VR intervention). Finally, Farra et al. (2018) conducted four focus-groups with 32 nursing students to gather their attitudes on using VR for decontamination training.

4.5.9.2 Methods of Analysis

The next area of investigation was reviewing the qualitative analysis methods employed by the researchers to generate their findings. Often, an explicit statement identifying a predefined method of analysis (e.g., thematic analysis, IPA, content analysis) was not forthcoming. However, during the screening and reliability stage, the inclusion of articles

where the method was implicitly discernible from the description of the analysis procedure were permitted (e.g., alluding to a coding practice).

By far the most common method was some variation of content analysis. This was employed by Allcoat and von Mühlenen (2018), Farra et al. (2018), Greenwald et al. (2018), and Kozhevnikov et al. (2013). Content analysis is the process in which researchers will identify common strands of data such as words, ideas, or themes, before quantifying these responses (Leech & Onwuegbuzie, 2008; Skjott Linneberg & Korsgaard, 2019). There were several ways in which researchers analysed and synthesised their data using this method of analysis. For example Allcoat and von Mühlenen (2018) grouped free-response answers into either “positive,” “mixed,” or “negative” feedback. Kozhevnikov et al. (2013) coded written responses for “helpful aspects” whilst using an immersive or non-immersive intervention to learn relative motion concepts. Subsequently, the responses were then quantified using content analysis to compare feedback between both modes of simulation (i.e., VR and desktop simulation).

The strategy employed by Fogarty et al. (2017) most closely resembled thematic analysis. Here, an iterative process of developing and reworking codes from survey and interview data was conducted. These subordinate codes were later developed into overarching themes that best explained the findings. However, the author did note that student statement that alluded to VR being “cool” were not classified with a code. There was no further explanation as to why the authors decided to exclude this attitude from the analysis process.

4.5.9.3 Student Attitudes and Experience

Next, student attitudes and perceptions across the included studies were examined for commonalities that underpin VR learning. One of the most frequent remarks from students was that VR facilitated a degree of “novel insight” into a given topic or concept. For example, all but two participants in a study that aimed to teach electrostatic principles stated that the VR condition gave them a unique perspective of the theory (Greenwald et al., 2018). Participants emphasised that the ability to visualise particles moving in real-time allowed them to understand the interaction between different

elements. These findings were similar to that of Kozhevnikov et al. (2013) who found that students were more likely to report unique visual insights into relative motion concepts after interacting with VR compared to a desktop simulation. For example, one participant noted that the VR was especially helpful because it was a “good way of doing things you can’t otherwise do” (Kozhevnikov et al., 2013, p. 959). The idea of facilitating “novel insights” was not merely restricted to science-based subjects. Fogarty et al. (2017) used VR to help students understand engineering principles related to the buckling of architectural structures and supports. Students reported that seeing these concepts play-out in 3D space gave them a unique insight into the processes at work, ultimately facilitating a novel insight into an otherwise abstract or conceptual theory. One student remarked that the insights gained helped them approach the post-test with a renewed sense of “confidence” that they knew the material (Fogarty et al., 2017, p. 04017013-8). Similarly, participants in a study by Farra et al. (2018) remarked that they felt as if they “were there” in the environment itself, helping to facilitate learning (p. 100).

An almost unanimous attitude across studies was that VR was a fun and engaging way of learning (Allcoat & von Mühlennen, 2018; Farra et al., 2018; Greenwald et al., 2018). For instance, Allcoat and von Mühlennen (2018) had students learn plant biology using either VR, a 2D video, or textbook. Using content analysis, student responses were grouped into either “positive,” “mixed,” or “negative” feedback. The study found that the VR intervention elicited the highest level of positive feedback when compared to the two competing methods. Greenwald et al. (2018) also quantified free-response answers, and found that most participants regarded VR as being more fun, engaging, and interesting than a 2D alternative. As one participant put it, VR was more “mentally stimulating and more fun” (Greenwald et al., 2018, p. 239). A more nuanced understanding of the student experience was explored by Farra et al. (2018), owing to a series of focus-groups that they conducted. When asked for more detail as to why VR was more fun or engaging, students remarked that they enjoyed it because it “didn’t feel like [...] learning” (p. 100). They also alluded to the fact that the VR experience felt more like a video game than a traditional learning exercise. Some students also reported that they thought VR allowed them to be an “active learner” as opposed to receiving the information passively (Farra

et al., 2018, p. 100). This was supported by the attitude that students enjoyed being “hands-on” with the VR activities.

There were a couple of noted drawbacks of using VR compared to other methods of learning. For example, Farra et al. (2018) reported that VR could sometimes elicit feelings of nausea; commonly referred to as “cybersickness.” This unpleasant feeling of nausea, dizziness, or light-headedness is akin to motion-sickness, and is believed to be caused by contradictory visual and balance inputs whilst wearing the headset (Yildirim, 2019). One noticeable absence from the included qualitative data was the lack of reference to student barriers or impediments. Only Allcoat and von Mühlénen (2018) touched upon this in any depth. They remarked that participants often found VR difficult to use and interact with compared to the non-immersive alternatives (i.e., 2D video, and textbook). However, participants did expand upon these remarks by noting that they found the VR challenging to interact with “at first” (Allcoat & von Mühlénen, 2018, p. 9). However, once they had been given time to fully familiarise themselves with the HMD and associated experience, these barriers were lifted. This suggested that any pedagogical VR experience should be pre-empted with a familiarisation period in order to allow participants to become accustomed to the material.

4.6 Discussion and Implications

The purpose of this review was to investigate VR’s effectiveness as a pedagogical method in education, as well as examining the experimental design and characteristics of the included studies. In addition, this review also wanted to investigate common attitudes and perceptions expressed by students through qualitative analysis.

The current study found that the utilisation of VR is typically restricted to a small number of subject areas such as science and engineering. Furthermore, a heavy reliance has been placed on the MCQ and test score measures to assess learning outcomes. In addition, VR interventions were typically short and isolated, and were not complemented with additional or supplementary learning material. Despite this, most studies did find a

significant advantage of using VR over less immersive methods of learning. This was particularly true when the subject area was highly abstract or conceptual, or focused on procedural skills or tasks. Furthermore, students were generally positive about using VR as a pedagogical tool, citing it as being fun, engaging, and facilitating novel insights into their given topic.

4.6.1 Restrictive Nature of VR Utilisation

The findings of the review suggest a relatively homogenous application of VR in terms of both the subject areas represented, as well as the learning domain being taught. Almost 70% of the studies were from the field of science or engineering, with other subjects being only marginally represented. It is worth noting that although medical disciplines made up a small proportion of the studies included, this was because most medical applications of VR feature surgical simulators and therefore were not included in this review. Most studies utilised VR as a way of teaching cognitive skills, with only a handful examining procedural or affective applications.

The findings of the review raise several issues when trying to assess the general effectiveness of VR in education. Similar to the findings of others (e.g., Jensen and Konradsen 2018; Radianti et al. 2020), the arts, humanities, and social sciences were underrepresented in the current review. This makes generalisable conclusions as to the cognitive benefit of the technology in these subjects challenging. One major reason for this under representation may be the lack of VR learning content, experiences, and teaching tools. Jensen and Konradsen (2018) highlighted that instructors are restricted to pre-existing or freely available VR material, and this often does not fulfil teaching needs or requirements. The skillset needed to produce and create wholly virtual environments that can be rendered and displayed in a HMD is still demanding, despite the release of affordable VR creation suites (e.g., Unity). Therefore, VR material required to teach social science lessons (or indeed any subject) is completely dependent on an appropriate experience already existing, or having the technical proficiency to create one. A potential solution to the lack of bespoke material could be the examination of the pedagogical effectiveness of 360° videos, as opposed to computer generated environments. This content is comparatively easier to create using appropriate video equipment and can be tailored to the individual needs of the instructor or student group. Widespread research

that examines the potential of VR in a multitude of diverse disciplines and learning domains will continue to be constrained by the availability of the requisite material. That is until such a time where bespoke and individually tailored VR experiences become more accessible.

4.6.2 Implications of Outcome Measures and Assessment Instrumentation

One of the most striking characteristics of the assessment instrumentation used in the studies was the reliance on the MCQ to assess learning outcomes. Although there have been many debates on the respective advantages and disadvantages of utilising the MCQ, it has generally been considered that it is most appropriate for testing large amounts of surface knowledge over the course of an entire syllabus (Excell, 2000). As O'Dwyer (2012) alludes to, the assessment instrumentation encourages comprehensive learning of the entirety of the taught material, as opposed to just specific components. However, since most of the studies featured single interventions of between 6 – 30minutes, doubts are cast on whether MCQs are the most appropriate way to assess learning. Since the MCQ was most commonly administered immediately after the VR experience, much of the information may still be stored in short-term memory, and is therefore unlikely to give an accurate reflection of more comprehensive learning or long-term retention.

A second disadvantage associated with the heavy reliance on the MCQ is the limited breadth of knowledge that can be assessed. In Jensen and Konradson's (2018) systematic review, the researchers found that none of the cognitive studies went beyond teaching *lower level* cognitive skills as defined by Bloom's taxonomy (Bloom et al., 1956). Similar results were found in the current review, with most studies requiring only a knowledge of previously learned material to successfully achieve the desired learning goal. Previous research on pedagogical assessment material (e.g., Ozuru et al., 2016) suggests that the MCQ cannot assess higher levels of cognitive understanding or conceptual knowledge. As a result, the restrictive nature of the assessment instrumentation may impede an appropriate demonstration of acquired knowledge and understanding. The utilisation of short or long-form answers could provide a more appropriate measure of the depth of learning achieved, giving the student an opportunity to demonstrate their conceptual understanding. Furthermore, VR research could benefit by expanding the very definition of what constitutes a learning outcome. This could be achieved by not relying solely on

the comparison of test-scores. Rather, researchers could examine how VR can foster more meaningful learning through experiential interventions, and then subsequent peer and classroom discussions.

4.6.3 Impact of Research Design and Methodology

The current review examined how VR is being utilised in experimental and applied settings, and the implications this has for assessing its pedagogical utility. In most studies, the participant took part in a single VR experience that was also short in duration. This presents several key challenges. Most importantly, the novelty of the VR technology itself may have impeded the learning experience of the user, especially if they had never used the technology before or were unfamiliar with it. This seemed to be demonstrated by Ray and Deb (2016) who found that in the initial sessions of VR learning, performance was on average poorer than those who underwent traditional teaching methods. It was only after the participants began to become familiar with the technology (on session number five) that learning surpassed the control group. Similarly, studies that allowed for extended exposure to VR (e.g., Akbulut et al. 2018; Alhalabi 2016; Molina-Carmona et al. 2018), either through free navigation, repeated sessions, or scheduled class time, tended to show an advantage of using VR over non-immersive or traditional methods. It is therefore important to address the potentially negative influence that VR's novelty may have, especially when outcomes are directly compared to another medium or method. Scepticism of media comparison studies were highlighted in the 1980s by Clark (1983), and then later re-addressed by Parong and Mayer (2018). As Parong and Mayer (2018) put it, the side-by-side comparison of two learning methods is an "apples-to-oranges type of comparison" (p. 788). This "apples-to-oranges" comparison is made starker when considering that VR is an unfamiliar technology to most in an educational capacity, and its pedagogical outcomes are being directly compared with familiar methods such as textbooks or lectures. It is important to consider that the novelty of HMDs and VR may hinder learning outcomes and classroom application, and it is therefore prudent to ensure that the degree of familiarity with VR technology is factored into any direct comparison. Indeed, qualitative findings by Allcoat and von Mühlenen (2018) found that students struggled with VR "at first," but this was alleviated with increased exposure. In practice, this could mean that participants require extended familiarisation periods or

free navigation before the start of experimental studies as a means of mitigating against potential problems caused by technological novelty.

In addition to the short intervention and exposure time, most studies did not complement VR with an additional method of teaching or self-learning. The limited number of studies that did tended to utilise web-based textbooks or modules, as well as lectures and scheduled class time. Indeed, those studies that combined or supplemented traditional class-based learning with VR (e.g., Akbulut et al. 2018; Fogarty et al. 2017; Johnston et al. 2018; Sankaranarayanan et al. 2018; Yoganathan et al. 2018) tended to show a learning advantage. This suggests that VR may be best employed as a form of blended or multi-modal learning to supplement and complement class-based instruction (Garrison & Kanuka, 2004). An area for investigation would be to examine VR's application longitudinally in a natural classroom environment. The current review contained only a limited number of studies that employed this approach; however, by implementing and studying how VR can be adopted and integrated into a module or syllabus, a clearer picture of its capabilities may emerge.

Learning theories ultimately provide a theoretical framework and foundation as how best to design educational interventions (see, Pritchard 2017; Schunk 2011). However, the review found that few papers explicitly state that any predetermined learning theory was used to advise the characteristics or methods of the study. Similar findings were reported in a systematic review by Radianti et al. (2020) examining VR use in higher education. Radianti et al.'s (2020) review found that in around 70% of the 38 studies included, no learning theory was mentioned as forming the foundation of the intervention. Several studies have shown that educators regard clear predefined intervention characteristics and objectives as essential components of VR teaching (Fransson et al. 2020; Lee & Shea 2020). It is therefore essential that future experimental and applied research is based on a sound theoretical basis that can advise how the technology can be appropriately utilised and assessed.

A final area that warrants further investigation is how qualitative data is collected from participants, and subsequently analysed. Only two studies utilised face-to-face methods of collecting feedback from students, either through interviews or focus-groups (Farra et al., 2018; Fogarty et al., 2017). Most studies analysed written responses gathered through online forms or questionnaires (Allcoat & von Mühlennen, 2018; Greenwald et al., 2018; Kozhevnikov et al., 2013). In some circumstances, the decision to leave extended or written feedback was an optional one (e.g., Allcoat & von Mühlennen, 2018). Although written responses can provide an insight into the attitudes of participants, they often lack the depth of detail that interviews and focus-groups can provide (Doody et al., 2013; Finch & Lewis, 2003). For instance, although Allcoat and von Mühlennen (2018) grouped VR responses into either a “positive,” “mixed,” or “neutral” category, this explains very little about a student’s actual *experience* with VR learning. Therefore, it is imperative that researchers implement more robust qualitative methods of data collection and analysis to capture a nuanced understanding of how students perceive pedagogical VR interventions.

4.6.4 Student Learning and Perceptions

The current review examined learning outcomes across three domains: cognitive, procedural, and affective. By far the most popular domain was the teaching of cognitive skills and knowledge which made up more than 80% of studies in the current review. Around half of those demonstrated a positive effect on learning when using VR over less immersive pedagogical methods. Most of the remaining studies showed no significant effect either way, with only a small number of papers exhibiting detrimental results. Researchers have suggested that the increased levels of immersive content that stimulate multisensory engagement can ultimately lead to more effective learning outcomes (Webster, 2016). When this is implemented in cognitive learning activities that required a high degree of spatial understanding and visualisation (e.g., Maresky et al., 2019), VR can allow the user to gain insights that are difficult to reproduce in reality. Indeed, in those studies with a qualitative component, students typically remarked that the visualisation and unique perspectives afforded by VR gave them a “novel insight” into the topic they were learning (see, Fogarty et al., 2017; Greenwald et al., 2018; Kozhevnikov et al., 2013). This review has already identified scientific subjects such as biology and physics as promising avenues for educational VR implementation. However, other

scientific disciplines that require abstract or conceptual understanding (e.g., chemistry, mathematics) could also benefit from the visualisation afforded by VR.

Studies that utilised VR for the teaching of procedural skills and knowledge produced encouraging results, with three of the four studies finding a significantly positive increase in learning (Bharathi & Tucker 2015; Sankaranarayanan et al. 2018; Yoganathan et al. 2018). Two of the studies featured a transfer component by having the user first practice the procedure in VR, and then use this form of experiential learning to complete a task in the real world. Yoganathan et al. (2018) had students practice how to tie a surgical knot in VR and then complete this task for real in-front of an expert. Sankaranarayanan et al. (2018) had medical students learn how to deal with an operating theatre fire by first practicing the procedure in VR, and then applying this knowledge to a mock emergency in a real operating room. Both studies found a positive effect of using VR as the training method by demonstrating improved results when performed in a real environment. These are encouraging findings for VR's effectiveness in psychomotor and procedural education, as there has been a degree of scepticism over whether VR simply produces a "*getting good at the game*" effect. For instance, Jensen and Konradsen (2018) point out that the honing of procedural skills within VR may simply lead to the participant becoming proficient when performing the task virtually, and this may not necessarily transfer to the real world. The current review has identified that the two procedural studies that implemented a transfer task did indeed demonstrate a significant benefit to using VR as an initial education method. This demonstrates that virtual training can be a successful precursor to implementation in the real world. For instance, VR could be useful in educating students in dangerous vocational subjects such as electrical engineering without risk to themselves or others. However, this view is based on a small number of studies, and it is therefore important that future procedural tasks utilise a transfer activity to understand the potential scope and parameters surrounding VR training and real-world application.

Only one study had a firm focus on the training of affective skills, namely by using VR as a way of teaching diagnostic interview techniques in a psychiatric setting (Gutiérrez-Maldonado et al., 2015). Although this study found no clear advantage to using VR, the

fact that only one such article was included means that any generalisable conclusion as to its efficacy is challenging. This is especially true since additional research beyond the scope of this review *has* found VR to be beneficial in an affective or behavioural change context. For instance, VR has been applied successfully in areas such as exposure therapy, anxiety disorder treatment, and empathy elicitation (Botella et al. 2017; Maples-Keller et al. 2017; Schutte and Stilinović, 2017). As a result of the strong non-educational body of literature suggesting VR can facilitate affective and behavioural change, future research should examine how this can be applied in an educational context, and then transferred to real-world scenarios. For instance, in their psychiatric interview experience, Gutiérrez-Maldonado et al. (2015) had users interact solely with virtual avatars, and did not have the participants demonstrate their learning with a real actor or patient. Therefore, just like with procedural skill acquisition, affective VR experiences should seek to understand how virtual learning can then be applied to real situations.

One of the most promising findings of this review was how students appraised and evaluated the VR interventions. Qualitative feedback from participants suggested that students found VR to be fun, interesting, and engaging (Farra et al., 2018; Greenwald et al., 2018). For instance, Allcoat and von Mühlennen (2018) found that students had a more positive perception of learning in VR compared to both a 2D video, and traditional textbook learning. Previous research has suggested that students who are more engaged and positive about their learning materials tend to perform better academically (see, Gamon, 2001; Heafner, 2004; Su & Cheng, 2015). Although this may not exclusively be the result of the VR intervention itself, motivation and positive affect plays a fundamental role in encouraging students to learn (Gamon, 2001).

4.6.5 Implications for Future Practice

This review has been able to identify a body of experimental and applied research that show the potential benefits of using VR in education. It has already been noted that VR has traditionally been used to teach low-level or fundamental skills and knowledge, and has not necessarily been used to facilitate what Bloom et al. (1956) would consider higher level learning. This would include analysing and evaluating experience. By expanding the definition of learning outcomes to encompass potential benefits such as an increased depth of understanding or the ability to identify more nuanced themes, pedagogical

practice can take advantage of the inherent strength of the medium. These should be comprehensively analysed to investigate learning outcomes that go beyond simple test scores.

The review has also been able to identify areas for improvement in future studies, which would address confounding variables and expand the scope of research. Firstly, as Allcoat and von Mühlénen (2018) suggest, the novelty of VR could hamper learning outcomes due to unfamiliarity with the technology. Therefore, it is important to factor in an extended familiarisation or free-navigation period that would help alleviate this concern. Additionally, follow-up qualitative analysis such as interviews or focus groups could help explore the phenomenology or direct experience of using VR, and highlight concerns relating to unfamiliarity or technological anxiety. The biggest concern relating to the assessment instrumentation was the over-reliance on MCQ style assessment. Although this method is deemed appropriate for assessing large amounts of surface knowledge, it may not reveal more nuanced forms of learning that extend beyond mere recall of information. Therefore, long-form essay questions, oral examinations, or group discussions could be used to facilitate students' ability to present their in-depth understanding and applied knowledge. Future research must base the nature of these interventions on a sound theoretical framework. This would assist in identifying specific learning objectives and methods of assessments. An explicit theoretical approach was commonly lacking in the included studies.

VR has already been demonstrated to be an effective tool in non-pedagogical behaviour change facilitated through experiential learning (Herrera et al. 2018; Shin 2018). For example, this might involve allowing someone to learn by having them embody the lived-experience of another person. Therefore, it was surprising not to see this facet explored more in the current review. There is already a strong body of evidence suggesting VR experiences can elicit high levels of empathetic response and perspective taking, and this could be explored within an educational context. For example, Dyer et al. (2018) used VR to allow health care students to take the perspective of an older patient with age-related medical conditions. This resulted not only in increased levels of empathy, but a better understanding of the condition itself. Therefore, these findings suggest that this

underutilised application of VR might have potential as an applied educational method, and should be investigated further.

4.6.6 Limitations

When conducting any systematic review, it is imperative that the limitations of the study are acknowledged when drawing conclusions. Indeed, many of the limitations of the current systematic review are not unique and have been encountered by previous researchers when they have attempted to synthesise previous findings (e.g., Jensen & Konradsen, 2018). For example, there is an issue surrounding the relative quality of many of the included studies in terms of their design, methodology, and analysis. This is not necessarily the fault of the studies' themselves, as many were designed and conceptualised as tech-demos, or user-evaluations as opposed to stringently designed scientific experiments. As a result, the purpose of many of the studies was simply to examine the efficiency of specific VR experiences, as opposed to gaining a theoretical and applied understanding of how the technology can be used in pedagogical practice. Some researchers have proposed that a quality threshold for inclusion should form part of a systematic review or meta-analysis (Meline, 2006). However, given that the purpose of this review was to understand *where* and *how* pedagogical VR has been applied, it seemed prudent to include these studies whilst simultaneously acknowledging their inherent weaknesses. By doing so, this thesis can address the limitations of the included studies, and then resolve to improve upon these in subsequent chapters.

4.6.7 Conclusion

The current review found that VR conferred a learning benefit in around half of cognitive studies, especially where highly complex or conceptual problems required spatial understanding and visualisation. Although many studies found no significant benefit of using VR over less-immersive technology, only a small number resulted in detrimental effects on learning outcomes. However, the homogenous nature of assessment instrumentation, such as an over-reliance on the MCQ may have stifled the ability for participants to demonstrate learning outcomes beyond low level cognitive knowledge. Short exposure times and isolated interventions could also pose a problem as the novel nature of the technology could negatively impact the amount of learning able to be imbibed. Most procedural tasks did show a benefit to utilising VR, and furthermore, there

was evidence that virtual skill acquisition could be transferred successfully to real world problems and scenarios. Although affective behavioural change has been widely studied in non-educational applications of VR, the domain was underrepresented in the current review, and is an important area for future investigation.

5 STUDY TWO - IMPLEMENTING VIRTUAL REALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION: INSTRUCTOR ATTITUDES AND PERSPECTIVES

A version of this chapter has been published in *Innovative Practice in Higher Education*, and can be found in Appendix 2:

Hamilton, D., McKechnie, J., Edgerton, E., & Wilson, C. (2021). Implementing immersive virtual reality in higher education: A qualitative study of instructor attitudes and perspectives. *Innovative Practice in Higher Education*, 4(2), 206–238. <http://journals.staffs.ac.uk/index.php/ipihe/article/view/210/342>

5.1 Chapter Overview

The previous chapter contained a systematic review investigating the pedagogical utility of VR in education. It found that VR conferred a learning benefit over traditional means of education, especially when the task required a high degree of visualisation. The review also concluded that students were generally receptive of educational VR, finding it fun, novel, and engaging. However, the review did not investigate the practicalities of applying the technology in a real classroom environment. One aim of this thesis is to ensure its conclusions are relevant to real-world practice. Having demonstrated VR's pedagogical utility, it is prudent to investigate the practicalities of applying such technology in an educational environment.

This chapter describes interviews with HE teaching faculty who have employed VR in a university setting. Building upon the weaknesses identified in Study One, this chapter describes the qualitative methods used to collect and analyse the data. Five overarching themes best encapsulate the attitudes and perceptions instructors espoused.

Implications and suggestions for applied practice are outlined, before a description of how the findings inform the future direction of this thesis are made.

5.2 Introduction

VR has been shown to be a promising pedagogical medium for teaching, learning, and engagement in a number of domains (Jensen & Konradsen, 2018). However, these findings tend to stem from experimental research as opposed to applied use in the classroom. As Fransson et al. (2020) highlights, VR research has often focused on learning outcomes and user experience whilst neglecting the practicalities of implementing the technology in an applied setting. Although VR may confer a learning benefit, these will not be realised if teachers and instructors cannot implement the technology effectively in their own pedagogical practice. Therefore, a thorough understanding of how VR should be utilised, as well as the associated logistical considerations, facilitators, and barriers is paramount to its eventual widespread application. The current study interviewed HE instructors across three institutions who had previously employed HMD based VR in their teaching practices. The study focused on the perceptions and practicalities of using VR as a pedagogical tool, as well as the associated logistical considerations that need to be accounted for.

5.2.1 Accounting For Instructor Attitudes

In the sphere of pedagogical VR, the attitudes of instructors play a vital role in determining the future success and efficacy of the technology. The Educational VR System Model first proposed by Alfalah and colleagues in 2017 provides a comprehensive conceptual framework for investigating the integration of VR within HE. This model highlights several key elements including user perceptions, educational materials, and system development (Alfalah, 2018; Alfalah et al., 2017). Most pertinent to the rationale for the current study is that the VR Education System Model draw attention to the need for mutual motivation and willingness in both students *and* instructors to successfully integrate such materials into HE (see, Alfalah, 2018; Alfalah et al., 2017, 2018).

Instructors' attitudes towards VR technology are of paramount importance, primarily because they are the primary agents of change and innovation within the educational system (Marzilli et al., 2014). Instructors' attitudes shape implementation strategies such as the choice of content, pedagogical framework, and where VR should be integrated within the curriculum (Dengel, 2018; Lee & Shea, 2020). It has been well substantiated that enthusiasm and willingness to embrace technology can foster a pedagogical environment more conducive to its eventual adoption (see, Huang et al., 2016a, 2016b; Shen et al., 2019). In addition, instructors possess a unique insight into the educational needs of their own students. This knowledge is invaluable in tailoring VR interventions to meet educational needs and ensure that the VR content is pedagogically sound. Instructors' expertise in their respective subject areas enables them to critically assess the suitability of VR materials, ensuring that they are academically rigorous and aligned with predefined learning outcomes and objectives.

Additionally, instructors play a crucial role in addressing barriers and impediments to successful implementation (Cooper et al., 2019; Fransson et al., 2020). Indeed, the adoption of specific strategies to address and overcome impediments informs future practice and can serve as an important lesson for other departments or institutions. As Southgate and Smith (2017) have highlighted, previous research has often neglected to understand the role that educators play in practically integrating novel technological systems. The systematic review in the preceding chapter has already demonstrated that VR can be educationally advantageous, and students are generally receptive towards its use. However, from a purely pragmatic perspective, if the primary agents of change (i.e., the instructors) are unwilling to support such innovation, then will students reap these benefits?

In contrast to instructors' attitudes, students' perceptions of VR as a learning tool are also significant but serve a different purpose (see, Alfalah, 2018; Alfalah et al., 2017). Namely, as end-users of the system, students can provide insight into its pedagogical efficiency, or need for appropriate structuring or scaffolding. While students' willingness to use and engage with VR systems is essential, the instructors ultimately decide how these systems are implemented and used in the educational context. Their role as educators, subject

experts, and technology users positions them at the forefront of educational innovation. As a result, they are the ones best able to provide actionable insights into educational integration, purpose, and problem resolution. This rationale underscores the critical importance of educators' perspectives in comprehensively understanding VR's potential within education. Simply, the adoption of innovative pedagogical technologies follows a top-down approach, rather than bottom-up, where it is the educators, rather than the students, who can determine the manner, location, and timing of incorporating such novel educational techniques. Consequently, it is essential that this thesis gives consideration to the attitudes of those who are best placed to drive innovation within HE – the educators themselves.

5.2.2 Instructors' Attitudes Towards VR in Education

The first major barrier to understanding attitudes is that research examining the perceptions of HE instructors is sparse. Most research has either focused on student attitudes towards VR (e.g., DePape et al., 2020) or that of schoolteachers or teachers-in-training (e.g., Cooper et al., 2019; Fransson et al., 2020). Therefore, the degree to which the attitudes of high-school teachers are generalisable to HE institutions is difficult to ascertain. However, there may be common perceptions, barriers, and practicalities that underpin attitudes towards VR across educational establishments.

The most fundamental attitudes to understand are those concerned with how and for what VR should be used? Apart from experimental research examining learning outcomes in specific disciplines, little attention has been paid to HE lecturers' perceptions of VR application. However, schoolteachers have intimated that highly abstract or conceptual topics such as those taught in physics, mathematics, or geography could benefit from VR (Dengel, 2018; Serin, 2020). Chou and Hoisington (2018) extended this idea further by proposing that VR could be used for virtual fieldtrips and excursions which would allow students to experience simulated environments; an approach which would be especially practical if the environment was too inaccessible or dangerous to be visited in reality (Cooper et al., 2019). Although these attitudes do not pertain directly to HE, there is no reason to think that these potential applications could not be of benefit to university students also.

Although limited research has examined attitudes towards VR and syllabus integration, the general consensus is that its use should be aligned with specific goals and learning objectives. Fransson et al. (2020) conducted interviews with schoolteachers in Sweden and found they were adamant that VR should not be used as a “flash-in-the-pan” (p. 3397). Rather, it should be used to complement the predefined learning outcomes prescribed within the larger syllabus or module. As one teacher noted, this means constantly assessing VR’s purpose as a learning tool in the classroom to ensure it is enhancing learning as opposed to being used as a gimmick. Like any form of technology, HE instructors must ensure that it is the learning outcome itself that dictates whether VR is used, and not the other way around (Picciano, 2009). To integrate VR in a spurious manner could render its application redundant regardless of whether this is done in a high-school, college, or university environment.

One prominent set of attitudes found among instructors relates to perceived internal and external barriers to VR implementation. In a study of HE computing instructors, Alfalah (2018) found that lecturers envisaged problems such as a lack of finance, training, resources, time, and administrative support. The need for professional development services prior to VR implementation was also deemed essential. Despite this, instructors were still positive about using VR as a pedagogical tool provided the requisite support was in place. Almost identical barriers have been identified by non-HE faculty, such as those in primary school and high school (Chou & Hoisington, 2018; Cooper et al., 2019; Fransson et al., 2020). This would suggest that these barriers are universal and a common concern. As a result, practical solutions and recommendations could help alleviate these concerns across the board as opposed to within just a specific institution. It is therefore important to examine the perspectives and attitudes of instructors who have already implemented the technology in order to inform best practice and ensure VR’s effectiveness as a pedagogical tool.

5.2.3 Novel Contribution

There are several reasons why the current study makes a novel and applied contribution to pedagogical VR research. Previous studies have typically utilised quantitative

techniques such as surveys, questionnaires, or Likert scales to gather teachers' attitudes towards VR (e.g., Alfalah, 2018; Dengel, 2018; Langhout, 2019; Serin, 2020). Although this method can be useful, it is often unable to provide the depth of insight into thought processes and attitude formation that qualitative approaches can. Therefore, the current study utilised semi-structured interviews to gather in-depth data from the participants. Another important reason for the current study is that little research has examined the attitudes of HE instructors towards VR. Most studies have sampled either primary school (e.g., Dengel, 2018), secondary school (e.g., Langhout, 2019), or pre-service teachers (e.g., Chou & Hoisington, 2018; Lee & Shea, 2020). Where higher or adult education instructors have been studied, they tend to be drawn from a single department or discipline, such as information technology (Alfalah, 2018) or EFL teachers (Ozkan, 2017). By interviewing instructors across several disciplines and institutions, the current study can gain a novel understanding of how VR is being perceived and implemented within universities. Finally, previous studies have often investigated the perceptions of educators who have never actually used VR before, either in the classroom or personally. These studies have tended to examine expectant beliefs and attitudes towards VR, but participants do not necessarily have a common point of reference. Conversely, participants in the current study all have at least one year of practical teaching experience using VR in a HE classroom, meaning they can give a first-hand account of the practicalities and their attitudes.

5.3 Study Aims

VR as an educational tool is still in its infancy when compared to more well-established technologies such as computers, laptops, and smartboards. Most research conducted within the field of pedagogical VR has examined its educational utility and potential to improve learning outcomes, as opposed to examining the practicalities, attitudes, and perceptions of those using it.

By conducting semi-structured interviews with HE instructors, the current study set out to understand the attitudes and perceptions towards using VR as a teaching tool. Several key aims were identified:

- To understand why instructors chose to use VR, and how they evaluated the experience.
- To examine the kinds of tasks, subjects, or domains that VR was used for, and how it was integrated into the curriculum.
- Gain insight into the logistical considerations of implementing VR in the classroom itself.
- Identify prominent facilitators and barriers to VR integration, and make practical recommendations as to potential solutions.

5.4 Methods

5.4.1 Participants

This study involved conducting one-to-one interviews with members of teaching faculty in a higher education institution. All participants needed to have teaching experience, and be employed as a professor, lecturer, teaching fellow, or other appropriate faculty position. Additionally, all participants had to have had prior experience of delivering teaching to students using VR. Examples of appropriate use include demonstrations during lectures, workshops, and seminars. In total, seven participants (three male; four female) drawn from three separate HE institutions in the United Kingdom were recruited for the study. According to both Braun and Clarke (2006) and Fugard and Potts (2015), this is an adequate sample size for a study of this nature using thematic analysis. Participants had on average 10.6 years ($SD = 6.8$) of teaching experience, and 2.1 years ($SD = 1.2$) experience of using VR in an educational capacity. Participants were drawn from a range of subjects and faculties including nursing, science, and creative industries.

An overview of participant demographic information and teaching experience can be found in Table 2. Pseudonyms were used for all participants to ensure that their contribution remained anonymous.

Table 2

Participant demographic information

Name*	Gender	Teaching Experience (years)	VR Experience (years)	Subject Discipline
Holly	Female	21	5	Psychology
Andrew	Male	19	2	Creative Industries
Amelia	Female	4	2	Nursing
Rebecca	Female	6	2	Nursing
Paul	Male	14	2	Health & Life Sciences
Christopher	Male	4	1	Health & Life Sciences
Sophie	Female	6	1	Biological Science

**Pseudonyms used*

5.4.2 Semi-Structured Interview

A semi-structured interview technique was used during the study, based upon the guidelines and suggestions set out by Smith and Osborn (2003). These typically lasted between 45 – 60 minutes. An interview schedule and associated prompts were used to guide and anchor the discussion, as opposed to stringently adhere to a specific set of questions (see Digital Appendix 5.1.). As the study aimed to explore the attitudes and perspectives of HE instructors based upon their prior experience with VR, the interview schedule was based upon the reflective-on-action model by Johns (1994). This model provided the framework for instructors to describe the scenario and their thought process, recount internal and external influences, and then reflect on their attitudes and opinions now (see Figure 8 for adapted model). There were several reasons why semi-structured interviews were employed as the qualitative method of choice over alternatives such as structured interviews or focus groups. Semi-structured interviews

allow for the researcher to more deeply explore or follow-up on insights raised by the participant that may not have been considered when devising the interview schedule (Louise & Alison, 1994; Smith & Osborn, 2003). As instructors would invariably have unique perspectives on VR owing to differences in experience, subject application, and domain; semi-structured interviews offered the degree of flexibility that structured interviews did not. In addition, it has been suggested that focus-groups are best employed when exploring social issues, or to generate debate or discussion around specific shared experiences (see, Nyumba et al., 2018; Then et al., 2014). However, the only shared reference that participants had was that they had previously used VR in an educational capacity. The specific HMD, software, subject domain, level of proficiency, and HE institution were all dependent on the individual themselves. Therefore, participants may have lacked the shared point of reference required to generate meaningful or extensive discussion within a focus-group setting. It was therefore deemed most appropriate to comprehensively explore the attitudes of each individual instructor towards VR by using one-to-one semi-structured interviews.

5.4.3 Data Collection and Transcription

All interviews were conducted in a quiet and private room at the staff members' own institution. The entirety of the interview was audio recorded using an Olympus VN digital voice recorder. Upon completion of the interview, recordings were transcribed verbatim with the assistance of the Express Scribe Transcription Software to manage the speed and pitch of audio playback (NCH Software, 2019). Non-lexical vocals (e.g., "um," "erm") and linguistic fillers (e.g., "like," "actually") were included in the transcript to give an accurate reflection of all spoken dialogue and utterances. A copy of the unabridged transcripts can be found in Digital Appendix 5.2.

Figure 8

Reflective-on-action model used for devising interview (Johns, 1994)

5.4.4 Thematic Analysis

Thematic analysis (TA) as set out by Braun and Clarke (2006) was chosen as the qualitative method of analysing the interview data. Due to a distinct lack of previous qualitative literature examining instructors' perceptions of university VR implementation, TA offers a theoretically flexible method of identifying key themes and concepts (see, Alhojailan & Ibrahim, 2012; Braun & Clarke, 2006). An inductive, or *bottom-up* approach was undertaken, in that no preconceived coding or thematic framework was used to instruct analysis. Once again, this approach was chosen as there is little previous literature that provides a sufficient predefined set of codes that would necessitate a more nuanced, theoretically-based analysis.

To simply describe the method of analysis as “thematic” would be an oversimplification. “Thematic analysis” is an umbrella term for a range of similar, yet distinct methods of qualitative analysis that each have their own idiosyncrasies. For instance, the emphasis on coding reliability and validity espoused by Miles et al. (2018) is very different from the

emphasis placed on researcher subjectivity promoted by Braun and Clarke (2021). Therefore, precision must be exercised in describing exactly *what* method of thematic analysis is being used, and *how* it is being implemented.

5.4.4.1 Reflexive Thematic Analysis

When this chapter (or the thesis is general) states that “thematic analysis” is being employed, it specifically refers to the method of “reflexive thematic analysis” outlined by Braun and Clarke (2019; 2021a; 2021b). The method has gained widespread acceptance and popularity in the social sciences since the authors published their seminal paper on the subject (see, Braun & Clarke, 2006). Indeed, many researchers have promoted its use by publishing worked-examples and step-by-step guides for successful implementation (e.g., Byrne, 2021). The method allows for the distillation of many original codes into a relatively small number of overarching themes that best encapsulate and describe the findings. Indeed, this overall method is not too distinct from the reductionist processes used in many versions of thematic analysis (see, Alhojailan & Ibrahim, 2012; Fereday & Muir-Cochrane, 2006; Miles et al., 2018). However, since 2006, Braun and Clarke have developed their method further by emphasising the “reflexive” component of their version. For all intents and purposes, the researcher themselves play an integral and active role in the interpretation of data, bringing *their own* experiences to the analysis process. In doing so, the authors state the inherent redundancy of reliability testing and objectivity in the process (Braun & Clarke, 2019b, 2021b, 2021a).

The idea of “reflexivity” is best encapsulated by Braun and Clarke’s assertion that themes are not “discovered,” but rather are “developed” (Braun & Clarke, 2019a). Themes do not precede analysis. Instead, themes are actively constructed and formulated by the researcher *themselves* through immersion in the data. An iterative process of annotating, coding, and reformulating themes necessitate an active involvement in the analysis process as opposed to being set-apart from it. In doing so, Braun and Clarke (2019a, 2019b) recognise and acknowledge that a researcher cannot help but bring their own experiences, philosophies, beliefs, or motivates to the analysis method (hence, the “reflexive” component). Rather than seeing this as an inherent weakness, Braun and Clarke conceptualise the researcher-centric view of analysis as being a strength (Braun & Clarke, 2019a). Indeed, they state that the ideas of generalisability and inter-rater

reliability espoused by positivist philosophies are ultimately incompatible with reflexivity as there cannot be a “right way to code.” As the principal researcher was responsible for every facet of the process from inception of the interview schedule, to facilitating the conversations, they cannot help but recognise and acknowledge their active role in the process. As Braun and Clarke state:

“Reflexive thematic analysis captures approaches that fully embrace qualitative research values and the subjective skills the researcher brings to the process – a research team is not required or even desirable for quality. Analysis, which can be more inductive or more theoretical/deductive, is a situated interpretative reflexive process. Coding is open and organic, with no use of any coding framework. Themes should be the final outcome of data coding and iterative theme development.”

(Braun & Clarke, 2020, p. 334)

The theoretical flexibility of TA coupled with the conceptualisation of researcher subjectivity being an inherent strength lends itself well to this project. Other methods were considered. However, given the aims and objectives of the current study, TA was deemed the most appropriate. For instance, the current study endeavoured to cover a broad range of practical perspectives, as opposed to a more specific phenomenon with the aim of generating future testable hypotheses. Therefore, competing methods like Grounded Theory did not align with the prescribed objectives of the research (see, Chun Tie et al., 2019). Instead, this study followed the guidelines and suggestions presented in a plethora of work published by Braun and Clarke over the past two decades (Braun & Clarke, 2006, 2019b, 2021b).

5.4.4.2 Process of Analysis

The process of analysis involved an initial familiarisation with the data by repeated reading of the transcripts and making preliminary notes. After this, initial codes were generated by providing descriptive annotations of interesting or recurrent occurrences in the data. Codes were both semantically and latently coded, in that not only was the

surface meaning provided by the interviewee noted, but also the interpretation of underlying concepts or ideas (a “reflexive” component). Next, an iterative process of identifying and reviewing codes was undertaken using NVivo 12 (QSR International, 2019). This software package made it easier to manage and visualise the large number of initial codes and annotations. Similar codes (referred to as “nodes” by Nvivo 12) were distilled and grouped together until around 40 remained.

When this process was complete, each code was physically written down and placed on a notice board where they could be physically moved around and placed within preliminary themes. There were two main reasons for taking this approach. Firstly, a physical visualisation of the codes allowed for them to be manipulated and rearranged at will. This satisfied the “immersive” and “iterative” component of TA as the notice board was placed in the office of the principal researcher for several weeks. Codes and themes were continuously moved, rearranged, or merged as new ideas and interpretations were formulated. The second reason for this approach was although NVivo is useful for arranging and collating codes neatly, the software tended to emphasise the quantitative data associated with the analysis. For example, the software keeps count of the number of times a code occurred across the data set. Although this is useful, it can also distort a more holistic approach to the data. For example, numerous occurrences of a code are not a prerequisite to determine its overall importance or classification as a theme. By using both technological and non-technological analysis methods in tandem, a complete and informed approach could be taken when generating overarching themes. An illustration of how certain codes might relate to overarching themes can be found in Digital Appendix 5.3.

5.5 Findings and Analysis

By using TA to analyse the data, five main themes were formulated that best encapsulate the overarching ideas espoused by the interviewees. These included: (a) applications and benefits; (b) curriculum integration; (c) classroom logistics; (d) barriers to application; and (e) evaluation. A brief description of each theme can be found in Table 3.

Table 3

Overview of formulated themes

Theme	Description
Applications and Benefits	Attitudes relating to <i>why</i> and <i>for what</i> VR should be used for in the classroom. For example, what subjects, domains, or activities?
Curriculum Integration	Attitudes relating to <i>how</i> VR should be used within the specific module. For example, should it supplement or replace existing methods?
Classroom Logistics	How the instructor navigates the logistics of implementing VR in the classroom itself (e.g., the physical space, supervision, and staff roles).
Barriers to Application	Instructor perceptions of the barriers and impediments that exist when implementing VR in HE. <i>Subtheme 1: Institutional Facilitation - Relates to barriers concerning how the university itself funds and supports VR implementation.</i> <i>Subtheme 2: Second-Order Barriers - Barriers that relate to the instructor's technological proficiency and self-efficacy.</i>
Evaluation	How instructors perceive and react to the response of their students towards VR as a learning tool.

5.5.1 Applications and Benefits

The *applications and benefits* theme concerns the nature of the tasks that instructors used VR for, as well as its associated pedagogical benefits. Instructors identified several domains and tasks where they felt VR could confer a novel learning benefit over traditional modes of education. Tasks that required experiential learning, or the need to embody the perspective of another person were commonly considered to be uniquely suited to VR. Indeed, these attitudes are congruent with the illusion of body-ownership described by Slater and colleagues (2009; 2022). By allowing students to occupy the body of a virtual other, it was hoped that the emotional empathy evoked would facilitate applied socio-cognitive change (as discussed in Section 2.2.3.). Instructors also remarked that VR was uniquely suited to provide this novel perspective:

“You can tell somebody, you can talk to them about it, you can show them pictures, but to be immersed in something for even a very short time and experience what someone might feel I think is phenomenal.”

Amelia

“I think it gives them a first-person perspective of what is going on. So yes, there are advantages. From that point of view, rather than in a traditional lecture where it goes in one ear and out the other. This actually puts them in a situation where they can actually relate to what is happening.”

Paul

To give a specific example, Rebecca used VR to teach nursing students about sensory difficulties that some patients might exhibit in a hospital setting. Through body-ownership of a virtual patient, ambient noise, lighting, and visual disturbances were all amplified to provide an embodied perspective of what it might be like to experience such a situation. Rebecca remarked that this experience facilitated behaviour change in her students when it came to applied practice. Far from being anecdotal, a body of research has supported the use of VR simulations for perspective taking and empathic elicitation. For instance, de Borst et al. (2020) found increased activity in areas of the brain relating to the bodily-self during a perspective taking VR experience involving emotionally salient stimuli. Similarly Herrera and colleagues (2018) demonstrated that participants who underwent a VR experience where they embodied a homeless person were more likely to display positive behaviour changes than those who did not undergo the VR simulation. Therefore, the desire of those interviewed to use VR as a tool for perspective taking and experiential learning is supported by a body of empirical evidence that suggests that it is more effective than non-immersive alternatives. Previous qualitative research (e.g., Chou & Hoisington, 2018) has also promoted the use of VR for “experiential immersion” (p. 363). Chou and Hoisington found that primary-school teachers thought that VR could give pupils a novel insight into the lived-experiences, cultures, and attitudes of other people.

They were keen to remark that this kind of insight is difficult to replicate using traditional means of education and is regarded as a promising application of VR.

Using VR to provide affective learning and first-hand perspective taking was not the only pedagogical application identified by instructors. The use of VR to teach students cognitive information, especially when this was highly visual or conceptual was also espoused. For instance, instructors believed that the technology could allow students to visualise environments that cannot be easily replicated in reality (e.g., inside a human brain). This would be especially useful in subjects like architecture, engineering, mathematics, and physiology where many theories require students to visualise complex or abstract arrangements. As Psychology lecturer Holly noted, it was through her personal experience of struggling to understand brain physiology that she decided to incorporate VR into her classroom:

"I think for me it was the visualisation really. I found that I was always really interested in the brain, but I could never get to grips with the structure and the function. But VR can allow you to step into that environment and rotate it and visualise it. It's totally unique and gives students a perspective that I simply can't."

Holly

Instructors in the current study also felt that VR could help solidify cognitive or theoretical concepts that were first learned in class using traditional teaching methods. As Amelia noted:

"We would use VR at the end, which kind of encapsulated all the theory and hands-on stuff that we done during the session."

Amelia

As well as encompassing theoretical learning, some instructors also used VR to assist revision by making 360° videos of their lecturers or seminars. Provided the student had access to a HMD at home, they could re-watch and review previous material in preparation for examinations, tests, and essays. By utilising HMDs to revise material in the same environment it was first encountered (e.g., a specific lecture hall or classroom), the instructor hoped it would help students “understand better” than simply reviewing PowerPoint slides or audio recordings. As Creative Industries lecturer, Andrew stated:

“If any of them miss it (students), and if they have access to the VR technology, then they can review it again.”

Andrew

The current study found that instructors had similar attitudes towards using VR as a cognitive teaching tool as other research. Instructors repeatedly expressed that VR could aid the visualisation of complex or abstract ideas and environments such as the human brain or construction and architectural principles. These findings align with those of Serin (2020) who found the majority of teachers interviewed either agreed or strongly agreed that VR could assist students’ schematic thinking and ability to visualise complex problems. The current study also found more novel applications in this domain such as using VR to revise and revisit previously taught material.

Previous qualitative studies examining the perceptions of educators towards VR have tended to promote the technology as a medium for simulated fieldtrips (e.g., Chou & Hoisington, 2018; Cooper et al., 2019), virtual laboratory experiments (e.g., Langhout, 2019), or the visualisation of spatial problems (e.g., Dengel, 2018). However, instructors in the current study frequently described using VR as a medium for experiential learning, perspective taking, and behaviour change. Many instructors hoped that by allowing their students to embody the lived experience of another, VR would elicit an empathetic response. Some instructors even said that their students displayed positive changes in behaviour and applied practice owing to the VR experience. In line with the systematic review presented in Study Chapter One, instructors were also keen to employ VR as a

means of cognitive learning support. This was especially true when VR could provide a degree of immersion and visualisation that could not be recreated using more traditional means of education.

5.5.2 Curriculum Integration

A recurrent theme in the data was that of curriculum integration, or how educators envisage VR being used and applied within the syllabus. As previously highlighted by Southgate and Smith (2017), this is a component of pedagogical VR research that has often been neglected. The most prominent attitude of participants was that VR should be integrated into the curriculum as a form of blended or multimodal learning. As Garrison and Kanuka (2004) note, blended learning combines traditional methods of teaching with technology to achieve a set learning outcome. Technology does not replace existing methods, but rather complements and supplements them. The current study found that instructors would utilise a range of didactic and technological approaches to achieve a set learning outcome in their classes. Instructors were keen to stress that it was important to integrate the VR experience into pre-existing methods of teaching:

“Education works that way. We have VLEs; we have online resources; we have Padlet; we have Turning Point. We have all these different technologies, that hopefully enhance the learning experience. VR should be used in that capacity. It should not be a replacement; it should be an enhancement.”

Andrew

Instructors also tended to be cautious about integrating VR as a stand-alone method of teaching in their curriculum. Although the consensus was that VR could be effective when applied properly, it could not be seen as applicable in all scenarios. One participant summed up this attitude succinctly when they noted:

“(VR) is not a panacea, but there is certainly a place for it.”

Holly

One of the implications of VR being viewed as a supplementary learning tool was that instructors acknowledged that careful planning had to be undertaken to ensure that the technology was appropriately integrated into the curriculum:

"It's not a toy. So, for us it has to be integrated into the teaching, it has to mean something. It has to reinforce the session that we use. So, it was very carefully planned."

Sophie

"I think it's about tailoring the lesson. It is like everything else, if you just use it for the sake of using it, and overkill, people don't even get the learning from it. I think it is about tailoring."

Christopher

Part of the integration process was to ensure that VR was not employed when its use was not required. As Rebecca succinctly summed up:

"You don't just use it because you want to use it. It has to mean something".

Rebecca

These attitudes are consistent with what Picciano (2009) termed as "blending with purpose" (p. 7). This approach places learning outcomes as the driving force behind the choice of teaching materials used, as opposed to the technology itself dictating the objectives. Instructors explicitly stated that to use VR without a predefined pedagogical purpose could impair the learning process. This was especially true if the technology was shoehorned into parts of the curriculum where its use was not warranted. Prior research in other institutions have reported similar attitudes. For instance, schoolteachers were vehement that VR should only be used for a specific purpose, and as part of a well-

structured and designed lesson (Fransson et al., 2020). Simply using the technology because of its novelty, or without a predefined objective could render its use redundant. In practice, this means that the technology should be used only when it can provide a unique perspective on a given topic. As a result, VR is not suitable for all subject areas or disciplines, and discretion must be exercised by module coordinators and instructors as to whether its use will confer an educational benefit for their students or not.

Clearly instructors see VR as a tool to supplement and enhance knowledge learned in class by using the unique immersive abilities of the technology. However, instructors did not suggest that it should be used as a means of replacement, nor did they convey the attitude that the technology should supplant traditional didactic forms of HE.

5.5.3 Classroom Logistics

Classroom logistics refers to how the instructor behaves and organises the VR lesson itself. This includes considerations such as the physical space, classroom management, and the need for additional support from members of staff and faculty. Most instructors referred to the fact that they did not have access to a dedicated VR space for teaching and had to manage with normal classrooms or lecture halls. This was often due to stringent room bookings, limited space on city campuses, or as a result of the number of students in the class itself:

“Because of the number of students we have, we can’t choose the classroom we get. With this (VR) we need enough space to be able to move up and down and around the place. But when you’ve got forty students in a class, it is really difficult to work with. It would be great to have a space just for the VR stuff. That is what we are working towards, but we aren’t there yet.”

Rebecca

“So, the majority of time we just use a normal classroom. Usually one with a bit more room. For the stationary kind of videos, it is fine. But if you had to say to

them, 'you need to stand up to do this,' that is when you'll run into problems. I don't think that space would be practical."

Paul

Although this concern is not unique to HE instructors as exhibited by Fransson and colleagues (2020), a novel finding was that a lack of dedicated space limited the *types* of VR experiences they could offer. For example, if chairs could not be moved, VR applications that required locomotion or extended movement were unable to be utilised. Instead, only experiences that required the student to remain stationary could be employed in teaching. As a result of these logistical considerations, a desire for a dedicated VR space or lab was almost universal. However, as instructors noted, universities often lack the resources or physical space to provide such a facility. Therefore, it is often the case that instructors had to work within the confines of their physical environment to deliver VR teaching.

A second logistical consideration was the number of students in each class. Most instructors noted that large class sizes created logistical problems in organising and managing lessons, as well as often needing to utilise additional staff members to assist. Instructors mentioned that they would often recruit other members of their faculty to be present in the classroom during VR lessons. For those who were unable to do this, they often conveyed the attitude that this was indeed a necessity for future practice.

"I guess what we have learnt is that you need enough people in the room to be able to support them (the students)."

Rebecca

"We really need a second person in class with us just for that first hour when we are doing that activity to help. Someone needs to be able to move the equipment around, (or) to be able to help."

Amelia

“So, we need extra resources in terms of manpower when we are doing that session as well, so that’s also a big factor.”

Christopher

Instructors also noted that they would need to consider how to manage the classroom appropriately to facilitate both traditional and VR learning. For instance, often classes would need to be broken down into multiple sub-groups to accommodate all students and give them a chance to undergo the VR experience:

“When we have three groups, all of them can’t use it (VR) at the same time. So, we have to break down the sessions. We have to work out, ‘right, one group can do the VR activity in the morning, the other in the afternoon.’ [...] The set-up time and planning is huge.”

Amelia

Both instructors in the current study as well as Fransson et al. (2020) mentioned the need for additional members of staff to help facilitate and manage the lesson. This is of course dependent on the flexibility of the individual institution to consider timetabling and scheduling practicalities so that additional staff members are available. Concerns relating to classroom management was also a prevalent attitude expressed by 50% of instructors in a study by Ozkan (2017). Furthermore, previous research has demonstrated that instructors often struggle with managing, structuring, and facilitating lessons even when non-VR tools such as computers and laptops are used (Tondeur et al., 2017; Windschitl & Sahl, 2002). These findings suggest that an element of control is lost whenever technology is integrated into the classroom, and instructors must address these logistical concerns with careful planning and lesson structuring.

5.5.4 Barriers to Application

One of the most common attitudes were the barriers and impediments encountered whilst using VR. These impaired the ability of the instructor to utilise the technology fully and are represented in two distinct subthemes based upon the nature and source of the barrier: *institutional facilitation*; and *second-order*.

5.5.4.1 Institutional Facilitation

Institutional barriers relate to the attitudes and perceptions that instructors had towards their institution's facilitation of VR teaching and innovation. Instructors were generally discouraged by the level of financial backing, investment and support they received from their own university. Instructors commonly remarked that although their institution was receptive towards using VR in principle, they seldom made the financial investment necessary. This made acquisition of headsets, computers, and software licences challenging.

"If the university want to go down this line then they will need to spend money, and they are not willing to."

Paul

"In my experience, certain universities, particularly the modern universities - the post-90s ones - are just really reluctant to spend the money to invest in this sort of thing."

Andrew

The problem of procuring financial backing for VR is not exclusive to the current study, but appears to be prevalent among instructors and educators from a variety of educational institutions (see, Chou & Hoisington, 2018; Cooper et al., 2019). Specifically, both the current study and existing literature found that instructors worried about acquiring funds from their institution to purchase HMDs and other necessary equipment.

When instructors were asked why institutions would not financially invest, many said that this was due to scepticism regarding VR's longevity and economic feasibility. As Andrew remarked:

"People are saying 'it is just a fad.' Therefore, they are not prepared to put any level of investment in [...] for something that may or may not be just a fad."

Andrew

Instructors were often understanding of their universities' reticence to make the financial injection necessary. If indeed VR fails to have a long-term future as a pedagogical method, universities may fail to see a tangible return on their investment.

The most common barrier resulting from a lack of institutional investment was obtaining enough headsets for the entire class. This often meant that HMDs had to be shared and rotated among multiple students, limiting the amount of time each person had to interact fully with the technology:

"It presents quite a lot of logistical problems for looking at equipment. Trying to get 230 students through the experience of using VR is quite a challenge [...] So our main problem is getting equipment especially when we have only six headsets at the moment."

Amelia

Additionally, instructors observed that many applications of VR made the presumption that students themselves had access to the technology, which was often not the case. This meant that students commonly could not access VR experiences outside of designated class times. One possible solution would be to implement an approach similar to that proposed by Olmos et al. (2018) referred to as "bring-your-own-device" (BYOD). BYOD involves students using their own smartphones to view 360° material by attaching them

to a Mobile-VR headset such as the Google Cardboard (see, Olmos-Reya, Ferreira-Cavalcanti, Soler, et al., 2018; Olmos-Reya, Ferreira-Cavalcanti, Contero, et al., 2018). However, this may cause additional problems such as insurance and liability concerns if a device is broken during classroom use. Additionally, it assumes that all students have a compatible phone that is capable of being inserted into a Mobile-VR headset.

Problems resulting from the institutions' IT and software systems was another common impediment. Ports being blocked by a firewall, poor internet connectivity, and restrictions accessing common VR platforms like Steam and Unity were noted. Even if these problems could be addressed, some educators had serious concerns that most universities do not have the technical infrastructure necessary to adopt VR. For instance, Andrew noted that he recorded lectures or seminars on a 360° camera for students to re-watch at a later date. However, a traditional one-hour lecture could generate a file in excess of 50-gigabytes. The instructor noted that no current university platform such as the virtual learning environment (VLE) could accommodate files of that size to be uploaded, shared, or streamed:

"The files are too big to stick on a VLE. So, the infrastructure currently in place is not set up to cope with that form of technology, and it never was."

Andrew

A lack of institutional investment and technological infrastructure are two of the issues raised by instructors in the study. Similar to Alfalah (2018), instructors were also concerned with the lack of an institutional support network and administrative guidance. This often led to instructors having nowhere to turn if they ran into problems using the technology. This led to nearly all participants stating that they were forced to use their "own initiative" when implementing VR into their teaching. This often consisted of trying various approaches to VR teaching to see what worked best:

"It is taken people like myself who quite literally are mucking around with this technology, who can see that it can kind of benefit some of my students."

Andrew

"Nobody has asked us to do it. But pretty much the drive of the project is wholeheartedly down to us and nobody else. So, I think it is a project we are trying to drive ourselves."

Amelia

Based on these concerns, it seems prudent to suggest that a centralised support network is an essential component of efficient VR implementation. A pooling of knowledge from across the university, even in an informal manner, could give instructors the support and guidance they need to facilitate the technology in their classrooms.

Regardless of the institutional barriers encountered, nearly all instructors agreed that it would take a shift in educational policy to accommodate VR in HE. This means that faculty, institutions, and third-parties will all need to interact to provide the conditions necessary for widespread adoption of the technology. For instance, barriers related to technical infrastructure cannot be solved by the institution alone and will require input and guidance from others to find efficient solutions.

5.5.4.2 Second-Order Barriers

Ertmer (1999) defined second-order barriers as those that are intrinsic to the individual themselves such as beliefs around self-efficacy and technological confidence. It is well established that these internal factors can influence the behavioural intention to use and adopt technology (see, Davis, 1989).

Although instructors noted that VR was a novel teaching method, they often remarked that their own lack of technical skills or proficiency was a barrier to upscaling or utilisation. Surprisingly, many of the instructors interviewed confessed to not being

technically savvy themselves but enjoyed using VR regardless. Statements like “I’m not technical” and “I’m a complete novice” occurred frequently. Despite their enjoyment and determination to utilise VR, the lack of technical knowledge commonly resulted in issues:

“We have hit so many snags and problems and we still don’t know how to fix it. I’m not the most technical person in the world, so I need someone there to help if things go wrong. Unfortunately, we don’t always know who to turn to in order to get that help.”

Amelia

“Things go wrong quite a lot, and it can be hard to fix them when you’re running a class. Things like the controllers not working or connecting to the headset. The problem is, when these issues pop up, I don’t know who in the university could give us that information.”

Rebecca

Several studies have identified a lack of self-efficacy and technical skills as being a source of apprehension among schoolteachers and HE instructors (see, Alfalah, 2018; Fransson et al., 2020). Therefore, appropriate institutional support and training is essential to give instructors the skills and knowledge necessary to implement VR effectively. Fortunately, as Lee and Shea (2020) demonstrate, it does not take long for individuals to develop the skills required when quality training is offered. However, this is often easier done in theory than in practice. One solution would be for VR facilitators to make use of their institutions’ Learning Technology team. Most HE institutions in the UK employ several Learning Technologists to work either centrally, or within a specific school or faculty. The role of these specialist members of staff is to help research, implement, and troubleshoot areas of pedagogical technology (see, Flynn, 2015; Fox & Sumner, 2014). In fact, research has found that close collaboration with a Learning Technologist not only improves the technical efficiency of HE instructors, but also their students (Logan & Stone, 2016). Therefore, a concerted effort between teaching faculty and specialist staff needs to exist in order to facilitate training and technical expertise. By doing so, instructors have a

direct point-of-contact to address any technical issues that they have, as well as be provided with additional professional development opportunities and support.

Instructors suggested that their lack of technical ability often resulted in suboptimal VR experiences being used in the classroom. For instance, instructors remarked that they did not know where to find bespoke material that was specifically relevant to their lesson. This was a concern already raised by Jensen and Konradsen, (2018) in their systematic review, and has been repeated by educators themselves (see, Chou & Hoisington, 2018). As a result, a few instructors attempted to create their own bespoke VR experiences. Unfortunately, a lack of confidence and proficiency using 360° cameras, editing software, creation suites, and HMDs meant that this was extremely challenging:

“It is a massive learning curve for all of us. None of us had really used VR before, never mind trying to create something. We had no idea about cameras, or what to buy, or how to edit it. And that was before we even got to the sound working. It’s a minefield.”

Rebecca

“It is just really difficult. The content that is currently available is okay, but it really wasn’t what we were looking for. I wanted something where students could actually interact and see the movement of the joints and muscles and things like that. I spoke to a few people about trying to create something really simple. But without knowing how to code and that sort of thing, it’s impossible.”

Sophie

It is therefore important to note that a lack of self-efficacy does not merely impact on the ability to *use* HMDs, but rather extends to the quality of VR experiences that are able to be offered to students. Fortunately, the educational VR market is undergoing exponential growth, and this is predicted to continue (Fortune Business Insights, 2023). Therefore, the availability of pedagogical VR software, bespoke creation suites, and experiences is

expected to increase over the coming years. Although this may not be suitable for all instructors, it does represent a shift in emphasis towards VR's educational utility. However, based on current research (e.g., Alfalah, 2018; Chou & Hoisington, 2018; Fransson et al., 2020), major barriers regarding self-efficacy, access to training, and technological efficiency all remain major impediments to optimal implementation. Although interest in educational VR experiences is expanding, this will not fundamentally change *how* it is implemented in HE institutions unless instructors and facilitators are given the requisite support, guidance, and training.

5.5.5 Evaluation

Instructors emphasised the importance of evaluating the VR teaching in their institution. Nearly all instructors interviewed thought it was important to gather feedback on the students' experience of VR learning through formal (e.g., questionnaires) or informal means (e.g., verbal feedback). The outcome of the evaluative process was important in deciding whether VR teaching was worth continuing to pursue. Students generally enjoyed using the technology which created excitement, heightened motivation, and resulted in the achievement of set learning outcomes. As one instructor noted, this influenced the decision to continue using VR:

"We would love for it to continue because it has been evaluated so well. It just added a different vibe to the room. They were excited. They were looking forward to it."

Holly

In addition, some instructors noted that their evaluations would form part of a grant proposal to request additional support from their institution. Regardless of the reason for evaluation, instructors generally had the attitude that students found learning through VR to be fun, exciting, and motivating. These attitudes are similar to a number of other studies that have investigated how instructors perceive student engagement (e.g., Chou & Hoisington, 2018; Lee & Shea, 2020; Serin, 2020). When students themselves are asked to self-report their level of enjoyment whilst using VR, they commonly express similar attitudes (e.g., Farra et al., 2018; Fogarty et al., 2017; Greenwald et al., 2018).

Although a positive student experience is not necessarily a prerequisite for better learning outcomes, previous research has generally concluded that motivation and engagement through technology can have a positive impact on achievement (e.g., Gamon, 2001; Heafner, 2004; Su & Cheng, 2015).

Although students enjoyed the VR sessions, instructors did witness some trepidation on the part of the user. Sometimes students were self-conscious when using the VR equipment in front of their peers. This was often the result of their physical actions (e.g., arm movements) in VR being without context to an outside observer. This sometimes led to embarrassment and a failure to interact fully with the technology, especially in a large class:

“People get very self-conscious as well I think when you are asking them to wear a headset in front of 30 other students in a class. I suspect that a lot of students don’t try it because they are self-conscious.”

Holly

A solution was to display what the user sees in VR on an external screen so that everyone else could watch it. This would mean that the observer could witness what the user was doing, providing a point of reference for their physical movements. As Christopher pointed out:

“People are less self-conscious if people realise what they are doing, rather than them just moving about randomly.”

Christopher

Additionally, smaller class sizes or the ability to use the HMD privately could help alleviate some of the anxiety associated with VR use.

Instructors also raised concerns that some students reported cybersickness, or the inability to use VR due to medical conditions. This is a common problem that has been identified already as a barrier towards educational integration of HMDs and associated technology (Jensen & Konradsen, 2018; Southgate & Smith, 2017). It is imperative that future practice factors in these considerations and makes alternative methods of learning available for students who cannot partake in VR.

5.6 Discussion and Conclusion

By conducting interviews with HE instructors across multiple institutions and disciplines, the study examined attitudes relating to the practicalities of implementing VR in university classrooms. Thematic analysis was used to interpret the data which yielded five main themes: (a) applications and benefits; (b) curriculum integration; (c) classroom logistics; (d) barriers to application; and (e) evaluation.

Instructors proposed a range of benefits and novel applications for VR teaching such as embodied experience and perspective taking. Not only did instructors propose that this could give students a range of novel insights into the lived-experience of others, but it could also facilitate practical behaviour change. For instance, one instructor remarked that nursing students who underwent a VR experience simulating multisensory processing difficulties displayed applied behaviour change in practice. Specifically, the instructor noted that students changed how they interacted with patients when they were on work-placement. Indeed, previous research has suggested that the immersive nature of VR can facilitate changes in participant attitudes, behaviours, and perspectives (e.g., Adefila et al., 2016; Bujić et al., 2020). Therefore, the integration of VR to give participants a unique perspective into the lived-experience of others offers a tantalising pedagogical opportunity for domains as varied as nursing, healthcare, and psychology. In addition, instructors also exalted the benefit of using VR to teach highly visual or abstract concepts. Indeed, these attitudes concur with the findings of the systematic review in Study One that tended to find a scholastic benefit to integrating VR when the task required schematic thinking or visualisation.

Regardless of the precise application of VR, instructors were almost universally agreed that it should form a supplementary component of the curriculum, not a replacement. One of the major contributions of the current study was to investigate exactly *how* VR was envisaged in terms of its practical application as a teaching medium. As other researchers have already mentioned, this has been an area of research that has often been neglected (Southgate & Smith, 2017). The findings suggest that instructors view VR as just “one tool among many.” Consistent with the edicts of educational researchers (e.g., Picciano, 2009), instructors remarked that VR has to serve a specific and predefined pedagogical purpose. It cannot merely be integrated because of its novelty value or “fun factor.” Rather, consistent with the body of non-university VR research (e.g., Fransson et al., 2020), instructors were of the attitude that the technology must only be applied where its use fulfils a predefined learning objective.

One of the most important aspects raised by instructors was the logistical considerations involved in implementing VR. This related to how instructors planned and conducted themselves when they were in the classroom. The current study, as well as the findings of Fransson et al. (2020) suggest that a dedicated VR space is needed to fully utilise the technology. Although instructors were still able to implement VR, they often mentioned that the lack of a dedicated space constrained the types of experiences that they could use. For instance, if the simulation required extended movement or locomotion, this was often challenging in a cramped environment. Instructors also remarked that they needed additional support from other members of faculty to accommodate the VR session. Similar to those attitudes espoused in Ozkan (2017), instructors had issues managing the class when the VR technology went wrong or students ran into problems. If VR is being implemented in a large class, an additional member of faculty could help troubleshoot problems, allowing the instructor themselves to continue teaching (e.g., a Learning Technologist). In addition, based on the findings of the current study as well as previous literature (e.g., Fransson et al., 2020; Ozkan, 2017), it may be advisable to refrain from using VR in larger classes. Rather, the logistics of using it with a much smaller number of students in a seminar or workshop might be easier to manage.

One of the most prominent attitudes was that of the barriers encountered when implementing VR. Instructors stated that support from their institution was generally poor. This was especially true when it came to procuring financial help to purchase HMDs, and associated licences. Indeed, this is an issue that is extremely common across educational institutions (Chou & Hoisington, 2018; Cooper et al., 2019). One of the reasons cited was that institutions commonly envisage VR as being merely a “fad” or “gimmick.” As a result, there was a general reluctance to invest the funds necessary to support teaching. Ironically, unless innovative instructors are given access to the dedicated space, support, and finance in the first place, it is difficult to challenge these institutional perceptions. The current study cut a wide swath in terms of its objectives and aims. Specifically, it endeavoured to gain a broad perspective of VR’s place within education as opposed to focusing on one particular aspect. However, on the back of the current findings, future research should specifically focus on the institutional barriers that instructors encounter. By not only interviewing instructors, but also senior university members (e.g., Principle of Teaching, Deans, Departmental Head), researchers can suggest practical and concerted efforts that could support innovative teaching. For instance, does university management conceptualise VR as merely a “fad,” or are there more fundamental reasons why support is lacking?

Despite the barriers, instructors were positive about the impact that VR had made to their teaching. They remarked that it helped motivate and engage students in the classroom, citing it as adding a “different vibe” to the educational experience. Although previous research has found similar attitudes (e.g., Chou & Hoisington, 2018; Lee & Shea, 2020; Serin, 2020), these typically are not in HE. In addition, the current study was able to understand *why* instructors thought the evaluation process was important. This is something that preceding research has typically not investigated or considered. For instance, instructors noted that a positive evaluation would likely form the basis of a grant application or request for further funding to support their VR endeavours. Although this study only interviewed instructors, their perception of their students’ response was similar to those identified in the systematic review. This is compelling evidence that students are receptive to the use of VR in HE. However, as stated at the beginning of this chapter, it is ultimately the attitudes of instructors that truly determines whether VR will

be implemented in the classroom. The current study has identified several barriers that could impede successful integration, and ultimately this thesis must take practical steps to study and address these.

5.6.1 Limitations

The current study attempted to gather a broad swath of attitudes on the subject of VR implementation in HE. One of the major advantages was that instructors were recruited from several institutions, offering a wide array of perspectives and attitudes. However, there are limitations that should be addressed.

All but one participant had been using VR in an educational capacity for two years or less. As a result, most instructors still had limited experience with VR teaching in HE. This lack of exposure might have amplified technical barriers such as a lack of self-efficacy or knowledge. Conceivably, those who have been using VR for a longer period will be more versed in its technical and applied aspects and be able to deal with issues as they arise. Despite this, the relative novelty of VR in general HE made it extremely challenging to identify instructors with a wealth of experience. Indeed, it was not until 2013 that the first commercially viable headset was launched (see, Freina & Ott, 2015; Lyne, 2013), meaning that the technology is still novel for most users. Future research should seek to examine the longitudinal change in attitudes associated with long-term VR application. By doing so, researchers and practitioners can make practical suggestions based on instructors' past experience, and what steps they took to overcome challenges and impediments.

5.6.2 Conclusion

The current study found that instructors were positive about the impact that VR could have on their subject. Instructors expressed that VR teaching was evaluated well by students who often found it fun, engaging, and motivating. However practical barriers relating to financial backing, institutional support, and self-efficacy were common. Although this did not dissuade educators in the current study, it could still have an impact on those who wish to implement the technology in future. Therefore, it is not enough for this thesis to merely report on these findings. Rather, practical solutions that may help

alleviate these major concerns should be sought, and then investigated. Indeed, this is a major advantage of the *multiphase approach* employed in this thesis. As Creswell and Plano Clark (2017) allude to, this means that the researcher is afforded the opportunity to investigate pertinent questions that arise in one study in the proceeding one. Therefore, issues surrounding curriculum integration, logistics, and accessibility can all be investigated further in the upcoming chapters.

6 STUDY THREE – PSYCHOLOGY LECTURERS’ ATTITUDE TOWARDS MOBILE VIRTUAL REALITY: A FOCUS GROUP STUDY

6.1 Chapter Overview

One of the most interesting findings from the preceding study centred on the idea of using VR as a means of *experiential* learning. Numerous instructors exalted the potential of VR to give their students an embodied experience of what it might be like *to be* someone else. Despite this approach being commonly employed in nursing and healthcare, it has applications in several diverse disciplines. For example, despite psychology (and the social sciences more broadly) being underrepresented in both Study One and Two, the idea of giving students a first-hand perspective of another’s life is a tantalising one. This is especially true when one considers that VR allows the viewer an unparalleled perspective into the cognitive processes and behaviours of another. Consequently, it was surprising to see that these applications had been neglected in psychological education. As already noted in the previous study, it is the receptiveness and willingness of the instructors themselves that dictate whether the technology will ultimately be applied within a module or curriculum. Therefore, the current study aimed to examine the attitudes of HE psychology instructors towards integrating and using VR technology within their teaching activities.

The next issue was to address a practical impediment raised in Study Two. Namely, that a lack of finance made the procurement and acquisition of high-end VR headsets challenging. Therefore, there was little utility in assessing the attitudes of psychology instructors using HMDs that they would likely not be able to acquire *en masse*. As a result, the current study implemented low-cost and accessible Mobile-VR headsets that could feasibly be distributed to all students on a particular course or module. As a result, instructors were given the opportunity to interact with a prospective teaching method that could be realistically implemented.

Attitudes and perceptions were collected through a series of online focus-groups, comprising of HE psychology instructors from a multitude of institutions across the United Kingdom. This allowed for the collection of a wide array of perspectives and attitudes, whilst also affording each focus-group member the opportunity to discuss their ideas among peers.

6.2 Justification and Novel Contribution

Both preceding studies have indicated that psychology has been an underrepresented area in pedagogical VR research. This is despite instructors in Study Two suggesting numerous experiential applications for the technology. For example, educators indicated that by allowing students to embody the lived-experience of another person, that student would ultimately be able to gain novel insights into a given topic. For example, students have the potential to better understand the cognitive processes of someone suffering from a mental health condition like schizophrenia or anxiety. However, as of yet, there has been no research that has investigated the attitudes of HE psychology staff towards the possibility of integrating this technology in education. Where limited research into HE perspectives has been carried out, this has been almost entirely quantitative in nature (e.g. Alfalah, 2018), failing to provide the depth of insight afforded by qualitative methods like interviews or focus-groups (Doody et al., 2013; Finch & Lewis, 2003). Further, at the time of writing, no research has exclusively focused on addressing the attitudes of HE psychology faculty towards low-cost and accessible Mobile-VR systems. As Study Two demonstrated, the high-end VR systems commonly employed in experimental research are often too expensive to be procured by instructors *en masse*. This represents a major impediment to wide-spread application in HE. Therefore, this study makes a novel contribution to the literature by specifically focusing on an accessible means of delivering VR experiences to students in universities.

6.3 Aims and Objectives

By conducting a series of online focus-groups, the present study aimed to address several key objectives:

- Identify a range of domains and teaching activities within HE psychology where Mobile-VR could be effectively applied.
- Understand the general perception towards Mobile-VR headsets such as user self-efficacy, accessibility, and efficiency.
- To understand how psychology lecturers perceive the impact of Mobile-VR on student learning and motivation.
- To assess whether Mobile-VR could alleviate some of the barriers associated with high-end hardware by being cheaper, more accessible, and easier to use.

6.4 Methods

6.4.1 Participants

The present study recruited 16 psychology lecturers (seven male; nine female) from 11 separate HE institutions in the United Kingdom. An advert was placed on social media platforms such as Twitter asking for interested parties to contact the principal researcher. Once initial contact had been made, the prospective participants were presented with an information sheet, allowing them to make an informed decision as to whether or not they wanted to partake.

Participants were required to be employed in a teaching capacity at a HE institution, as well as having no previous experience of delivering VR in an educational capacity. Personal experience of VR (e.g., through gaming or entertainment) was however permitted. The reason for this restriction was to ensure that all focus-group members had a similar level of experience with pedagogical VR. This helped ensure that attitudes and perceptions could be discussed among peers who all had a similar level of experience and point of reference. In addition, this also helped prevent focus-group members with

experience of pedagogical VR dominating the discussion, potentially stifling the exchange of ideas that focus-groups can facilitate (see, Then et al., 2014).

The average age of a participant was 34 years ($SD = 8$) with a range of 24 – 58 years. Participants had on average five years ($SD = 4$) of teaching experience in a HE capacity. There were eight (50%) focus group-members who stated they had previous experience with VR technology in some capacity. Of those eight, six had used VR for gaming purposes, one for entertainment and films, and one for research.

6.4.2 Mobile-VR Headset

A Maxbox 3.1. Mobile Headset was posted to all focus-group members to allow them to access 360° material (see Figure 9). Like the Google Cardboard, the HMD is flat-packed and self-assembled upon delivery. It allows smartphones of around 6.5” inches with a built-in gyroscope to access VR content on a variety of online platforms. The HMD accommodates all operating systems (i.e., Android or iOS) provided that the relevant 360° applications are installed on the phone (e.g., YouTube, Google Expeditions, Vimeo, Within). A QR code printed on the side of the HMD allows the user to register it with the Google Cardboard app, providing a personalised and calibrated experience. A more in-depth overview of Mobile-VR, and how its technical hardware and specifications differ from high-end HMDs can be found in Section 2.2.4.2.

Figure 9

MaxBox 3.1. Mobile-VR Headset used in this study

6.4.3 Virtual Reality Stimuli

Participants received links to psychology relevant VR experiences. These 360° videos covered clinical, forensic, environmental, and developmental psychology. The suitability of each 360° experience was discussed and approved by the principal researcher and three additional members of the supervisory team. Discussions centred on three key criteria: (a) whether the video was of acceptable quality (i.e., resolution and graphics); (b) whether the video presented an accurate experience of what it purported to represent (validity); and (c) whether the experience would be of educational interest and value to psychology lecturers. Copyright permission to use the clips as part of this thesis was sought and granted by all holders prior to commencement of the study. A full list of required viewing can be found in Table 4. Links to each of the videos can be found in Digital Appendix 6.1.

6.4.4 Procedure

Approximately two-weeks prior to the online focus-group, participants were sent the HMD along with a set of instructions detailing how to assemble and access material (see Digital Appendix 6.2.). Participants were emailed URL links to a variety of 360° videos relevant to psychology education. As a minimum requirement, all focus-group members were asked to watch the four 360° videos before taking part in the focus-group. This was to ensure that all participants had a common point-of-reference before discussing the experience. In addition to the mandatory viewing, the primary researcher also encouraged focus-group members to seek out additional content independently. Links to a list of common VR applications such as Google Expeditions and Within were provided with the initial instruction information.

Total study participation time was approximately one-and-a half-hours (thirty minutes to assemble and watch VR material, followed by a focus-group of approximately one hour). A timeline of the procedure can be found in Figure 10.

Figure 10

Timeline of study showing process for participants

Table 4

List of VR stimuli provided to instructors before focus groups

Title	Domain	Length	Description
Autism TMI Simulation	Clinical Psychology	2:06	Video gives the participant a first-hand perspective of what it is like to be a child with autism in a busy shopping mall. The video simulated sensory overload with distorted visuals and sound.
A Walk Through Dementia – Walking Home	Clinical Psychology	3:20	A first-hand experience of what it is like to be an elderly person with dementia. The video presents an inner monologue of the person’s thought process, often exhibiting confusion and disorientation. The video also shows a range of visual disturbances that are common in Dementia sufferers.
6x9: An Experience of Solitary Confinement	Environmental and Forensic Psychology	2:50	The video presents a computer-generated view of a solitary confinement prison cell. The video narrates the psychological implications associated with continuous confinement in these types of environments. Written visuals are also projected onto the cell wall, explaining the various infractions that could lead to confinement in the first-place.
First Impressions: A Virtual Experience of the First Year of Life	Child Development	5:37	A narrated experience that allows the watcher to take the perspective of a newborn infant. The video simulates the changes in visual and auditory perception through the first year of life. In a portion of the video, the participant experiences what it is like to undergo childhood neglect and its developmental consequences.

6.4.5 Online Focus Groups and COVID-19

As already discussed in Section 3.4.3., the intrusion of the COVID-19 pandemic fundamentally altered how data were collected in this thesis. Within the context of the current chapter, this was the first study that was conducted during a period of lockdown. Consequently, the utilisation of face-to-face data collection techniques was rendered impossible, and alternative strategies had to be devised. Fortunately, the pragmatic approach utilised in this thesis (as discussed in Sections 3.4.2. – 3.4.3.) allowed for the incorporation of data collection methods that best met the requirements of the research question (see, Morgan, 2014). In practice, this meant that the overarching objectives within this thesis were not beholden to a specific method (e.g., *in-person* interviews or focus-groups). Although the pragmatic approach is congruent with adaptations to research methodology, the foremost challenge entailed a comprehensive re-evaluation of the existing literature to ascertain the effectiveness and appropriateness of transitioning to online data collection. Indeed, this need to quickly pivot from one method to another underscored much of the qualitative research undertaken during the lockdown phase (see, Johnson & Odhner, 2021).

One of the most important considerations that substantiated the use of online focus-groups was the possibility of reaching a larger participant pool. As Richard et al. (2018) states, the use of a remote platform can provide greater insight into a given phenomenon by increasing geographical and institutional diversity. Unlike Study Two where face-to-face interviews were constrained to the immediate vicinity of the researcher, the utilisation of online focus-groups allowed for the collection of data across numerous institutions and countries of the United Kingdom. Pertinent to the issues raised in the methodological chapter (see, Section 3.4.1.1.), Richard et al. (2018) also highlights that this institutional diversity has the potential to increase the generalisability and transferability of findings. For example, speaking to instructors from a range of HE institutions with different cultures, resources, and student demographics extends the “soft-generalisability” of findings across contexts (see, Braun & Clarke, 2021b). By

examining a greater range of perspectives, the researcher can suggest ways in which the findings and applied recommendations might be applicable across institutions.

A second consideration concerns the logistical practicalities of conducting focus-group research. Traditionally, logistical considerations such as booking rooms, timetabling participants, and setting-up recording equipment would have demanded a great deal of intricate coordination (see, Finch & Lewis, 2003; Then et al., 2014). Often, this will be accompanied with high dropout rates, or “no-shows” which invariably would disrupt, postpone, or even cancel sessions. However, the current study utilised an online appointment calendar (Doodle) where participants could sign-up and be automatically sent a Zoom link. As Halliday et al. (2021) demonstrates, the utilisation of an online platform significantly reduces the rate of dropout, leading to reduced disruption in data collection.

A fundamental aim of the current study was to use the group dynamic to facilitate an in-depth discussion about attitudes towards Mobile-VR in psychology. The presence of peers within the group allows individuals to share their opinions and perceptions based upon a common experience of Mobile-VR (Then et al., 2014). Alternative qualitative methods such as one-to-one interviews would not have allowed for this interaction (Gill et al., 2008). The focus-groups followed a semi-structured approach similar to the interview technique set out by Smith and Osborn (2003). This allows for a greater degree of flexibility by not stringently adhering to a predefined set of questions, but rather a general set of prompts. In practice, this means that the moderator can follow-up on interesting or novel statements made by the focus-group members that may not have been initially considered.

The final consideration prior to data collection was to select an appropriate platform for conducting the online focus-groups themselves. This was particularly challenging due to the proliferation of similar online meeting systems (e.g., Microsoft Teams, Skype, Zoom). Ultimately, Zoom was chosen as the most appropriate platform to conduct data collection. This selection was informed by several factors, notably its documented utility in previous

psychological and pedagogical focus-group investigations (e.g., Elzainy et al., 2020). Moreover, Zoom offered the advantage of an integrated recording feature, obviating the need for additional third-party recording tools, and further, it did not necessitate the provision of institutional guest access (unlike Microsoft Teams).

6.4.6 Conducting the Online Focus-Group

The study conducted four online-focus groups each comprised of three to five members. The number of members in each group is within the recommendations previously set for synchronous online discussions (see, Abrams & Gaiser, 2017; Poynter, 2012). This is typically smaller than face-to-face interactions owing to logistical considerations whilst using online platforms (Tuttas, 2015). However, as Finch and Lewis (2003) state, focus-groups comprising of members from a professional background (i.e., academic staff) tend to contribute more openly to discussions, meaning large numbers are not always necessary. Therefore, the use of smaller numbers in each focus-group was deemed acceptable. Further, previous research (e.g., Woodyatt et al., 2016) has shown that the quality of focus-group data is not compromised by conducting it online as opposed to face-to-face.

The practicalities of conducting and moderating the focus groups themselves required adaptation to ensure quality in data collection. As Halliday et al. (2021) intimates, participants tend to talk less in online settings, perhaps owing to a lack of social and/or non-verbal cues from others (Richard et al., 2018). Therefore, it was important to give everyone the opportunity to voice their attitudes and opinions. To do this, the principal researcher adopted a “*sequential round-robin*” approach by explicitly asking each member of the group to contribute their own thoughts in-turn, before opening the discussion up to everyone. This ensured that each individual had the opportunity to contribute before it was discussed within the larger collective. Consequently, a diverse range of attitudes could be heard, which also assisted in generating a constructive discussion.

The moderator started by asking introductory questions about the physical Mobile-VR headsets, and how easy these were to navigate (e.g., “what were your perceptions when

you first saw the headset?” “Did you encounter any difficulties in assembling the headset or navigating to the specific experiences?”). The purpose of this was to gain an understanding of whether Mobile-VR could be more user-friendly and intuitive than the high-end systems that had typically been used in the preceding two studies. Next, the principal researcher wanted to examine attitudes pertaining to the specific VR experiences themselves (e.g., “was there a VR experience that you found particularly interesting?”), and how this could be integrated into teaching (e.g., “would you use any of these experiences in your own classes?”) This facilitated a healthy discussion between peers as to the nature of the VR material, and also allowed instructors to discuss the possible methods of application within their own institution. Finally, questions relating to barriers or impediments that they foresaw were raised. A detailed description of all the questions and associated prompts can be found in Digital Appendix 6.3.

6.4.7 Data Collection and Transcription

Each focus-group was conducted via Zoom and lasted approximately 60-minutes. This was for two main reasons. The principal researcher was responsible for moderating the discussion by prompting responses from participants and ensuring everyone had an opportunity to speak. All focus-groups were audio and video recorded to assist with later analysis. On completion of the discussion the audio file was transcribed verbatim by the principal researcher, and then imported to NVivo-12 for analysis. An unabridged copy of the transcripts can be found in Digital Appendix 6.4.

6.4.8 Method of Analysis

The present study used a combination of analysis methods to gain a nuanced understanding of attitudes and perceptions. First, Constant Comparison Analysis (CCA) was used to formulate a set of themes that were consistent across all four focus-groups. Then, Micro-interlocutor Analysis (MIA) was employed to interpret levels of consensus within the group in relation to key components and ideas.

6.4.8.1 Constant Comparison Analysis

Constant Comparison Analysis (CCA) finds its roots in grounded theory (Glaser, 1992; Glaser & Strauss, 1967), but has since commonly been applied in the analysis of focus-group data (Leech & Onwuegbuzie, 2008, 2011). Doody et al. (2013) identified three

distinct stages involved in the analysis process. First, open coding is performed by annotating transcripts and applying small descriptive codes to data excerpts. Next, axial coding involves collating initial codes into broader categories. Finally, an iterative process of selective coding involves the generation of overarching themes that illuminate the findings of the focus-group. This process is repeated for each focus-group in turn, *constantly comparing* whether themes formulated in one group are consistent with the others.

Data was both semantically and latently coded so explicit and implicit meaning could be interpreted by. A hybrid thematic framework similar to that described by Fereday and Muir-Cochrane (2006) was also employed in the study. Deductive themes, or those generated from prior research (e.g., Study Two) were used to address the key aims outlined in Section 6.3. In addition, inductive analysis was also undertaken to explore data with no preconceived coding or thematic framework (Nili et al., 2017).

An anticipated question that will invariably be raised is why Braun and Clarke's (2019b; 2021b) reflexive thematic analysis was not employed in this study. After all, this method was used in the preceding qualitative study. The justification for this lies in the *unit-of-analysis* that was ultimately of interest. As the current study utilised focus-groups to examine perceptions, the researcher must be conscious of the prevailing *group* attitudes, and not necessarily that of individual members *within* the group. This is markedly different from conducting interviews where the individuals themselves are ostensibly the *unit-of-analysis*. Although CCA has many of the same processes and qualities of TA (e.g., immersion in data, annotation and coding, generating themes), it incorporates a specific component that lends itself well to focus-group research. Namely, it allows for the study of “multiple groups to assess if the themes that emerged (sic) from one group also emerged (sic) from other groups” (Onwuegbuzie et al., 2009, p. 6). As a result, there is a strong emphasis placed upon the analysis of groups, as opposed to their constituent participants.

An example of the coding map and framework can be viewed in Digital Appendix 6.5. This shows the relationship between initial codes, and the later developed themes.

6.4.8.2 Micro-Interlocutor Analysis

Micro-interlocutor Analysis (MIA) is a novel method of focus-group analysis developed by Onwuegbuzie et al. (2009). MIA is predicated on the idea that by using only the focus-group itself as the unit of analysis, important information divulged by the individuals *within* the group is often neglected. In particular, the degree of agreement and dissent in response to key components or ideas. As a result, vague quantitative statements such as “*the majority agreed that...*” or “*only a minority disagreed with...*” are commonly employed to articulate consensus (Sechrest & Sidani, 1995). MIA analyses participants’ verbal responses (e.g., “Yes,” “No,” or a descriptive example statement), lexical utterances (e.g., “Uh-um,” “Hmm”), and body language (e.g., nodding/shaking of the head) to assess the degree of consensus within the group (Onwuegbuzie et al., 2009; 2010).

The purpose of CCA is to look for common strands or themes that occur across multiple focus-groups (Leech & Onwuegbuzie, 2008; Onwuegbuzie et al., 2009). Indeed, that is why it was chosen as the most appropriate method of examining the qualitative data. However, it is also recognised that that focus-groups are ostensibly comprised of *individuals*, and to exclusively focus upon the group dynamic using CCA ignores this important aspect. Accordingly, it was thought prudent to employ such methods that facilitate a more nuanced investigation of the data by using complimentary analysis (i.e., CCA, and MIA).

Table 5 presents analysis criteria, codes, and definitions used in the current study. These are based upon the suggestions and guidelines laid out by Onwuegbuzie et al. in their 2009 article.

Table 5*Codes used in micro-interlocutor analysis process*

Response	Code	Description
Agreement/Consensus	A	Participant indicated agreement with the premise based upon a nonverbal (e.g. nodding) or short verbal (e.g. "yes," "I agree") response.
	SA	Significant agreement or consensus. Participant agreed with the premise and provided an anecdote, significant statement, or concrete example to highlight.
Disagreement/Dissent	D	Participant indicated disagreement with the premise or component based upon a nonverbal (e.g. shaking head) or short verbal (e.g. "I disagree") response.
	SD	Significant disagreement or dissent. Participant disagreed with the premise and provided an anecdote, significant statement, or concrete example to highlight.
No-response	NR	Participant did not provide a verbal or non-verbal response, indicating neither agreement nor disagreement.

6.5 Findings and Analysis

By using constant comparison analysis, six main themes were formulated that were consistent across all four groups. These were: (a) experiential learning; (b) accessibility of Mobile-VR; (c) student engagement and motivation; (d) pedagogical impact; (e) curriculum integration; and (f) barriers to adoption. A summary of each theme is presented in Table 6.

Table 6

Overview of the themes and subthemes

Theme	Description
Experiential Learning	Perceptions towards VR being used as an experiential learning tool, and its related applications within psychology.
Accessibility of Mobile-VR	Theme concerns the attitudes and perceptions towards Mobile-VR HMDs and their associated benefits.
Student Engagement and Motivation	The attitudes of lecturers regarding how Mobile-VR influences student engagement with learning material.
Pedagogical Impact	Attitudes relating to how Mobile-VR can impact student understanding, attainment, and outcomes.
Curriculum Integration	Examines how psychology lecturers would integrate Mobile-VR into their module, and in what capacity.
Barriers to Adoption	<p>Theme examines the various barriers and impediments that lecturers identified as being important in Mobile-VR adoption.</p> <p><i>Subtheme 1: Financial Barriers – impediments related to a potential lack of financial support for VR teaching.</i></p> <p><i>Subtheme 2: Content Barriers – barriers related to a lack of suitable pedagogical content.</i></p>

6.5.1 Experiential Learning

Across groups, instructors were encouraged about using Mobile-VR as a means of facilitating understanding through experiential learning. Experiential learning places the learner at the centre of the educational experience, giving them an active role in knowledge acquisition (Kolb, 1984). Through direct observation and interaction, the learner is able to reflect and then integrate new information with existing schemas (Kolb, 1984; Kolb et al., 2011). Focus-group participants emphasised VR’s unique ability to simulate the experiences of others and could ultimately enhance student learning. This could be particularly effective if the psychological state or temperament of the student was markedly different than that of the person they were embodying:

“I think VR would be useful in letting people step into other people's shoes. It gives students a chance to experience different ways of thinking, or what it's like to respond anxiously to a social situation when they themselves might be quite confident. I think it could be useful in demonstrating how differently people perceive the world.”

Martin

“I mean, putting yourself in the shoes of others is a really good way to learn.”

Tessa

In line with the theoretical framework of embodiment as delineated by Slater et al. (2022) along with Banakou et al. (2016, 2013), VR possesses the capacity to engender a sensation of possession over a virtual avatar, which is markedly separate from the user's actual identity. This notion aligns with the perspectives of psychology educators observed in the present study, suggesting that VR can effectively convey substantial disparities in psychological disposition or sensory processing to the participant through the phenomenon of body ownership (Slater et al., 2009; 2022). This ability of VR to bridge these diverse aspects underscores its potential as a transformative tool in fostering a deeper understanding and empathy towards differing identities, thereby contributing significantly to the discourse on embodiment and identity in virtual environments. MIA was used to assess the degree of consensus regarding whether Mobile-VR could facilitate effective experiential learning. Analysis found that 81% of group members responded positively to Mobile-VR being an experiential learning tool, often with a desire to incorporate it into their own teaching. There was no explicit dissenting opinion (a full breakdown of the MIA analysis can be found in Table 7 at the end of this section). Therefore, most saw Mobile-VR as providing an educational insight through direct representational experience. This was commonly expressed as the capacity to identify and understand the emotional state of the person being represented through the illusion of body-ownership:

“Experiencing what other people experience and putting yourself into the position of someone as a tool to make students reflect [...] this is an area where I would like to see VR used.”

Kevin

These attitudes were similar to those observed in Study Two, indicating that psychology lecturers hold comparable perceptions as to the efficiency of Mobile-VR for experiential learning. Indeed, this underscores the potential transferability of such findings across educational domains, highlighting VR’s efficiency at delivering embodied experiences in a myriad of pedagogical contexts. In addition, whether high-end HMDs (as commonly used by instructors in Study Two) or Mobile-VR is used, these findings suggest that immersive technologies can provide an unprecedented insight into the cognitive and lived realities of another. Although 360° videos and smartphone-based systems might lack the visual acuity and sophistication of more powerful HMDs (see, Poppe et al., 2017), this study demonstrates that the educational utility of both mediums might be best realised in their ability to allow users to “step into the shoes” of another person.

A notable difference was that psychology lecturers did not place the same emphasis on eliciting an empathetic response as those in the previous study. The likely explanation for this attitude lies in the divergent purpose of the VR experience itself. Study Two featured many instructors from the field of nursing and healthcare who utilised VR as a tool for *behaviour change*. This behaviour change was often achieved as a result of experiential learning eliciting an empathetic response. The student could then alter their behaviours and actions in applied scenarios such as hospitals and nursing homes. Conversely, psychology lecturers in the present study envisaged experiential learning facilitating theoretical knowledge and understanding; not behaviour change. Therefore, psychology lecturers placed a stronger emphasis on the academic value of the technology as opposed to its potential vocational benefits.

Far from experiential learning being conceptualised in merely an abstract fashion; lecturers were able to provide concrete examples of where it could be used in the

classroom. The most prominent attitude was that it should be implemented in the teaching of mental health psychology. By embodying someone with a mental health or developmental condition (e.g., ASD, anxiety, Dementia, Alzheimer's), students could supplement their theoretical knowledge of associated symptoms and perceptual differences. By fully immersing the student in the experience, lecturers hoped that they would gain a greater understanding of the condition than through conventional methods of teaching such as lectures, standard video clips, or required reading:

"I always try to make sure that whatever condition I'm teaching, the class watch some videos on YouTube, or we read some testimonials from people to see what it's like to live with each of these conditions. And actually, I think something like VR would be one step better than that."

Eilidh

"When I was a student, I always remember reading about certain disorders in books, but not having an understanding at all of what was actually going on in that person's mind. I always thought: 'what type of life do they live?' I think that's the hardest thing to get across when you're teaching things like mental health. We could give students these cardboard VR headsets [...] and we might be able to bridge that gap that we currently don't have at this point in time. So, for that experiential stuff, I think VR would be really useful."

Mark

These quotes highlight the difficulty in effectively communicating mental health concepts through traditional didactic or technological teaching means. Like the findings of Study One, and the attitudes conveyed in Study Two, psychology lecturers explicitly state that there is an advantage to conveying conceptual problems through Mobile-VR. This substantiates the idea that VR is best utilised when conventional means of teaching are unable to fully elucidate the ideas or concepts being presented. This is succinctly exemplified by a participant when they said:

“I want something where you can really kind of feel it rather than just trying to describe it.”

Nicole

As previously intimated, lecturers promoted Mobile-VR as a means of increasing theoretical understanding of mental health conditions. They hoped that students could integrate information learned through the experience with existing knowledge acquired through seminars, workshops and lectures.

“VR could solidify some of that theoretical learning if they've got experience that they can map it onto.”

Martin

“And I think the (VR) mental health stuff maps quite well to a lot of theory.”

Tessa

These ideas are consistent with the experiential learning theories laid out by Kolb (1984) and Kolb et al. (2011). By allowing students to reflect on how VR experiences integrate with existing knowledge, they can actively implement it in an academic context such as coursework and exams. Consistent with previous research, the embodiment of a virtual avatar is considered paramount in facilitating theoretical knowledge acquisition and novel perspectives. For instance, Adefila et al. (2016) had students undergo a VR experience called *myShoes*, where they take the perspective of a Dementia sufferer. After reflecting on the experience, students displayed significantly heightened knowledge of Dementia symptomology at post-test compared to pre-test. Subsequent research has also supported using VR to increase knowledge of Alzheimer’s disease (Campbell et al., 2021) as well as schizophrenic symptoms such as psychosis (Formosa et al., 2018). In addition, the systematic review conducted in Chapter Three concluded that cognitive learning tasks that are challenging to reproduce in reality are particularly well suited to VR. These

studies demonstrate that the attitude of psychology lecturers to implement Mobile-VR as a form of experiential learning is grounded and supported by a body of empirical research.

6.5.2 Accessibility of Mobile-VR

As discussed in Study One and Two, high-end VR headsets often require a reasonable degree of technical competency and proficiency. Previous studies have identified that educators often lack the training opportunities or time required to build these skills (Alfalah, 2018). Therefore, the current study employed a low-cost and accessible Mobile-VR headset to investigate whether psychology lecturers could integrate the technology into their teaching activities. The current theme therefore concerns the perceived advantages of the Mobile-VR hardware. Specifically, it describes the affordances of the physical headset itself. Any perceived pedagogical advantage to students is described in the next section.

The most prominent attitude across groups was Mobile-VR's relative ease of use. This related to the assembly of the HMD itself, as well as the ability to navigate to, and access 360° content and material easily. When asked how easy the Mobile-VR headset was to assemble, 81% of lecturers agreed that it was a simple process requiring minimal effort. Only one participant disagreed, stating that they had a little trouble owing to poor eyesight. However, the consensus was overwhelmingly positive when it came to ease of assembly:

"I thought it was really good. And the fact that it comes flat-packed and goes through the letterbox seems really accessible. And when I looked at the instructions it was easy enough to build up and my phone seems to work pretty well with it."

Nicole

"I think it was really quite easy to put together. I didn't require any additional instruction. I just used it out of the box. It was very easy, very straightforward. And it seemed to work fine on my phone."

Tessa

Psychology lecturers were positive about just how quickly the Mobile-VR HMDs were to set-up, requiring no major installation or configuration. And unlike high-end hardware such as the Oculus Rift, a major advantage is that it utilises technology that most students already have access to (i.e. smartphones):

"In terms of the kit, I like the fact that it was quite easy to set up. And the fact that it was using tech that most folk already have, so it's using their mobile phones. I can see how that's going to be so helpful with regards to the practicalities of actually using this stuff in the classroom."

Eilidh

The next component to consider is how lecturers perceive the usability of Mobile-VR hardware. As numerous technological models have already intimated (see, Davis, 1989; Venkatesh et al., 2003), the ease of use or accessibility of a technology can ultimately influence the decision to interact with it (Davis, 1989). Lecturers remarked that Mobile-VR was extremely user-friendly, and they had little problem operating the system. This is likely because Mobile-VR does not require the user to learn a new application or interface. Rather, a habitual knowledge of the users own mobile phone is sufficient for accessing material and watching content. The comments of most interest were from lecturers who had previously used or owned high-end VR systems (although not in an educational capacity). They intimated that the Mobile-VR HMD was in fact more user friendly, accessible, and easier to calibrate and configure than previous hardware:

"Just to say with the quality of them, I bought my other-half a good quality headset a few years ago, and that took ages to kind of set the focus and make

sure it was working properly. But this one worked immediately. I had no issues with focus or anything. I really couldn't have been more impressed with the quality of it. I was surprised."

Kirsty

"In comparison to that (high-end HMD), I just found this so much easier. And so I find just being able to sit there and have a light device on my face made it so much easier to engage with the material and stay focused on it."

Mandy

Previous studies have identified a range of second-order VR barriers (Ertmer, 1999) intrinsic to educators from a range of institutions. These commonly centre on self-efficacy and technological apprehension when it comes to operating new pedagogical systems (see, Alfalah, 2018; Cooper et al., 2019; Fransson et al., 2020). However, despite all lecturers in the present study being naïve to educational Mobile-VR, there was little apprehension regarding ease of use and usability of the hardware. This suggests that Mobile-VR may alleviate many of the technical barriers associated with high-end systems, such as lack of technical confidence, training resources, or professional development. Therefore, Mobile-VR may provide an advantageous entry-level system for small-scale classroom integration for both staff and students.

As was the case with the previous theme, lecturers not only identified the affordances of an accessible Mobile-VR system in abstract terms, but they also provided examples of how accessibility translates to applied practice. A reoccurring view across all four focus-groups was that Mobile-VR could be used as a teaching tool during COVID-19. Unlike high-end systems, lecturers stated that a Mobile-VR headset could be posted to a student's residence, allowing them to access material from home. The flat-packed nature of the Mobile-VR headset, relative ease of use, and lower cost means that students could potentially access learning material that would have otherwise not been privy to:

"I think that the flat-packed aspect is really good. Especially now that you could possibly send it out to students that are at home because of COVID and remote learning. That's something I wouldn't have considered before."

Olivia

"You could send these out to students. If you do that, I can't imagine that they wouldn't be curious about what this is; especially now with remote learning."

Nicole

Clearly, this is not an option available to educational facilitators of high-end VR systems. Indeed, the inability for students to access VR learning outside of the traditional classroom environment has been identified as a barrier by previous researchers. In practice this means students have traditionally not been able to revisit or revise VR material from home, resulting in short or isolated classroom exposures. Although lecturers in the current study identified Mobile-VR's accessibility as potentially facilitating distance learning during COVID-19; in practice this is not context specific. Mobile-VR gives psychology lecturers the opportunity to equip their students with the means to view immersive content regardless of whether a blended, distance, or hybrid learning approach is utilised. This degree of flexibility would be difficult to replicate if it were not for the accessible nature of Mobile-VR technology.

6.5.3 Motivation and Engagement

As already discussed, psychology lecturers intimated that Mobile-VR is an accessible and user-friendly approach to immersive technology. However, yet to be discussed is the perceived impact that this will have on their students. The current theme therefore highlights the perceived pedagogical advantages of implementing Mobile-VR in HE psychology curricula. Lecturers conveyed the attitude that Mobile-VR could lead to higher academic motivation and classroom engagement, as well as suggesting how this engagement could manifest and be evaluated.

The most frequently predicted impact of Mobile-VR on the student experience was the ability of the technology to increase motivation and engagement. Motivation can generally be defined as the process in which goal-oriented behaviour is first initiated, guided, and ultimately maintained (Ratner, 2014). However, in an education context “motivation provides a source of energy that is responsible for why learners decide to make an effort, how long they are willing to sustain an activity, how hard they are going to pursue it, and how connected they feel to the activity” (Rost, 2006, p.1). Lecturers thought Mobile-VR would provide an enjoyable learning medium that would excite students’ curiosity:

“I do think that there's something to be said for making sessions more engaging and enjoyable. If you can buy them (students) into the session with something like Mobile-VR, then obviously it is going to help them. I think this could be a really cool way of doing that.”

Erin

“I don't think there is anything wrong with having a cool bit of technology, or a cool add-on as long as its related to the topic. [...] And I think that this (Mobile-VR) would be the kind of thing that a lot of students would find very engaging and enjoyable.”

Scott

“As has already been said, I think as long as you make the learning goals clear from the outset, then VR is going to gain a lot of traction. It is definitely something I'm interested in, and I think it'd be really exciting for my students as well.”

Daniel

In addition, MIA found most lecturers (69%) implied that Mobile-VR could increase motivation when learning psychology, exemplifying that Mobile-VR would likely be an

engaging tool for students. These attitudes are similar to those presented in the previous study (Study Two) by lecturers who had already implemented VR in HE. In addition, previous research examining the perspectives of non-university teaching faculty has already identified VR as being an engaging learning tool (Lee & Shea, 2020; Serin, 2020). This is consistent with Smith’s (2017) concept of *analytical generalisability*, suggesting that the motivational properties of Mobile-VR extend beyond both the method (i.e., Mobile-VR or high-end VR) and place (i.e., university or non-university) of delivery. This has wider ramifications for motivation frameworks and theoretical research in the field of education. Specifically, it has been well substantiated that the integration of technology can increase student motivation and subsequent academic attainment (e.g., Heafner, 2004; Su & Cheng, 2015). As opposed to seeing this merely as a consequence of the sophistication of the technology itself, researchers have proposed that the relevancy of its pedagogical integration and the satisfaction it instils is integral for facilitating engagement (see, Goksu & Islam Bolat, 2021; Keller, 1987, 2010). Consequently, the application of a well-designed and relevant learning activity should increase pedagogical motivation and engagement regardless of whether Mobile or high-end VR is used. As the current study demonstrates, lecturers are generally positive that the accessible and low-cost system can facilitate this.

6.5.4 Pedagogical Impact

Far from viewing the engagement achieved through Mobile-VR as an end in itself; lecturers spoke about how it could be treated as a means to deeper learning. Lecturers in the current study did not express an expectation that a direct or causal link exists between Mobile-VR and better learning outcomes. Unlike many of the experimental studies discussed in Chapter Three (Study One), lecturers were not of the opinion that an isolated Mobile-VR intervention would necessarily lead directly to higher quantifiable attainment (e.g. through test scores). Rather, focus-group members expressed the opinion that Mobile-VR could foster deeper understanding of theories and concepts through in-depth classroom discussion. By being engaged and motivated to interact with the Mobile-VR experiences, students could share and discuss pertinent themes, insights, and ideas with their peers. Over half of participants (56%) explicitly stated that the combination of a Mobile-VR experience followed by a subsequent classroom discussion would be an ideal way of both fostering and evaluating pedagogical impact:

"I think VR should be used at the beginning of a seminar or workshop. Then it would be followed by taking the VR headset off, and then having an in-depth discussion about how everyone experienced the situation, and how this relates to the content that was covered in the lecture beforehand."

Mandy

"It is hard to get students to talk to one another. Especially at the start of a new module. I think this could help get students chatting and discussing what they've seen. That way, they're learning from each other too."

Eilidh

Lecturers expressed the opinion that Mobile-VR use in psychology could provide novel insights into related topics, and this could then be used as a basis for wider discussion. These insights would be generated from the experiential learning components previously described, and later explored and discussed among peers. One suggested way of facilitating these conversations was to place students into small workgroups or breakout rooms after undergoing a Mobile-VR experience:

"After using the VR you could get a discussion going. After everyone has watched it you put them (students) into small groups and they can all talk about the experience. That would be the way I would use this."

Scott

It was hoped that the engaging nature of VR learning would motivate students to share their thoughts and experiences with their peers. This can be seen as a form of collaborative learning, a practice that involves working in groups to complete tasks or learn new concepts (Laal & Ghodsi, 2012). This collaborative approach is quite different from the traditional notion of VR being a purely solitary activity. Focus-group members

envisage the technology having the effect of encouraging interaction and positive group dynamics. This appears to be a relatively novel insight among psychology lecturers as most efforts at combining collaborative learning with VR focus on real-time interaction *within* the virtual environment (Greenwald et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2019). Whereas, in the current study, lecturers envisage group discussions as being a follow-up activity using the VR to first engage and then motivate students to learn. Research such as that conducted by Panitz (1999) has already promoted collaborative activities as being an effective way of motivating students and increasing conceptual understanding. Therefore Mobile-VR could serve as an important catalyst to these discussions, providing a depth of insight difficult to convey in conventional teaching methods.

A final benefit of using Mobile-VR to facilitate discussion is that it ensures the viewing of VR material is not merely a passive experience, but one the student must actively engage with. As one participant postulated, knowing that another learning activity (i.e. group discussion) is to follow the Mobile-VR experience would motivate students to be more attentive, encouraging them to imbibe as much information as possible. Active participation has already been suggested as an important academic benefit of group activities and collaborative learning (Laal & Ghodsi, 2012). As that participant remarked:

“You can get students to watch something like a forensic psychology experience and then discuss it in their groups. They’d say ‘oh, I didn’t see that, did you?’ or ‘that was not what I took away from the experience.’ I think it would be really effective to use the Mobile-VR because the students aren’t just sitting there watching it. They know they’re going to have something to do or discuss it afterwards. That is my opinion anyway.”

Olivia

The systematic review presented in Study One critiqued the over reliance on assessment instrumentation such as the multiple-choice questionnaires. The rationale for such critique was that these measures may not be sensitive enough to capture more nuanced forms of learning, therefore failing to fully elucidate the pedagogical impact of VR

technology. Group discussions and other peer-to-peer interactions were suggested as more appropriate alternatives that could help students showcase a wider breadth of knowledge and understanding. It is therefore encouraging to find psychology lecturers identifying this as a way of both facilitating learning and evaluating the effectiveness of the technology.

6.5.5 Curriculum Integration

As already intimated by Southgate and Smith (2017), research has commonly failed to address how VR can be integrated into HE curricula. For instance, is VR's purpose to supplement or replace conventional means of classroom teaching? In the previous study chapter, this thesis addressed the attitudes and considerations associated with VR integration in numerous disciplines. The current theme specifically examines the attitudes of psychology lecturers towards low-cost Mobile-VR integration.

When asked how they perceive Mobile-VR being best integrated into psychology, focus-group members were almost unanimous that it should be used as a supplementary teaching method. Across focus-groups, the consensus was that Mobile-VR should not be viewed as a replacement for conventional teaching practices, but rather one that can complement them. Several remarks were made that directly address the supplementary integration of Mobile-VR with existing methods of teaching:

"But generally, the VR would also be supplementary. As I said before, it would just be used to provide a general experience. And then the teaching will come in about evidence-based practice, and theory, and that sort of thing. So, I can only ever see it being supplementary rather than a replacement."

Mark

"I don't know if that could replace, you know, a traditional seminar or whatever. But I think it's a good complement to it. Even in terms of just breaking things up and adding a bit novelty. I think that is quite important in terms of helping students to be engaged and motivated throughout."

Martin

“It has to supplement the class for me. I guess I just don't think it would be enough to entirely replace seminars or workshops because they (the students) would miss out on so much of the experience that's important to their learning.”

Kirsty

MIA identified that 75% of focus-group members explicitly mentioned that they envisage Mobile-VR as a supplementary method of education as opposed to a replacement of traditional means. There were no significant dissenting statements. These attitudes are consistent with those conveyed by lecturers in the previous chapter. Although Chapter Four (Study Two) interviewed lecturers already familiar with pedagogical VR from numerous disciplines, the attitudes expressed here among unfamiliar users are remarkably similar. Mobile-VR is seen as just one tool among many that can be utilised in conjunction with traditional means of education. Lecturers expressed that they did not see Mobile-VR as necessarily superior or in competition with traditional forms of teaching, but rather one that can be amalgamated with it:

“You need a range of methods. You can use things like VR but you have to combine them with traditional methods at the same time. You need that balance.”

Liam

“I don't know if I'd say that Mobile-VR would be better than traditional methods. But I do think it would work as a compliment.”

Martin

Again, the findings of both the previous chapter and the current study substantiate the attitude that Mobile-VR's use within education is a supplemental one. As previously

described, psychology lecturers envisage Mobile-VR within the context of multimodal learning. This approach utilises a range of didactic, visual, auditory and technological means to facilitate and encourage learning (Yelland, 2018). Consistent with the attitudes espoused in the current study, Yelland (2018) also emphasised this important feature of the multimodal approach: “digital technologies are viewed as being complimentary (sic) to other resources, rather than alternatives, or in competition with, traditional modalities” (p. 1). Unfortunately, there has been little qualitative research examining the attitudes of HE lecturers towards Mobile-VR module integration (Southgate & Smith, 2017). For this reason, the current study makes an important and novel contribution to the existing body of literature examining VR’s pedagogical role. Although previous research has also supported VR’s role as a supplementary tool (e.g., Fransson et al., 2020), this has been within the confines of primary education, and not in universities. Although all educational institutions invariably have a degree of crossover and commonality, the practicalities of delivering HE is still markedly different. Shorter class times and more independent study mean that pedagogical techniques in one institution (e.g., a primary school) do not necessarily translate to another (e.g., university). However, based upon the current findings, it would be reasonable to assert that the holistic view of VR integration across disciplines and institutions is that it is best utilised as an accompaniment to conventional teaching means, and not as a replacement. The current study represents the first time that this has been substantiated in HE instructors using Mobile-VR.

Although psychology lecturers were vehement in their perception of Mobile-VR as a supplementary tool, the question of *when* it should be used has yet to be answered. The overarching attitude both within and between each focus-group was that VR must be integrated with *purpose*. That is to say, there must be a specific and predefined learning goal in mind that Mobile-VR can help achieve.

“I don't think it should be that every class is going to use VR, because that's not the point of it. We should only be using it if there's a real need and there's going to be some kind of educational benefit out of it. So, it is something that I'm going to think about using and see if there is a possibility of appropriately

implementing it. But yeah, it would need to be in very specific circumstances and for a specific learning reason.”

Erin

“Yeah, I think I would really like to use it. But I think the approach you would need to take it to make sure the VR and the specific material intertwines with what you’re teaching and what the learning outcomes are for your students.”

Mandy

“In terms of teaching, I think it largely depends on what you’re wanting to teach. And then after that you see if there are any VR videos or films that would actually add to teaching and make it worth showing.”

Eilidh

Substantiating these attitudes were remarks made by lecturers with regards to what you *should not* do when integrating the technology. If implementing Mobile-VR with purpose was the optimal approach, then “shoehorning” it into lessons where its use was not warranted was fiercely discouraged:

“When I was watching them, I was thinking how this needs to be useful to teaching first and foremost. Sometimes there’s no point just putting things in there for the sake of it.”

Jennifer

“I need a clear idea of what I want to achieve in the classroom, and then I go out and find the materials. If you don’t do that, it can be very easy to venture into that place where you say ‘I just want to use VR in the classroom so I will find somewhere to use it.’ That would definitely be something I would try and avoid.”

Amanda

"If I'm having to try to shoehorn this stuff in and make relevant, then it's probably not going to be relevant, is it?"

Kevin

The clear attitude of lecturers in this study is that Mobile-VR will not be applicable in all circumstances or scenarios. Previous literature has often anticipated that Mobile-VR has the potential to be viewed as a "gimmicky new technology" if implemented spuriously (Johnson, 2018, p.230). Indeed, Cooper and Thong (2018) identified this very issue as being a potential pitfall in immersive technologies being integrated successfully into science education. Similar to the findings of Study Two, as well as previous research in non-HE environments (see Cooper et al., 2019; Fransson et al., 2020), the current study identified the need for careful and purposeful integration of Mobile-VR into psychology curricula. It was the attitude of lecturers that the choice of whether to use Mobile-VR must be driven exclusively by the learning outcome or goal being pursued. It is important that the desire to use Mobile-VR does not lead to the technology dictating the learning objectives. Appropriate implementation is therefore predicated on psychology lecturers predefining their pedagogical objectives prior to adoption in the classroom. This pre-emptive planning will allow for them to identify topics or concepts that may be better understood or facilitated using Mobile-VR. By doing so, the purposeful integration of Mobile-VR has the potential to engage students by providing unique insights into psychological phenomenon.

6.5.6 Barriers to Adoption

Barriers to adoption refer to the practical impediments that lecturers envisaged if they were to attempt to integrate Mobile-VR into teaching. A range of barriers were identified that can generally be broken down into two main sub-themes: (a) financial barriers; and (b) content barriers. Each sub-theme is discussed separately below.

6.5.6.1 Financial Barriers

Financial barriers are those impediments that are primarily the result of a perceived lack of institutional support for Mobile-VR funding. The most common concern centred on the financial investment necessary to buy the requisite number of headsets and associated equipment. This was despite all lecturers being explicitly told of the relatively low cost of the Mobile-VR headset prior to being asked about potential barriers:

“I guess finance would be my first probably - my first most obvious one, I guess. Trying to evidence that this would be a significant addition to student’s experience and things like that, I think, would be difficult.”

Mandy

“And then you’re going to need to buy the equipment, obviously. So yeah, there’s definitely a barrier there at the moment in terms of getting funding.”

Liam

“Institutions as far as my own goes would not spend any money, ever. That’s regardless of whether it increases motivation, learning or engagements or whatever. It doesn’t matter. There is no money.”

Amanda

Despite the comparatively low cost of the Mobile-VR headset, MIA revealed that only one lecturer made a significant dissenting statement regarding poor institutional support. Kevin remarked that the “teaching focused” nature of his own institution meant that he felt confident that a future Mobile-VR teaching project would be readily funded by management. However, clearly this is not the prevailing attitude among psychology lecturers in the current study. Most lecturers (69%) explicitly expressed doubt that their institution would readily support the possibility of Mobile-VR learning with an initial financial injection. This was a surprising finding as it was hypothesised that the

introduction of a low-cost VR solution would alleviate some of the financial pressures associated with the funding of high-end systems. However, like the findings of Study Two, as well as limited previous research with HE lecturers (e.g., Alfalah, 2018), cost remained a central concern. This is despite Olmos-Raya et al. writing in 2018(a) that Mobile-VR was close to overcoming the cost barriers associated with the introduction of immersive technology in teaching. Clearly, based on the findings of the current study, any such conclusion has been premature and overstated. Although Olmos-Raya et al. (2018b) advocated for the bring your own device (BYOD) approach being a cost-effective solution to immersive learning, it does not necessarily factor in the often large upfront cost associated with Mobile-VR. Although the individual unit price of Mobile-VR is comparatively small, a minimum bulk order is typically needed to secure enough headsets for an entire class. This large initial cost appears to be the major stumbling block. As one participant noted:

“If you have a massive class, then I just don’t think it is going to be feasible in terms of finance.”

Eilidh

It is worth noting that this does appear to be a universal barrier that is not exclusive to HE establishments (see, Chou & Hoisington, 2018; Cooper et al., 2019; Fransson et al., 2020).

Despite psychology lecturers often remarking that the financial aspect was the greatest barrier in the introduction of Mobile-VR, this was often an automatic assumption as opposed to one based upon experience. For instance, many lecturers had already formed a preconceived or expectant attitude that any request for financial assistance in supporting Mobile-VR learning would be automatically denied by their department or institution. Phrases like “I guess” or “I think” were commonly used when it came to the perceived outcomes of seeking support for innovative teaching:

“I think my biggest practicality would, would still be cost. I think if I said to my director of teaching, I want to spend £700 on this, I think she’d say ‘no’.”

Erin

“I guess the same. I guess finances is probably the biggest barrier. If I was to go to my boss and ask for money for VR, the answer would probably be ‘no, we have got no money’. That’s what I think they’d say.”

Eilidh

The above excerpts exemplify that some lecturers already have a preconceived attitude that financial support will not be available for any Mobile-VR teaching. Therefore, some lecturers may not feel confident or motivated enough to approach their institution in the first place to request or enquire about access to funding. A range of other variables may influence this decision such as academic position, length of employment, relationship to management, university support networks, or past experience. It would therefore be prudent to not merely conceptualise financial barriers as an aspect of institutional support alone. Rather, the preconceived attitudes of lecturers clearly play a role in that there is a general assumption that financial assistance to support the use of Mobile-VR will not be forthcoming. This presents an important initial barrier in that some psychology lecturers (or HE lecturers more generally) may dismiss the possibility of even being able to acquire the technology out of hand. As Tondeur et al. (2017) concludes, pedagogical innovation is centred on institutions having policies that incentivise novel technological approaches to teaching. It is therefore paramount that departments and institutions take the initiative to encourage their staff to pursue Mobile-VR teaching in psychology if this is felt to be beneficial to students. And part of this support will undoubtedly need to consist of financial support in the form of applications and grants to acquire headsets. Despite close to a decade of pedagogical VR research and application, associated costs remain one of, if not the most important impediments to widespread adoption.

6.5.6.2 Content Barriers

Based on their two-week experience with the Mobile-VR headset, psychology lecturers identified a fundamental barrier that they felt could hamper implementation. Namely, a lack of good quality or appropriate 360° content was identified as an impediment to future implementation in HE psychology classes. This also extended to scepticism surrounding whether the creation of bespoke content was feasible given the level of technical proficiency required.

As part of the study, participants were sent links to a range of freely available 360° content that was relevant to psychology education (see Table 4 in Section 6.4.). They were also instructed to seek out content independently through various VR applications and platforms. Although psychology lecturers could see the potential of using Mobile-VR as a means of experiential learning, they did identify a lack of appropriate or bespoke content to be an impediment for their own teaching. Lecturers commonly remarked that many of the 360° videos available online were of poor quality and would not be appropriate for their own classes. To take just one example, lecturers were critical of the *Autism TMI Simulation* video that was suggested as being a possible resource in the teaching of clinical psychology:

"I don't teach on kind of clinical module, but I thought the video was a bit 'twee' and not entirely realistic. They were very stereotypical, and quite slow. And I just don't know if it was the best representation of that condition."

Kirsty

"I think the autism video was a very intense representation of the condition. Autism affects people in different ways. But every single thing someone with autism can experience was put into that one video."

Olivia

“The first video; the autism one. I felt like it was more of a panic attack than an everyday experience of somebody with autism.”

Kevin

Apart from lecturers citing concerns about content quality, they also identified a lack of content that was appropriate for their individual teaching needs. For instance, based on their experience with the headset, lecturers commonly remarked that they envisaged difficulty in procuring content appropriate for their classes:

“I do a lot of teaching on third- and fourth-year modules. And when you get to that stage, we are looking at very specialised areas. I found it really difficult to find specific things that actually met my requirements.”

Mandy

“I did try and explore this (using VR) last year. And I just could not find anything on YouTube and so on that would actually work in my class.”

Liam

“I mean, if you completely rely on what videos already exists out there, you might not actually find any that would be that helpful.”

Eilidh

From the focus-group discussions, psychology lecturers identified several impediments within the context of access to material. First, pre-existing VR content was often unsuitable for use in the classroom. As the quotations here demonstrate, lecturers were concerned that VR material was of poor quality, or not wholly representative of the condition it purported to show. However, (and rather paradoxically) lecturers stated that they would be completely dependent on this suboptimal pre-existing material unless they acquired the technical proficiency necessary to create their own bespoke material. In the

absence of appropriate material that can be harmoniously integrated into psychology classes, the only alternative is to create material from scratch. Indeed, many lecturers identified this as being the optimal solution to the problem of suboptimal content. However, this immediately raised additional barriers such as a lack of time to learn content creation skills, and a lack of technical proficiency in these matters:

“We need a platform or software where we can create the videos ourselves or we can get ones that are specific to our needs. But at the moment, I just don’t even know where I would begin with that.”

Mandy

“The other problem that we have is creating your own videos. That comes down to two things: cost and time. You need more money to buy even more equipment and then you need to spend time to learn it all.”

Amanda

“I think that the biggest problem for me is that I would want to learn how to develop my own. If I was going to take this on, I would want to train myself on how to develop these videos. Because using what is already available online, I’m having to try to shoehorn stuff in and make it kind of relevant, and it’s probably not going to be relevant. If I want to make it really effective in my teaching, I need to create my own. But I don’t know how difficult that will be. What kind of camera do I need? What can of software do I need? It seems like a big undertaking.”

Kevin

Similar to the findings of Study Two, the lack of appropriate content is a major barrier to widespread VR integration. As has already been discussed at length in Section 6.5.5., the spurious integration of suboptimal VR experiences could be counterproductive. To use a poor quality 360° video because it is somewhat relevant to the content covered in class

would be at odds with Picciano's (2009) edict to integrate “with purpose” (p. 7). That is to say, the lesson itself should not be moulded to align with a specific 360° video that a lecturer wants to show in class. Psychology lecturers in the current study were emphatic on this point. They therefore identified the best solution as being the creation of bespoke psychological content that would directly adhere to the predefined curriculum. However, as previous studies have indicated (see, Alfalah, 2018; Fransson et al., 2020), it takes time for instructors to build up the skills necessary to operate the VR equipment itself, never mind to create bespoke content. Therefore, to reemphasise a conclusion of both Study Two and the associated publication (see, Hamilton et al., 2021), institutions must provide a support networks that facilitates a holistic approach to VR integration. That is to say, content creation must be viewed with the same importance as developing competency with the VR headset itself. Past research into Mobile-VR has tended to overemphasise the need for training with the HMD, whilst downplaying or completely negating the need to develop the material itself (e.g., Olmos et al., 2018).

In practice, universities should seek more cross-departmental cooperation to appropriately develop good quality 360° clips, films, and experiences. For instance, psychology staff liaising with computer science, animation, or creative filmmaking faculty/students to assist in the development of bespoke content. In addition, from a purely technical point of view, the creation of material for use with Mobile-VR headsets is significantly more straight-forward than those associated with high-end VR systems. For example, 360° content can be created and directly uploaded to YouTube, Vimeo, or other streaming sites without need for digital certificates or application signing.

Ultimately, access to appropriate content in the short-term remains a major barrier for the successful integration of Mobile-VR in HE psychology. However, by taking a holistic approach to its integration, prior planning can identify whether appropriate content already exists, or whether it might need to be created from scratch.

Table 7

MIA analysis table for each participant within focus group

	Focus Group 1					Focus Group 2			Focus Group 3					Focus Group 4			Overall Agreement (%)
	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15	P16	
Finances barriers pose a problem	NR	NR	NR	A	NR	A	A	A	A	NR	A	SD	NR	A	A	A	69%
Mobile-VR useful for experiential learning	A	A	NR	NR	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	NR	81%
Easy to assemble Mobile-VR headset	SA	NR	NR	A	A	SA	A	A	A	A	A	A	D	A	A	A	81%
Mobile-VR would motivate and engage students	NR	NR	A	NR	A	NR	SA	A	NR	A	SA	SA	SA	A	A	A	69%
Mobile-VR as a supplementary method	SA	A	SA	SA	SA	A	SA	A	A	SA	NR	A	NR	NR	A	NR	75%
Mobile-VR can facilitate classroom discussions	A	NR	NR	A	SA	SA	A	A	A	A	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	A	56%

Note. Consult Table 5 in Section 6.4.7. for a full overview of the codes used for MIA.

6.6 Discussion and Conclusion

The purpose of the current study was to assess the attitudes of psychology lecturers towards Mobile-VR integration in their classes. By conducting a series of focus-group discussions with lecturers naïve to Mobile-VR technology, the study was able to address pertinent attitudes that could influence intention to implement. Using constant comparison analysis and micro-interlocutor analysis in tandem, six overarching themes were formulated. These were: (a) experiential learning; (b) accessibility of Mobile-VR; (c) student engagement and motivation; (d) pedagogical impact; (e) curriculum integration; and (f) barriers to adoption.

Like the findings of Study Two, psychology lecturers identified Mobile-VR's ability to deliver immersive experiential learning as being uniquely suited to psychology education. Being able to take the perspective of another person, especially within the context of clinical or mental health psychology, could allow students to gain unprecedented insight into the lived experiences of another. Therefore, educators should be aware of the transferability of these applications across educational domains and delivery mediums. Whether using high-end systems or accessible Mobile-VR, educators across the last two studies have exalted the benefits of immersive technologies to provide experiential learning opportunities. And as Papachristos et al. (2017) has already concluded, Mobile-VR is an effective and accessible method of facilitating such pedagogical experiences. Despite this, there was a marked difference in the attitudes regarding the *purpose* of such an exercise compared to previous studies. Experiential learning in Study Two was viewed within the context of vocational learning and behaviour change, whilst the current study framed such learning within a purely academic framework. This was likely because many of the lecturers in Study Two used VR as a procedural tool for student/patient interaction, whereas the attitude in the current study was that it should be used as a tool for supplementary theoretical learning. Previous empirical work has substantiated the utility and effectiveness of VR as a tool for increasing knowledge through first-hand experience and perspective taking (e.g., Adefila et al., 2016; Campbell et al., 2021). However, unlike many of the experimental studies

identified in Study One, lecturers here did not view the pedagogical impact of such learning as being merely quantitative (i.e., learning outcomes on tests or assessments). Rather, psychology lecturers hoped that increased student motivation and experiential insight would facilitate in-depth classroom discussion among peers. These collaborative learning practices would allow psychology students to share insights and perspectives based on a shared Mobile-VR experience in the classroom. Indeed, these discussions would form part of a predefined learning objective where Mobile-VR would supplement a variety of other traditional teaching methods and materials.

It was hoped that the use of low-cost and accessible Mobile-VR headsets would alleviate many of the barriers encountered with high-end hardware in Study Two, as well as in previous research (e.g., Alfalah, 2018; Cooper et al., 2019; Fransson et al., 2020). Psychology lecturers were enthused at just how easy Mobile-VR was to operate, remarking that it was user-friendly and required very little training. This bodes well for future applied practice as previous models of technology acceptance identified the degree to which a system is easy to use as being a central determinant of future integration (Davis, 1989). Mobile-VR may therefore be a far more intuitive immersive technology to integrate in HE psychology classrooms compared to high-end systems like the Oculus Rift. Although lecturers were encouraged at the relative ease of use of Mobile-VR, there were several common impediments and barriers that have also been identified in the previous study (Study Two). Although the unit cost is relatively small, psychology lecturers still identified an initial financial investment as being a major barrier. Many were apprehensive about approaching their institution or department for funding, preemptively assuming that financial support would not be forthcoming. Furthermore, psychology lecturers identified the reliance on pre-made 360° content as being a major issue. It is clear that a common trope running through the studies of lecturer perspectives is a need for bespoke material suited to individual teaching needs.

6.6.1 Limitations

A potential limitation of the current study could have resided in the fact that lecturers only had around two-weeks to interact with the Mobile-VR headset prior to the focus group. Given that all participants had never used VR in an educational capacity before, this may not have been enough time to develop a fully informed opinion. For instance,

they may not have had time to watch additional material beyond that originally prescribed. However, longer exploration periods such as those used by Lee and Shea (2020) tend to be reserved to pre-service teachers in full-time education. To employ a similar approach with full-time lecturers who already have a range of teaching and administrative responsibilities would not have been feasible. A second limitation is the lack of control over the type of mobile smartphone used by each focus-group participant. Differences in screen size, resolution, processor, speaker, etc. could all have influenced the attitudes both positively and negatively towards the experience. However, a truism of the Bring Your Own Device (BYOD) approach advocated by the current study is that in a naturalistic classroom environment, staff and students *will* all be using different phones. Therefore, the current study is a natural reflection of how this kind of technology will ultimately be implemented in HE psychology classrooms.

6.6.2 Conclusion

By conducting a series of online focus-groups, the current study made a novel contribution in understanding the attitudes of psychology lecturers towards pedagogical Mobile-VR. Lecturers were generally positive about the future applications of the technology, suggesting that experiential learning could help supplement traditional theoretical understanding. Further, they felt that Mobile-VR provided a user friendly and accessible means of delivering immersive technology to their students. However, barriers remain in terms of addressing the financial feasibility of implementing such technology in HE institutions, as well as the availability of appropriate 360° content.

7 STUDY FOUR – USING VIRTUAL REALITY TO LEARN MENTAL HEALTH CONCEPTS: A QUALITATIVE STUDY OF STUDENT MOTIVATION AND LEARNING

7.1 Chapter Overview

The two previous chapters have investigated the attitudes and perspectives of HE lecturers towards VR integration in the classroom. A common perceived benefit was that VR may allow students to embody the lived experience of another person, resulting in increased understanding. Psychology lecturers in Study Three identified clinical and mental health psychology as being one such domain that may benefit from the experiential insights afforded by Mobile-VR. Furthermore, they remarked that the integration of Mobile-VR might help facilitate student motivation and engagement with the subject matter. Therefore, it was decided to implement Mobile-VR in a Psychology of Mental Health module within a university setting. The current study investigated student attitudes as they pertain to learning, motivation, and engagement through semi-structured qualitative interviews. The current chapter describes the methods and procedures employed, before discussing the findings and analysis. Like the previous two studies, this chapter follows a layout and structure similar to that suggested by Riley (2014).

7.2 Background and Novel Contribution

Lecturers and instructors in Study Two relayed the benefits of using VR as a means of knowledge acquisition through experiential learning. Lecturers from a variety of disciplines remarked that the ability to embody the perspective of another would allow their students to change their behaviours and attitudes in the context of applied practice. This was especially true in areas such as healthcare and nursing. Psychology lecturers in Study Three also identified experiential learning as an encouraging and novel method of teaching disciplines such as mental health or clinical psychology. However, psychology

lecturers envisaged the benefits of VR as being mainly academic as opposed to facilitating behaviour change in applied settings. It was postulated that VR could help bridge the gap between a purely theoretical understanding of mental health concepts and the novel insights afforded by body-ownership of a virtual avatar. Further, psychology lecturers also remarked that the use of Mobile-VR technology could engage and motivate students to learn by providing them with an innovative means of acquiring information and knowledge. Therefore, this study will integrate Mobile-VR in a psychology of mental health module and examine the student perception of their motivation and learning. In particular, the study seeks to understand the motivational factors that drive learning and knowledge acquisition whilst using Mobile-VR.

The current study makes several novel contributions to literature. Most importantly, it represents a shift in how pedagogical VR is conceptualised and studied. For instance, the systematic review in Study One has already demonstrated that VR can be an effective means of providing academic and scholastic learning. In addition, students tend to view this integration positively, citing that it is an engaging and enjoyable medium in which to learn. However, most of these findings are drawn from experimental, media-comparison studies where VR is conceptualised as being “in competition” with competing methods of education (e.g., VR versus a PowerPoint, VR versus a traditional lecture). As educators made clear in Studies Two and Three, this is precisely *not* how they envisage its place in the educational sphere. Rather, they view it as just one pedagogical tool among many. Consequently, this study takes VR out of the lab, and into the classroom. A pre-defined HE module forms the basis of its integration by allowing students to interact with the technology as a supplementary educational tool. In doing so, this study starts to move away from the traditional question of “if” VR should be used, and starts to investigate the “why” and “how” it should be used.

The current study also represents the first time that Mobile-VR has been integrated into an existing psychology of mental health module. As identified in Study Two and Three, despite VR’s potential in psychological education, it has thus far been underutilised and understudied. In addition, no other study has used a motivational framework (ARCS, see Section 7.4.2.) to qualitatively examine the relationship between student learning and

motivation whilst using Mobile-VR as a pedagogical technology. Therefore, the current study is not only able to identify the specific factors that have the potential to underpin Mobile-VR learning but can also make practical recommendations for applied use in the classroom.

7.3 Aims and Objectives

The present study employed one-to-one semi-structured interviews with students following post-hoc integration of VR material in a mental health module. By employing this method, several key study objectives were identified:

- To investigate whether the positive perception of VR as a tool for mental health education espoused by lecturers (see Study Three) was also reflected by students.
- To understand the degree to which students perceived the benefits and advantages of using Mobile-VR as a pedagogical tool in mental health education.
- To examine the specific factors that can influence student engagement through VR using an established motivational framework (ARCS).

7.4 Theoretical Framework

As scholars and researchers have long emphasised, a theoretical framework is an essential component to any study (Lederman & Lederman, 2015). A theoretical framework grounds the project in existing theories, allowing the researcher to plot a roadmap to achieve the stated aims and objectives.

There are two main aspects to consider when conducting the current study. Firstly, the findings of Study One as well as previous research (e.g., Radianti et al., 2020) has identified a distinct lack of pedagogical theory informing VR application. Therefore, it is imperative that explicit consideration of *how* the technology is expected to inform students of mental health concepts is given (thus grounding its application in theory). Secondly, as Section 7.3. has already outlined, a fundamental objective was to ascertain the motivational factors that might influence VR learning. This requires a conceptual

understanding of the various factors that underpin motivation in an educational context. As a result, it necessitates that any pedagogical framework also recognises the role that attention, engagement, and motivation plays in the educational process. These factors are discussed in the proceeding section.

7.4.1 Generative Learning

A *generative learning* approach was applied when devising the VR intervention. As Osborne and Wittrock (1985) remark, *generative learning* allows for the student to integrate new knowledge with pre-existing information. The overarching theory stipulates that people are not merely passive recipients of information. Rather, the learner must actively construct meaning by forming relationships between existing schemas and new sources of knowledge (Wittrock, 1992). This overall approach is uniquely suited to the aims and objectives of the current study. Specifically, it was not the intention to teach students an entirely new concept or theory (this had already been done during the module). Rather, it was hoped that VR would help build-upon current knowledge and existing understanding of the relevant conditions. As Grabowski (1996) states, this approach allows the learner to “reorganise, elaborate, and/or reconceptualise information” (p. 898). This ultimately leads to what Wittrock (1989) classifies as “accommodative learning,” or the ability for someone to form an entirely new concept of a topic (p. 349). In relation to the current study, it was envisaged that this new conceptualisation would be acquired through the VR experiences (e.g., schizophrenia simulator) and integrated with knowledge obtained during the curriculum (through lectures, workshops, presentations, etc.).

The second reason a *generative learning* approach was deemed most appropriate was its strong emphasis placed on the motivational factors underpinning knowledge acquisition (Hanke, 2012). Building on the earlier works of Aleksandr Luria (1973), Wittrock (1992) recognised the role that arousal plays in attending to educationally salient stimuli. Wittrock (1992) suggests that attention and motivation is a prerequisite to building and constructing meaning between previously acquired knowledge and new sources of information. If someone is not sufficiently motivated to engage, they will ultimately fail to make the effort necessary to form these relationships. Conversely, a well-structured

and attention-grabbing medium has the potential to facilitate the engagement necessary to encourage learning. Considering that this study aimed to examine students' perception of a VR intervention for teaching mental health concepts, as well as its motivational factors, a *generative learning* framework was uniquely suited to the aims and objectives.

7.4.2 ARCS Motivation Framework

As aforementioned, a *generative learning* framework was employed as it provides a structured roadmap for: (i) using VR to build-upon pre-existing mental health knowledge; and (ii) investigate the role of motivation in the learning process. However, although motivation and engagement constitute a fundamental component of *generative learning* processes, the theory does not expand upon the specific factors that underpin educational "motivation" as a construct (Hanke, 2012). As a result, this research might have been undertaken with an altogether vague notion of how motivation should be conceptualised and investigated. Therefore, it was decided that an existing framework should be used to guide the nature of the research (i.e., use a deductive method to inform the interview schedule and subsequent analysis). Any guiding motivational framework had to be compatible with the overarching *generative learning* approach by being: (i) grounded in educational theory; and (ii) consistent with the theoretical underpinnings of the theory (see, Grabowski, 1996; Hanke, 2012; Wittrock, 1992). The ARCS module of motivation proposed by Keller (1987, 2010) was ultimately regarded as the most appropriate choice.

The ARCS model was used to inform the nature of the interview questions, as well as act as a deductive framework for analysing qualitative data. The ARCS model postulates that students are motivated by their instructional materials in four distinct ways. Educational material must be (i) attention grabbing; (ii) relevant to learning objectives; (iii) instil a degree of confidence in the learner; and ultimately this will lead to (iv) satisfaction and motivation to learn. In 2010, Keller developed the Instructional Materials Motivation Survey (IMMS) to quantitatively assess his ARCS framework by examining each of the aforementioned constructs. This 36-item questionnaire was used as the basis for the interview schedule by probing the attentional factors, relevance, confidence, and satisfaction whilst interacting with VR. Although this represents the first time that the ARCS framework has formed the basis for qualitative research in pedagogical VR, the

theory has previously been employed in quantitative investigations of associated technology (e.g., Di Serio et al., 2013; Khan et al., 2019; Stepan et al., 2017).

7.5 Methods

7.5.1 Module Characteristics

The present study featured post-hoc integration of VR videos in a Psychology of Mental Health module at a Scottish university. The module was delivered over 14-weeks to fourth year psychology students. Due to COVID-19 restrictions, the module was delivered entirely online through a combination of synchronous (e.g., online workshops) and asynchronous learning activities (e.g., recorded lectures, journal articles). These covered various topics related to mental health including anxiety, mood, and personality disorders. Students were assessed through a mid-term essay, and an end of module examination.

A series of VR videos relating to content taught during the module was presented to participants after their final exam (for a list of the videos, see Table 8 in Section 7.5.7.). This was to ensure those participants did not receive an unfair advantage/disadvantage by participating in the study compared to those who did not. Therefore, the delivery of VR content was *post-hoc* (i.e., after all teaching and assessments had taken place) as opposed to integrated *throughout* the module.

7.5.2 Participants

The present study recruited six participants comprised of one male and five females. The average age of a participant was 25 years old ($SD = 5$), ranging from 22 – 36 years of age. This sample size has been deemed sufficient for a project of this nature, allowing for a comprehensive analysis whilst at the same time not being unwieldy (see, Braun & Clarke, 2013; Fugard & Potts, 2015). All participants had to have enrolled and completed the Psychology of Mental Health module during the current academic year. Only one participant stated that they had any prior experience with VR technology.

Volunteer sampling was employed as the method of recruitment in this study. The principal researcher advertised the study at several synchronous online sessions, most commonly the mandatory weekly seminars. An online advert was also placed on the module's virtual learning environment (VLE) page. Students could then contact the principal researcher directly by email to receive further information about the study and complete the informed consent form. A Mobile-VR headset would then be posted to their residence which would allow them to watch the required VR content. All participants were told that they were free to keep the headset at the conclusion of the study. It is important to note that the principal researcher was not involved in the delivery of the module, and had no formal interaction with the students in a teaching capacity. Consequently, the possibility of socially desirable interview answers were reduced.

7.5.3 Procedure

A Mobile-VR headset was posted to each participant's residential address a couple of days after the final module exam. This ensured that all learning material and assessments had been completed prior to watching the VR material. The Mobile-VR headset was the same model used in Study Three. A description of the headset and its specifications can be found in Section 6.4.2. Participants were emailed links to three VR videos relevant to material covered during the Psychology of Mental Health module. Participants had approximately two weeks to watch the clips before taking part in an online one-to-one interview via Zoom. Interviews were semi-structured in nature (see, Smith & Osborn, 2003) and lasted approximately 45-60mins. A list of interview questions and associated prompts can also be found in Digital Appendix 7.1. At the conclusion of the study, participants were told that they were free to keep the Mobile-VR headset. This both ensured that there was no cross-contamination due to COVID-19 and served as a form of remuneration for participating in the study.

7.5.4 Construction of Interview Schedule

As stated in the aims and objectives, the present study examined the attitudes of students as they relate to motivation and subsequent perceived learning. Therefore, it was essential that the interview questions and associated prompts were constructed appropriately to investigate this phenomenon. As a result, a deductive approach was

taken in that the interview schedule was influenced and derived from a pre-existing questionnaire and framework. Keller's (2010) Instructional Materials Motivation Survey (IMMS) derived from his earlier ARCS framework was used (Keller, 1987). A more detailed description of this is provided in Section 6.4. By using this approach, each of the four motivational factors could be addressed, allowing for a nuanced and comprehensive conversation with the participant. In addition, the semi-structured nature of the interview still allowed for adequate flexibility to deviate from these factors if interesting points were raised. A full list of interview questions and prompts can be found in Digital Appendix 7.1.

7.5.5 Data Collection and Transcription

Each one-to-one online interview was audio and video recorded to assist with subsequent transcription. All interviews were transcribed verbatim by the principal researcher with the assistance of Express Scribe Transcription Software – a program that allows the user to slow-down or speed-up recorded speech. Once this was completed, paper copies of each interview were printed for manual annotation, as well as being important to nVivo 12 for subsequent analysis.

7.5.6 Thematic Analysis

Like Study Two, reflexive thematic analysis (RTA) was deemed the most appropriate method of qualitative analysis for the present study. An in-depth summary of RTA, as well as a discussion of its benefits and advantages has already been undertaken and can be found in Section 4.4.4.

Like previous studies conducted in this thesis, RTA employed an iterative process of organising and reorganising themes. For instance, originally Experiential Learning and Content Relevance comprised of two separate and independent themes. However, during the recursive process of rereading transcripts, it was decided that students placed relevance on the VR content *precisely because* it afforded them an embodied experience of what it was like to suffer from a mental health condition. Therefore, this was amalgamated into a single all-encompassing “Relevance Through Experience” theme.

7.5.7 Virtual Reality Stimuli

Participants received links to three VR videos that related to mental health topics covered during the module. This included content about anxiety disorder (covered in Week 4), bipolar disorder (covered in Week 6), and schizophrenia (covered in Week 7). Each VR clip was chosen in consultation with the module coordinator ensuring that it was directly related to content covered in class, as well as being an accurate representation of the condition it purported to represent. A detailed description of each clip is included in Table 8 below. Links to all VR videos used in the study can be found in Digital Appendix 7.2.

Table 8*List of VR material provided to students prior to interviews*

Title	Length	Description	Generative Learning
Inside Anxiety – A 360° Degree Video Drama	9:10	A point-of-view experience that allows the student to embody someone with an anxiety disorder as they live their daily lives. An inner monologue (voiceover) describes the person's thoughts whilst other people interact with them in a variety of settings.	Students learn about the symptoms of anxiety disorders in class. However, VR allows the viewer to experience these symptoms as if they themselves had the disorder. In addition, the VR clip can exemplify precise situations where someone might experience a panic attack. Visual and auditory cues induce a state of panic in the viewer that cannot be replicated by other means of teaching.
What Bipolar Disorder Feels Like (360°)	3:34	Computer generated imagery is altered and changed in response to a voiceover describing first-hand accounts of patients' experience with bipolar disorder. This describes accounts of manic depression and mania, with the VR providing a visual account of the testimony (e.g. visual disturbances).	Students will cover the symptoms/treatment of bipolar disorder in class. However, the VR builds upon this learning by providing first-hand accounts and testimony from real patients. This humanises the condition. Further, the VR gives students a visual perspective of the various cognitive disturbances experienced, as well as articulating the polarity of the depressive and manic episodes.
Schizophrenia – A Paranoid Episode	1:21	The viewer takes the embodied perspective of someone suffering a paranoid episode on the street. Visual disturbances and audio hallucinations can be seen and heard.	Students learned about the symptoms of schizophrenia and psychosis through online lectures and reading. The VR supplements this learning by allowing the student to actually experience what hallucinations could feel like. In addition, the clip allows the student to experience the frightening nature of psychosis. This is difficult to adequately explain in a didactic setting.

7.6 Findings and Analysis

The present study seeks to understand the attitude of HE students towards using Mobile-VR as a learning tool for mental health concepts. In particular, the study investigated the factors that influenced motivation and engagement with the technology. Using thematic analysis, four themes were formulated: (a) holding attention; (b) relevance through experience; (c) knowledge application; and (d) tangential learning and future inquiry. A brief description of each of these five themes is provided in Table 9 below.

Table 9

Overview of formulated themes

Theme	Description
Relevance Through Experience	Relates to student understanding of how VR related to core module content. Mainly how theoretical concepts could be “experienced” through VR.
Holding Attention	Theme examines the intrinsic immersive factors of Mobile-VR, and how they influence student motivation.
Knowledge Application	Theme examines the influence that Mobile-VR’s applied utility can have on a student’s motivation to engage with it.
Tangential Learning and Future Inquiry	Students display heightened motivation to independently seek out additional information after a VR experience.

7.6.1 Relevance Through Experience

In his 1987 paper, Keller succinctly outlines the concept of content relevance as a means of pedagogical motivation. If a student were to ask, “why do I need to learn this?” or “why do I need to do this,” and an adequate explanation is not forthcoming, then the content may not be wholly relevant to the overall learning objective (Keller, 1987, p. 3). Simply put, students must understand *how* learning activities relate to the overarching aims of

the curriculum. For instance, the integration of Mobile-VR in a mental health module must allow for students to understand how the VR experiences directly relate to the concepts or theories they have learned in class.

Over the course of the analysis, it became apparent that the embodiment component of VR learning was central to contextualising and imparting relevance to the educational material. Referencing Kolb et al. (2011), this study underscores the pivotal role of experiential learning in situating the learner at the heart of the educational process, facilitating the absorption of new information through active engagement. This approach is significantly enhanced by the integration of body ownership and embodiment afforded by VR, allowing students to gain a deeper understanding of the associated mental health conditions (Slater et al., 2022). Integrating VR into mental health education enhances learning beyond the traditional classroom setting, facilitating a connection between theoretical concepts and experiential insight. VR's immersive nature allows students to experience firsthand the realities of those living with mental health issues, effectively moving beyond the constraints of conventional instructional approaches. This shift towards a more embodied grasp of educational content creates a meaningful and impactful resonance with students. Indeed, the connection between theoretical ideas and the embodied perspective of mental health was mentioned repeatedly:

“Saying, here's the theory and here is what the DSM (Diagnostics and Statistics Manual) has said about this disorder. And now we are going to experience what that might be like [...] I could think back to some of my lectures and think ‘okay, this is how it must feel’ if that makes sense?”

Monica

“Well, I think I understood the point of them (the VR). Obviously, we have read about each of those conditions. So, you kind of know what people experience – but I have never actually experienced it first-hand. That’s what the VR done.”

Sophia

As indicated by these responses, the idea of experiential insight and relevance to course content is intrinsically linked. Students understand how the content of the VR material is related to information that they have previously learned in class, and this affords them the opportunity to garner novel insights. This practice is precisely how instructors and lecturers envisaged VR being integrated in psychological education in Study Three (in particular, see Section 5.5.1. and 5.5.5.). By making the VR content as specific as possible to the core learning objectives, students see the relevance of utilising such technology for their learning needs. As Picciano (2009) has previously stated, this allows VR to be integrated “with purpose” into a specific curriculum or module (p. 7).

As has already been discussed, students were able to identify how the VR materials were related to content covered in class. They were motivated to engage with the VR content because it helped bridge a gap between a purely theoretical understanding of a specific condition (e.g., bipolar disorder), and an embodied perspective of it. Ultimately, an important consideration lies in precisely how the students makes sense of this embodied perspective if it is going to have any pedagogical value. Throughout the interviews, participants remarked that although traditional teaching methods allowed one to gain theoretical or conceptual knowledge of a mental health condition, VR allowed the participant to *experience* what it was like to suffer from it. As several participants remarked:

“I think it (VR) could be more effective than watching just a lecture on mental health. Don’t get me wrong, lecturers are very informative, and they tell you what you need to know. But telling me what I need to know and feeling what I need to know is totally different. So, the VR adds to the experience.”

Sophia

“I think it just felt - even though they were short - quite realistic. You feel as if it’s real, and that you can interact with it. So, it was just a very different kind of experience to actually learn from compared to what I am used to. You feel as if

you are personally inside their head, you feel as if you actually are them – I haven't experienced that before.”

Elliot

The feeling of embodiment described by participants was not confined merely to a general understanding of what it is like to suffer from a mental health condition. Rather, some participants were able to give specific examples of how the VR material provided relevant additional information to supplement understanding. For instance, Taylor and Sophia remarked that the bipolar disorder clip allowed them to fully appreciate the polarity of depressive and manic episodes experienced in the condition (see Table 8 for a brief overview of the clip). As suggested by the responses, traditional means of teaching gave students a general understanding of symptomology, but the VR material built upon this:

“The bipolar one. The ‘high.’ I didn’t realise ‘how high’ - or how magical it was. I knew that they tended to say there were happy – but I never quite grasped how manic that high was [...] I just associated it with happiness. But it is not just that. That VR experience showed me that colours are brighter, and sounds are nicer – that I did not realise at all. So that was an eye-opener.”

Taylor

“In the bipolar disorder one – obviously they were saying that things can be dark and then suddenly turn very bright. That was very good to watch because you don’t really appreciate just how dramatic that shift is – it felt quite real in a sense [...] When you read about it, you understand it to a certain extent. But the VR allowed you to feel as if you were the person going through it. It was really effective.”

Sophia

Here, Sophia touches upon an important and interesting point. She states that reading about the condition can facilitate knowledge acquisition “to a certain extent.” But it is the VR experience that allows the student to transcend a purely theoretical understanding of the disorder and start to internalise and assimilate those *feelings* with the self. As Villalba et al. (2021) puts it, mere data is no substitute for embodied experience when understanding the subjective reality of another. This is a clear example of how relevant Mobile-VR content can help expand and supplement exiting knowledge.

The essence of any novel pedagogical system is that it provides an effective means of learning that cannot be replicated using another method (whether that be 2D videos, slideshows, educational games, etc.). Therefore, students must assess how relevant VR is to their educational needs within the context of all other available methods of learning. When students were asked about the benefits of Mobile-VR for mental health education, they often directly compared it to traditional means of teaching encountered during the module. Students remarked that they gained novel insights into the cognitive processes of a sufferer through experiential VR learning, something that they did not fully appreciate by reading journal articles or watching lectures. Therefore, students were not only able to appreciate VR as a relevant source of psychological information, but also compared its effectiveness directly with other forms of learning:

“I think it was more interesting and effective than the research papers. I think in a lot of (the articles) there’s a lot of jargon or technical terms that are difficult to understand. And so sometimes you can get really lost in what they’re actually trying to get across [...] But I think the VR definitely helps in getting across what it must be like to suffer from the condition. I don’t think you really get that from just reading. It’s less personal.”

Monica

“It is certainly easier to imagine it if you have the VR experience. Especially because you kind of saw how it visually impacted that person and how they

experienced it. So, it added more valuable information than if you were just reading the symptoms or the PowerPoint just had a list of things to read though.”

Sophia

“It was more of a realistic experience of each of the disorders compared to when you just sit and read about them. I got more of an understanding from it.”

Elliot

These quotes clearly suggest that participants perceive value in the novel insights afforded by VR technology. Namely, embodied experience allows students gain a first-hand perspective of what it feels like to suffer from a mental health condition. However, does this necessarily lead to a more refined and nuanced understanding of the condition itself? Only a handful of previous studies have investigated VR’s utility as a pedagogical tool for mental health concepts, and seldom has this been in the context of psychology education (e.g., Bidaki et al., 2020; Formosa et al., 2018; Lee et al., 2020). For example, Formosa et al. (2018) exposed 50 participants (a mixture of students and non-students) to a schizophrenia VR simulation, in addition to gathering a range of quantitative pre and post-test measures. The study found that participants significantly increased their levels of knowledge and empathy in relation to schizophrenic symptoms after exposure. This would suggest that VR is not only an effective means of learning cognitive information about symptomology, but also can lead to the empathetic response reported by many participants in the current study. Despite this, Formosa et al.’s (2018) study did not have a control group, making it difficult to ascertain whether differences in empathy and knowledge acquisition could also be replicated using traditional means of teaching. However, the current study *did* expose students to a range of synchronous (e.g., seminars and workshops) and asynchronous (e.g., VR clips and recorded lectures) activities, and participants were adamant that the VR experiences were more effective in conceptualising the subjective feelings of the sufferer than other methods.

Despite VR showing potential as a pedagogical tool in psychology, there is one anticipated objection that is bound to be raised by lecturers. Namely, is the current study advocating that VR is a better method of learning simply because it was viewed by the students as more effective and engaging than recorded lectures or journal articles? The answer is invariably, “no.” Despite students expressing that the VR was superior in allowing them to comprehend how an individual experiences a mental health condition, they did not say that it was relevant to all areas of theory. For instance, VR is unlikely to have assisted in the understanding of diagnostic and treatment methods, or neuropsychological factors associated with mental health conditions. Students simply expressed that VR was superior in allowing them to imagine the symptomology and experiences of the sufferer from an embodied perspective. Therefore, as advocated throughout this thesis and by others (e.g., Fransson et al., 2020), VR should be used as a supplementary method of learning where its use is best justified, and not as a replacement for the whole. However, the current study did find that students reported gaining novel insights into the lived experience of mental health sufferers through engagement with VR material. Therefore, the attitudes espoused by lecturers in Study Three regarding VR’s potential use as an experiential learning tool is also embraced by students. As Alfalah et al. (2017) has previously iterated, this synchronous attitude is essential in helping both staff and students utilise the technology to its full potential.

7.6.2 Attention and Immersion

A key objective of the current study was to understand the motivational factors that might drive student engagement with Mobile VR. So far, the prominent theme of experiential insight has been discussed with reference to both academic instructors and students. However, the current study also wanted to understand whether other motivational factors could influence students’ perception of VR technology.

As Keller (1987) intimated when developing the ARCS Model; drawing attention to a pedagogical method (such as VR) is a necessary, but not sufficient step to motivating students. Rather, the pedagogical method in question must draw *and hold* the attention of students. Several participants remarked that a novel attribute of using VR for mental health learning was that it completely encapsulates the viewer, filtering out distractions from the outside environment. Using Mobile-VR requires the participant to place their

smartphone inside the viewer, and then hold the headset over their eyes for the duration of the experience. As a result, the participant is effectively *cut-off* from outside interference such as distractions from computers, laptops, or mobile phone notifications. At its best, the VR medium facilitates an experience where the participants' attention is undivided by other distractions. Indeed, participants made direct reference to this aspect:

“Especially when you are watching the other videos or reading the articles, you can get easily distracted. Whereas when you have the VR headset on, you feel like you can’t really escape it because you get immersed in the experience. You don’t have any other distractions, as you are totally immersed in it. That is the good thing about it.”

Sophia

“But it is 100% more immersive – because when you have the headset on you can’t see anything else. You can’t get distracted by other things going on round about you. You are totally focused on the experience – you can move around and see everything.”

Elliot

“I just – I think it is so good because you’re totally focused on that one little task that you are doing. You’re in a total bubble whilst you’re doing it. That does help you learn so much more. You are focused on that and nothing else.”

Victoria

As a means of direct comparison, Sophia and Elliot further reiterate the point that Mobile-VR is capable of holding attention in a way that other asynchronous materials (e.g., required reading) cannot:

“Even you can just drift off and get distracted (while reading journal articles). Whereas with this you get sucked in and it holds your attention. Like I said, even with the last video, it was long, but it did not feel like nine minutes at all.”

Sophia

“The other stuff gets a bit tiring – you loose interest really quickly. But the VR is very interesting and you’re excited to see more. You are totally transported to that situation.”

Elliot

Although the concept of presence and immersion have been widely studied in VR (e.g., North & North, 2016; Shu et al., 2018), there is limited research on how the concept directly impacts educational motivation. Where immersion and presence have been studied in a pedagogical context, researchers are primarily interested in the interaction between subjective presence and precise *learning* outcomes, as opposed to motivation *per se* (e.g., Makransky et al., 2017). Therefore, it was a key aim of the current study to address specific motivational factors that may underpin engagement with Mobile-VR technology.

Students in the current study have suggested that an intrinsic characteristic of VR, namely the fact that it completely immerses and surrounds the participant, is itself a motivating factor. The nature of the VR experiences requires the participant’s undivided attention and active participation for the duration of the activity. As several participants have already cited, this is in direct contrast to many other traditional forms of pedagogical practice (e.g., required reading). In these circumstances, students tended to “get distracted,” “drift off,” or “loose interest.”

One objection is to propose that student motivation has little to do with the immersive nature of VR. Rather, motivation is simply derived from the novelty of the system, and not the unique characteristics of the technology itself. Indeed, researchers have previously

stated that novelty alone may be a driving factor behind student motivation (Cooper et al., 2019). Others (e.g., Makhkamova et al., 2020) have been cautious, and proposed the need for future research in ascertaining the precise interaction between VR's "novelty effect," and its intrinsic attributes in driving engagement. However, responses in the current study are suggestive of motivational factors that are influenced by more than a mere novelty effect. Rather, participants commonly made direct and overt reference to VR's immersive capabilities as a driver of engagement. It was precisely *because* of VR's ability to fully immerse the participant in a pedagogical medium, free from background distractions or external stimuli, that many students claimed they engaged with the material. As Keller (1987) ARCS's model stipulates, to derive motivation through pedagogical means, an educational method must grab and then sustain students' attention. In VR, the sustaining of attention is achieved by the full encapsulation of the participant within the virtual environment, limiting outside distractions or external stimuli.

7.6.3 Knowledge Application

One of the most important aspects of motivating students to interact with any pedagogical method is that it inspires confidence in the learner (Keller, 1987). In particular, the student should be confident that they can take the knowledge they have gained, and apply it successfully in their academic endeavours (Di Serio et al., 2013; Loorbach et al., 2015). Therefore, one of the fundamental aims of the current study was to investigate whether students envisaged an applied benefit to VR integration. Namely, are students motivated to learn using VR because they gain practical knowledge that can be demonstrated successfully in scholastic activities?

As part of the Psychology of Mental Health module, students were assessed using two main methods: a mid-term essay, and an end-of-module examination. Therefore, during the interviews, participants made multiple references to how the VR content would have helped them in both activities. Remember, although the VR content was integrated as part of the module, its delivery was *post-hoc*, meaning it took place after all assessed activities. Therefore, students reflected on the perceived applications of the VR content in hindsight.

When asked if and how VR could be applied in an academic context, students intimated that it would have helped expand or “flesh out” their exam or essay answers:

“When we were writing our papers, if some people had seen that (the VR clips), they may have taken a very different perspective. When we were writing some of our exam answers I feel like this would have opened a few doors. It would have helped a little bit to express a different perspective.”

Monica

“I think it (VR) mostly would have helped for the exam for the Psychology of Mental Health module because for some of the questions, we had to compare different disorder. So, I think the VR would have helped to expand and flesh out some of those answers more.”

Sophia

“Yeah, I think it (VR) would definitely have helped me if I was to see it before I went into an exam. Just because you have that life experience, and you can relate back to what you’ve learned. You can use the VR to expand on the knowledge that you have learned. You can give specific examples of symptoms and things. I like how you can actually use the information you get from the VR in a real situation like an exam.”

Victoria

Students were confident that if they were afforded the opportunity to interact with VR material prior to their assessed activities, they could have use it to expand on existing answers. Students did not suggest that the VR material provided a wealth of new or novel information; rather, it helped expand their current understanding of the concepts or theories. Further, students were confident that this expansion of knowledge could be successfully applied and demonstrated in their module essay and exam. When asked to expatiate on their earlier remarks, Monica reasoned that although her prior knowledge

would have been sufficient in answering the exam question, the additional of VR would have supplemented her response with other relevant information and material:

As I said – I think it (VR) could have given the exam answers a lot more depth actually. You know, you could have shown more depth of learning. Because – we know the answer, but sometimes you need a little bit more in an exam or an essay. VR could have provided that I think.”

Monica

Indeed, this perception is shared by numerous participants who were interviewed over the course of the study. This suggests that students felt confident that VR material could provide a range of practical examples that could help supplement their academic assignments. As numerous studies have remarked, students who feel confident in their ability to apply knowledge gained through an educational medium such as VR, will be more motivated to engage and interact with it (see, Khan et al., 2019; Proske et al., 2014). Therefore, it is of paramount importance that VR is integrated in such a manner that students can envisage a practical and applied benefit to its use. As previous studies have found, students who are confident that their educational tools provide information that can specifically be applied to examinations or assessments are more likely to interact with it (Su & Cheng, 2015). As has been repeatedly communicated throughout this thesis, VR should not be implemented in a manner that is spurious or lacking in predefined learning objectives. Rather, students place value on experiences that give them the confidence to ultimately demonstrate what they have learned in applied academic contexts such as examinations and essays.

7.6.4 Tangential Learning and Future Inquiry

An intriguing, and thus far understudied aspect of VR learning is its potential to inspire future independent learning. In higher education, VR has typically been imagined and then integrated as an end in itself. That is to say; VR is used in an isolated capacity to provide specific information about a specific subject or topic area. These comprise a diverse range of subject areas including anatomical education (e.g., Maresky et al., 2019),

engineering (e.g., Fogarty et al., 2017), and computer science (Akbulut et al., 2018). However, as Study Chapter One of this thesis has already highlighted, the isolated intervention and assessment of VR integration has meant that little is known about its subsequent influence on learning. For instance, no research has examined attitudes relating to VR's potential to motivate independent learning after the main pedagogical objectives have been completed. This is to say, do students see VR simply as an end in itself, or do they envisage it as a means to future enquiry?

The idea of motivating individuals to self-educate around a given topic is related to the concept of tangential learning. Although tangential learning has typically been studied in the context of video-games (e.g., Rokošný, 2017), it is not confined to a single technology or application. The underlying concept is that if information is presented to an individual in a medium that they enjoy interacting with (e.g., a recreational computer game), they will be more motivated to seek out content surrounding that topic independently. To give a specific example, Squire et al. (2008) found that students who were exposed to a political and historical computer game became more likely to seek scholarly information related to that topic (and in turn improve their grades). Indeed, educators have also begun to realise the potential of using tangential learning approaches to motivate students to engage with material independently (Mozelius et al., 2018).

As the current study has shown, students have stated that they found VR motivating as it held their attention, was relevant to their academic activities, and the knowledge gained could be demonstrated in applied contexts. However, participants also commonly expressed and demonstrated instances of independent learning and self-educating behaviours consistent with tangential learning. It was precisely *because* students enjoyed interacting with the VR material that they conveyed a motivation to explore related content using their own initiative. It is important to state that participants were not explicitly told to seek out additional content after watching the assigned VR videos. Therefore, any future inquiry undertaken by the student was at their own discretion. The motivational effect of VR to stimulate curiosity was summed up concisely by one of the participants:

“I think people are generally intrigued and enjoy VR. And I think for a lot of people, that intrigue itself is enough to think – ‘oh, I will go and find out a bit more information’ about whatever they are watching.”

Monica

Nearly all students remarked that they either had or intended to use the VR headset to seek out additional VR content on the subject of mental health. Specifically, students wanted to use VR to embody or experience first-hand the symptoms associated with other conditions not covered during the module. This intrigue to seek additional VR material independently was highlighted by several participants:

“The way the schizophrenia video was presented was so eye-opening and showed how horrendous it is. But that makes me want to investigate it more. I would want to investigate other conditions from a first-hand perspective using the VR. I think it gives you a more well-rounded understanding of the conditions.”

Sophia

“I was even looking at different VR videos that I could watch on the VR headset. I would be interested in looking up other conditions that I have learned about over the course of the Psychology of Mental Health module. You know – different disorders. See if there are other videos like that [...] As I said you want to learn and find out more on your own – it (VR) motivates me to do that.”

Elliot

The above examples exhibit a willingness to seek out additional VR material within the confines of the Psychology of Mental Health module. However, there was evidence that participants were also motivated to use VR to self-educate around other subjects or classes they were taking as part of their degree. For example, Sophia was so motivated by

the unique first-hand perspective afforded by VR that she planned to use it in her other psychology classes:

“So, I am intrigued – as I know we can keep the headsets I have been finding more of these kinds of videos and using the headset more just to get different perspectives. Because I am doing Atypical Development as my other module – so I was interested to find some similar videos from developmental psychology and those kinds of topics and use the VR headsets. So, I would really want to keep using this sort of thing. I actually want to find more videos to learn more about different disorders and that sort of thing. For example, like autism. That’s something we are looking at in another one of my modules, and it is a common disorder that keeps coming up. I think the VR could add a lot of valuable information about that.”

Sophia

Later in the interview, Sophia was keen to reemphasise the motivational influence VR had in encouraging additional independent learning:

“I would try and find more VR videos just because it more – like I said, one of the modules I am doing is Atypical Development – obviously they go over autism and ADHD and so on. So, it will definitely be interesting to try and learn about that through the VR stuff – that same perspective. So, I do want to seek that out.”

Sophia

Consistent with the core principles of tangential learning, participants displayed a willingness to seek additional psychological material precisely because they enjoyed interacting with the medium. As several students remarked, they would independently search for VR content that was not prescribed either as part of the module, or as part of the specific study. Students were keen to emphasise that this self-seeking behaviour fulfilled an academic or scholarly purpose and was not merely for enjoyment or

entertainment. As the above examples highlight, students remarked that they looked for additional content to “learn,” “find out more,” or “get different perspectives” on mental health or psychological concepts.

If VR was only to motivate students to self-educate using additional VR content (as opposed to other modes of learning), it could be argued that its tangential learning qualities are rather limited. For instance, there is only so much someone can learn about a given topic by watching 360° content on a Mobile-VR headset. However, participants in the current study also remarked that they were motivated to self-educate using a range of other pedagogical methods, having first been motivated by the VR content they were assigned. For instance, participants cited turning to academic papers and documentaries to further explore a mental health condition that they were interested in:

“It (VR) got me interested in the conditions and the symptoms and things like that. You know – even just that wee bit of interest kind of motivates you to go and take a look at things on your own. So, I watched some of the VR videos that were on the suggested list on YouTube [...] I also got a couple of second-hand books about people’s experiences with schizophrenia and things like that. It’s really interesting and I think it will help me too.”

Monica

“It makes you personally involved and that makes you want to find out a bit more about the subject. I think it opens your eyes that bit more. The schizophrenia one was really eye opening for me. After watching it I just thought. ‘I want to find out more about this.’ So, I watched a couple of TED talks on YouTube that were really interesting. As I said, I think the VR makes you want to find out more.”

Taylor

“I watched the schizophrenia video a couple of times. I actually even showed it to my family members because I thought they’d be interested too. It’s not just the

VR though – it kind of spurs you on to do your own research. I wanted to read a bit more about the condition from other places, so I looked at some papers and some different websites.”

Elliot

As exemplified by participant responses, the use of VR can create an initial spark in motivating further inquiry. Far from encouraging students merely to watch additional VR material, participants demonstrated a willingness to seek out academic sources of information on a given topic or subject. Most importantly, students consistently remarked that the assigned VR material was a crucial motivating factor in deciding to self-educate around the topic. This is consistent with other forms of pedagogical technology (e.g., game-based learning) that have the potential to elicit self-educating behaviours in students (Mozelius et al., 2018). As Mozelius et al. (2016) suggests, using an engaging or attractive pedagogical medium to introduce concepts can “inspire learners to further self-study” (p. 3). Mozelius et al. (2016) was also able to empirically demonstrate that the more salient an educational experience was, the more likely students are to self-educate. Although this previous research has been conducted in the field of game-based learning, the qualitative findings of the current study suggest that it has the potential to apply to VR learning too. The relative cost-efficiency and accessibility of Mobile-VR technology means that a large cohort of students can be provided with a headset capable of displaying 360° content. If VR can be successfully integrated as a supplementary method of education in psychology (see Sections 4.5.2. and 5.5.5. for a detailed overview), students may be motivated to further self-educate around a topic as a result of their experience. This provides a tantalising possibility that the benefits of VR integration may not only be immediate, but rather can have long-term ramifications in how students interact with their course material.

The current research provides novel insight into the potential for VR to elicit self-educating behaviours and future inquiry in psychological education. Students remarked that they were motivated not only to seek additional VR content on the topic of mental health education, but also to pursue scholarly and academic resources. In addition,

students were not explicitly instructed to conduct this independent learning behaviour. Rather, the motivation and initiative to search for additional material occurred entirely organically as a result of engagement with the initial set of VR material.

7.7 Discussion and Conclusion

The current study represented the first time this thesis has specifically investigated student attitudes as they pertain to VR in psychological education. By conducting a series of semi-structured interviews, the study aimed to assess specific factors that influence motivation and engagement with the VR medium. By employing reflexive thematic analysis, four themes were formulated that best encompassed the data; (a) relevance through experience; (b) attention and immersion; (c) knowledge application; and (d) tangential learning and future enquiry.

The current study primarily employed a deductive approach to analysis by using previous research and literature as a basis for theme formulation. In particular, the study leaned heavily on Keller's ARCS model of pedagogical motivation (see, Keller, 1987, 2010). Although previous research has used Keller's ARCS theory as a basis for quantitative analysis of motivation (e.g., Di Serio et al., 2013; Khan et al., 2019; Stepan et al., 2017), the current study represents the first time it has been employed as a qualitative framework to investigate VR in psychology education. Preceding research has typically used Keller's (2010) Instructional Materials Motivation Survey (IMMS); a 36-item questionnaire, to quantify levels of motivation and engagement with educational systems. However, employing a purely quantitative approach to understanding motivation and engagement with a novel pedagogical system will undoubtedly fail to provide the level of nuance that qualitative approaches can (Ochieng, 2009). Therefore, by pursuing an underutilised qualitative approach, the current study provides an in-depth analysis of four key themes as they pertain to student attitudes in educational VR.

Throughout this thesis, a predominant concept has been that of experiential or embodied learning. Psychology lecturers in particular have highlighted the future potential of

allowing their students to embody the lived experience of another person. Nowhere has this application been met with more intrigue than allowing students to experience what it might be like to live with a mental health or psychological condition. However, the current study represented the first time that this thesis has specifically investigated the attitudes of students. From the interview data, it was clear that students derived relevance from the VR material by relating it to content that was covered in class. Several students remarked that it helped bridge the gap between a purely theoretical understanding of a specific condition, and an experience of what it might be like to live with it. For instance, one student made reference to the fact that the DSM-5 provides a theoretical perspective of symptoms, whilst VR allows them to experience how those symptoms might manifest in a real-world scenario. It was precisely the ability for the student to link the embodied experience to previously learned information that gave the VR relevancy. From a purely applied standpoint, students need VR to be integrated in such a way that they understand how its content relates to prior knowledge and learning objectives (Fransson et al., 2020). Unfortunately, much prior research neglects to address how VR is related to core curriculum content. This can be because VR is used as a standalone experience that is not integrated into a predefined curriculum (e.g., Johnston et al., 2018; Parong & Mayer, 2018), or because the VR lesson is of no practical relevance to the participant pool (e.g., psychology students participating in a VR lesson about plant biology [Allcoat & von Mühlennen, 2018]). As Keller (1987) remarks, a student must understand immediately how an educational activity relates to their overarching learning goals to motivate them to engage. In the current study, the prevailing attitude was the student's derived relevancy by relating the experiential VR clips to theoretical information. Didactic information could be supplemented and expanded upon by giving students a visceral experience of what it "feels" like to suffer from a psychiatric condition. As was memorably remarked by one participant, there is a difference between *telling* someone what they need to know, and then *feeling* what you need to know.

Just because a pedagogical tool is relevant to the learning objectives, it still might not be sufficient in encouraging students to interact with it. For instance, the ARCS model of motivational design states that it is imperative for an educational medium to grab and hold the attention of the participant (Di Serio et al., 2013; Keller, 1987; Loorbach et al.,

2015). Throughout the current study, students made reference to many of the unique qualities of VR technology to both grab attention, and then sustain it over a period of time. Of particular interest was the idea that the VR headset completely enveloped the participant, filtering out background distractions and stimuli. This allowed the student to experience the VR material with undivided attention. Students were also keen to compare this mode of learning with other asynchronous activities that they encountered over the course of the Psychology of Mental Health module. They remarked that attention could start to drift and wane when they were reading journal articles or the required textbook chapters. In contrast, students emphasised that the VR headset completely held and sustained their attention throughout the experience.

As has already been discussed, VR material must be relevant to content that has been covered in class. Students must be able to link themes or concepts experienced in VR to theoretical principles that have been taught as part of the core curriculum. However, this is but one part of the motivational framework. As Keller (1987) makes clear, students must also understand how they can *apply* the knowledge learned through VR in a practical way. Students must be confident that they can learn valuable information from participating in the experience, and then be able to apply this in their academic endeavours. A prominent attitude expressed by students was that they could apply what they learned in the VR experiences to their module assignments. Students remarked that the VR would help them add new perspectives on essay and exam answers undertaken as part of their assessments. In particular, the idea of *fleshing-out* or expanding on answers, especially around the topic of symptomology, was prevalent. As this study did not employ a post-intervention assessment, it is difficult to ascertain exactly how this additional information would have manifested in an applied example. This is certainly an area that can be explored later in this research project. However, students did remark that it would have helped them compare and contrast the symptoms of different conditions or provide the additional information necessary to *flesh-out* answers. However, what is not in doubt is that students derived value from the VR activities precisely because they envisaged an applied benefit to its use. They were confident that they could take information garnered as part of the experience, and practically apply it to their assessed materials (i.e., exams and essays). This serves as an important practical

lesson for those higher education institutions or lecturers who wish to integrate VR as part of their modules or lessons. Motivation is predicated on students being given the opportunity to demonstrate their learning in an applied context after the initial intervention. As discussed in Study Chapter Two and Three, this could comprise of a classroom discussion surrounding the VR material. Or as the current study has intimated, students must be able to envisage how they could practically apply the information they have learned to a post-intervention assessment, exam, or essay. Indeed, in practical advice given to educators, Keller (1987) remarks that instructors must explicitly state the “future usefulness” of any instructional material prior to implementation (p. 4). By doing so, students are more likely to be motivated to engage with the educational tool.

A novel attitude expressed in the current study was that of tangential learning, or the proclivity to engage in unprompted future study. This concept is founded upon the idea that if information is divulged using a medium the student enjoys interacting with, they will be motivated to explore these theories using their own initiative (Mozelius et al., 2018; Rokošný, 2017; Squire et al., 2008). As Keller (1987) would classify it, this is a “natural consequence” of students engaging with the VR material in the first place (p. 5). Students expressed that they were motivated to seek out additional VR material on the subject of mental health after engaging with the initial prescribed videos. They displayed a curiosity for exploring additional VR perspectives of psychiatric conditions such as developmental disorders like ADHD and autism. Students were also able to link the information learned to other psychology modules they were taking as part of their degree (i.e., learning was not confined to the Psychology of Mental Health module exclusively). Far from prompting students to only engage with additional VR content, participants also expressed that they were motivated to seek additional reading or lecture material as a result of the experiences. In effect, VR could serve as a *jumping-off point* to inspire students to take responsibility for their own learning and pursue independent study. However, what remains to be seen is whether the propensity to self-educate is applicable to all areas of psychology. The current study looked exclusively at experiential VR material related to psychiatric and mental health conditions. Therefore, it is possible that students may not be as motivated to self-educate around other psychological topics as a natural consequence of viewing VR material. Indeed, this thesis aims to investigate VR’s

application in non-clinical topics in future chapters. However, what the current study does contribute is the novel attitude that VR technology can prompt students to undertake future inquiry on a given topic using their own initiative. Importantly, this motivation to investigate further stems from the enjoyment and intrigue afforded by the VR experience. This suggests that VR may have longer-term benefits beyond the immediate integration of the technology into classes. As has already been discussed, students are motivated by VR because they envisage the applied benefits it confers to assessments (e.g., exams and essays). However, an unexpected and novel benefit may be that it inspires independent learning that will benefit students beyond just their immediate assessed materials. Therefore, the attitudes raised in the current chapter should serve as a springboard for future exploration into the phenomenon of VR integration and self-education.

7.7.1 Limitations

As has already been mentioned in the introduction to this chapter, the VR materials were given to students in a *post-hoc* manner. Simply put, students were given access to the VR content after they had completed all assessed material in the Psychology of Mental Health module. For ethical reasons, a subset of students could not be given access to VR content prior to examination in case it gave them an unfair advantage over their peers. This means that student used hindsight to express attitudes about how the VR *could* have been useful *if* they had been given access to it during the module itself. As a result, attitudes were not collected in real-time as the student progressed through the module. In addition, it is challenging to know whether students would have displayed the same level of motivation if the technology had been used on a more frequent basis. These are limitations that can be addressed in future studies by taking several steps. The first is to integrate the VR content fully as an asynchronous learning tool throughout the duration of the module. By doing so, students can choose whether to engage with it as they would with any asynchronous learning activity. Secondly, attitudes should be studied at multiple predesignated intervals throughout the curriculum so that information can be collected in real time. Finally, at least some of the VR activities should occur prior to undertaking assessed activities. As a result, students can formulate more informed attitudes about VR's ability to provide useful information and material for exams, essays, and assessments.

7.7.2 Conclusion

In this chapter, semi-structured interviews were analysed using thematic analysis to assess attitudes relating to VR's use in a psychology module. In particular, the study attempted to understand the key motivational factors that drive students to interact with the technology. Four overarching themes were formulated that best gave a holistic overview of the attitudes of the six students interviewed. Participants remarked that the VR was relevant to their academic endeavours precisely because it bridged the gap between a theoretical understanding of a mental health condition, and an actual *experience* of it. Furthermore, they suggested that they could practically apply the information learned in exams, essays, and assessments. Students found these experiences to be particularly salient and attention grabbing because of VR's unique ability to completely envelop the user in the environment. This held their attention and filtered out background distractions. Finally, a novel finding of the current study was that VR could help motivate future inquiry and inspire self-learning. As students found the VR medium to be intrinsically engaging and enjoyable, many attempted to garner subsequent information from additional VR clips, documentaries, research articles, and books.

8 STUDY FIVE – USING MOBILE-VR IN ENVIRONMENTAL PSYCHOLOGY: A QUALITATIVE AND NEGATIVE CASE ANALYSIS

8.1 Chapter Overview

In the previous chapter, this thesis explored the attitudes and motivations of psychology students towards using VR as a tool for learning mental health concepts. Consistent with the perceptions of instructors and lecturers in Study Chapters Two and Three, students were generally positive about using the technology as an educational medium, citing several key factors that drove motivation. The current chapter presents the findings of a study that fully integrated VR as an asynchronous learning activity in an Environmental Psychology module. By tracking levels of motivation and engagement at predesignated intervals throughout the module, it became evident that the attitudes and perceptions of one participant deviated substantially from the others. It was therefore decided to undertake an in-depth negative (or deviant) case analysis of this student to better understand how their attitudes could be reconciled with the prevailing opinions of students.

8.2 Study Background

Throughout this thesis, students and lecturers have extolled the benefits of using VR technology as a means of experiential learning. Specifically, lecturers in Study Three were positive about integrating VR as a means of teaching mental health concepts and theory. A follow-up study (Study Four) found that students were generally positive about this application, remarking that it allowed them to gain novel insights into the lived experience of others. As evidenced by the attitudes and perceptions of participants (see, Section 7.6.1.), this novel insight was typically facilitated through body-ownership of someone suffering from that specific condition (see, Bertrand et al., 2018; Slater et al., 2022). Colloquially, being “in the shoes” of another allowed the participant a greater

insight into another's everyday experience. However, clinical and mental health psychology represents only a small fraction of the topics that make up the psychological discipline. This begs the question as to whether VR's use within psychology education is restricted to embodied learning, or whether it has potential in more abstract or conceptual topics.

To examine this broad question, the current study integrated VR into an Environmental Psychology module. Environmental Psychology is generally interested in understanding the interaction between human beings and their physical environment. Perhaps paradoxically, this interaction with the *physical environment* is associated with a myriad of conceptual and abstract ideas such as personal space, territoriality, and evaluations of privacy; ideas that could be challenging to relay using traditional teaching means. Therefore, in consultation with the module coordinator, VR clips that could help elucidate some of these ideas were integrated at various timepoints throughout the module.

A limitation of the previous study was that it integrated VR in a *post-hoc* manner. As a result, students had to employ a degree of hindsight in formulating attitudes relating to how the VR activities might have impacted their learning. One solution is to integrate VR within a psychology module itself, as opposed to employing it after all assessed material has been completed. By making the VR content available to *all* module participants (regardless of whether they participated in the study or not), no student was privy to information or materials that other students were not. A second limitation of the previous study was that it collected data at only one isolated timepoint. Although this approach worked well within the confines of *post-hoc* VR integration, it is unable to track changes in attitude over a longer time-period. Therefore, student attitudes and perceptions were monitored over the entire 14-week module using a reflective diary, and the Instructional Materials Motivation Survey (IMMS) (see, Keller, 2010). On week-14, one-to-one semi-structured interviews were conducted with all participants to gain a detailed understanding of student attitudes towards module integration.

Most students were positive about using VR as a means of learning environmental psychology, citing that it helped motivate and engage them in their education. However, a single participant (the negative case) was resolute in their attitude that the VR was not an engaging or motivating learning tool, nor was it helpful in understanding associated theory. These perceptions represent a significantly divergent attitude compared to those encountered elsewhere in this thesis. It was therefore decided that a negative case analysis was conducted to examine the attitude of this single participant in-depth. The current study explores where and why these attitudes and perceptions differ, and whether these can be reconciled with the prevailing opinion that VR is an enjoyable and engaging pedagogical utility.

8.2.1 Novel Contribution

The current chapter makes a range of novel contributions to our understanding of how VR can be applied in psychological education. Firstly, as has already been mentioned in this chapter, the current study integrated VR as an asynchronous learning tool across an entire module. As the systematic review in Study Chapter One outlines, most studies have utilised VR as a single, stand-alone, and isolated learning activity, giving students only limited exposure to the technology (see Section 3.5.3. for a more detailed overview). The systematic review found that 72% of studies included featured only a single VR intervention, with limited opportunity to interact with the technology outside of the scheduled class time. Therefore, the current study integrated VR at several predesignated intervals throughout the module, giving students ample opportunity to interact with the technology.

By integrating VR fully within a predefined module, the current study also makes a novel contribution by providing a naturalistic and ecologically valid environment to examine its impact. For instance, the VR activities were integrated as just one tool among many (an example of multi-modal learning) with no specific emphasis placed upon it. As a result, students were free to choose if they wanted to interact with it or not. For example, a student could choose to utilise the asynchronous VR activities in weeks two and four, but not in week eight. Unlike experimental studies, or those that utilise VR as a sole teaching method, students could freely choose if and when they interacted with it.

Consequently, utilisation and the attitudes that form as a result were allowed to develop freely, and not as a result of forced or mandatory use. Most importantly, this mode of integration (i.e., VR being just one tool among many) is consistent with the real-world attitudes of lecturers and instructors who have been interviewed throughout this thesis (see Study Chapters Two and Three).

Currently, no existing research has investigated the effectiveness of VR in improving comprehension of theoretical concepts in the field of Environmental Psychology. This study aims to determine whether VR can facilitate the understanding of abstract or conceptual themes pertinent to the field. This research diverges from prior VR applications, primarily focused on the medium's capacity to promote embodied learning and improve insights into mental health issues. For example, previous investigations within this thesis (notably, Study Four) have deployed the body-ownership illusion to aid students' socio-cognitive grasp of associated conditions, as discussed in works by Bertrand et al. (2018) and Slater and colleagues (2009, 2022). However, the VR experiences employed in the current study place less emphasis on the perception of specific body-ownership with its myriad of perceptual and visual cues. Instead, the focus is on providing the viewer an illusory experience of being in a particular environment instead of being a specific *person* (congruent with Slater and colleagues [2009; 2022] concept of Place Illusion). For example, the appreciation of architectural spaces focuses on promoting learning through increased environmental and spatial awareness rather than through physical embodiment.

Finally, no previous research has employed a negative case analysis as a means of better understanding the attitudes of higher education students towards VR. As evidenced throughout this thesis and previous research, most students have a positive attitude towards VR being used as a learning tool in education. However, what happens when a particular participant holds an opinion contrary to that of most others? Generally, researchers would dismiss these attitudes as being atypical, and of limited consequence to an overall theory or idea. However, as Athens (2015) remarks, a negative case analysis allows for the possibility of reconciling these divergent attitudes with the prevailing opinion of others. Therefore, the current study represents the first time that this

approach has been undertaken to better understand how VR can be best applied in future pedagogical application.

8.3 Aims and Objectives

By integrating VR into a pre-existing Environmental Psychology module, the present study has several key objectives:

- To investigate the degree of engagement and motivation when VR is used as an asynchronous activity in a distance learning context.
- To understand VR's educational capacity in elucidating conceptual or abstract theories in Environmental Psychology.
- Attempt to reconcile divergent attitudes towards pedagogical VR by conducting a negative case analysis.

8.4 Methods

The following section provides a detailed overview of how VR was integrated into the Environmental Psychology module, and how the data were collected. It also gives a detailed description of how the negative case analysis was conducted, as well as its justification for being used as the qualitative method of analysis in this study.

8.4.1 Module Overview

The current study integrated VR into a fourth year Environmental Psychology module at the University of the West of Scotland. The module was conducted online (due to COVID-19) over the course of 14-weeks. A total of six students took part in the module; four of whom signed-up to the study. The module comprised of a weekly synchronous seminar (conducted online), as well as a range of asynchronous activities that students had to complete. Each of asynchronous activities related to a specific topic that was covered over the past week. Examples include crowding and privacy, architectural psychology, and restorative environments. Asynchronous activities comprised of a mixture of recorded lectures, required reading, journal articles, and suggested videos. In addition, on

predesignated weeks, students could also access several VR videos that related to concepts or topics that had been covered over the past seven-days.

All materials relating to the module were included on the associated virtual learning environment (VLE) page. From here, students could access the links to the VR clips, as well as other asynchronous activities associated with the module.

8.4.2 Integration of VR Material

As previously stated, one of the fundamental aims of this study was to fully integrate VR into a pre-existing psychology module. Therefore, the precise nature of its application was discussed and implemented in collaboration with the Environmental Psychology module coordinator. Congruent with the attitudes espoused by lecturers in Study Two and Three, it was important that the VR material was not *shoehorned* into topics where it would have little practical utility. To mitigate against this, in-depth discussions were had between the module coordinator and principal researcher to identify specific theories or topics within the module syllabus that could benefit from VR integration. It was only *after* these topics had been identified did a search for relevant and freely available 360° material take place. Again, this was to ensure that the teaching material influenced the choice of VR content, and not the other way around (an important point that has been made numerous times in this thesis). An iterative process of identifying and evaluating VR content was then undertaken until a final list of 360° videos were confirmed for use in the module. After the consultation process was complete, four topics were identified as suitable for having accompanying asynchronous VR material: Week 4 – Environment and Personality; Week 7 – Architectural Psychology; Week 9 – Institutional Environments; and Week 11 – Natural Environments and Restoration. A detailed description of each of the VR clips included, as well as how they related to the theoretical concepts covered in the module is included later in this section.

Consistent with the attitudes of psychology lecturers in Study Three, the VR component was integrated as a means of supplementing taught material. Its purpose was not to replace existing methods of teaching, but rather to help reinforce theoretical concepts

that were covered in class. Therefore, the same core teaching materials were present as in previous year groups, with the addition of the asynchronous VR content.

8.4.3 Recruitment and Participants

8.4.3.1 Recruitment Process

The integration of VR material in the Environmental Psychology module meant that all students were able to access the VR content, regardless of whether they decided to take part in the study component or not. All enrolled students were posted a Mobile-VR headset (see, Section 6.4.2.) prior to commencement of the module, allowing them to freely access the 360° material from home. All students enrolled in the class were contacted prior to the start of week-one and asked whether they would be willing to participate in the study (i.e., agree to complete the reflective diary and have a one-to-one interview). In the email contact, it was emphasised that those who did not wish to participate in the study would not be at an academic disadvantage and would still have the same access to core teaching content. Those who took part in the study were remunerated with a £20 Amazon Voucher that was given to them at completion of the study (on Week-14).

8.4.3.2 Participants

Of the six students enrolled on the Environmental Psychology module, four decided to participate in the study. Although this is a relatively small sample size, it still represents ~67% of all students who were originally enrolled on the module. Of the four participants, one was male, and three were female. The average age of the participants was 28 years old ($SD = 5$). None of the participants indicated that they had any prior experience with VR technology in any capacity. A list of the participants can be found in Table 10. Despite the smaller sample size, this study incorporates several recommendations by Braun & Clarke (2020, 2021c) that help mitigate these limitations. These will be briefly discussed in the associated sections below.

Table 10*Demographic information for participants*

Name*	Gender	Age (years)	VR Experience
Robert	Male	37	None
Evelyn	Female	26	None
Antonia	Female	25	None
Lesley**	Female	23	None

**Pseudonyms were used for all participants; **Negative case*

8.4.4 Negative Case Analysis

Negative (or deviant) case analysis has often been cited as an underutilised method of analysing data across the social sciences (Ross, 1963). When dealing with participant data that significantly deviates from the norm, certain methods of analysis (especially quantitative) tend to employ a degree of data clean-up. As remarked by Hanson (2017), outliers are generally viewed as a nuisance with the potential to skew the overall picture of the data. As a result, those data points outside a predefined threshold (e.g., two standard deviations from the mean) are discounted from the analysis. This is a common problem in qualitative analysis too. As qualitative data tends to be analysed and presented in *themes* (e.g., thematic analysis or constant comparison analysis), those participants whose attitudes do not conform to one of the formulated thematic groups tend not to be presented. As Potter (1996) intimates, the purpose of most traditional forms of qualitative analysis is to present an overall “pattern or regularity” (p. 20). However, as Wicks (2010) states, employing negative case analysis ensures that every piece of data collected in a qualitative study (regardless of its uniformity or divergence) is given equal consideration. This ultimately provides a more robust understanding of a particular phenomenon.

Negative case analysis is utilised because there can be much to learn from participants whose attitudes, ideas, or opinions deviate from that of the group. As Athens (2015) expressed, the purpose of negative case analysis is not only to examine divergent ideas or attitudes, but also to reconcile these with an overarching theory or framework. By doing so, the researcher can examine whether these divergent attitudes are truly anomalous, or whether further consideration is needed to the overall theory (Athens, 2015; Mays, 2000; Potter, 1996).

Negative case analysis is unique in its application in that it can be thought of as a *post-hoc* method of examining qualitative data. For instance, few researchers would conduct a qualitative study in the expectation that a negative or deviant case is going to arise (although some research have intentionally sought out negative cases [e.g., Doherty & Bersani, 2020]). These divergent cases typically only become apparent when the analysis process has been commenced or viewed in its entirety. As a result, there is no predefined structure of how to present a negative case analysis. For instance Mann et al. (2020) conducted a negative case analysis of three divergent participants drawn from a larger cohort of 124 participants. The researchers did not explicitly include data from the typical cases, and instead focused exclusively on the negative ones. On the other hand, Gretter et al. (2019) conducted and presented a traditional thematic analysis, whilst only mentioning how attitudes deviated from established literature in the discussion. An example from the field of psychology (Rizq & Target, 2010) saw researchers describe a single negative case (one participant) subsequent to presenting findings from their twelve typical participants. The point of illustrating these examples is to emphasise the lack of a predefined structure or style when it comes to deciding how to present the negative cases. Therefore, this study took a similar approach to that of Rizq and Target (2010) by conducting a qualitative thematic analysis, and then providing an overview of the typical cases. After these have been presented, an in-depth examination of the negative case is carried out, using the themes formulated from the typical cases as a means of comparison. Importantly, this process attempts to reconcile certain divergent attitudes with the typical experience of students allowing for a range of suggestions for applied practice.

Indeed, the integration of both typical and deviant cases confers several advantages. Firstly, incorporating a negative case analysis enhances comprehensive coverage of the research area under investigation by examining a range of perceptions and attitudes. As Braun and Clarke (2020, 2021c) suggest, this focus on “richness,” “complexity,” and “data coverage” can help mitigate against the limitations of a smaller sample size. Secondly, it can also assist in a broader discussion of “generalisability” and “transferability” (for a more detailed overview of these concepts, see Section 3.4.1.1.). For instance, the ideas of “assessment relevancy” espoused by the negative case are generalisable to motivational frameworks (i.e., ARCS) in a range of educational contexts (see Section 8.5.5.1.).

8.4.5 Procedure

Prior to commencement of the Environmental Psychology module, all students (regardless of whether they participated in the study component or not) were posted a Mobile-VR headset to their residence, as well as instructions on how to use it. On specific weeks, links to a selection of relevant VR material was posted to the VLE allowing students to access the 360° content with their headset.

Those who chose to participate in the study were asked to complete a series of tasks over the course of the 14-week module. On predesignated weeks, they were sent a link to a QuestionPro survey that prompted them to complete a reflective diary concerning their thoughts about the teaching materials used during the previous seven days. Example questions included: “of all the asynchronous activities encountered in the past seven-days (online lectures, video clips, online reading, virtual reality experiences), what one(s) did you find most engaging or motivating?” and “was there a particular asynchronous learning method or material that you did not enjoy over the past seven-days? Why was this?” A full list of questions contained in the reflective diary can be found in Appendix 8.1. Students were prompted to complete this reflective diary on four separate occasions during the module. On two of those occasions, VR had not been used in the previous seven-days, so should not have influenced their perception of the module’s teaching materials. On the other two occasions, VR *had* been used in the previous seven-days, and therefore might be explicitly mentioned during a student’s reflections. Students were

given seven days (from day of issuing) to complete their diary as not to cause an overlap with other teaching materials and topics covered in subsequent weeks. Again, it is worth reemphasising that at no point were students made aware that the VR component was the thing of particular interest to the principal researcher. By conducting the study in this manner, the chance of favourably biasing the VR material as a result of researcher promotion was minimised. Student attitudes towards VR material could therefore be generated in as naturalistic an environment as possible.

On Week-14 (the last week of the module), one-to-one semi-structured interviews were conducted with each of the participants enrolled in the study. These interviews were all conducted via Microsoft Teams and lasted between 45-60mins. An in-depth description of this type of interview technique (and its relative merits) has already been extensively covered. It was only during the interview (after some general introductory questions) that participants were informed that attitudes relating to the asynchronous VR activities were the focal point of the study. Until this point, no particular emphasis was placed on the VR content, allowing the student interaction with the technology to unfold naturally.

Depending on whether the student said they did or did not interact with the VR material, the principal researcher followed a series of prompts on an interview schedule to garner more information (see Digital Appendix 8.2.). If students stated that they did interact with the material, they were asked a series of questions related to their overall experience with VR and how this impacted their perception of the module (e.g., “was there a particular VR experience you found particularly motivating or engaging?” “Did the VR help to conceptualise or visualise topics that you learned in class?”). If the student stated that they seldom interacted with the VR material (as was demonstrated by the negative case), they were asked a series of questions that could further elucidate the reasons for this (e.g., “was there a particular reason you did not interact with the material?” “Was there anything that could have been done to increase your engagement with the VR material?”).

8.4.6 Data Collection and Transcription

The current study utilised a form of data triangulation to collect a range of information from participants. Data triangulation refers to the qualitative practice of gathering information from a variety of sources, allowing for a comprehensive and in-depth understanding of the topic (Carter et al., 2014). Specifically, this study utilised what Patton (1999) referred to as “method triangulation.” Method triangulation involves the collection and analysis of multiple data streams, such as those from interviews *and* reflective diaries, as opposed to an isolated or single source. Again, this is congruent with Braun and Clarke’s (2013, 2020, 2021c) focus on the richness and complexity of data streams, and not merely the size of the recruited sample. By utilising this method of data triangulation, the study was able to investigate in-depth attitudes of a smaller number of participants as opposed to a broad, but surface level understanding of a larger group.

All reflective diary entries were collected via QuestionPro, an online platform for hosting surveys and questionnaires. Once these diaries had been completed, the written content was imported to nVivo12 to help assist analysis. The reflective diary questions can be found in Digital Appendix 8.1. The end-of-module interviews were conducted via Microsoft Teams. These were both audio and video recorded to aid the transcription process. A copy of the semi-structured interview schedule can be found in Digital Appendix 8.2. Once the interviews had been completed, the audio information was transcribed verbatim with the assistance of Express Scribe transcription software. The manual transcribing of interviews from the raw recordings aided in the iterative process of reading and rereading interviews to gain a more nuanced sense of the data. Once the interviews had been transcribed, these were also imported to nVivo12 to assist in the analysis process. Digital Appendix 8.3. contains copies of the interview transcripts.

8.4.7 Virtual Reality Stimuli

As mentioned in Section 8.4.2., the integration of VR material was done in consultation with the module coordinator (an expert in Environmental Psychology). As a result, not only was the quality of the VR material a factor in its inclusion, but also its suitability to reinforce conceptual theories and ideas learned in class. Table 11 below presents a detailed summary of each of the VR videos included as part of the module, where and

when it was integrated, and how its content related to material covered as part of the core curriculum. Digital Appendix 8.4. provides URL links for all videos included on the module.

Table 11

Description of all VR videos provided during the Environmental Psychology module

Week/Topic	Title	Description	Relationship to Theories
Week 4 – Environment and Personality	Koyoyo Train Station – 360° Experience	Point-of-view experience of what it is like to walk through one of the busiest metro stations in Japan. The video features the cramped conditions experienced on trains, and also on the station platforms. Viewers are taken on a “walk along” experience.	During this week on the module, students were taught concepts relating to environment and personality. This involved subjects such as personal space and territoriality. The two VR clips give students the chance to experience a busy and noisy urban environment (something that they could not during the COVID-19 pandemic). Students would be expected to relate their experience in VR to taught content on the subject of personal space, and how this might influence territoriality.
	Chandni Market, Delhi VR Experience	VR camera is played in a busy Indian marketplace. There is lots of noise as people and cars drive past. Camera remains stationary throughout the experience, allowing the participant to survey the environment.	
Week 7 – Architectural Psychology	The Macallan Distillery 360° Experience	The video gives the viewer a 360° experience of the design of the Macallan Distillery in Scotland. The building has been designed to blend into the surrounding environment and landscape – something that is emphasised throughout the experience. There are a number of landscape, aerial, and interior shots that allow the viewer to examine areas of interest.	During Week 7, students learned about how architectural choices can influence human behaviours and attitudes. In the first example (Macallan Distillery), the building design can be appraised by how it attempts to blend into the existing landscape. In the second video, students should appreciate how specific architectural and design choices are conducive to effective student learning in higher education. For example, in Week 7, workspace design and the use of natural light was covered, and this is something the viewer should be able to relate to in the video.
	VR Experience of The London School of Economics University	360° guided tour of the new London School of Economics building. The tour guide discusses the architectural design that is conducive to good student learning including classrooms, outside areas, break-out areas, and lighting.	

<p>Week 9 – Institutional Environments</p>	<p>The Texas Jail VR Experience</p>	<p>Video takes the viewer on a guided tour of the booking process, and internment in an American jail. The viewer gets a first-hand perspective of the cells, communal areas, and recreation facilities. Prisoners also speak directly to the viewer, expressing the lack of personal space and privacy.</p>	<p>Both 360° videos from this week examine the theme of Institutional Environments, The two videos chosen are from contrasting perspectives: the first being a prison; and the second being a hospital. In the first video, students would be expected to reflect on whether architectural and design choices are conducive to rehabilitation or not. Students would also be expected to reflect on themes discussed in Week 4 (e.g., personal space) and how these are influenced by design choices.</p> <p>In the second clip, explicit information about architectural design choices are made. Through taught material, students should already be aware of the theoretical concepts around institutional environments. The Great Ormond Street tour should reinforce these theoretical ideas by providing a concrete and applied example of how these choices manifest in a real environment.</p>
<p>Week 11 – Natural Environments and Restoration</p>	<p>Virtual Nature Walk in Glastonbury, UK</p>	<p>The VR experience takes the viewer on a nature walk in a woodland area of Glastonbury, UK. As well as imagery, the video also features nature and bird sounds. The 360° video was initially composed as a means of relaxation and mindfulness.</p>	<p>As part of this week’s activities, students had to reflect on what part the natural environment plays in human mood and behaviour (especially in the context of wellbeing). One of the weekly tasks was for students to reflect on local walks or environments that they found restorative.</p> <p>Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, and/or the urban residence of many of the students, the VR allows the viewer an experience of environments that they may not otherwise have access to. Students would be expected to reflect on theoretical concepts around restorative environments that were covered during the class.</p>
	<p>Most Beautiful Scenery – 360° VR Video</p>	<p>The video utilises a series of short clips showcasing a collection of natural scenery.</p>	

8.5 Findings and Analysis

As already outlined, there is no predefined structure or method for presenting a negative case analysis. In the current study, the negative case itself only became apparent during the analysis process when a series of discrepant attitudes were first noticed. By first employing a traditional thematic analysis, a deductive approach could be utilised by comparing a series of overarching themes from typical participants to that of the negative case. Therefore, the following section will give a summary of the findings from the three typical participants, before conducting an in-depth examination of the one negative case. As the negative case will be a focal point of analysis, the themes from the typical participants will be more concise in nature when compared to previous chapters.

The current study aims to understand the attitudes and perceptions of students towards Mobile-VR when fully integrated into an existing psychology module. In particular, using a variety of measures (reflective diary and one-to-one interviews), the study attempted to understand the motivational factors that drove students to interact (or not) with VR technology. In contrast to the previous study (Study Four), asynchronous VR content was integrated throughout the module, and student were prompted for feedback at predesignated time intervals. Using thematic analysis, four main themes were formulated from the typical cases: (a) breaking up the learning process; (b) holistic motivation; (c) relationship to module content; and (d) limitations of practical application. Table 12 below provides a brief overview of each of these four themes.

Table 12

Overview of formulated themes

Theme	Description
Breaking Up the Learning Process	Students remarked that the VR was motivating to use because it provided a welcome break from traditional asynchronous methods experienced during distance/online learning.
Holistic Motivation	Theme is concerned with how the integration of asynchronous VR activities influenced student motivation, engagement, and attitudes with the Environmental Psychology module itself (as opposed to merely with the VR component).
Relationship to Module Content	Students were able to relate theoretical concepts or ideas taught in class to experiences presented through the VR headset.
Limitations of Practical Application	Evidence of motivation to engage with VR content despite students citing a lack of practical applications for VR content (e.g., could not apply VR learning to exams or essay assignments).

8.5.1 Breaking Up the Learning Process

At the time of conducting the study, COVID-19 had meant that students had been learning online for approximately 18-months. As a result, participants in the current study had become accustomed to the university’s virtual learning environment (VLE) being the primary source of material. Through the VLE, students could also access required reading (in the form of journal articles), a series of online lectures, and links to relevant video and multimedia content. Participants in the current study remarked that this method of engaging with higher education content had become somewhat “*samey*,” as it had been utilised in an almost identical manner across all modules that they were enrolled in. As a result, students remarked that one of their biggest motivators for using VR was that it helped “break up” the module by adding a degree of novelty and originality. The idea that

it was something that students looked forward to engaging with was brought up in nearly all of the conducted interviews:

"I think it was nice accompaniment or supplement to what we had. As I said, I would have been quite happy to have used the headset every week – from week one right through to the end if it was available. Because it is almost as if it was a really welcome break. It breaks things up. It a nice distraction from sitting in front of your laptop all day reading through journal articles and reports. I think that was a really nice part of the whole VR thing. It was something that you looked forward to trying because it didn't feel too much like actual work."

Robert

"It definitely made it more fun. All my other modules are just purely academic stuff. There is no little videos or things to break it up that you can watch. So yeah, definitely, it has made it more enjoyable. It kind of makes this module stand-out in your mind. It sort of makes it completely different by just having one wee thing like the clips [...] I think the fact we have been working from home for the past year gave the VR stuff an extra impact."

Evelyn

"I thought that it was more a case of being a fun and kind of engaging way to understand the material. Over the last year I would say most of my learning has been done online. And most of those classes are exactly the same, you know? You kind of just sit in front of your laptop all day and it can just get pretty boring and repetitive. So, I thought the virtual reality clips were just a nice way of breaking things up a little bit. It made things just a little more fun. It was nice to know that there were fun activities to do other than just read journal articles or read lecture slides. It was kind of engaging to know that there was a fun activity to do after you had done all the kind of boring ones that are common you know in online learning now with COVID."

Antonia

It is clear from the student responses that they place a strong emphasis on VR's ability to instil a degree of novelty in the learning process. This is not a theme that was prominent in the previous study (Study Four). This could have been because it was conducted much earlier in the COVID-19 pandemic, and students had not yet become as disenfranchised with repetitive nature of some online learning activities. In any case, Keller (1987) does cite "variability" as an important strategy for improving engagement and motivation in any form of education. Therefore, the introduction of asynchronous VR activities would have likely intrigued students by offering a markedly different experience from what they were used to. Indeed, even within this thesis, psychology lecturers have already cited VR as a supplementary apparatus for "breaking up" parts of the module, and keeping students interested and engaged (see Section 6.5.5.). These findings could not be more timely. García-Morales et al. (2021) has already identified keeping students motivated or sufficiently attentive as a major barrier in the increasingly online-centric view of higher education (especially post-COVID). This has been a view echoed by numerous researchers and educators (e.g., Chiu et al., 2021; Ferri et al., 2020). Consistent with the findings of the current study, Liang et al. (2020) cites boredom and lack of enthusiasm as being specific impactors of student motivation in scholastic activities. Therefore, it is of paramount importance to identify and successfully integrate strategies that can help combat a general feeling of malaise or demotivation in HE students.

Research by Rahiem (2021) has already cited curiosity with novel pedagogical technology as a driver of motivation and academic engagement during distance learning. Therefore, even though students conceptualised the integration of Mobile-VR as a means of merely "breaking up" traditional online activities, it could serve a far more important purpose in continuing to motivate students to learn. The accessibility and economic value of Mobile-VR headsets can also mean that students can continue to access asynchronous VR content when they return to a more traditional form of higher education (i.e., on-campus activities). Although the idea of "breaking up" the often repetitive nature of online learning is especially prudent in the current climate, there is no reason to think that it

cannot be employed as a means of supplementing existing methods when a higher degree of normality is resumed.

Although instructors themselves may see little utility in employing a technology that only provides a momentary distraction from online learning, it would be prudent to see the bigger picture. If indeed students are motivated by the simple application of “breaking up” learning with the aid of Mobile-VR, this could have ramifications in how students perform academically, and how they evaluate the learning experience. Indeed, students did remark that the incorporation of Mobile-VR influenced how they assessed the Environmental Psychology module as a whole.

8.5.2 Holistic Motivation

Participants often explicitly stated that Mobile-VR provided welcome relief from the traditional means of acquiring information in a purely online course. Not only did this seem to have an impact on how they viewed Mobile-VR itself, but it also influenced their perception of the Environmental Psychology module as a whole. In this scenario, not only did the adoption of VR content seem to confer a transient benefit by motivating students at certain predefined intervals, but also shaped how they conceptualised and evaluated the entire experience of the class. For example, when asked whether he thought that the integration of VR made the Environmental Psychology module more interesting, Robert responded:

“It makes it more fun and engaging. Absolutely. Absolutely, yes.”

Robert

However, it was the follow-up that provided insight into how the adoption of VR would later shape his perception of the module as a whole:

So immediately I was intrigued (by the VR), and I guess that alone made me more interested in the module. You know, it grabbed my attention straight away. It was a nice addition.

Robert

This was also evidenced by an entry in the participant's reflective diary in the first week:

"Having received the VR headset I am very interested to see how they are going to be implemented into our studies."

Robert (excerpt from reflective diary – Week 1)

Robert was not the only student to highlight how the use of VR as an asynchronous method shaped their evaluation of the entire module. For instance, participants expressed surprise at how the use of a "wee thing" like VR could influence their enjoyment and engagement with the core content:

"Yeah, it (VR) definitely made it more fun. All my other modules are just purely academic stuff. There is no little videos or things to break it up that you can watch. So yeah, definitely, it has made it more enjoyable. It kind of makes this module stand-out in your mind. It keeps it interesting all the way through. It sort of makes it completely different by just having one wee thing like the clips [...] It motivates you to pay attention to other things like the lectures or just the course in general."

Evelyn

"The VR helped me be quite engaged with the module overall. I think that a lot of other students even in other modules would probably feel the same [...] I think it made the module a lot of fun. So, for me the module sticks out in my mind because we did have the VR clips to watch. As I have said before no other module or class that I have been in before has used that sort of technology, so I suppose it as a really kind of novel way of me being able to learn and interact. It is something I looked forward to using. It kept me interested because you never

knew what kind of video was coming next, or how it would relate to the topic.

That was cool.”

Antonia

Some students even remarked that they informed their peers about the Mobile-VR content available on the module because they found it so interesting or novel. For instance, Antonia followed-up on her previous comment by remarking that the use of Mobile-VR shaped how she described the module to other people:

“So, when people would ask me what elective modules I was doing this semester, I would always bring up the fact that I was doing the Environmental Psychology module. When they asked things like how it was going, I would always say that we were using the VR headsets and it was really quite different.”

Antonia

What is clear from these remarks is that the integration of Mobile-VR does not merely provide a means of “breaking up” online content. It appears that its benefits extend beyond this by shaping how students evaluate and reflect on the module in its entirety. An excellent example of how this can manifest was Robert’s insistence that just by providing the foreknowledge that VR was going to be used during the class, it immediately made him more invested and interested. From an instructors point of view, there is a common assumption that happy, engaged, and motivated students tend to produce better academic results (e.g., Hussein & Nätterdal, 2015). Although motivation and engagement are not necessarily precursors of scholastic achievement, there is a wealth of evidence to suggest that engaging students through technological means does have the potential to produce better learning outcomes (e.g., Gamon, 2001; Heafner, 2004; Su & Cheng, 2015). However, where this study takes novel strides is to qualitatively examine these motivational factors over an entire 14-week curriculum. For instance, previous research often places emphasis on student motivation with the VR technology *itself* (e.g., Liou & Chang, 2018; Makransky et al., 2017), or motivation within a single, isolated, non-integrated lesson (e.g., Parong & Mayer, 2018; Stepan et al., 2017).

However, by directly integrating Mobile-VR into a predefined and accredited psychology module, this study does not only examine how students evaluate the VR experience itself, but how this shaped attitudes towards the module holistically.

As is clear from the selected quotations, students are not merely stating that the use of VR was “fun.” There are plenty of examples in literature of students (e.g., DePape et al., 2020; Depape & Barnes, 2019) and educators (e.g., Bower et al., 2020; Serin, 2020) exalting the fun-factor of using VR. This is by no means a novel finding. However, what this study can demonstrate is that student interaction with asynchronous VR activities can influence their perception of the module as a whole (not just the VR component). By integrating fun, self-guided VR content at predefined intervals, students maintain their levels of motivations and engagement over the course. Instructors however must exercise a degree of caution. As Lege and Bonner (2020) implicitly suggest, VR will only remain an engaging or motivating medium until such time that it becomes “banal” or overused (p. 169). Therefore, its propensity to motivate is likely contingent on its appropriate and spared usage.

8.5.3 Relationship to Module Content

As has already been explored in this thesis, students can derive motivation from relating VR content to information that they have already acquired in class. For example, in Study Four, students were able to see how mental health concepts and theories were related to embodied experiences in VR. Of particular interest in the current study was how students would be able to draw relationships between VR content and the far more abstract nature of certain concepts or ideas in Environmental Psychology.

As has been stated on numerous occasions, the relevance of any pedagogical medium will directly impact students’ perceptions and attitudes towards it (e.g., Di Serio et al., 2013; Keller, 1987, 2010). In the previous study (Study Four), the VR content was closely aligned to the material taught in class (e.g., the lecture on the symptoms of schizophrenia directly related to the embodied experience of those symptoms in VR). However, many of the VR materials utilised in the Environmental Psychology module did not have the same degree of linearity in their relationship between taught material and VR experience. For

instance, the two VR clips used in Week 4 were not *explicitly* on the subject of personal space or territoriality. Rather, they comprised of 360° footage of an environment (i.e., a train station and marketplace) that just happened to be busy and crowded. However, those videos could just have easily been used to exemplify architectural choices or urban design and planning. It was the responsibility of the student themselves to impress upon the video their own relevancy to taught material. That is to say, students were expected to focus on just a single component of the video (i.e., overcrowding), and then relate this to theories and concepts about personal space that were covered in class.

What was clear from the students' attitudes was that they derived meaning and value from the VR content because they *could* relate it to theories and concepts learned during the module. To focus on the aforementioned example, Robert made reference to the VR clips encountered in Week 4. He remarked that he was able to understand how concepts of personal space delivered through the lectures and asynchronous course material were illustrated in VR. When asked whether there was a particular set of VR experiences that stood out in his mind, he answered:

"I would say the train station one certainly. And I think there was another one of a market-place in India. So yeah, that really kind of brought home the theme that we were learning about that week. It really related to the task that we had to do for that week as well. It related well to personal space in urban environments, so it brought those two factors together which I really liked. To stand somewhere and actually see people moving around and being all bunched together allowed me to kind of picture what [the lecturer] meant by personal space."

Robert

When prompted for more information on exactly how the VR content related to concepts of personal space, Robert touched upon the supplementary nature of VR to provide a concrete example of a theoretical concept presented in another medium (i.e., a journal article):

“When you’re reading a journal article about something like personal space for example, the VR helps you relate that information and immerse yourself in an actual example. It takes that written information and makes it real in a sense.”

Robert

Here the participant touches upon an interesting idea that has already been briefly mentioned in the systematic review in Study Chapter One and by psychology lecturers in Study Chapter Three. Namely, the idea of using VR as a technology for visualising or reinforcing abstract or theoretical ideas that are difficult to convey using traditional didactic methods of teaching. For instance, Robert derives relevance from the experience precisely because the VR video presented a concrete visual example of an intangible or abstract concept like physical space. This was evident from one of the entries in his reflective diary:

“The VR clips add a different level of course material interactions that I have not encountered before. It brings real world experiences relevant to the coursework and makes a change from extensive reading.”

Robert (excerpt from reflective diary – Week 4)

The same idea was succinctly expressed by Antonia when she remarked:

“I do think overall it (VR) helped kind of make sense of the more ‘out there’ theories. It made them seem a little more relevant, you know. It made it relatable to something that you could actually watch using the headset.”

Antonia

The ability of the VR experiences to provide concrete examples of theoretical ideas was cited as a motivator of engagement by multiple other participants. As Antonia put it, to

take an “out there” idea and then give students an immersive example of it was seen as a particular strongpoint of the technology. Further, students expressed that the tendency to link relevant theories to tangible experiences was a motivating factor when it came to continuing to engage with the VR material as they progressed through the module:

“I could see how the VR related to the module as a whole. So, the impact of green-spaces on mental wellbeing and so on. So, it wasn’t always like a direct you know – correlation, between what you were watching and that week’s lecture. But you could work out how the VR videos were supposed to relate to the stuff that you covered in the class. You maybe had to think about it a bit yourself, but you could always relate it back to something you learned previously. That’s what I liked about the clips to be honest.”

Evelyn

“I would do the 360° tours of some of the buildings or architectural spaces and things. So, sometimes I would be able to see certain elements in the buildings that were discussed in class. So, like how aesthetic it was, or the use of space and things like that. So, I do think it helps being able to relate that back to things in the lecture material. You kind of keep an eye out for certain things and then I thought to myself ‘oh, I remember that idea from a lecture or seminar’ or something like that. It wasn’t like it was spoon-fed if you get what I mean? You could use your own experience to relate back to the other stuff we used in the class.”

Antonia

As Hodgson et al. (2019) states, one of the most promising avenues of VR application is the ability to provide students a concrete or visual example of highly abstract theories or concepts. Indeed, this has been used as justification for the implementation of VR to teach complex and visual-dependent ideas as varied as spatial arrangements and theoretical engineering (Katsioloudis et al., 2017; Molina-Carmona et al., 2018). Keller (1987)

explicitly states that motivation and engagement can be garnered precisely by employing educational tools that can offer “concreteness” of theoretical concepts (p. 4).

Students made reference on numerous occasions to having to apply their own subjective understanding of how the VR material related to concepts taught in class. As one participant remarked, they were not “spoon-fed” or explicitly prompted to focus on a specific aspect of the VR experience. Rather, they had to actively “think about” how concepts or ideas presented in the clips related to the taught material that they had encountered as part of the module. Antonia makes mention of drawing upon her understanding of space and aesthetics when viewing a 360° video of a specific building. There is certainly a contrast in how students make sense of these experiences when the current study is compared to those videos used in Study Four. As already mentioned, the relevance of videos employed in Study Four were effectively unambiguous. For instance, a lecture describing a specific mental health condition and its associated symptoms was then supplemented by a VR clip that allowed participants to experience these symptoms through body-ownership. Students could subsequently build upon their understanding by integrating information learned through classroom activities with the relevant VR material. However, students in the current study seemed to conceptualise their experience differently. They were partly motivated by the VR because it necessitates a degree of lateral thinking and subjective association between previously learned content and the 360° experience. For instance, when viewing a VR experience of a train-station, the video did not explicitly prompt the viewer to concentrate on the fact it was busy or crowded. Rather, it was the responsibility of the student themselves to impress pedagogical meaning upon the experience by relating it to learned theories. The findings suggest that Place Illusion (PI) as described by Slater and colleagues (2009; 2022) is sufficient in facilitating an appreciation of the physical space – however, the meaning ascribed to such experience is not prescribed in the same way as previous studies. Unlike the preceding chapter (Study Four) with its focus on body-ownership (see, Slater et al., 2009; 2022), the current study utilised VR that did not incorporate visual or auditory cues suggestive of specific embodiment. Rather, learning was achieved through immersion in a physical environment related to taught material (e.g., a hospital, distillery, or university campus) as opposed to being “in the shoes” of a specific individual.

Students in the Environmental Psychology module derived motivation for asynchronous VR activities in part due to its relevance to taught content. In particular, students said that they enjoyed being able to draw associations between the theoretical ideas presented in class, and the concreteness of a visualised example presented in VR. It is important to emphasise that most students placed intrinsic value on the VR component because of its relevance to taught material. This conceptualisation of VR is of particular interest when it comes to the negative case (presented later), as it becomes clear that not all students attribute relevance in this way. Rather, one student in particular seems to conceptualise the relevance of an educational tool to its subsequent likelihood to be assessed in follow-up activities.

8.5.4 Limitations of Practical Application

One of the most intriguing findings of the current study concerns how students evaluate the applied usefulness of the asynchronous VR activities. In the previous study (Study Four), participants seemed to derive a great deal of motivation precisely because they stated the VR videos would be helpful in exams and assessments. For instance, several participants noted that the VR would have helped “flesh out” existing answers and responses as a result of undergoing the embodied VR experience. However, this was not the attitude of students in the current study. Participants were of the consensus that the VR activities conferred limited applied benefits and did not provide sufficient additional information to be helpful in assessed contexts. When asked about their perception and attitudes of VR’s applied utility in Environmental Psychology, responses were almost universally sceptical:

“(VR) wasn’t something I used to study as such. I wouldn’t sit and revise with the VR. I mean, you can’t reference a VR clip, you know. Yeah, it maybe gave me some insight or example into a certain topic, but I don’t know how I’d apply what I learned in that clip to an essay or something [...] As I said, I think the VR was just a little distraction – but a very relatable one. So, I am not trying to downplay it by saying that. It was very relatable. But as a stand-alone thing, I just don’t think you can learn much information from it.”

Robert

“I think – I’d say it’s more of a motivating thing rather than strictly learning. Because you are taking part in the VR and you are right in the middle of it, it encourages you to learn more about why this is important and pay attention. I’m not saying that the VR isn’t helpful. But I would say it’s more of a motivating thing to use rather than something I think I’d get lots of information from. It motivates you to pay attention to other things like the lectures or just the course in general [...] It is more of a motivation thing. I don’t see me studying or learning much new information from it. It’s not a direct thing if that makes sense. I don’t think I would be able to use some of that information in an exam setting. You can learn some things from it – you know, appreciate things. But I don’t know if that would necessarily translate into putting that down on an exam or something.”

Evelyn

“I don’t know how I would go about kind of demonstrating what I learned from those videos. The VR clips were not like journal articles or so on. It is not as if you can reference the information that you get from them. So, I don’t really know how I would be able to actually use that information in an applied context [...] As I said before I think that I did learn some new things from the VR clips, but I didn’t see any opportunity to actually apply that information in a classroom setting or in an exam or something like that.”

Antonia

As exemplified by the participant responses, students were adamant that the asynchronous VR activities were of limited applied use in terms of helping with exam or essay answers. As a follow-up, participants were also asked whether they thought the VR would have been helpful as a revision tool by allowing students to revisit previously

covered material. Again, the general consensus was that students did not envisage VR as being helpful in this scenario:

"I wouldn't say that I would have used the VR headset for revision and things like that. I don't really know if it would have been useful or kind of suitable for doing revision for exams. I am not sure that it would have been helpful or so on - as I said I think that the VR clips were more about being engaged and motivated during the module and getting to experience things in a slightly different way."

Antonia

By examining students' attitudes towards the applied utility of asynchronous VR activities in the Environmental Psychology module, two observations come to the fore. The first of these concerns the dichotomy between attitudes in the current study, and Study Four. What is it about the VR experiences in Study Four that give them a perceived applied value, whilst those in the current study do not seem to confer the same advantage? Secondly, research has intimated the importance of educational tools to confer an applied benefit in order to generate motivation and engagement (e.g., Di Serio et al., 2013; Keller, 2010; Khan et al., 2019). However, students in the current study exhibited a high degree of motivation to interact and engage with the VR content *despite* them acknowledging that it was of little applied benefit. Simply put, students continued to interact with the asynchronous VR content even though they stated that it was of limited benefit for exams and assessments.

The first set of attitudes to address are those concerned with students' perceptions of VR's applied utility. Although participants stated that they enjoyed interacting with the content, they also noted that they did not think that it would confer an applied benefit in their scholastic activities. These attitudes generally challenge those presented elsewhere in this thesis and in previous literature. For instance, whether you examine the attitudes of instructors and teachers (e.g., Langhout, 2019; Serin, 2020) or students and learners (e.g., Depape & Barnes, 2019; Shu et al., 2018) – the general perception is that VR integration can lead to better understanding and learning outcomes. Even within this

thesis, students in Study Chapter Four remarked that mental health VR experiences would have assisted them in answering essay and exam questions. However, that was not the attitude encountered in the current study.

There are several possible explanations for this occurrence. Firstly, the content of the VR experience might have simply reinforced certain theories or ideas, but not necessarily added to them. As several participants remarked, the VR videos were “relatable” or “relevant,” but not necessarily something that they would gain new information from. This was in contrast to the previous study chapter (Chapter Four) where participants remarked that the VR afforded them novel insights into mental health conditions. These attitudes seem consistent with some of the qualitative data gathered by DePape et al. (2020) in response to a psychology VR experience. In that study, one of the participants remarked that the experience was not educationally valuable precisely because they already knew most of the information from other sources. Therefore, it could be that applied value is predicated on the idea that VR must provide a degree of novel insight unobtainable by other means. As VR did not facilitate this in the current study, students failed to see practical applications for its use.

This is related to a second point. It could be that the nature of the VR videos themselves were not conducive to applied or novel learning. VR content in the current study tended to be *disembodied* as opposed to experiential. That is to say, students did not embody the lived experience of a specific individual (unlike Study Four). Rather, they were simply placed in an environment (e.g., a nature walk) and expected to impart their own meaning and relevancy on the content. This brings us to the final explanation. It could be that the VR content was not scaffolded appropriately when integrated into the module. As Keller (1987) states, it should be explicitly stated how the use of a pedagogical tool will benefit the students who use it. However, as VR was integrated as an asynchronous method of learning, there was little accompanying information regarding exactly how each video related to a core module component. Therefore, students had little guidance of what precisely to look out for when watching each of the videos.

8.5.5 The Negative Case

The following section details the negative case analysis. Specifically, it focuses on Lesley, a 25-year-old female whose attitudes diverged from that of the other participants in the study. She exhibited low levels of interaction with the VR material, as well as expressing a general sense of dissatisfaction and demotivation with the technology. As Wicks (2010) states, a negative case analysis ensures that *all* data are accounted for, even if it runs contrary to the general pattern. As a result, divergent findings can either be reconciled with existing theories or ideas by presenting a more nuanced form of analysis; or new avenues may be need to be explored to explain anomalous results (Athens, 2015; Mays, 2000). Using existing themes from typical cases, the following section details how the conceptualisation of VR differs between the negative and typical cases.

8.5.5.1 Relevance Through Assessment

As discussed in Section 8.5.3., students generally derived relevance through VR's relationship with taught material. By providing a concrete example of a theoretical concept, students understood how the asynchronous VR activities related to the core module content. However, this is not how the negative case appeared to conceptualise VR's place within the module (or indeed any form of asynchronous content). Rather, Lesley's understanding of relevance was tied more closely to its ability to be assessed as part of the module's learning outcomes. As Lesley knew that the VR content was not going to form part of an assessment or follow-up activity, she remarked that she was not motivated to interact with it. Lesley compared VR to the mandatory class activities to illustrate this point:

"I think for me whenever I am doing any sort of learning then I have constantly got to be thinking about what the point of that activity actually is. And for the VR clips I just didn't really understand what the end goal actually was [...] For example the weekly activities had an end goal in mind. So, we knew that they would be discussed or presented at the weekly seminars. That meant that it was integrated with that kind of purpose in mind."

Lesley

Lesley brings up the idea that pedagogical activities must be integrated with a “purpose in mind.” This is consistent with Picciano's (2009) idea that educational tools must be applied with a clear, predefined goal as the end objective. However, Lesley appeared to conceptualise the idea of *purpose* differently from how it was integrated into the module. Whereas typical cases seemed to understand *purpose* as being related to reinforcing theories and principles learned in class, Lesley derived purpose from the perspective of assessment preparation. As the VR content did not form part of the assessment criteria of the module, she did not feel as if it had a predefined purpose. As Lesley remarked:

“My biggest motivator for reading the journal articles was knowing that it was going to help during the essays and exams. I actually found that out quite early on that it was going to be a big part of preparing and learning for the assessments. So, I think that was my biggest motivator. The end goal was the exam or the assessments. So even though the VR might have been more fun than the journal articles, I used it less just because I knew it wasn’t going to play a big part of the assessment stuff.”

Lesley

It is interesting to note that the negative case did not dismiss the VR activities as being unenjoyable. That is not the reason that they were reluctant to interact with it. Rather, they placed greatest emphasis on the material that would help them fulfil the module’s core assessment criteria. Conversely, the typical cases focused less on this component, and derived motivation and satisfaction through its relevance to taught content, and ability to “break up” the online-centric nature of module. Numerous researchers have stated that VR must be integrated with a clear, predefined purpose in mind (e.g., Fransson et al., 2020; Southgate & Smith, 2017). However, this may neglect to address the idiosyncrasies in how individual students define “purpose.” In the specific instance of the negative case, this *purpose* is almost wholly attributed to the likelihood of VR to be assessed, or to help with module assignments.

This poses a simple question: how can VR be integrated to motivate those who place the greatest emphasis on assessment? As part of the interview, Lesley was explicitly asked what would have motivated her to interact with the VR material more fully. She responded that the expectation of VR forming part of a follow-up activity would have been essential:

“But it kind of seemed – I don’t want to say ‘pointless.’ But because there wasn’t a task as such to go with it, I didn’t think it was worth spending a lot of time on. But maybe if there was something that sort of accompanied the VR clips then I would have been more kind of motivated to interact with it.”

Lesley

When prompted to give specific examples of what kind of follow-up activities would have motivated her to interact with the VR, she responded:

“I think maybe a questionnaire or even like a group-discussion or something. As long as there is something that sort of gives it a purpose, I think I would have liked it a lot better.”

Lesley

As evidenced by the attitudes of the typical cases, a follow-up activity or applied application is not a prerequisite for engagement with VR. However, the negative case has demonstrated that satisfaction or content relevancy alone may not be sufficient to encourage all students to engage with VR. For the negative case specifically, relevancy is placed upon VR’s relationship with assessment as opposed to its relationship with taught content. These findings should be considered in light of the existing theoretical framework provided by ARCS (see, Keller, 1987, 2010). This study extends beyond merely conceptualising pedagogical relevancy as a product of knowledge acquisition and attainment. Instead, it highlights that relevancy is also derived from students’ anticipation of formal and informal assessments. This dual perspective of relevancy

encompasses the content taught and integrates the expectations set for evaluation. The use of a follow-up activity such as a group discussion has already been proposed as a means of motivating and engaging students in this thesis. For example, in Study Three, psychology lecturers remarked that a classroom discussion or collaborative activity would foster a more active approach to VR learning. As previous research has already recognised the benefits of peer-learning and discussion (e.g., Laal & Ghodsi, 2012; Panitz, 1999), this may be an effective way of motivating those more reluctant to engage with VR. If educators seek to encourage VR participation among *all* students, then this negative case analysis has reiterated the need for fully integrated follow-up activities. Although the absence of this will not dissuade all students from engaging with VR (as evidenced by the typical cases), it will be enough to discourage some students who place a primary relevance on an activity's link to assessed material.

8.5.5.2 Study Strategy and Time Management

During the course of the interview, it became clear that idiosyncrasies in how the negative case managed her academic load and time constraints also influenced her decision not to interact with the VR content.

When Lesley remarked that she did not feel motivated to engage with the VR content, the interviewer wanted to get a more detailed understanding of how she typically interacted with asynchronous learning activities. What became clear is that the negative case was very deliberate in how she structured her study time. She cited that she gave priority to tasks that she deemed to be most important; often those ones that had a direct relevance to future assessed material or the acquiring of new information. As Lesley remarked:

"It's about how I kind of prioritise my time and resources and so on. If I had to explain it, I'd say it's about being strategic about what you look at and study. I don't see the point in wasting lots of time on something that doesn't really add much to the whole learning experience."

Lesley

As a follow-up, Lesley was then asked what she thought constitutes an effective use of time in an academic sense. The purpose of this question was to understand how the participant assigned priority to tasks that need to be completed, and how VR might fit into this overall picture:

"I think it's all about that end goal again. The final exam. I like to be strategic about how and what I study and revise. So, things that have a goal or an end point will always take priority."

Lesley

Again, Lesley expressed that the most efficient use of her time is on tasks that have a follow-up activity or relate to assessed material. To spend time interacting with content that did not ultimately contribute to these end goals was deemed to be ineffectual and counterproductive. The participant remarked that due to other academic and work commitments, she were forced to devise a stringent study schedule and strategy that left little time for interacting with non-essential material:

"I mean I'm really quite busy. I have a part-time job and other modules and a dissertation and so on that all need done. So, I do think you have to be kind of tactical about how you study and spend your time."

Lesley

Obviously, not all students will have the same time constraints placed upon them. For instance, many students do not have part-time jobs, or may be taking modules that have a less intensive workload. However, Lesley did note that her fourth-year dissertation was of primary focus and occupied a large amount of their available time. It therefore stands to reason that specific year groups or cohorts may have more difficulty finding time to interact with asynchronous VR content than others (especially if this is optional or does not contribute to assessed material). As a result, integrating VR into earlier year groups where the workload is less intense may afford them more time to engage with the

activities. Ultimately, if VR does not provide tangible benefits in terms of academic achievement or follow-up, some students will deem it a low priority and fail to engage. Conversely, if VR is integrated as a core assessed component (especially in later year modules), the additional workload might put pressure on students who are already stretched. The current study therefore lends credence to the ideas promulgated by Southgate and Smith (2017) in that the appropriate and considered *integration* of VR is of utmost importance. If asynchronous VR is integrated as a supplementary optional, some students are inevitably not going to engage due to time constraints or differences in how they assess priority. On the other hand, if it is decided that VR will be integrated alongside follow-up activities, consideration must be given to whether this will contribute to an additional workload that would be deemed unreasonable.

8.5.5.3 VR Scaffolding and Integration

The final reason for the participant's general disinterest in the asynchronous VR content relates to how the material was integrated and promoted within the module. The negative case conveyed the attitude that the integration method was not conducive to grabbing and sustaining interest in the activities over the course of the curriculum. Specifically, Lesley noted that lack of accompanying information or an explicit statement of how each VR video related to taught material demotivated her in terms of engagement:

“When the links for the VR videos were posted online, there was no other information to go along with it. So, I didn't really know what the point of the video was because there were no real instructions about what the purpose of it was [...] I just think that it needs to be actually integrated into the module better. So, you need to constantly be aware of what the purpose is.”

Lesley

The general attitude is related to two important concepts in pedagogical motivation. Namely that of attention and relevancy (Keller, 1987, 2010). During the Environmental Psychology module, links to the VR clips were uploaded to the VLE at predefined intervals. Other than the title of the video and a very brief description, there was little information

as to its content or relationship to specific theories or concepts. Indeed, this is how many of the other asynchronous activities (e.g., journal articles, 2D videos) were presented to students. However, in the example of the negative case, the lack of an explicit statement of relevancy ultimately failed to grab their attention. She implied that the crucial period to engage them with the VR content was right at the very start of the module. She stated that their biggest issue regarding VR integration was that its purpose was not made explicitly clear from the beginning:

“See, I am not necessarily against VR or using technology per se. But the way it was kind of introduced in this module meant that I just didn't see the purpose. Other than getting the headsets in the first week or so, I just didn't get what the aim of it was. It wasn't made clear to me.”

Lesley

To follow-up on this interesting point, the interviewer asked her whether a more explicit introduction to how VR was going to be used would have changed her attitude. Lesley responded:

“Yeah, definitely. It would have shifted my focus so I could spend more time on the material if I was told that it was important. But I think that would have had to be made clear right back at the very start of the module. It is quite difficult to get engaged with it if you haven't been using it from the start. So, after I hadn't been using it for a month or so I just didn't go back to the VR stuff. Other stuff just tends to get in the way, and it fell by the wayside.”

Lesley

Lesley again expresses the idea of a crucial time-period to encourage engagement with the VR component. If the instructor is unable to adequately convince the student of its importance or intrinsic value right from the very start, it is difficult to pick it up again later in the module. As Lesley put it, if engagement with VR is not achieved early on, then

it falls “by the wayside.” Again, it is important to stress that this was not the general consensus. The typical cases were exposed to the VR activities in the same manner as the negative one, yet they *were* motivated to engage. However, what the negative case does demonstrate is that if VR is to appeal to *all* students, then increased scaffolding and an explicit statement of its benefits is needed from the start. The negative case has consistently and frequently ascribed “purpose” as being the driving force behind her decision to engage with academic material. Further, she also expressed the need for this purpose to be explicitly stated from the outset. Although increased scaffolding is unlikely to affect those students who are already motivated to engage with VR, it might help those who are more reluctant.

From an applied perspective, lecturers and academic specialists (e.g., Learning Technologist) could provide a short session during the introductory lecture discussing how VR will be applied during the module. This would give students the opportunity to ask questions and get familiar with how the technology fits the specific learning outcomes. In addition, a detailed overview of precisely how each VR experience relates to specific theories could prime students to derive meaning from the activity. This could be as simple as providing students with a few specific aspects to look out for as they view the VR content. If instructors or module coordinators choose to integrate VR, it is ultimately their responsibility to convince students of its purpose. From analysing the negative case, it is clear that this purpose must be explicitly stated at the earliest opportunity to grab and then maintain engagement and motivation.

8.6 Discussion and Conclusion

The current study investigated student attitudes as they pertain to using VR as an asynchronous learning activity. By fully integrating VR into a fourth year Environmental Psychology module, the study was able to examine how VR would be received in a natural pedagogical setting. A range of data collection techniques and analyses were used to understand how students perceived using VR to reinforce and exemplify a range of abstract or conceptual theories. By conducting thematic analysis on participants’ reflective diary entries as well as a series of semi-structured interviews, four themes were

formulated that best captured how VR was perceived; (a) breaking up the learning process; (b) holistic motivation; (c) relationship to module content; and (d) limitations of practical application. In addition, one participant (Lesley) exhibited attitudes that ran contrary to those of most other students included in this study and in the thesis in general. It was therefore deemed prudent to conduct a negative case analysis to further explore how this participant's attitudes were shaped, and to see if these could be reconciled with the typical cases. This negative case analysis explored three pertinent themes that best captured the dichotomy between them and the typical participants: (e) relevance through assessment; (f) study strategy and time management; and (g) scaffolding and integration.

Unlike the previous study (Study Four), the VR activities were fully integrated into the Environmental Psychology module. As a consequence, student attitudes could be examined across a greater period of time as opposed to an isolated intervention at the end of a module. One of the most prevalent attitudes espoused by students was the idea that the use of VR helped "break up" the module, providing a degree of novelty that they had not encountered before in online learning activities. As a wealth of literature has concluded, keeping students motivated with academic material is one of the most prominent barriers facing educators as they wrestle with the challenges of online-centric education (Chiu et al., 2021; Ferri et al., 2020; García-Morales et al., 2021). However, as Keller (1987; 2010) has proposed, utilising a degree of variability in teaching methods can help alleviate some of the issues around lack of motivation. Further, Rahiem (2021) specifically cited the use of technology such as VR as being particularly effective in generating engagement and motivation with scholastic activities. As a result, VR in this instance should not be viewed as merely a "gimmick" as many researchers have previously worried (e.g., Cooper & Thong, 2018; Johnson, 2018; Lee & Shea, 2020). Rather, the ability of VR to "break up" some of the repetition associated with distance learning kept students engaged with other facets of the module. Indeed, not only did students convey the attitude that VR helped them stay motivated with module content, but it also positively influenced their perception of the Environmental Psychology curriculum itself. By fully integrating VR within the module, the current study makes a novel contribution by assessing the effect that the technology can have on students' overall perception of the class. As already mentioned, previous studies have tended to

examine levels of motivation with a single, isolated VR intervention (e.g., Parong & Mayer, 2018). However, the findings of the current study highlight the positive influence that VR can have on student attitudes towards the whole experience. Therefore, the introduction of immersive technology should not be seen as a standalone or self-contained method of education. Rather, when integrated properly, it can play a positive role in how students perceive and interact with all synchronous and asynchronous educational activities.

Of particular interest was how students made sense of the relationship between VR content and learning outcomes. For most students, they derived relevance from the VR content through its ability to provide concrete and visual examples of theoretical concepts and ideas. Indeed, this “concreteness” as Keller (1987) puts it has already been cited as one of the most intriguing avenues for VR application (Hodgson et al., 2019). For example, students mentioned that the ability to take an abstract idea like “personal space” or “territoriality” and then see how this translates to a real-world scenario (e.g., in a crowded train station) was particularly thought-provoking. In addition, despite limited guidance on how the VR experiences explicitly related to taught material, students mentioned that they enjoyed using their own powers of discernment to link concepts and ideas together. However, this attitude was not universal. Unlike the typical participants, the negative case derived meaning not from VR’s relevance to taught material, but rather its relationship to assessment. As the asynchronous VR content did not have a follow-up activity, nor did it form part of the core module outcomes, the negative case saw little benefit of interacting with it. As a result, they regarded it as low priority, choosing to engage with those tasks and activities that had a more direct relationship with assessed content. No other study has implemented a negative case analysis to examine a student’s perception of using VR in education. By doing so, the current study has uncovered conceptual differences in how individual students define relevance in their teaching methods. Generally, students understood relevance as the relationship between the VR content, and its ability to provide a specific example of a theory or idea learned in class. However, the negative case conceptualised relevance primarily as a pedagogical method’s relationship to assessed learning outcomes. Therefore, if VR lacks a follow-up opportunity to express learning, then some students will be completely demotivated to interact with it.

One of the most intriguing findings from the current study concerns students' attitudes towards VR's applied pedagogical benefits. In the previous study, students remarked that VR would have conferred practical advantages to their academic coursework, such as helping to expand essay or exam answers. However, all participants in the current study (typical *and* negative cases) expressed scepticism as to whether VR would have had any tangible benefit that could be exhibited in assessed learning activities. Simply put, there is a marked difference between how students evaluate the practical application of VR in the previous study (Study Four – Psychology of Mental Health), and the current one. This poses a fundamental question; why? One explanation concerns the amount of novel information that VR can impart in the Environmental Psychology module. Participants remarked that they did not learn anything new from the experience. Rather, it could be the case that the VR content simply illustrated or reinforced content that the student was already aware of. Unlike Study Four, the lack of novel insight could have led to students forming the attitude that the VR was of little practical benefit to their scholastic activities. As exemplified by DePape et al. (2020), if students believe they have already acquired the requisite knowledge through traditional sources (e.g., lectures, seminars, journal articles), then a series of VR activities might be viewed as of little applied value. However, this is not necessarily an argument in favour of negating VR when its practical applications are limited. Clearly most participants derived motivation, engagement, and enjoyment from the experience *despite* mentioning that it was of limited use in exams or essays. Therefore, as suggested by Southgate and Smith (2017), a more measured appraisal of VR's specific purpose is needed prior to integration. If VR's role is primarily to motivate or engage students with module content, then it does not necessarily need to provide a wealth of practical or applied applications. However, if VR is conceptualised as a tool to impart knowledge, then it must provide novel information that can then be demonstrated in follow-up activities such as exams and assessments. Clearly, unlike Study Four, students were not convinced that the VR activities significantly contributed to novel insights into the topics conveyed in the Environmental Psychology module. This poses another important question; why?

When comparing the attributes of the VR content used in the current study to that of Study Four, one contrasting property stands out. Namely, the reduced emphasis on *body-ownership* of a specific virtual avatar (see, Slater, 2009; Slater et al., 2009, 2022). In Study Four, participants embodied the lived perspective of a specific person, and experienced their socio-cognitive reality through visual and auditory cues. This provided a degree of novel insight that would otherwise have been inaccessible through conventional means of education. Nevertheless, the present study signifies a change in emphasis by prioritising the concept of Place Illusion (PI) rather than embodiment and socio-cognitive assimilation. This change in approach is the consequence of divergent learning objectives across psychological domains. Many of the theoretical ideas espoused in Environmental Psychology do not necessitate the embodiment of a specific virtual avatar to appreciate (i.e., there was no need to understand symptomology or clinical presentations). Instead, the focus was on using VR to foster a strong sense of PI and appreciation of the environment, aiming to elucidate abstract and conceptual ideas related to human interaction with physical space. The VR experiences in this context are used to supplement traditional teaching materials by providing immersive experiences that highlight concepts such as territoriality, and evaluations of privacy without needing users to identify with a specific virtual avatar. For instance, during Week 7, the academic appreciation and evaluation of architectural spaces could be accomplished by creating the impression that one is inhabiting a particular location (e.g., a university building), rather than embodying a specific person (e.g., body-ownership over someone having a panic attack).

8.6.1 Limitations

Although the entire class (six enrolled students) would have been within the sample size recommendations for conducting thematic analysis (see, Fugard & Potts, 2015), only four students participated in the study itself. Unfortunately, when integrating an intervention within a predefined module, there will always be constraints placed on the level of participation and engagement. Indeed, throughout their work, Braun and Clarke (2020, 2021b, 2021c) have emphasised the role that “pragmatism” plays in the overall recruitment process. They recognise that sample size is just one of a multitude of different factors that impact the quality and applicability of research. Therefore, a holistic view of the research in terms of its integration and richness of data collection is necessary for a

thorough evaluation of its contribution. Further, the in-depth description of the methods and analysis process presents an opportunity for a thorough evaluation of the transferability of its findings.

A second consideration is having access to additional sources of data. Although the current study did employ “method triangulation” (Carter et al., 2014; Patton, 1999) by using interviews and reflective diaries, there was scope to integrate additional measures that would have provided increased data convergence. For example, by obtaining additional ethical permission, end-of-module evaluations or student assessment results could have been obtained. This would have added an additional layer of analysis by providing additional sources of information not contained within the interviews or diaries.

8.6.2 Conclusion

In this chapter, VR was fully integrated as an asynchronous learning activity in a fourth-year Environmental Psychology module. Using a variety of data collection methods such as reflective diaries and semi-structured interviews, the study examined how students conceptualised VR’s place within an online teaching environment. Typically, students remarked that VR helped “break up” the monotony of repetitive online activities and kept them engaged with other facets of the module. Far from merely providing an engaging distraction from online activities, students also enjoyed the relevancy of VR content in reinforcing ideas and theories learned in class. For instance, students remarked that VR helped illustrate conceptual ideas by providing a concrete example of them. Despite this, students were unanimous that the asynchronous VR activities would provide limited applied benefits in terms of helping answer exam or essay questions. Although students said that VR could provide a degree of “insight” into a given topic, they were less sure of how they could directly apply this to their assessed learning. As aforementioned, generally students were motivated to engage with the VR content despite its limited practical utility. However, a single participant (the negative case) expressed a lack of interest or incentive to engage with the technology. Specifically, they remarked that a lack of follow-up activity or practical benefit meant that they saw little point of interacting with VR. They went on to explain that their individual study strategy and external

circumstances meant that they viewed VR as a low priority when compared to other activities that directly impacted assessed learning outcomes.

9 STUDY SIX – DIFFERENCES IN LEARNING OUTCOMES AND ATTITUDES IN EXPERIENTIAL AND NON-EXPERIENTIAL VR

9.1 Chapter Overview

In the previous two chapters, student attitudes as they pertain to VR use in psychological education have been investigated. In Study Four, students responded positively to using VR as a means of learning mental health concepts through experiential learning. They remarked that they would likely be able to demonstrate increased understanding in essays and examinations because of the VR intervention. However, students in the proceeding study (Study Five) were more sceptical of VR's applied application, citing that the technology fulfilled a primarily motivational purpose as opposed to a scholastic one. What are the fundamental differences in the two sets of VR experiences that could explain this discrepancy? And, does a sufficient explanation of these differences have practical ramifications for how VR should be designed and applied in practice.

The following chapter describes a within-subjects mixed-methods study that exposed psychology students to two types of VR experience on the subject of mental health: (a) an embodied/experiential condition (Experiential VR); and (b) a didactic non-experiential condition (VR Lecture). The experiment was interested in examining learning outcomes, motivational attitudes, and degree of empathetic response in both conditions.

9.2 Study Background

As alluded to in the preceding section, there appears to be a discrepant attitude between those participants in Study Four and Study Five. To briefly reiterate, participants in Study Four (Psychology of Mental Health) conceived an academic benefit to VR integration, whilst those in Study Five (Environmental Psychology) were more sceptical of its scholastic value. A potential reason for this may reside in the nature of the VR experiences

themselves. In Study Four, strong emphasis was placed on VR clips that allowed the participant to embody the lived experience of another person. The immersive nature of this first-hand perspective granted viewers a unique insight into the symptomology of various mental health conditions (e.g., visual disturbances, auditory hallucinations, thought processes). As has already been discussed in Section 2.2.2., this illusion of body-ownership can help facilitate a profound sense of embodiment, allowing for transformative psychological and behavioural responses, even when the avatar significantly differs from the user's cognitive profile (Banakou et al., 2016; Osimo et al., 2015). In turn, students responded by stating that this novel method of VR presentation allowed them to gain a deeper understanding of various conditions, and this would ultimately be conducive to applied learning. Not only did these experiences facilitate body-ownership, but they were also designed and edited with visual and auditory effects to simulate a *specific* person, experiencing a *specific* set of symptoms, in a *specific* context. Consistent with previous studies (see, Banakou et al., 2016; Bedder et al., 2019), this may allow students to assimilate the virtual experience with their own socio-cognitive perspectives, facilitating a more nuanced understanding of the phenomenon.

On the other hand, many of the topics covered in Study Five placed less emphasis on the embodiment of a virtual avatar. Rather, information tended to be presented in a more conceptual manner, perhaps stunting the level of emotional engagement seen in previous studies. For example, the appreciation of architectural spaces and design were conveyed without body-ownership of a virtual avatar (see, Slater et al., 2022). Therefore, understanding was achieved through environmental and spatial perception, leading to an experience that is less about physical representation and more about cognitive engagement. Although students may have felt present within the virtual environment, this was often done without direct body-ownership or the embodiment of a protagonist (see, Pan & Hamilton, 2018; Slater, 2018; Wilkinson et al., 2021). Even when the VR experiences were filmed from a point-of-view (POV) perspective (e.g., Koyoyo Train Station or Great Ormond Street Hospital tour), there was far less emphasis placed upon the illusion of specific body-ownership. For instance, unlike those VR experiences presented in Study Four, no visual or auditory cues conveyed how the embodied individual (or lack of) was physically and emotionally reacting in that situation. For

instance, the experience of Chandni Market was used to illustrate a lack of personal space and territoriality in urban settings. However, no editing techniques were incorporated that would suggest the viewer was embodying a particular individual. No heavy breathing or darting gazes would suggest that the experience was designed to elicit a predefined reaction or response congruent with a lack of personal space (unlike Study Four). This lack of specific body-ownership may fail to elicit the same level of emotional assimilation as those used in previous chapters (i.e., the body-ownership associated with being a young girl with autism at a party). Consequently, could the far more *experiential* VR with its illusion of body-ownership and embodiment be the driving force behind its perceived scholastic value?

9.2.1 Aims and Objectives

Building upon the discussion concluded in the preceding section, the observed divergence in perceptions of VR's educational efficacy between Study Four and Study Five may stem from the distinct nature of the VR experiences themselves. To explore this theory, this study aims to compare learning outcomes and attitudes between two distinct VR delivery approaches. Specifically, a set of three didactic VR lectures were created to impart the same knowledge as a trio of experiential VR clips, each focusing on different mental health issues. Should the experiential and embodied nature of VR enhance learning and perspective-taking, we anticipate identifying a marked improvement in these areas when compared to the outcomes from the more passive, didactic VR lectures.

The second aim of the study relates to an argument first raised in Study One. Namely, MCQs are not an appropriate means of evaluating VR's effectiveness as a pedagogical tool. Researchers have previously raised concerns surrounding the use of MCQs to assess relatively short or isolated educational interventions (see, Excell, 2000). The reason for this is that MCQs should generally only be employed when the objective is to assess a large amount of surface knowledge over the course of an entire curriculum. Consequently, the current study sought to examine whether more nuanced forms of assessment can detect subtle changes in understanding and knowledge acquisition that MCQs cannot. To examine this proposition, both an MCQ and extended-answer questionnaire (EAQ) were utilised to gather learning outcomes both pre- and post-intervention. EAQs have been recommended as being a more appropriate measure of

deeper and more complex learning (Parmenter, 2009). The current study will investigate the conceptual differences between MCQs and EAQs by assessing their ability to demonstrate understanding and knowledge after each VR intervention. In addition, interviewed participants were explicitly asked about their approach to answering both types of assessment as a way of identifying conceptual differences between each method.

Examining the studies that have been presented in this thesis so far provides a justification as to why the current study is necessary. Namely, the systematic review and qualitative studies of both educators and students have demonstrated an effectiveness and desire to use VR in the classroom. Therefore, the question of “if” VR should be used should have been dispelled. There are clearly pedagogical benefits to students (both in terms of learning outcomes and affective appraisal); and educators have displayed a willingness to implement given the right conditions. Consequently, experimental research must move beyond the rudimentary media-comparison approach (the proverbial “if” question) and engage with the more pertinent “how” question. The current study takes this approach by examining two competing modes of VR presentation: experiential and non-experiential (didactic). In doing so, this study dispenses with the common trope of comparing *across* media types (e.g., VR versus 2D video), and promoting research that examines effectiveness *within* the same overarching medium (i.e., VR). Consequently, this study will inform the types of VR experiences that educators should implement in their classroom when teaching mental health principles to students.

9.2.2 Conceptually Defining Experiential and Non-Experiential VR

The current study is predicated upon clearly understanding the distinction between “experiential” and “non-experiential” VR. Indeed, a clear and coherent conceptual definition of these two terms is imperative in anchoring the study in the foundational concepts introduced in the initial chapters of this thesis (see, Section 2.2). It is essential to establish, with clarity, that these two modes of VR presentation represent unique and separate experiences within the domain of VR.

Congruent with the VR materials used in Study Four, experiential VR is characterised by a profound sense of personal ownership over a virtual avatar *and* their perceptual

experiences. This mode of presentation is theoretically anchored in concepts like embodiment and body-ownership as described by Slater et al. (2022) and Blanke et al. (2015). Again, this suggests that such VR experiences instigate a transformative shift in bodily self-awareness, thereby influencing socio-cognitive processes through the assimilation of the avatar's perceptual processes with the self. An example of this is the immersive experience of embodying a 16-year-old girl named Layla, who has autism and is attending a family gathering (see, Guardian, 2017). This VR experience imparts an unmistakable sense of specificity and contextuality, facilitated by auditory and visual cues (e.g., blurred vision, visual disturbances, amplified background noise) that offer the user a nuanced understanding of the avatar's physiological and perceptual state. This type of VR engagement captures the essence of Slater et al.'s (2022) illusory concepts like *place*, *plausibility*, and particularly, *body-ownership*. Through the simulation of specific symptoms associated with the condition, the VR experience produces a compelling sense of embodiment. Consequently, the viewer experiences a transient, yet profound insight into the lived experience of a specific individual, transcending mere cognitive understanding facilitated through didactic means of teaching.

Conversely, the bespoke *non-experiential* VR clips markedly de-emphasise the simulation of distinct embodiment and the provision of multisensory cues. Instead, these clips allow the viewer to engage with content at a cognitive level, devoid of the sensory information associated with body-ownership. Information, particularly relating to mental health symptomatology, is conveyed in a didactic and theoretical manner (via a lecturer), lacking the direct experiential component facilitated by virtual avatar ownership. This form of VR primarily leverages Place Illusion (PI), producing a sense of presence within a lecture or classroom setting (refer to Section 2.2.1.2). However, it falls short in replicating the nuances of body ownership and Plausibility (Psi) that are crucial for an immersive experience of mental health symptoms. Users remain detached observers, acquiring knowledge on symptoms through a purely didactic approach, devoid of the visual or auditory stimuli that might otherwise suggest the embodiment of a specific virtual character. The absence of body ownership precludes users from adopting the physical sensations characteristic of individuals experiencing mental health symptoms,

emphasising a significant dichotomy between “experiential” and “non-experiential” delivery methods.

9.3 Methods

In Study One, and in its associated publication (i.e., Hamilton et al., 2021b), several criticisms were raised of previous VR research. The most pronounced issue centred on that of the assessment instrumentation used to assess learning outcomes. In particular, the over-reliance on multiple-choice-questionnaires and the generally poor description of their reliability and validation were of particular concern. The current study has addressed these most pertinent factors by explicitly stating how these concerns have been addressed.

9.3.1 Study Design

A within-subjects mixed-methods design was employed in this study. Participants were randomly assigned to either treatment group A or B, which dictated the order in which they received the VR video clips.

9.3.2 Participants

Several issues arose whilst recruiting for this study. Despite strong initial interest, there was a substantial drop-out rate at various intervals throughout the process. Initially, 41 prospective participants completed either the initial pre-intervention questionnaire, or the first post-intervention questionnaire. By the end of data collection, 28 participants had completed all mandatory aspects of the study (dropout rate of >30%). Three follow-up reminders were sent to registered participants, as well as a final invitation to those who had expressed interest. The reason for this dropout rate is likely multifactorial. Despite remuneration, the commitment and participation time was lengthy (~2.5hrs) and had to be completed over the course of several days. In addition, the current study took place during a period of lockdown where learning and teaching was taking place exclusively online. As a result, students might have had little interest or motivation for taking part in yet another form of online activity. Indeed, researchers have identified this phenomenon as a form of “technological fatigue” (see, Bullock et al., 2022; Fauville et al., 2021).

In total, 28 participants completed the study (7 males; 21 females) with an average age of 28 years old ($SD = 10$; Range 18 – 54). Of those participants, 10 (35.7%) stated that they had previous experience with VR technology in either an educational or entertainment capacity. Those participants with previous experience were asked to rate their perceived degree of familiarity with VR on a ten-point Likert scale. The average familiarity score was 3.8 ($SD = 1.9$).

Of the 28 participants who partook in the study, a subset of eight people (1 male; 7 females) also completed a semi-structured interview at conclusion of the study. The average age of these eight participants was 32 years old ($SD = 13.6$; Range 20 - 54). Of those interviewed, two participants stated they had previous VR experience, and six did not.

All participants were undergraduate psychology students at the University of the West of Scotland. As a prerequisite, participants *must not* have previously been enrolled on the Psychology of Mental Health module – thus ensuring that base knowledge was similar. In addition, a history of severe anxiety or any other condition that may have been exacerbated by the VR footage also precluded participation. A process of volunteer sampling was performed to recruit participants to the study. Online notices were placed on the Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) as well as official social media channels. In addition, a 360° promotional video was created that was then posted to the university's official Twitter and Facebook page. This helped garner additional interest in the study. Remuneration in the form of a £20 Amazon Voucher was given to participants who took part in the initial stage of the study. An additional £5 voucher was given to those participants who volunteered to take part in the online interview at the conclusion of the experiment.

9.3.3 Virtual Reality Stimuli

The present study aimed to assess learning outcomes and subjective appraisal of two forms of VR mental health education (experiential vs non-experimental VR). There were three specific mental health topics chosen: (a) Schizophrenia; (b) Anxiety Disorders; and

(c) Autism Spectrum Disorders. These three conditions are covered extensively in the Psychology of Mental Health (Bachelor of Science) module, meaning the material covered mirrored the real curriculum. A pre-existing experiential VR clip was chosen for each of the three mental health topics. In addition to pre-existing experiential clips, three bespoke VR clips were also created for each of the mental health conditions. A detailed description of how these clips were created and evaluated can be found in Section 9.3.3.2. Links to the VR videos can be found in Digital Appendix 9.1.

9.3.3.1 Experiential VR Clips

Three pre-existing Experiential VR Clips were chosen that each represented a separate mental health condition: (a) schizophrenia; (b) anxiety disorder; and (c) autism spectrum disorders. To be considered “*experiential*,” the VR clip had to allow the viewer to embody the perspective of another and see the world as they see it. Therefore, each of the three clips featured a first-hand, point-of-view perspective where the viewer *was* the person suffering from the condition. For example, during the autism experience, the viewer embodied the perspective of a young girl called Layla during a family party. The viewer experienced the disturbances in the visual field, or the amplification of loud or sudden noises exactly as the sufferer would perceive them. Section 9.2. provides a more in-depth discussion of how these distinctions relate to the theory of body-ownership in VR.

Each clip was assessed by three lecturers in psychology, and two independent researchers who are experts in mental health. They ensured that each clip was an accurate reflection of the condition that it purported to show. In addition, they proposed a range of potential multiple-choice and extended-answer questions that could be included in the study. The schizophrenia clip used in Study Four was popular among participants and was therefore included again in the current study. The VR experience of anxiety disorders took place in a UK university setting and was therefore deemed especially relevant for student participants in the current study. Finally, the Autism VR experience offered a unique insight and perspective as the protagonist was a young girl – a demographic that has traditionally been underdiagnosed and misrepresented. As a result, the VR clip allowed viewers not only to experience autism symptoms; but also many of the misunderstandings associated with the condition in young women.

A detailed list of the three Experiential VR clips can be found in Table 13 below.

Table 13*List of Experiential-VR videos presented to participants as well as a description*

Title	Condition(s)	Length	Description
Schizophrenia – A Broken Mind	Schizophrenia and Psychosis	5:24	A point-of-view experience of someone suffering from the visual and auditory symptoms of schizophrenia. This includes hallucinations, paranoid episodes, voices in the head, and disorganised thinking.
Four Walls – An Anxiety VR Experience	General Anxiety Disorder and Panic Disorder	6:15	The viewer takes the first-hand perspective of a university student suffering from social anxiety and panic attacks. The video features auditory overlays expressing the tendency for sufferers to “overthink” in response to social situations. The clip also exhibits the visual disturbances and sense of terror associated with a panic attack.
The Party – A Virtual Experience of Autism	Autism Spectrum Disorder	7:21	The viewer takes the perspective of a young girl suffering from Autism Spectrum Disorder at a family party. Using an inner monologue, as well as various auditory and visual effects, the viewer experiences the sensory overload and discomfort associated with the condition. This culminates in a meltdown at the end of the experience where the protagonist is gripped by a sense of urgency and need to escape.

9.3.3.2 Creating Non-Experiential VR Clips

The creation of the bespoke non-experiential VR clips followed a step-by-step and sequential process. This was necessary as there was no pre-existing VR material that would have been suitable for use in the study. Therefore, the creation of the material from scratch was the only viable alternative to examine the research questions. This involved a four-stage process.

The first stage consisted of the complete auditory and visual transcription of the three previously selected experiential VR clips. The auditory and written information included in these clips were transcribed verbatim, as well as detailing the on-screen visual information. This ensured that an accurate reflection of all explicit and implicit information provided in each of the three clips was recorded. A full copy of the transcription can be found in Digital Appendix 9.2.

The next stage was to create a presentation script based on the information recorded from the experiential transcripts. A script was created for each of the three topics that would be presented in a purely didactic form. This was matched for explicit and implicit content included in the three experiential clips. Of paramount importance was ensuring that the non-experiential presentation did not include any additional information that was not otherwise included in the three pre-existing experiential clips (and vice versa). The non-experiential scripts were then validated by two experts in the field of mental health psychology and autism. They ensured that the information presented was accurate and made suggestions as to how the wording could be changed to better articulate its meaning.

The next stage involved the completion of a “proof of concept” video. The purpose of this was to trial various filming techniques to identify optimal conditions and locations for the final set of videos. As a result of the process, the optimal distance between the camera

and the presenter, the relative position of the presenter, and what location could offer the best sound and lighting could be ascertained.

Following the initial “proof of concept” exercise, the final recordings for the non-experiential videos were produced. An experienced lecturer who had previously taught on a Psychology of Mental Health module volunteered to present the information. The footage was captured in a traditional seminar room using a Samsung Gear 360° camera (2017 version). Using a dual-lens setup, the footage was captured at a resolution of 4096 x 2048 pixels (4K Ultra-HD) in MP4 format. The previous proof-of-concept study found that the on-board microphone was sufficient for collecting clear audio from the lecturer giving the presentation. The presenter stood approximately 6-feet away from the camera that was positioned on a tripod at a height of around 1.75 meters. The presenter spoke directly to the camera whilst reading from a teleprompter positioned behind the camera.

The final stage involved post-film editing. The raw footage was edited and mastered using a combination of Samsung Action Director and Adobe Premier Pro 2017. Titles and text were included to accompany the didactic information provided by the presenter. This typically took the form of written lists and subtitles that accompanied salient information. The footage was then exported as a 360° film that could then be uploaded to YouTube and played on a Mobile-VR headset.

9.3.4 Assessment Instrumentation

As stated in Study One, VR research has tended to utilise MCQs as the sole method of assessing learning outcomes. In the same chapter, it was posited that this method of evaluation may not be sensitive enough to capture more nuanced forms of learning and understanding. Therefore, two separate instruments were devised for the current study. The first was a bespoke 24-question MCQ covering content in the experiential and non-experiential VR clips. To examine the question of assessment sensitivity, an extended-answer-questionnaire consisting of four questions was also devised. Both instruments will be outlined in the following sub-sections.

9.3.4.1 Multiple-Choice Questionnaire

The MCQ consisted of 24 questions, split into four categories (six questions per category). These categories covered the three mental health conditions featured in the VR videos (schizophrenia, anxiety disorders, and autism), as well as a fourth category that aimed to examine how well participants differentiated between conditions. Each questions had four possible answers with one being correct, and three being incorrect. Example questions can be seen in Table 14 below, with the full questionnaire presented in Digital Appendix 9.3.

Table 14

Example of multiple-choice-questions used to assess learning outcomes

Category	Question	Answers
Anxiety Disorders	Women are more likely than men to be diagnosed with an anxiety disorder, but by how much?	A. Twice as likely* B. Three times as likely C. Four times as likely D. Five times as likely
Schizophrenia	What is a defining characteristic of schizophrenia?	A. Panic attacks B. Having multiple personalities C. An inability to distinguish what is real from what is not* D. Problems with memory
Autism Spectrum Disorders	What reason is given for the underdiagnosis of autism in females?	A. Symptoms of autism are less severe in women B. Autism only tends to affect males C. Women are better at masking the symptoms associated with autism* D. Screening and diagnostic tests are not suitable for females

Category	Question	Answers
Differentiation Questions	Which of the following statements is true?	A. Anxiety disorder is more common in men than women B. Females are diagnosed with autism more frequently than men C. Men and women are diagnosed with autism at the same rate D. Autism is more commonly diagnosed in men, whilst anxiety is more prevalent in women*

*Denotes correct answer

Questions were formulated by the lead researcher by cross-referencing common strands of information across both the experiential and non-experiential transcripts. Simply put, all questions on the MCQ could be surmised by watching either the experiential or non-experiential VR clips. It was only the way the information was presented that differed across clips. For example, if a participant watched the experiential schizophrenia clip, they would have a first-hand perspective of seeing figures or shadows that were not real. This same information was presented in the non-experiential clips, except this time the lecturer delivered the information didactically (i.e., directly relaying the information verbally).

The next step involved the evaluation of the assessment instrumentation. Firstly, the validity of the MCQ was assessed by two independent researchers who are experts in the field of autism and mental health conditions. They watched each of the experiential and non-experiential VR clips, before assessing the MCQ. In particular, they examined whether the questions presented were clear and easy to understand, and whether the correct answer was an accurate reflection of the condition. They provided written feedback on how questions could be reworded to make them more comprehensible, as well as suggesting several “incorrect” answers that would more closely reflect a real Psychology of Mental Health assessment.

Next, as a response to criticism raised in Study One, additional validity and reliability checks were considered. As a consequence, the Standards for Educational and Psychological Testing report was consulted (see, American Educational Research Association et al., 2014). In particular, the pronounced weaknesses of previous MCQ questionnaires were examined as highlighted by the MERSQI quality assessment tool (Reed et al., 2007). In their 2014 paper, Rios and Wells provide a comprehensive overview of how to address several common oversights when it comes to assessing the internal structure of MCQs. Firstly, measurement invariance, or the relative *fairness* of an assessment across various population subgroups (e.g., gender, race, age) was considered. As the sample numbered only 28 participants, and collected limited demographic information, a thorough statistical analysis such as that proposed by Millsap (2012) was unsuitable. However, no previous literature has demonstrated systematic evidence of major discrepancies in performance in either VR or mental health activities based on HE student demographics. Therefore, given that the MCQ would be applied only within the context of the current study, a nuanced analysis of measurement invariance was deemed unnecessary.

Next, the internal consistency and reliability of the MCQ assessment was considered. As Rios and Wells (2014) state, this is commonly assessed using Cronbach's Alpha (see, Cronbach, 1951). Indeed, previous VR studies that have utilised an MCQ assessment have attempted to report this value to confirm the internal consistency of their questionnaire (see, Kozhevnikov et al., 2013; Parong & Mayer, 2018). However, typically these studies have sample sizes far below the recommended threshold for a useful Cronbach's Alpha value to be ascertained. For instance, conventional analysis requires approximately 10 participants per item, although there has been a degree of debate on the precise number (see, Yurdugül, 2008). However, the current study would have required a sample of around 240 participants to accurately measure the internal consistency using Cronbach's Alpha (24 multiple-choice items, multiplied by 10 participants per item = 240). Therefore, any attempt to report this value would not provide an accurate or useful measure of internal reliability.

9.3.4.2 Extended-Answer Questionnaire

In Study One, it was argued that there had been an over reliance on MCQs to assess learning outcomes in VR research. It was proposed that extended-answer-questions (EAQ) could afford participants additional opportunities to demonstrate more nuanced forms of learning and understanding. Therefore, the current study included three EAQ as part of the learning outcome assessment.

One EAQ was posed from each of the three mental health topics covered in the VR clips: (a) anxiety and panic disorders; (b) schizophrenia; and (c) autism spectrum disorders. Participants were instructed to use the free-response box to type an answer of between 50 – 500 words. To make the instructions clearer, an example question and associated response was presented prior to answering the questions. The three EAQs are presented in Table 15 below.

Table 15

Extended-answer-questions to assess learning outcomes

Category	Question	Maximum Points
Anxiety Disorders	As anxiety is a mental health condition, the sufferer is unlikely to be affected by physical symptoms. To what extent do you agree with this statement? Why?	8
Schizophrenia	For sufferers, schizophrenia has been described as “one of the most [...] frightening of all mental illnesses.” Using specific examples, provide evidence to support this claim.	8
Autism Spectrum	How might a social event such as a birthday party be adapted to be more comfortable for someone suffering from an Autism Spectrum Disorder?	7

Prior to implementation, each of the three questions were validated by the same two independent researchers that examined the MCQs. They helped devise an appropriate scoring system as well making practical suggestions to address any ambiguity in the questions. For example, the original schizophrenia question read: “a 2007 article called schizophrenia ‘one of the most [...] frightening of all mental illnesses’ (Picchioni & Murray). Using specific examples, provide evidence to support the claim made by the authors.” However, the independent researchers raised concerns that having a direct reference to an article within the body of the text might have inadvertently conveyed that knowledge of its specific content was needed to answer the question. Any reference to the article within the body of the question was thereafter removed.

By consulting Chapter 5 of the Standards for Educational and Psychological Testing (see, American Educational Research Association et al., 2014), a marking scheme was devised to assist in the interpretation of responses and scoring. Each question had a specific set of marking criteria with one-point being awarded each time a response aligned with the predefined marking scheme. A final score could then be awarded to each response. At the conclusion of the study, a random subset of responses were distributed to three separate psychology lecturers to perform benchmarking. This ensured that the scoring performed by the principal researcher aligned with that of experienced psychology markers. A copy of the marking criteria for each question can be viewed in Digital Appendix 9.4.

9.3.5 Additional Measures

In addition to measuring learning outcomes, the current study sought to understand the impact different methods of VR presentation had on student attitudes. In particular, the study examined the impact of presentation method on student motivation, and empathetic response. The data collection tool for each of these factors is discussed in-turn.

9.3.5.1 (Reduced) Instructional Materials Motivation Survey

The Instructional Materials Motivation Survey (IMMS) is a 36-question scale developed by Keller (2010). The survey assesses student motivation and engagement in four key areas: attention, relevance, confidence, and satisfaction. The scale has already been

utilised in numerous studies that examine the impact of educational technology on student engagement (e.g., Di Serio et al., 2013; Gopalan et al., 2016; Stepan et al., 2017).

However, due to the extended participation time, there were concerns that the original IMMS may be too time-consuming, resulting in participant dropout. As a result, a revised version of the IMMS called the Reduced Instructional Materials Motivation Survey (RIMMS) was used (Loorbach et al., 2015). The RIMMS distils the original set of 36-questions to 12 (three from attention, relevance, confidence, and satisfaction). A validation study conducted by Loorbach and colleagues (2015) found that, despite the smaller number of items, the RIMMS was a more robust post-intervention measure of student motivation than the original IMMS. As a consequence, the RIMMS was employed as a quantitative measure of student motivation and engagement with both modes of VR. A full copy of the scale can be found in Digital Appendix 9.5.

9.3.5.2 Perspective Taking and Empathetic Response Scale

Previous studies conducted in this thesis have highlighted experiential learning and perspective taking as being central to the VR experience. Participants have exalted the benefits of VR to give them an unparalleled first-hand perspective of the lived experience of others. Until now, this attitude has been expressed exclusively using qualitative methods such as focus-groups and interviews. However, the present study wanted to also understand this phenomenon in a quantitative context to compare and contrast the experience between different modes of presentation (i.e., does *experiential* VR elicit a significantly higher empathetic response than a simple *didactic* experience?)

One of the most cited quantitative measures of empathetic response is the Interpersonal Reactivity Index (IRI) developed by Davis (1980). Specifically, two key factors are identified as being prominent in the measuring of empathetic response. Namely, these are *empathetic perspective taking (EP)*, and *empathetic concern (EC)* (see, Davis, 1983). Higher levels of *empathetic perspective taking* is associated with being able to embody and assimilate the psychological perspective of another with oneself. *Empathetic concern* is concerned with the degree to which someone can sympathise or feel compassion for the lived experience of another.

One of the key reasons why the work of Davis (1980; 1983) was deemed suitable for the current study is that it has already been integrated into VR research. For instance, Schutte and Stilinović (2017) used eight items (four from EP and EC) measured on a five-point Likert scale to assess empathy in response to a refugee VR experience. These eight items were adapted from the earlier work of Davis (1983) to be used in the context of a VR lesson. As a result, the current study adapted the wording of Schutte and Stilinović's (2017) original questions to be suitable for the current study. To take a specific example, Schutte and Stilinović's (2017) original question of "I tried to see things from Sidra's (the protagonist) point of view" (p. 710) was changed to "I tried to see things from the point of view of someone suffering from the mental health condition." Participants rated their response from one to five, with one representing "*does not describe me well*" and five representing "*describes me very well.*" A full copy of the scale can be found in Digital Appendix 9.6.

9.3.6 Semi-Structured Interview

To gain a more nuanced understanding of the various factors that underpin learning and attitudes in both VR interventions; semi-structured interviews were conducted with a subset of participants. Although this was not a compulsory aspect of the study, participants could indicate whether they would be willing to take part by checking the requisite box on the Consent Form. Each participant who took part in the interview was given an additional £5 Amazon Voucher as remuneration.

The semi-structured interview was based upon the guidelines and framework set out by Smith and Osborne (2003). This has already been covered extensively in this thesis, so there is no need of extensive reiteration here (see Section 5.4.2.). All interviews were conducted online via Microsoft Teams and were recorded for later transcription. Each interview lasted approximately 30-minutes. A full copy of the interview schedule and associated prompts can be found in Digital Appendix 9.7.

9.3.7 Procedure

Using a process of volunteer sampling, participants submitted an *expression of interest* in the study by contacting the principal researcher directly. They were then sent a QuestionPro link to the Participant Information and Consent Form that they had to read and agree to.

Next, they completed basic demographic information such as age, gender, and whether they had used VR in any capacity before. They also inputted shipping information so their Mobile-VR headset could be posted to their residential address. Finally, they were asked to create a unique username that they were to use for the duration of the study. This was to ensure that participant information could be collated across the numerous interventions, whilst also ensuring that each person remained anonymous.

Immediately after signing-up for the study and providing demographic information, participants were required to complete the pre-intervention MCQ and EAQ on QuestionPro. Full details of these questionnaires can be found in Sections 9.3.4.1. and 9.3.4.2. As the study was taking place remotely, the principal researcher was concerned about the possibility that students would simply *search* for the answers to questions they did not know (e.g., using Google). To try and allay any fear of embarrassment that might have prompted the participant to Google answers and responses, a notice was placed on QuestionPro prior to commencement of the MCQ:

Important. Please Read.

You are now going to be asked some multiple-choice-questions. These will be on the subject of mental health conditions. It is absolutely essential that you do not Google or otherwise search for answers that you do not know. If you are unsure, please guess.

Your answers are all completely anonymous, so nobody will know what score corresponds to what specific individual. The point of this research is to examine

whether the VR content we are going to show you later can increase understanding of this topic.

To reiterate, at this stage, we do not expect you to know the answers to these questions.

Thank you for your understanding.

A similar notice was placed prior to the commencement of the EAQ:

Important. Please Read.

*You are now going to be asked some Extended-Answer-Questions. These will be on the subject of mental health conditions. Once again, it is essential that you **do not** Google or otherwise search for answers that you do not know. If you are unsure, you can write down what you think the answer could be. In this set of questions, you should write a short paragraph (maximum 500-words) in response to each of the three questions posed. Try and avoid simply writing bullet-points. Again, if you are unsure, please feel free to guess or simply limit the length of your response to answers you think are correct. We do not expect you to know all of the answers.*

The participants were prompted to tick a box after each notice to confirm that they agreed to abide by the terms and conditions of the study.

After completing the pre-intervention questions, the Mobile-VR headset was posted to the participants' residential address along with assembly instructions. Four days after the pre-intervention questions were completed, participants were contacted with details of the first intervention. Based on whether they were randomly assigned to treatment group A (Experiential VR first) or B (VR Lecture first), they were sent URL links to three VR videos that could be watched on YouTube (see Section 9.3.3. for full details of the VR content). Participants were instructed to watch each video only once, and to do so in a quiet and private place where they would not be disturbed. Using the online Short.io

service (*Short.io*, 2022), each URL link could only be opened once before it expired. This helped prevent participants from repeatedly replaying VR clips if they did not know the answer to a subsequent question. If participants accidentally clicked on the URL link, they could request it was reissued by contacting the principal researcher directly. After watching each video, participants were required to complete the MCQ and EAQ again. A similar message to that of the pre-intervention stage was posted to discourage participants from searching for answers they did not know.

Immediately following the completion of the MCQ and EAQ questions, participants completed the RIMMS, and the Perspective Taking and Empathetic Response Scale outlined in Sections 9.3.5.1. and 9.3.5.2. Participants were required to watch all three VR experiences and complete the requisite questionnaires and scales within 24-hours of receiving them. This was to ensure that there was not significant variation in the time-interval between watching the VR material and answering the questions.

Four days after completing the first intervention, the participants were sent the second set of VR videos (Treatment Group A received the VR Lectures, and Treatment Group B received the Experiential VR clips). Using the same process outlined above, the participants watched each video clip, and completed the required questionnaires and scales. Upon completing this stage, all participants were directed to a Debrief Sheet on QuestionPro and were sent remuneration in the form of £20 in Amazon Vouchers.

As indicated, after completion of the mandatory stages, participants could opt to participate in a semi-structured interview. This was conducted via Microsoft Teams and gave additional insight into the attitudes and perspectives associated with interacting with both VR mediums. In total, eight participants were interviewed (1 males; 7 females), with five being from Treatment Group A, and three from Treatment Group B. A diagram detailing the stage-by-stage process involved in the study can be found in Figure 11.

9.3.8 Analysis

The following section briefly outlines the method of analysis used for both the quantitative and qualitative data collected during the study.

9.3.8.1 Quantitative Analysis

The MCQ, EAQ, RIMMS, and the Perspective Taking and Empathetic Response questionnaire were analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. All quantitative data was analysed using JASP Statistics Version 0.16 (JASP Team, 2022). Assumption checks for the suitability of parametric statistics were conducted prior to each analysis. Full details of the statistical models and tests employed can be found in the requisite analysis sections below.

9.3.8.2 Qualitative Analysis

The current study also conducted a series of semi-structured interviews with a subset of eight participants. These interviews were transcribed verbatim, and then imported to nVivo 12 for analysis. Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA) as described by Braun and Clarke (2006; 2019) was used to formulate themes that gave an overarching account of the data. The process of RTA has already been covered extensively throughout this thesis, and therefore does not need to be detailed here. For an in-depth description of the RTA process, and its associated advantages, see Section 5.4.4.

Figure 11

Flowchart displaying the study procedure

9.4 Results and Findings

The following section will be split into its two constituent parts: quantitative results, and qualitative findings. These will be presented in-turn, before a general discussion of their combined implications is presented.

9.4.1 Quantitative Results

9.4.1.1 Multiple Choice Questionnaire Outcomes

Participants completed the MCQ at three separate intervals during the study. First at the pre-intervention stage, and then again following their first and second VR intervention. The average pre-intervention MCQ score was 16.9 out of 26 ($SD = 1.9$). With an overall mean pre-intervention score of 65%, this would suggest that students had a moderate understanding of mental health concepts prior to the VR intervention.

A “*knowledge gain score*” was calculated by subtracting the participants’ pre-intervention MCQ score from the post-lecture and post-experiential VR score respectively. Next, the main and interaction effect for *intervention type* was examined. A repeated measures general linear model was used with a two-level within-subjects factor named *VR intervention type* (dependent measures being experiential VR and VR lecture). A single between-subjects factor was included named *sequence order* (A = Experiential VR then VR Lecture; B = VR Lecture then Experiential VR). The pre-intervention MCQ score was treated as a covariate in the model to control for any baseline differences in performance. Type III Sum of Squares calculation was employed in the model configuration. It is important to note that the covariate scores were *centred*, by taking the average pre-intervention score and subtracting it from each covariate value. As Schneider et al. (2015) states, this is essential when the experiment has within-subject factors as failing to do so will result in loss of statistical power. Further, they also express concern that no standard statistical software accounts for this automatically:

“Automatic centering of the covariate has not been incorporated into standard statistical packages such as SPSS, SAS, or R. Moreover, we are not aware of any mention of the need to center the covariate before entering data into these

programs in any of the manuals that have been published for users of these three packages that we have examined. Hence, when the experiment contains within-subject factors, it is necessary to center the covariates across all participants before using any of these programs.”

Schneider et al. (2015, p. 7)

There was no significant main effect of *VR intervention type* on MCQ score, with the VR Lecture ($M = 4.29$; $SD = 2.42$) and Experiential VR ($M = 4.36$; $SD = 1.85$) producing similar levels of learning outcomes; $F(1, 25) = .072$, $p = .791$, $\eta p^2 = .003$. This suggests that neither mode of VR presentation contributed to significantly better attainment than the other when measured on the MCQ. In addition, there was no significant interaction effect between the treatment group *sequence order* and *VR intervention type*; $F(1, 25) = 2.21$, $p = .149$, $\eta p^2 = .081$.

9.4.1.2 Extended Answer Outcomes

Participants completed the EAQ at the pre-intervention stage, and after each subsequent VR intervention. The EAQ consisted of three long form answer questions that can be found in Section 9.3.4.2. Using a predefined marking scheme, a potential score of 23 points could be awarded in total. Marking was conducted by the principal researcher with an additional benchmarking protocol to ensure accuracy and reliability. A subset of the EAQs from each of the three stages (pre-intervention, post-VR Lecture, and post-Experiential VR) were benchmarked by three lecturers in the field of psychology. These benchmarked scores were then compared to those of the principal researcher to ensure consistency of interpretation in the marking scheme.

The average pre-intervention EAQ score across all participants was 9.3 out of 23 ($SD = 3$). This translates to an overall average score of 40.4% at the pre-intervention stage, suggesting that participants generally struggled with the extended answer format.

Using an identical method to that described in 9.4.1.1., a “*knowledge gain score*” was calculated for both intervention types. The same repeated measures model as described

above was used to examine main and interaction effects. There was a significant main effect of *intervention type*, with the Experiential VR treatment producing significantly higher gain scores ($M = 5.8$; $SD = 2.8$) on the EAQ than the VR Lecture ($M = 3.8$; $SD = 3.1$); $F(1, 25) = 9.51$, $p = .005$, $\eta p^2 = .276$ (see Figure 12). In addition, there was no significant interaction effect of *intervention type* and *order sequence* $F(1, 25) = .897$, $p = .353$, $\eta p^2 = .035$, suggesting that carryover effects or treatment order did not contribute to these differences.

Figure 12

Bar chart showing the mean gain scores on extended-answer-questions by VR type

9.4.1.3 (Reduced) Instructional Materials Motivation Survey Results

The RIMMS was used to quantitatively assess the level of intrinsic participant motivation with each of the two VR methods (VR Lecture and Experiential VR). For a detailed description of the RIIMS scale, see Section 9.3.5.1. A Shapiro-Wilks Test was conducted to ensure the assumption of normality was met. The test indicated that the data were normally distributed ($W = .939$, $p = .102$), and a parametric test could be used.

A paired-samples t-test found that overall levels of participant motivation were significantly higher when viewing the Experiential VR material ($M = 4.5$; $SD = 0.56$) compared to the VR Lectures ($M = 4.2$; $SD = 0.67$); $t(27) = 2.60$, $p = .015$, $d = 0.49$ (see Figure 13). This suggests that levels of motivational affect as measured through attention, relevance, confidence, and satisfaction (Loorbach et al., 2015) were significantly more pronounced when viewing experiential footage compared to the lectures.

Figure 13

Bar chart displaying the mean RIMMS scores per intervention type

9.4.1.4 Perspective Taking and Empathetic Response Scale

The current study attempted to quantify levels of empathetic response in the two modes of VR presentation. The Perspective Taking and Empathetic Response Scale addressed in Section 9.3.5.2. provides a detailed description of the measure employed. First, the *total empathy* score was compared between the two modes of VR presentation. Prior to running the inferential statistics, a Shapiro-Wilk Test of Normality was conducted to ensure that a parametric test could be used. The Shapiro-Wilk test was non-significant,

suggesting that were data are normally distributed ($W = .950, p = .193$). A paired-samples t-test found that the Experiential VR intervention produced a significantly higher *total empathy score* ($M = 4.5; SD = 0.48$) than the VR Lecture ($M = 4.2; SD = 0.59$); $t(27) = 2.50, p = .019, d = 0.47$ (see Figure 14 below).

Next, the scale was broken down into its two constituent factors: *perspective taking*, and *concern*. A paired-samples t-test found that levels of *perspective taking* were significantly higher in the Experiential VR intervention ($M = 4.4; SD = 0.61$) than the VR Lecture ($M = 4.0; SD = 0.80$); $t(27) = 2.17, p = .039, d = 0.41$. In addition, *concern* scores were also significantly higher in the Experiential VR intervention ($M = 4.6; SD = 0.4$) compared to the VR Lecture ($M = 4.2; SD = 0.4$); $t(27) = -2.82, p = .009, d = 0.53$. In summary, Experiential VR material elicited significantly higher levels of overall empathy, perspective taking, and empathetic concern than the VR Lectures.

Figure 14

Bar-chart showing the mean empathy scores and sub-scores per VR type

9.4.2 Qualitative Findings

The following section gives an account of the qualitative findings derived from the semi-structured interviews conducted. Unlike previous studies presented in this thesis (Study Two, Three, Four, and Five), the current chapter describes a mixed-methods approach. Therefore, unlike previous chapters, the current section will not contain an in-depth analysis of the qualitative findings. Rather, the qualitative and quantitative findings will be discussed together in the general discussion later in this chapter.

As already outlined, RTA was used to formulate a series of overarching themes that gave a holistic account of the interview data. In total, three themes and two subthemes were developed: (a) conceptualising knowledge acquisition; (b) relation to assessment (comprising of the subthemes; [b1] conceptual differences; and [b2] developing an extended response); and (c) empathy through experience. A brief summary of each theme can be found in Table 16.

Table 16

Tables showing the themes and sub-themes derived from the thematic analysis

Theme	Description
Conceptualising Knowledge Acquisition	Theme describes how participants conceptualised both VR experiences (i.e., VR Lecture and Experiential VR) in their ability to acquire new knowledge and understanding.
Relation to Assessment	<p>Theme concerns participant attitudes towards the assessment material included in the study (MCQ and EAQ).</p> <p><i>Subtheme 1: Conceptual Differences – participants were of the attitude that each assessment type probed different levels of understanding.</i></p> <p><i>Subtheme 2: Developing an Extended Response – subtheme focuses on the reflective processes and approaches to answering extended answer questions, and how this differed from MCQ responses.</i></p>
Empathy Through Experience	Participants conveyed the attitude that the Experiential VR clips in particular were fundamental in developing a sense of empathy and perspective taking.

9.4.2.1 Acquisition of Knowledge

A central objective of the current study was to understand how participants conceptualised their learning experience. In particular, this focused on how alternate modes of VR presentation (i.e., Experiential VR and VR Lectures) contribute differently to the acquisition of knowledge and information.

From the interviews, it was clear that participants conceptualised the pedagogical utility of the VR lectures differently from the experiential VR clips. Participants made explicit reference to the VR lectures being useful for learning *fact-based* information such as figures or statistics, whilst the experiential clips helped participants understand the lived-experience and symptomology of the specific condition. These differences appeared to alter the central focus of each experience. For instance, participants remarked that they

used the lectures to garner didactic forms of information, whereas the focus of the experiential clips was the immersion in the world of the protagonist:

“My attention and focus was on what this person was going through (in the Experiential VR clips)– and not necessarily trying to gather facts as such. But when it came to the classroom (VR Lecture), I was more driven to remember the facts. So, it was quite a different approach for each one. I felt that the ‘facts’ or ‘stats’ were easier to recognise in the lecture; but the experience is where I felt I understood what was going on [...] A lecture for me tells you about a topic. It gives you information. But actually being in a situation where you are seeing things through their eyes gives you a whole new perspective. You are immersed. You truly feel. So that gave me more information than just sitting back and being disconnected from it. The experiences made me feel part of it.”

Michael

“I definitely felt I could take the perspective of that person more when doing the experience. In lectures, I think you focus on facts and percentages. But the experience was different. I felt you really got an idea of what that person was going through.”

Karla

As can be deduced from the participant remarks, both modes of VR presentation seem to be conceptualised quite differently by the interviewees. On one hand, the VR lectures appear to occupy the same pedagogical space as traditional didactic forms of education (such as a face-to-face activity), whereas the experiential clips offer a new perspective and insight for acquiring information. This idea can be summed up succinctly by one of the participants when they noted:

“The VR lectures were very much the same as any other lecture – the only difference was that you were using the VR headset. But the experience of being that person was very different to what I have encountered before.”

Michelle

As Michelle exemplifies, although the medium of delivery (i.e., a VR headset) might be unique or novel, the substance of the information is ostensibly the same as any form of traditional education. Simply put, although the VR headset offers an unconventional means of viewing lecture material, the educational information contained within is no different from what students would be regularly exposed to on a HE psychology course. That begs a simple question; if the VR headset itself is not the driver of novel knowledge acquisition, what is? And the answer seems to lie in a common perception that has been present throughout this entire thesis. It is the embodied perspective that the *experiential* clips facilitate that ultimately offer novel opportunities for learning and understanding. In particular, participants mentioned that they acquired knowledge through the experience of “being in the shoes” of someone suffering from a specific mental health condition. As one person puts it:

“I wasn’t standing on the outside. I actually was that person.”

Janice

And by being “that person,” participants remarked that their understanding extended beyond mere theoretical knowledge, and led to an appreciation of how mental health conditions can impact lived experience:

“You don’t think about mental health in such an abstract way when you can pin that experience to a specific person. That’s what I really liked about the point-of-view clips. I felt I understood what it was like to be them”

Michelle

“There is a difference between academic knowledge, and then ‘experience.’ The VR gives you that experience. It gives you an understanding of how it looks in practice”

Isabella

“When it came to learning and understanding the symptoms of the condition, I think the first set of clips (experiential VR) brought the whole thing to life. It stayed with me – I think that is why I felt as if I learned more [...] When you listen to a lecturer, you can get an idea of what the theory is. But actually listening to the person’s thoughts – that inner monologue – it was completely different.”

Karla

As surmised by the responses, the participants expressed that the experiential VR clips allowed them to acquire knowledge and understanding that the VR lectures could not. In particular, participants remarked that the ability to embody the lived experience of another person gave them a unique insight into how each condition impacts patients’ lives. As already alluded to, this is not simply the result of using a novel pedagogical delivery method like VR headsets or HMDs. Rather, the specific nature of the VR clips themselves must be conducive to evoking an embodied perspective, allowing one to see and experience the world as others do. Ultimately, this is the difference between, as Janice already put it, “standing on the outside,” and standing on the inside. To have access to another’s perceptions, inner monologue, and cognitive processes allows for participants to acquire knowledge as the result of direct experience, as opposed to merely didactically. These findings concur with the earlier attitudes of general HE lectures (Section 5.5.1.), psychology teaching faculty (Section 6.5.1.), and psychology students (Section 7.6.1.). The qualitative findings of the present study suggest that students indeed place specific emphasis on VR material that allows for them to embody the lived experience of another person, and ultimately glean novel insights and information from this.

9.4.2.2 Relation to Assessment

One of the fundamental aims of the current study was to evaluate and understand how different methods of assessment could be incorporated into the VR learning process. In particular, both an MCQ *and* EAQ were used to gauge the degree of knowledge acquisition from differing modes of VR presentation. As part of the qualitative process, it was hoped that a more nuanced understanding of how participants approached and assessed these differing assessment criteria could be identified. Further, interviewees were asked whether both types of VR were equally effective at helping them answer the assessment activities, or if they perceived differences in their educational utility.

From the interviews, it was clear that participants conceptualised the MCQ and EAQ differently, both in terms of its overall purpose, and their strategies for answering the questions. Specifically, participants remarked that they regarded the EAQ as a more efficient way of demonstrating the length and breadth of their knowledge acquisition. Further, it was also noted that the experiential VR material allowed students to develop ideas and arguments that better assisted them answer the EAQs. To elucidate this idea, the *Relation to Assessment* theme has been broken down into two constituent subthemes; (B1) Conceptual Differences; and (B2) Developing an Extended Response.

9.4.2.2.1 Conceptual Differences

From the interviews it was clear that participants conceptualised the EAQ differently from the MCQ. At its most fundamental, participants saw the EAQ as an opportunity to demonstrate more nuanced understanding of mental health concepts acquired from the VR experiences, whilst the MCQ only probed surface knowledge. This general perception was exhibited by several participants in their interview:

“Those questions (MCQ) were very facts based if you know what I mean. It wasn’t as if you needed to think too deeply. It was a case of just remembering the lecture and picking the correct answer.”

Janice

“The long-form ones (EAQ) - you had to draw on the knowledge from the experiences. You don’t only draw on your own experience, but also from the VR as well. I felt as if I had the chance to display what I have learned. On the other hand, the multiple-choice seemed a bit targeted. It was just a case of selecting the correct one.”

Isabella

“You can click on any answer in a multiple-choice. But when you actually have to talk about something more – then you get insight into what you have learned or seen. See, if you haven’t paid attention, you’ll find it really difficult to write or discuss something. Whereas, with the multiple-choice, you have a one in four chance of getting it right.”

Kelly

As participants have expressed, the EAQs allowed them the freedom and opportunity to articulate their understanding of mental health concepts. As Kelly suggests, one must assimilate information with existing knowledge and experiences to successfully formulate a cohesive response to the EAQs. On the other hand, the MCQs were restrictive in targeting only a specific aspect of the topic, and participants seemed to have an explicit awareness that they could always guess correctly (alluded to by Isabella and Kelly). This overarching idea was expressed succinctly by one of the participants when they noted:

“I didn’t feel what I learned really came across in the multiple-choice. I didn’t feel as if I was given the opportunity to express myself.”

Alice

9.4.2.2.2 Developing an Extended Response

Now that the participants have clearly demonstrated a conceptual difference in their understanding of MCQs and EAQs; it is important to understand *how* these differences

manifest when formulating responses. As has already been seen (Section 9.4.2.2.), participants generally conclude that MCQs probe only a limited breadth of their understanding and knowledge of mental health concepts. On the other hand, participants suggest that they had to be more deliberate and nuanced in their approach to answering the EAQ. Specifically, participants conveyed the attitude that they had to formulate a cohesive response by reflecting on what they had previously learned, and then devising a structured argument:

“I needed to focus more on the extended answers. With the multiple-choice, I knew the answer was always going to be there anyway. But with the extended answers I needed to structure an argument and not get lost. I don’t think I have ever done that too well. But I didn’t feel as if answering the question was so...automatic if that makes sense? I actually had to sit and think about it. Not just the answer, but making the whole thing make sense.”

Janice

It is interesting to note the participant’s perception that the reflective process of formulating an extended response helped them appreciate the depth of their understanding. Not only did they have to reflect on their own learning from the VR clips, but also had to synthesise and present this information clearly. This contrasts quite drastically with the idea of the MCQ responses being “automatic” or “targeted.” The process of reflection when developing an appropriate response was also reiterated by several other participants:

“They (extended answer questions) were a really good way of reflecting and thinking about the insight I got from the experience. So, I felt it helped me understand what I had taken away from those videos.”

Michael

“I think that they (the extended answer questions) helped me expand on my knowledge and understanding. I mean the other one is fine, but it’s just a tick-box. You’ve always got a chance of getting that right. But the other one made me reflect on the experience.”

Isabella

As far back as Study One, the question was posed as to whether MCQs were too restrictive in detecting more nuanced forms of comprehension and understanding (see Section 4.5.3.). Originally, this point was raised in response to the potential limitations of MCQs to detect changes in learning outcomes and academic attainment. Indeed, participants in the current study have identified several inherent weaknesses of the MCQ assessment method. For instance, they claim that it did not provide the opportunity for them to fully demonstrate what they had learned, neither did it probe deeper understanding of the concepts or theory. However, in making this point, participants have espoused a far more fundamental idea that could have ramifications for how VR learning is assessed in future. Indeed, the inclusion of EAQs can be viewed as *part of* the learning process, as opposed to a mere assessment of it. Participants suggest that the very process of answering a series of EAQs forces them to first reflect and then synthesise the information gleaned from the VR experiences. This process of reflection and synthesis allows students to construct and formulate a structured response to each question. Not only do they have to answer each question correctly, but as Janice previously remarked, this answer must be organised and arranged in such a way that it makes sense to the reader. As participants have alluded to, this process of reflection, synthesis, and argument development does not feature as heavily when answering MCQs. Indeed, those interviewed state that completing a multiple-choice assessment elicits an almost “automatic” response when selecting the correct answer. In contrast, participants conveyed the attitude that answering the EAQs forced them to purposefully reflect on their learning experience, and then arrange this information in such a fashion that it can be reflected in their written responses.

9.4.2.3 Empathy Through Experience

The idea of VR being an “empathy machine” is a common trope that has been used as both a pejorative and complementary description of the technology (see, Bujić et al., 2020; Hassan, 2020; Herrera et al., 2018). However, most studies tend to examine the concept of empathy in the context of attitude and behavioural change, as opposed to academic learning. As the current study examined the differences in experiential and non-experiential VR material, it was pertinent to understand what influence this might have played in the process of generating empathetic concern. In addition, the interviews set out to probe whether these factors might have influenced learning outcomes.

As a result of both the quantitative and qualitative data collected, it was clear that participants were of the attitude that the experiential VR clips elicited more empathy than the VR Lectures. This entire concept can be summed up with just one response:

“The difference between empathy and sympathy sums it up for me. Sympathy is all about standing on the outside and saying, ‘that is a shame.’ But I felt empathy. I really did. That was the difference between the lecture and the experience. With those point of view clips, I felt as if I was that person. I felt connected to them. Especially the schizophrenia experience. That must be horrific.”

Michael

Again, the common idea of embodied perspective seems to be a driving factor in the ability to empathise and understand the experience of another. Michael notes that this same experience was not as prominent in the VR Lecture, but rather was a unique attribute of the experiential material. This ability of the Experiential VR clips to elicit an empathetic response from the viewer was a prominent one, backed up by almost every participant who was interviewed:

“When using the VR headset, that experience of being someone; it allows you to see the facts come to life. Actually, looking down and seeing things crawl up your

arms – or the noise, the sheer noise. It creates so much empathy because you know what someone is feeling. I felt like that was so eye-opening.”

Michelle

“The first set of videos (Experiential VR) – I felt a connection with that person. It wasn’t just passive. I felt really bad for them. You could relate it to a real person and feel what they are feeling.”

Janice

“It was absolutely terrifying. The hallucinations and so on were really impactful. Especially the voices that made you feel really paranoid and uneasy. I never imagined that is what it would feel like. I felt so sorry for them. It was horrible to contemplate actually.”

Karla

From the participant responses, the Experiential VR material is uniquely placed to foster empathetic concern and perspective taking. The idea forwarded by Janice that the experience is not merely “passive,” seems to play a prominent role in this perception. Instead, the viewer presents the attitude that they are taking an active role in assimilating the experience of the person they are embodying with themselves. This idea can be exhibited in a subtle yet telling turn-of-phrase used by many of the interviewees. Namely, the use of possessive pronouns and adjectives when describing the VR experience. For example, during the schizophrenia experience, Michelle noted that spiders were crawling up “your arm,” and Karla said that the voices made “you” feel paranoid. Michael also used similar language when describing her feelings whilst viewing the autism experience:

“I was more invested in the first set of videos, definitely (experiential). It is all about the empathy and the fact you are that person. The VR is immersive – you can’t escape it. You’re buckled in. [...] Like when I was watching the autism video – I felt as if everyone’s eyes were on me. It is quite unnerving. It feels as if you’re

being stared at or talked about. It must be so uncomfortable actually being in that situation.”

Michael

Although this use of language might be overlooked, it gives an important indicator as to how participants perceive the experience of embodied perspective. This same assimilation of the protagonist with oneself was not evident when participants discussed the VR Lectures. Rather, it seems to be a unique characteristic of the experiential nature of the embodied material. This gives an indication as to how these types of experiences are capable of eliciting the empathetic response evident in the current study. Viewers do not merely sympathise with the situation of another; but rather they can fully embody the thoughts and cognitive processes of that person as if they were their own.

9.5 Discussion and Conclusion

The present study utilised a mixed-methods within-subjects design to examine several fundamental aims and objectives. Firstly, the study compared differences in learning outcomes for experiential and non-experiential modes of presentation using both an MCQ and EAQ. The quantitative results demonstrated that although both modes of presentation produced comparable results in the MCQ assessment, the Experiential VR clips resulted in significantly higher learning gains than the VR Lecture on the EAQ. Secondly, the study compared the subjective levels of motivation and empathy in response to the two categories of VR experience. Results showed that the level of motivation (measured using the RIIMS) and empathetic response were significantly higher in the Experiential VR treatment compared to the VR Lecture. To gain a more nuanced insight into these factors, semi-structured interviews were conducted with a subset of eight participants. The aim of these interviews was to garner additional insight and information into the learning process. Using RTA, three themes were formulated that best encapsulate the attitudes and experiences of the participants: (a) acquisition of knowledge; (b) relation to assessment, (b1) conceptual differences, (b2) developing an extended response; and (c) empathy through experience. In this section, both

quantitative and qualitative findings will be discussed together in order to give a holistic overview of the study's implications.

9.5.1 Learning Outcomes on the MCQ

One of the fundamental aims of the current study was to examine learning outcomes in relation to differing modes of VR presentation. This served two primary purposes. First, it allowed for an investigation into the efficacy of both experiential and non-experiential VR for learning mental health concepts. Secondly, different assessment techniques could be evaluated for their sensitivity to detect knowledge acquisition.

The quantitative analysis of MCQ performance found no significant differences in learning attainment between the two modes of VR presentation. Further, there was no significant interaction effect of sequence order, indicating that carryover and order effect did not influence knowledge acquisition performance. Ostensibly, both versions of the VR experience produced comparable results as indicated by the MCQ. As already alluded to by Parong and Mayer (2018), the majority of studies that examine learning outcomes in the context of VR have utilised a media-comparison method. Essentially, VR has been *compared* to an alternative form of teaching or media. For instance, VR has been compared with 2D videos or desktop simulations (e.g., Greenwald et al., 2018; Moro, Stromberga, et al., 2017), as well as textbooks and written material (e.g., Allcoat & von Mühlennen, 2018). As a result, little research exists that directly evaluates differing modes of VR presentation in the context of knowledge acquisition and learning outcomes.

Despite the lack of directly comparable research, the findings of the MCQ have several ramifications for both theory and applied practice. First, it could be that both presentation types are equally effective at delivering mental health concepts. For example, research has already found that altering the same VR experience by manipulating immersion levels has little impact on knowledge acquisition (e.g., Rupp et al., 2019). Also, many of the more traditional media-comparison studies suggest that as long as the core learning content is the same, the method of delivery (e.g., VR) does not impact student performance (e.g., Greenwald et al., 2018; Moro et al., 2017; Stepan et al., 2017). As both VR presentation types in the current study were specifically designed to

relay the same explicit information, it might not be too surprising to see comparable learning outcomes across both methods of delivery.

9.5.1.1 But Does the MCQ Provide the Full Picture?

Despite comparable results on the MCQ, any assertion that both modes of VR provide comparable knowledge acquisition is too simplistic. Since Study One of this thesis, doubt has been cast on whether MCQs give a true reflection of the learning and understanding garnered from VR experiences. To briefly recap, MCQs might not be sensitive enough to capture more nuanced forms of learning and understanding, meaning that students cannot appropriately demonstrate the breadth of their knowledge. For example, the common application of MCQs in VR research does not appear to be the result of a definitive pedagogical theory or previous studies. In fact, given that most VR interventions are short and isolated (see, Hamilton et al., 2021a; Jensen & Konradson, 2018), many researchers have posited that the use of MCQs are wholly inappropriate in the first place (Excell, 2000; O'Dwyer, 2012). Indeed, from the interviews conducted, many participants remarked that the MCQ was akin to a *memory exercise*, as opposed to demonstrating and displaying wholesale changes in understanding of the given topic. Many of the participant intimated that they did not have to think too deeply when it came to answering the questions, commonly citing that there was always a chance that they could guess correctly. Further, one participant even explicitly stated that the MCQ restrained them from fully expressing themselves. These attitudes and perceptions are surprising, not least because a wealth of research has exalted students' preference for MCQs over EAQs (e.g., Tozoglu et al., 2004; Zeidner, 1987). Students' attitudes in the current study were more closely aligned to that of HE lecturers who generally criticise MCQs as failing to promote learning, and being ineffectual at probing deeper understanding (see, Parmenter, 2009). The fact that neither assessment contributed towards a final grade or formal examination might have led to a more balanced view of each respective methods inherent benefits or weaknesses. For instance, Parmenter (2009) suggests that student preference for MCQs is typically predicated on the idea that they are easier, and more conducive to "obtaining a high test score" (p. 57). On the other hand, although students are less receptive towards them, EAQs are viewed as being a more valid and accurate assessment of knowledge acquisition. However, what can be in

no doubt is that participants were capable of conceptualising both assessment types as being markedly different in their scope and ability to probe knowledge and information.

To further investigate this issue, the current study incorporated both an MCQ *and* EAQ. As already alluded to, no significant differences in learning outcomes were present when the evaluation was conducted via the MCQ. This might lead to the already stated simple assumption that both VR methods produce comparable levels of knowledge acquisition. However, this is unlikely to be the case, namely because the study *did find* that the Experiential VR clips produced significantly better learning when measured on the EAQ. But why was this the case? Could it be that the EAQ is more sensitive at detecting nuanced forms of learning that are best relayed through the Experiential VR? Or could it be that the significantly higher levels of motivation, engagement, and empathetic concern produce better learning? Furthermore, might it be that the process of answering the EAQs *themselves* forces participants to reflect more deeply on their knowledge acquisition? Likely, the answer is multifactorial and complex. However, these are covered in the proceeding sections.

9.5.2 Are EAQs a More Accurate Reflection of Learning?

The integration of an EAQ as part of the current study encouraged participants to be reflective in the process of answering the questions. From the interviews, participants noted that the EAQ forced them to reflect on the information that they had learned, especially during the Experiential VR material. In contrast to the MCQ, participants indicated that the act of reflecting and formulating an appropriate answer was *part of* the learning process itself, as opposed to merely a demonstration of it. For example, as part of the interviews, participants were explicitly asked what they thought the major differences were between the two competing types of assessment (i.e., MCQ and EAQ). Numerous interviewees remarked that unlike the MCQ, the EAQ prompted them to reflect and deliberate on the information that they had acquired through the VR experiences. They were then forced to strategically formulate an extended response that best demonstrated what knowledge they had garnered as a result of the interventions. Indeed, pedagogical research has postulated that extended answer responses are best suited to

allow students to display, as Nieswandt and Bellomo (2009) put it, “meaningful understanding” (p. 333).

9.5.3 Experiential VR Increases Scores on the EAQ

One of the most striking findings of the current study is that the Experiential VR material produced significantly higher *gain scores* on the EAQ than the VR Lecture. An argument has already been postulated that the MCQ may not be sensitive enough to capture a truly “meaningful understanding” of the learning content (Nieswandt & Bellomo, 2009, p. 333). Therefore, it is now prudent to discuss why the Experiential VR content produced significantly better assessment results on the EAQ than its MCQ counterpart.

A residing factor that could explain the increase in learning scores after viewing the Experiential VR may lie in the EAQ’s sensitivity to detect knowledge gained through direct experience. As Kolb (1984) alludes to, the purpose of experiential learning is to allow students to be active participants in the educational process. In doing so, they can imbibe, process, and assimilate new information with existing knowledge and schemas (Kolb et al., 2011). This overarching idea can be best encapsulated in an old, yet wholly accurate reflection that experiential learning involves the “whole-person in both his feeling and cognitive aspects” (Rogers, 1969, p. 5). In no other medium is this reflected better than in the embodied perspective afforded by Experiential VR. Indeed, a range of studies have already utilised this embodied perspective to positive effect (e.g., Adefila et al., 2016; Bidaki et al., 2020; Formosa et al., 2018). But from a practical point of view, the assessment instrumentation must allow students to demonstrate the knowledge they have gained through embodied and experiential learning. Indeed, it is challenging to envisage an MCQ that would allow students to synchronously illustrate their base knowledge of a given topic, whilst also giving them the freedom to fully express their understanding of the experience. By their very nature, MCQs are restrictive and, as one participant succinctly put it, “targeted” in their approach to probing information. However, as has been alluded to throughout this thesis, experiential learning through VR does not merely provide the conceptual or theoretical foundation of a given topic. Rather, it brings those theories “to life” by giving the viewer a concrete and tangible example of how such concepts play out in practice (e.g., by *experiencing* what it is like to have a mental health condition as opposed to merely being told about it). Therefore, to truly

understand the depth of this experience, the student must be afforded the freedom to demonstrate the knowledge in an unrestricted manner. And one way in which this can be done is through long-form responses such as those found in the EAQ. Indeed, multiple researchers have already suggested that EAQs give a more robust and valid assessment of learning outcomes (Nieswandt & Bellomo, 2009; Parmenter, 2009). This assertion exemplifies the importance of considering the evaluative method prior to making assertions about the pedagogical effectiveness of learning interventions. For instance, if this study had followed the single MCQ method favoured by many studies identified in the systematic review (e.g., Akbulut et al., 2018; Maresky et al., 2019), it would have likely concluded that there was no inherent difference in the learning provided by Experiential VR and VR Lectures. However, the incorporation of the EAQ allowed for more nuanced differences in learning to be detected that might have otherwise been overlooked.

9.5.3.1 Motivation and Engagement Drives Learning

Now that the relative advantages of incorporating an EAQ has been discussed, it is important to once again reflect on *why* the Experiential VR material produced significantly better learning outcomes compared to the VR Lecture. As demonstrated in Section 9.4.1.3., the Experiential VR clips resulted in significantly higher subjective motivation and engagement than its Lecture counterpart. The RIMMS scale, and its overarching ARCS framework of instructional design postulates that higher levels of motivation is a key predictor of effective learning (Keller, 1987, 2010; Loorbach et al., 2015). This assertion is supported by a recent meta-analysis demonstrating that the ARCS framework is positively associated with both academic achievement, and also motivational level (Goksu & Islam Bolat, 2021). During the interviews, it was clear that participants regarded the Experiential VR clips as being more engaging and motivating to interact with. In the case of one participant, they noted that the VR Lecture was akin to a standard on-campus experience, with the only difference being that they were watching it with a headset. On the other hand, interviewees exalted the ability of the Experiential VR material to allow them to fully embody the lived-experience of a mental health sufferer. Most participants acknowledged that this was a totally novel way of learning information, and therefore was likely a driving factor in increasing motivation and engagement.

9.5.3.2 Experiential VR Facilitates Perspective Taking

Throughout this chapter, the idea that Experiential VR allows participants to truly embody the perspective of a mental health sufferer has been a prevalent one. However, the evidence and implications of this assertion should be examined further. As demonstrated in Section 9.4.1.4., Experiential VR was shown to produce significantly higher levels of *perspective taking*, *concern*, and *overall empathetic response* compared to the VR Lecture. However, what are the applied ramifications of this, and how does it relate to learning outcomes?

The current study makes a novel contribution to the literature by examining the level of perspective taking and empathetic concern across two alternate modes of VR presentation (i.e., Experiential VR and VR Lecture). This allows for a thorough understanding of how differing types of VR material can impact participants' ability to empathise with the experiences of another. However, similar to the aforementioned comparison with learning outcomes, little previous research exists that this study can be directly compared to. For instance, when investigating perspective and/or empathy, previous studies have tended to use a pre/post-test design to gauge *gain scores* in empathetic response (e.g., Formosa et al., 2018). Alternatively, other studies have simply conducted an intervention vs control group design to assess the effectiveness of VR to increase perspective taking and empathy (e.g., Jütten et al., 2018). No previous research has compared two competing methods of VR presentation. Using a modified version of the empathetic response scale used by Schutte and Stilinović (2017), the current study assessed the levels of *empathetic perspective taking* and *empathetic concern*. The findings clearly demonstrate that the overall empathy, perspective taking, and empathetic concern scores were all significantly higher in the Experiential VR intervention than the VR Lecture. In practice, this demonstrates that the Experiential VR material increased participants' ability to embody and assimilate the lived experience of another with oneself. In addition, the Experiential VR clips were also more effective at evoking compassion and concern for those living with mental health conditions. These results were supported with qualitative findings from the interviews conducted as part of the study.

Numerous participants made reference to feeling “empathy” or feeling “sorry” for the protagonist they were embodying. Furthermore, participants expressed a visceral or profound reaction to the Experiential VR clips; especially the schizophrenia material where they were able to appreciate the severity of visual and auditory hallucinations. Previous studies have already demonstrated VR’s innate ability to foster empathetic concern and perspective taking by placing the viewer at the centre of the experience (e.g., Campbell et al., 2021; Martingano et al., 2021; Shin, 2018). To this end, the old trope of VR being the “empathy machine” certainly has a basis in empirical research (see, Hassan, 2020). However, this is the first study that has truly attempted to compare the subjective experience of viewers using two alternate types of VR presentation whilst teaching the same core content. The current research demonstrates that not all *types* of VR experience can produce the same degree of empathetic response. Rather, the specific way in which the content is presented to the viewer is crucial in fostering perspective taking and concern. Simply put, the use of a HMD is a necessary but not sufficient means of generating a profound empathetic response on the part of the participant. Rather, the experience itself should allow the viewer to embody the lived-experience of another person and afford them the opportunity to experience the world exactly as *they* experience it.

Congruent with Slater's framework (see, Slater, 2009; Slater et al., 2022), the notion of body-ownership is crucial for the enhanced perspective-taking facilitated by experiential VR. This principle underlies how experiential VR, in contrast to didactic VR lectures, significantly promotes empathy, perspective-taking, and engagement with immersive content. Body-ownership within VR generates a profound sense of physical and emotional synchronisation with a virtual avatar, enabling users to deeply internalise and assimilate the lived experiences of another. This is markedly different from a VR Lecture, where although the HMD is still being used, the experience does not allow the viewer to embody the sufferer. Rather, the viewer only received information in a didactic fashion, similar to that of a traditional classroom lecture or seminar. Indeed, during the interviews, one participant stated that they did not find the essence of the VR Lecture to be fundamentally different to a traditional classroom presentation. This bolsters Picciano's (2009) edict that any technological integration must be done “with purpose”

(p. 7). It is not enough to simply employ HMDs because they are novel. Rather, both content creators and educational facilitators must develop and employ VR content that fully utilises the unique perspectives afforded by the technology. To that end, the positive impact of Experiential VR on engagement, motivation, perspective taking, and empathy point to embodied point-of-view experiences being a particularly effective use of VR hardware.

9.5.4 Limitations

One limitation that has already been anticipated is the online nature of the study, especially given that the research examined learning outcomes. As already outlined, a number of safeguards were put in place to stop participants searching for answers, or otherwise *cheating*. Each URL link to the VR video expired after a single click to help prevent the VR experiences from being rewatched. In addition, a notice was placed at the start of each MCQ and EAQ session asking participants to agree not to search for answers, and reiterating that all information pertaining to scores and learning outcomes were completely anonymous. However, these measures can only mitigate against confounding factors to a certain extent. Future research could extend these safeguards by having a researcher present whilst the participant is completing the MCQ and EAQ. For instance, although the VR experiences could be watched from home, the learning outcome component should be completed on-campus under supervision. Unfortunately, due to the COVID pandemic, this options was not available during the timeframe of the current study.

A second limitation involves the VR content itself. In the current study, only the VR Lectures were bespoke, having been created by the lead researcher specifically for the purposes of the research. The Experiential VR clips were already pre-made, and formed the basis for the script that would later become the lecture material. Ideally, both versions of the VR content would have been made from scratch, allowing for full quality control and validity over the nature of the content. For instance, the content covered in the Experiential VR videos could more closely align to the core curriculum, meaning that the material was an accurate reflection of what was taught on-campus. However, time-constraints and the COVID pandemic meant that the lead researcher was unable to recruit and procure actors, sets, or other necessary components in order to do this. As has been

discussed already in Study Chapters One and Two, the feasibility of creating VR content from scratch is a major barrier to successful technological integration. However, the present study has demonstrated that simple 360° films like a VR Lecture can be created reasonably quickly, easily, and with only a working-knowledge of VR techniques (see Section 9.3.3.2.). However, to further explore the objectives and implications of the present study, it would be prudent to also ensure that the Experiential VR clips are also individualised for purpose, and this presents its own range of barriers and impediments as already discussed extensively throughout this thesis.

9.5.5 Conclusion

The objective of the current study was to explore fundamental differences between two alternate modes of VR presentation. Using a within-subjects, repeated-measures design, participants underwent both an experiential and non-experiential (VR Lecture) VR intervention. In addition to collecting quantitative outcomes such as knowledge acquisition (using an MCQ and EAQ), motivation, and empathetic response, a series of semi-structured interviews were also conducted. Participants performed significantly better on the EAQ after the Experiential VR compared to the VR Lecture, whilst no difference was found on the MCQ. In addition, using two quantitative scales, participants reported significantly higher levels of motivation and empathy after viewing the Experiential VR material. A series of semi-structured interviews suggested that participants found the Experiential VR clips provided a degree of embodied learning and perspective taking that the VR Lectures simply could not. From this, participants noted that they were able to gain a nuanced understanding of what it is like to suffer from a mental health condition, as well as reporting a high degree of empathetic response.

A major contribution of the current study was that it compared learning outcomes across two assessment criteria. As this thesis has generally been critical of the (over)use of MCQs to assess VR learning outcomes, a complementary EAQ was also included. Results demonstrated that although no significant differences were found on the MCQ, the Experiential VR material produced significantly better scores on the EAQ. This supports the posited hypothesis that in many cases, MCQs are simply not sensitive enough to detect more nuanced forms of learning and understanding. By using the EAQ, students remarked

that they were forced to reflect on their experiential learning, whilst also forming a cohesive and coherent argument to meet the learning objectives. This suggests that EAQs can be used as a means of assimilating and organising previously learned knowledge, as opposed to simply being a demonstration of it.

10 GENERAL DISCUSSION

10.1 Chapter Overview

The final chapter presents a holistic discussion of this thesis' contribution to pedagogical VR research. This is based on the empirical contribution of six original studies, as well as the current body of research in this field. It is worth reemphasising that each individual study chapter already contains its own discussion. Consequently, it is not the intention of this chapter to simply describe each study in isolation. Rather, its purpose is to offer an integrated perspective of how this entire thesis has addressed the research questions, made a novel contribution to literature, and made suggestions for applied practice.

10.2 Expectation Versus (Virtual) Reality

The beginning of this thesis started with some rather bold pronouncements. Namely, there was an expectation (if not an inevitability) that VR was on the cusp of fundamentally revolutionising education on a scale unparalleled in human history. Companies like Meta and Microsoft announced that their technology would allow for a universal community of learners to interact, collaborate, and experience pedagogy in a manner that would have been unimaginable just a decade ago (Hedrick et al., 2022; Lin et al., 2022; Rospigliosi, 2022). No longer constrained by mere didactic forms of instruction, students would now have the opportunity to visit an otherwise inaccessible location (e.g., Markowitz et al., 2018), embody another human-being (e.g., Formosa et al., 2018), or visualise an abstract concept or principle (Fogarty et al., 2017). Not only this, but VR was also touted as a motivational tool that would encourage inquisitive and reticent students alike. Just a glance at the promotional material created by those spearheading such VR initiatives showcase the confidence in such products (Meta, 2022; Microsoft, 2021; World Economic Forum, 2022).

From the outset of this thesis, the objective was to scrutinise VR's place within education based on empirical evidence – not media hype. Indeed, both instructors and students

have exhibited positive and receptive attitudes towards VR's integration as a pedagogical tool. However, no instructor or student conceptualised VR as being an all-encompassing educational environment like that predicted by the Metaverse. Rather, its utility was thought of as being complementary or supplementary – a far cry from how such technology is commonly advertised. In addition, a range of logistical and applied concerns were also raised that need to be acknowledged and rectified to ensure the successful assimilation of VR in HE. Many of the practical considerations such as the receptiveness of end-users, or the logistical intricacies of implementation do not seem to feature in the bold and flashy tech reports. Indeed, for a few well-financed or technically savvy institutions, these practical issues may not present a major obstacle. However, for most universities, the implementation of VR will likely be a slow *trickle-down* process fraught with practical impediments.

How does this thesis make a distinction between the expectations of educational revolution, and the practical reality of implementation in HE? As already stated, this necessitates a balanced perspective based on research, evidence, and reflective consideration.

10.2.1 Summarising Key Findings

This thesis examined the efficacy and implementation of VR within HE through a multiphase approach that investigated a set of predefined, overarching research questions (see, Section 3.2 for an overview). The aims included an in-depth investigation of VR's current and future utilisation in HE and a mixed-methods approach to understand attitudes, perceptions, and objective learning outcomes. This research sought not only to make a theoretical and empirical contribution to the literature but also to improve the applied implementation of VR in HE.

Central to this investigation was an initial systematic review, which was fundamental in anchoring this thesis within the research area. This included both a thorough investigation of the empirical literature, as well as associated applied learning theories. This review found a notable preference for VR's use in scientific and engineering disciplines, highlighting the tangible advantages of employing the technology over more

traditional pedagogical means (e.g., digital resources, lectures, PowerPoints), particularly in tasks that demanded abstract thinking or visual comprehension. Despite this, some studies showed no significant advantages to using VR. However, the assessment instrumentation used to evaluate knowledge acquisition (typically MCQs) may not be sensitive enough to capture more nuanced forms of comprehension and understanding. This foundational insight highlighted VR's potential to bolster learning outcomes and the importance of integrating appropriate evaluation methods to capture such information.

Subsequent chapters turned their focus to examining the attitudes of educators towards VR. These studies revealed that perceptions of the technology were generally favourable, recognising its potential as an additional tool for curriculum delivery. However, challenges such as poor institutional support, technological limitations, and issues in content creation hindered its effective integration. This disparity between theoretical effectiveness and practical application emphasised the critical need for further investigation into VR's viability as a teaching tool. In Study 3, discussions among psychology lecturers identified a consensus on VR's effectiveness as a supplementary educational tool, particularly in the domain of mental health education facilitated through body-ownership. The adoption of accessible Mobile-VR mitigated some of the financial and technological barriers previously encountered. Nonetheless, the ongoing engagement with VR content and its relevance to academic outcomes were crucially dependent on its alignment with assessment and educational objectives. This principle was supported by the argument that VR, like any supplementary method of education, must be implemented with a clear, predefined purpose (see, Picciano, 2009).

An in-depth exploration of VR's potential to facilitate experiential learning within psychology further elucidated its role in enabling immersive comprehension of topics such as mental health. By facilitating a sense of "body-ownership" over a virtual avatar (see Slater et al., 2009; 2022), VR provided viewers with an embodied experience inhabiting another person. This contrast with traditional educational mediums showcased VR's ability to maintain student attention and enhance learning processes, particularly by fostering a deeper understanding of theoretical concepts through experiential immersion.

In conclusion, this thesis substantiated the pedagogical value of VR in HE, underscoring its capability to transcend traditional learning paradigms through immersive experiences. It elucidated the pivotal factors influencing VR's educational integration, including the necessity for robust assessment methods and the imperative alignment of VR content with pedagogical goals. The culmination of this research offered practical recommendations for VR's applied practice, championing an experiential learning approach that leveraged VR's novel capacities to enrich educational experiences and outcomes.

10.3 Empirical Contributions of this Thesis

In the previous section, the main findings of this thesis were briefly summarised. In doing so, a clear outline of this thesis' contribution to the field of pedagogical VR can be appreciated. However, examined through a holistic lens, it is important to understand where these findings have confirmed, challenged, or expanded upon the research area in its entirety. It is the aim of this section to highlight and further explore the main empirical contributions that this thesis has made, and in doing so, cement how these evidence-based approaches can be applied in pedagogical practice.

10.3.1 Experiential Learning Through Embodiment

Experiential learning is predicated upon the idea that students imbibe information through active, first-hand experiences, before reflecting on these processes (Murray, 2018). In university environments this is often facilitated through "hands-on" activities such as practical simulations, field-trips, or excursions (Roberts, 2011). However, the increasing use of VR has opened new avenues in allowing students to gain novel insights and knowledge through direct experience. Although the systematic review in Study One identified numerous studies that allowed students to get "hands-on" with abstract or visual concepts like cell biology (e.g., Johnston et al., 2018) or physics and spatial arrangements (e.g., Greenwald et al., 2018; Kozhevnikov et al., 2013), no research was identified that allowed participants to *embody* the experiences of another person. This was surprising in-light of the findings of Study Two and Three, where HE lecturers

exalted the potential of VR to allow students to experience the world as others experience it. This was especially prominent in the field of mental health psychology where numerous instructors remarked that VR could help elucidate difficult to convey concepts like psychiatric symptomology.

Numerous studies have employed VR to enhance understanding among participants regarding the profound impact of conditions such as schizophrenia, Alzheimer's disease, and psychosis on individuals' lived experiences (e.g., Bidaki et al., 2020; DePape et al., 2020; Formosa et al., 2018). While these investigations have predominantly centred on eliciting empathy and changing behaviour, they have not significantly addressed the integration of these experiences within established educational modules, nor have tended to focus on formal knowledge acquisition. Therefore, this thesis has attempted to critically assess the role and value of pedagogical VR within a natural higher education setting. Particularly, the research presented in Study Four introduces a series of embodied VR experiences to psychology students enrolled on a mental health class. This study revealed that students highlighted VR's capability to facilitate more detailed and sophisticated responses in their academic assessments. Furthermore, research within the field of mental health has already demonstrated that VR contributes to improved learning outcomes (e.g., Formosa et al., 2018). Nonetheless, Study Four marks the first occasion where students have explicitly praised the distinct benefits of VR in the context of formal academic evaluations.

Incorporating VR in subjects related to clinical psychology and mental health appears as a promising avenue for practical application. By aligning these experiences with traditional educational methods such as lectures or prescribed reading, students can enhance their existing knowledge through novel insights. This form of generative learning facilitates a more robust comprehension and appreciation of the complexities associated with mental health conditions. Expanding on the existing framework, the concept of embodiment and body-ownership offers an innovative pathway to deepen students' understanding of clinical psychology and associated domains. Slater's work (e.g., Slater et al. [2022]) has highlighted how the illusion of body-ownership can profoundly transform participants' perceptions and interactions within virtual

environments, effectively allowing them to “step into the shoes” of another individual. This innovative approach enriches students' theoretical knowledge and equips them with an unparalleled understanding of the conditions being studied, bridging the gap between academic theory and tangible (virtual) reality.

The unique aspect of body-ownership in VR, as proposed by Slater et al. (2022), significantly enhances the pedagogical value of VR by providing an unparalleled insight into the subjective experiences of individuals with mental health issues. Consequently, the implementation of VR experiences, grounded in embodiment and body-ownership, represents a significant advancement in educational practice, offering students a comprehensive and nuanced perspective on mental health that traditional educational formats may not fully convey.

The fundamental idea that VR is ideally placed to offer experiential learning was not merely demonstrated with explicit remarks provided by students. Rather, it was also exhibited when this thesis attempted to examine its application in other pedagogical domains. Indeed, if this thesis had focused exclusively on mental health, it might be accused of being too narrow in its scope to make discernible recommendations or contributions to wider practice (indeed, an in-depth discussion of “generalisability” has already been conducted in Section 3.4.). However, previous research has often promoted VR's application as a means of facilitating far more conceptual or abstract theories and ideas (Serin, 2020). To that end, Study Five fully integrated a series of asynchronous VR activities into an Environmental Psychology module – the first time this has been done. The fundamental idea that VR is ideally placed to offer experiential learning was not merely demonstrated with explicit remarks provided by students. Instead, it was also exhibited when this thesis attempted to examine its application in other pedagogical domains. Indeed, if this thesis had focused exclusively on mental health, it might be accused of being too narrow in its scope to make discernible recommendations or contributions to wider practice (indeed, an in-depth discussion of “generalisability” has already been conducted in Section 3.4.). However, previous research has often promoted VR's application to facilitate far more conceptual or abstract theories and ideas (Serin, 2020). To that end, Study Five fully integrated a series of asynchronous VR activities into

an Environmental Psychology module – the first time this has been done. The essence of the VR experiences in question primarily deviated from an “embodied” perspective, wherein the observer lacked a sense of ownership over a distinct character within the VR environment (a concept discussed extensively by Slater and colleagues in 2009 and more recently in 2022). This absence of specific body-ownership may have resulted in a deficiency of visual and auditory stimuli that might otherwise amalgamate the user's sensory experiences with those of the avatar. Participants frequently reported an inability to identify practical advantages of VR, despite acknowledging its relevance and motivational properties. They noted that the VR tasks, lacking synchronicity, offered minimal innovative insights applicable to their formal academic assessments. Among the most pronounced distinctions observed between Studies Four and Five was the inherent nature of the VR content. It was suggested that the experiential properties of the VR—encompassing the body-ownership of a specific character within a particular scenario, undergoing a unique set of experiences—truly enriched users with novel understandings and the practical application of knowledge. This hypothesis found empirical support in Study Six, wherein VR experiences characterised by specific body-ownership significantly outperformed their non-experiential counterparts (i.e., the 360° lectures). Study Six addressed a fundamental critique of Parong and Mayer (2018), who argued that comparisons within traditional media studies were inequitable, likening them to comparing “apples to oranges” (p. 788). The argument's essence shifted towards identifying the most effective types of VR experiences, rather than questioning the viability of VR as an educational tool in itself. Through a comprehensive analysis, Study Six not only reaffirmed the benefits of experiential VR with its illusion of embodiment, but also demonstrated a tangible impact on learning through EAQ assessments.

It can be easy to fall into the trap of assuming that such empirical contributions only have ramifications for students. This is not the case. As was mentioned on several occasions in Studies Two and Three, instructors often find it challenging to impart knowledge that requires a degree of experiential understanding or personal relatability. For instance, reading schizophrenia symptoms from the DSM-5 might allow instructors to convey a degree of surface knowledge, but giving students an appreciation of what it really *feels* like is a very different challenge. However, this thesis has demonstrated that

VR can be an effective tool in an educator's arsenal. By carefully planning and structuring how the curriculum is delivered, instructors can supplement their traditional approaches with a novel means of elucidating key concepts.

These ideas relate to the most striking, salient, and all-encompassing participant quote in the entire thesis. Namely, through didactic means of education, instructors can "tell" students "what they need to know." However, by effectively utilising VR, instructors can allow students to "feel what they need to know." And this gets to the very heart of the experiential benefit that VR can confer. It broadens the range of learning outcomes that instructors can facilitate. Not only can scholastic knowledge of topics be improved (e.g., Formosa et al., 2018), but attitudes, behaviours, and preconceptions can all be challenged through body-ownership of a virtual other (see, Adefila et al., 2016; Bidaki et al., 2020; Wan & Lam, 2019). Indeed, the introduction of VR might allow for instructors to broaden the scope of their educational approach in topics such as mental health. For instance, VR could assist in the discussion of more attitudinal issues such as bias or stigma in clinical populations. Indeed, VR could help enable an in-depth discussion of these issues by allowing for a shared experience or common point of reference among students. Consequently, it is important to recognise that the integration of VR has the potential to expand not only the pedagogical tools available to HE instructors, but also the very nature of the learning objectives being offered.

10.3.2 Generative Learning Theories Align with Experiential VR

As Southgate and Smith (2017) have outlined, pedagogical VR research has often suffered from poor attention to *how* the technology should be integrated, and the overarching motivation for doing so. Traditionally, the use of learning theories have been employed to help facilitators justify their pedagogical approaches by recognising how students imbibe, process, and then demonstrate learning (see, Pritchard, 2017; Schunk, 2011). However, it was not until Radianti and colleagues published their 2020 review that it became clear that VR research often negates to mention its theoretical underpinnings. Indeed, the systematic review conducted in Study One also concurred with these findings in experimental studies. The result is that it is often challenging to discern exactly *why* VR is being used, and how researchers and facilitators expect it to contribute to learning and knowledge. Far from providing a merely theoretical or scholastic exercise, an

appreciation of learning theories is also fundamental to designing and implementing effective HE modules. For instance, descriptions of teaching methods and their justification are often needed for academic quality review panels, as well as module proposals or changes (see, Donnelly & Fitzmaurice, 2005). As a result, this thesis has made significant strides in being able to finally frame VR within preexisting learning frameworks. This has been challenging given the limited research that has proactively addressed these concerns (see, Radianti et al., 2020). However, by giving forethought not only to how VR should be implemented, but also *why* its implementation would be expected to facilitate knowledge acquisition, a comprehensive justification for its application can be proposed.

Despite the perceptions of companies like Meta and Microsoft, both students and instructors envisage VR as forming nothing more than a supplementary method of education. For instance, in the entirety of this thesis, no student or instructor thought that VR represented a wholesale replacement for traditional means of education (so much for lecture theatres being built from “code” [Meta, 2022]). But what is more interesting is how those same students made sense of the type of learning that VR was able to facilitate. For example, students in Study Four remarked that they already had a foundational understanding of core mental health concepts, but the supplementary VR helped bring that understanding “to life.” These findings are consistent with ideas promulgated by *generative learning theory*. Generative learning is established on the idea that students build upon their pre-existing knowledge by being “physically and cognitively active in organising and integrating new information” (Wilhelm-Chapin & Koszalka, 2016, p. 1). To this end, generative learning has often been conceptualised as a branch of cognitive constructivism with its emphasis on active as opposed to passive learning (see, Kalina & Powell, 2009; Yilmaz, 2011). By embodying the perspective of another person, it is clear to see why experiential VR in particular is congruent with notions of active and involved learning.

Through attitudes of pedagogical supplementation (not replacement), and active participation in the learning process, this thesis has contributed to the applied and theoretical perspective that VR is suited to generative forms of learning. For instance,

students in Study Four remarked that although lectures and seminars formed the basis for theoretical and conceptual understanding, the VR material added new perspectives and insights through active experiential learning. Indeed, in the small number of studies that *have* explicitly addressed the often negated importance of pedagogical theory, generative learning has been a particularly promising avenue for implementation (e.g., Makransky et al., 2020; Parong & Mayer, 2018). It addresses the fundamental edict that all forms of blended or multi-modal learning must be integrated “with purpose” (Picciano, 2009, p. 7). This thesis has demonstrated that both instructors and students believe that VR can augment foundational understanding of a given topic with additional insights and perspectives. Researchers and facilitators should therefore be cognisant of learning theories and practices when applying VR in their own capacities. Learning theories allow for instructors to justify pedagogical choices in relation to their expectations, goals, and objectives (Kolb et al., 2011; Pritchard, 2017; Schunk, 2011). This thesis has made a fundamental contribution to knowledge by demonstrating that generative learning theories are aligned with experiential practices through VR.

10.3.3 Promoting Engagement Through VR

There has been a wealth of research that has endorsed VR as a means of increasing engagement and motivation (e.g., Kustandi et al., 2020; Molina-Carmona et al., 2018). This has been of particular interest since 2019, where schools, colleges, and universities have sought new technologies to increase pedagogical engagement during the COVID pandemic (see, Maulana & Purnomo, 2021). Indeed, this thesis corroborates previous research that suggests both students and lecturers envisage VR as being an important driver of motivation and engagement (Chou & Hoisington, 2018; Lee & Shea, 2020). However, two main issues were identified in the existing body of literature. First, few studies examined the attitudes of HE instructors towards pedagogical VR; rather they tended to focus on primary and high school instructors (e.g., Dengel, 2018; Fransson et al., 2020). Secondly, where student motivation and engagement were examined, it tended to be done after an extremely short and isolated VR intervention (similarly to how learning outcomes were typically studied). For instance, some research had students interact with VR simulations lasting only ten minutes before expecting them to give an informed perspective of the technology (e.g., Farra et al., 2018).

To address these concerns, Study Two and Three utilised interviews and focus-groups to garner a nuanced understanding of how the technology would impact students. Lecturers in Study Two remarked that VR added a general sense of excitement to existing lessons and sessions. Psychology teaching faculty in Study Three thought that VR could achieve “buy-in” from students by priming them to learn and engage through motivation. These attitudes are consistent with a multitude of other studies that have promoted VR as a tool for increasing motivational response in educational environments (e.g., Alfalah, 2018; Maulana & Purnomo, 2021; Olmos-Reya, Ferreira-Cavalcanti, Contero, et al., 2018). In itself, these findings are rather non-surprising, and have been well-substantiated in a variety of recent reviews (Jensen & Konradsen, 2018; Radianti et al., 2020). However, this thesis *has* been able to expand upon this general area of motivation and make two key novel contributions. The first, a rather unexpected consequence of the COVID-19 pandemic, is that VR could help educators motivate students whilst undertaking distance learning. The second contribution identified that the introduction and implementation of VR could fundamentally change students’ overall perception of an entire module or class (something that previous work has seldom identified).

10.3.3.1 Motivating Hybrid Approaches to Learning

Both students and instructors have articulated that the applicability of VR transcends mere pedagogical deployment within classrooms. A plethora of reports and publications have introduced innovative methodologies aimed at amplifying learner motivation and engagement amidst remote and blended educational settings (e.g., Chiu et al., 2021; García-Morales et al., 2021; Rahiem, 2021). These methodologies frequently leverage empirically substantiated practices employed by online academic establishments. Yet, conspicuously absent from these scholarly discourses and commentaries is an exploration of the potentiality of VR as a conduit for affording learners an immersive and stimulating educational experience. Limited research has advocated for Mobile-VR as an economically viable and accessible medium to supply learners with immersive experiences (e.g., Chowdhury et al., 2017; Moro, Stromberga, et al., 2017). Nonetheless, these studies have not capitalised on the distinctive attributes of Mobile-VR’s design (namely, its flat-pack form) to suggest the distribution of HMDs to distance learners and their utilisation as a mechanism for asynchronous learning. However, this thesis has been

able to garner the evidence to suggest that this is a promising utilisation of such technology in pedagogical settings.

By allowing both educators and students to interact with Mobile-VR HMDs in the comfort of their own homes, the motivational potential of such an approach became clear. For example, psychology lecturers in Study Three remarked that they had never considered such application of the technology before, however it seemed intuitive given the ease in which HMDs could be delivered to students. Students in Study Four and Five were explicit in suggesting that the use of Mobile-VR could help motivate and engage them in scholastic activities. For example, VR was cited as a means of “breaking up the learning process” by punctuating the often *sameness* of online instruction. Indeed, Rahiem (2021) cites student curiosity surrounding new technology as being an instigator of engagement and motivation. Fortunately, VR has consistently been shown to confer significantly higher levels of motivation than other non-immersive technologies (see, Makransky et al., 2020; Parong & Mayer, 2018). Although it requires a degree of planning and forethought, this thesis has demonstrated that students can benefit from the increased curiosity and engagement that VR can facilitate from their own homes.

It is essential to understand that these motivational aspects are not constrained to distance learning. Although a plethora of researchers, educators, and authors have promoted the idea that hybrid learning will become the new normal post-pandemic (see, García-Morales et al., 2021; Murphy, 2020; Thornton, 2020), this thesis has never been predicated on that assumption. Simply, the findings of this thesis must be applicable regardless of whether HE reverts to a pre-pandemic state, or hybrid approaches become increasingly more common. Fortunately, previous research has already demonstrated that Mobile-VR can be successfully integrated as an on-campus activity to increase learning and overall engagement (e.g., Hussein & Nätterdal, 2015; Olmos-Reya, Ferreira-Cavalcanti, Contero, et al., 2018; Olmos-Reya, Ferreira-Cavalcanti, Soler, et al., 2018). However, this thesis has demonstrated that such approaches can also be incorporated asynchronously as well. Students in Studies Four and Five displayed a motivation and willingness to engage with VR activities that are related to their scholastic endeavours. Therefore, even in traditional HE modules, there may be scope to incorporate VR as an

asynchronous and supplementary method of education that can be accessed through the VLE. Where this approach becomes even more interesting is when the second novel contribution is considered. Namely, VR seems to increase levels of engagement and motivation across an *entire* module, and not just in those predefined time-periods where the technology is used.

10.3.3.2 VR Promotes Holistic Motivation

The second novel finding in relation to engagement and motivation is that students expressed that they became positively disposed to a particular module when VR was used, even if it was of little practical or applied value. Again, “applied value” relates to the attitude that the technology would confer a tangible benefit in assessment activities such as essays, reports, or exams.

Students on the Environmental Psychology module in Study Five remarked that VR helped the class “stand out” in their minds, and they would often “look forward” to the VR material being posted. This attitude is similar to the *tangential learning* approaches mentioned in Study Four (see, Mozellus et al., 2018). By allowing students to interact with a medium they enjoy using, they are motivated to engage and interact with the core learning material. This has two ramifications. First, it provides novel evidence that VR can generate not only transient engagement or enjoyment; but also facilitate an all-encompassing motivation that runs across an entire module as opposed to a single timepoint. These findings only came to light by addressing the methodological weaknesses of previous research. Namely, VR research tends only to use a single and isolated intervention (Jensen & Konradsen, 2018; Radianti et al., 2020). However, by integrating VR into an already established HE module, and collecting data at several predefined intervals, a more nuanced understanding could be formulated. By giving students an extended exposure to VR, they could better articulate how its inclusion shaped their wider perception of the module.

The second implication of “holistic motivation” prompts a far more applied question. Namely, it once again raises the fundamental question of *why* and *when* VR should be used. Despite students in Study Five finding little applied benefit to the technology, they

did state that it increased their motivation for the module in general. Therefore, if a facilitators' objective is to simply engage and motivate their students, it may not be essential that it confers an obvious learning benefit. For example, instructors may wish to include such activities because they promote engagement with the *overall* curriculum, and reduce fatigue that may accumulate through repetitive teaching practices (Francis, 2017; Rost, 2006). Although this approach might not confer a direct relationship between VR integration and academic performance, evidence does suggest that engagement and motivation can be a precursor to academic success (Gerber et al., 2013; Harbour et al., 2015). Ostensibly, the facilitator will need to identify their own motives, reasons, and objectives for VR integration, and make a value judgement as to whether its inclusion will fulfil these aims.

10.4 Methodological Contributions

Apart from exhibiting a range of empirical contributions, this thesis has also made strides in identifying *how* pedagogical VR should be investigated. These methodological contributions not only build and improve upon previous work but provide an insight into how future research should be conducted. The purpose of this section is to outline these key methodological issues, and address how this thesis has been able to challenge or expand upon them.

10.4.1 Eclecticism in Research Approaches

One of the most noticeable methodological contributions of this thesis is its eclecticism in research approaches. Philosophical eclecticism can broadly be defined as the practice of deriving and applying ideas and methods from a diverse range of sources (Fatić & Zagorac, 2016). When applied to methodology, this refers to using a broad swath of research, data collection, and analytical methods. From a purely philosophical perspective, the eclectic mix of methods aligns with the pragmatic approach first introduced in Section 3.4.1. in that no one research paradigm is adhered to (see, Greene & Hall, 2010; Morgan, 2014). However, this is not the main strength of this approach. Rather, the diversity of research methods employed in this thesis allowed for the exploration of a range of research questions, as well as identifying and then improving upon the weaknesses of prior work.

Investigating the attitudes of instructors provides a good example of where this eclecticism has been beneficial. For instance, previous research has been rather one-dimensional in how it chooses to understand the attitudes and perceptions of educators towards pedagogical VR. For example, there has been a reliance on using quantitative questionnaires and scales to assess the receptiveness of teaching faculty (e.g., Alfalah, 2018). On the other hand, this thesis has used complementary methods of interviews *and* focus-groups to build upon our understanding of VR's place in HE. For instance, only by conducting semi-structured interviews in Study Two did the practical and logistical concerns relating to VR implementation come to light. For example, educators expressed that accessibility and finance were major impediments in its practical application. Practical solutions could then be devised and investigated accordingly. Specifically, focus-groups with members of teaching faculty allowed this thesis to gain a unique insight into the potential of Mobile-VR to ameliorate many of the original concerns associated with high-end technology. Although previous studies have employed some qualitative techniques such as written reflections (e.g., Chou & Hoisington, 2018; Cooper et al., 2019), none have been able to identify problems, propose solutions, and then practically examine whether these could be effective within the same project. However, this thesis was able to do exactly that by implementing a range of overlapping and complementary research approaches that built upon preceding findings.

The eclectic mix of research methods helped this thesis investigate a diverse range of aims and objectives. However, the diversity in the analysis techniques themselves also helped provide a more nuanced understanding of pedagogical VR. For instance, by utilising a range of analytical methods, this thesis was able to consider *all* data that were collected across the empirical studies. Simply put, the contribution of every participant could be taken into consideration. At first, this may not appear to be a unique or novel selling point. Surely, any well-designed study would include the contributions of its entire sample. But this is not necessarily the case. For example, the limited number of focus-group studies that have investigated VR (e.g., Farra et al., 2018) only use the "group" as its primary unit of analysis. Indeed, this seems to be a common approach when utilising methods of analysis derived from thematic approaches such as Constant Comparison

(see, Doody et al., 2013; Leech & Onwuegbuzie, 2007, 2008). This means that the contributions of individual participants *within* each group are often neglected, which renders a potential goldmine of interesting insights redundant. However, this thesis identified the intrinsic weakness of dismissing such data and implemented practical methodological solutions to address it. For instance, by employing MIA as described by Onwuegbuzie et al. (2009a, 2009b), Study Three was able to understand the degree of consensus in regards to pertinent attitudes surrounding VR implementation in HE. Indeed, this is something that no other qualitative study has been able to do.

In a similar vein, the use of a Negative Case Analysis in Study Five (Section 8.5.5.) allowed a participant with a very different viewpoint to have their voice heard. For example, in traditional qualitative research, a single participant whose attitudes stray from the prevailing consensus will usually have no influence on the formulation of later themes. This is analogous to an outlier in quantitative research being deleted from the data set. However, through its sheer diversity of research approaches, this thesis was also able to consider these attitudes through a Negative Case Analysis. Not only does this give the participant a platform to express their opinions, but it also fundamentally recognises that these findings are every bit as important, useful, and valid as those that conform to the norm (see, Hanson, 2017; Wicks, 2010).

Finally, it is essential to recognise that the eclecticism of this thesis, and the various methods employed within does not signify a lack of consistency or focus. Rather, it represents the best attempt at addressing a diverse range of research objectives. Each method was carefully selected as it offered a unique insight and perspective into the role that pedagogical VR has in HE. From an applied point of view, future researchers should become acquainted with the wide array of methods and techniques at their disposal. This is particularly pertinent when considering the attitudes and opinions of those participants who do not have a positive response to VR. If indeed VR is to become a pedagogical mainstay, then researchers and educators can no longer dismiss the attitudes of detractors as simply anomalous. Instead, they will have to implement such methods of analysis that carefully consider those attitudes, and can facilitate practical solutions to

alleviate such concerns. Indeed, this thesis has taken an important first step in doing just that.

10.4.2 Moving Beyond Multiple-Choice

The issues around the over-reliance on MCQs has been discussed at length throughout this thesis. Therefore, this section will contain only a brief overview of the most important findings and discussions from the empirical studies.

Prior to the systematic review in Study One, and its associated publication (see, Hamilton et al., 2021b), little consideration had been given to *how* VR's educational utility was being assessed. A review of the literature found that there was an almost universal over-reliance on MCQs to evaluate learning. In many ways, this is unsurprising. MCQs are generally considered a quick and easy way of evaluating learning outcomes, and are therefore a convenient choice for researchers and educators wanting to gauge understanding (Parmenter, 2009; Tozoglu et al., 2004; Zeidner, 1987). However, as Excell (2000) has stated, the use of such methods is generally inappropriate for short, isolated, and/or otherwise truncated interventions. As a result, to rely solely on their outcomes may not give an accurate reflection of VR's capabilities to educate and inform.

Study Six demonstrated that with the inclusion of an EAQ, the researcher was able to detect tangible pedagogical benefits that the MCQ could not. As has already been stated, if Study Six had exclusively relied on the MCQ, then it might have assumed that there were no discernible differences between the two presentation types. These findings exemplify why researchers, facilitators, and lecturers must carefully consider the methods they employ when attempting to assess VR's utility. As educators throughout this thesis have remarked, this does not necessarily have to be done in a purely formal fashion (e.g., through questionnaires or assessment). Rather, informal methods such as group or classroom discussions could also serve as a means of evaluating the effectiveness of VR's contribution to education. It is therefore imperative that researchers and educators apply more robust and all-encompassing measures of knowledge acquisition in future experimental research and applied practice.

10.4.3 Examine *How*, Not *If*

As exhibited by the systematic review in Study One, a great deal of research has examined the fundamental question of whether VR *should* be used. Typically, this justification is derived from whether VR confers a learning benefit over less immersive types of pedagogy (see, Jensen & Konradsen, 2018; Radianti et al., 2020). For example, whether VR is better at teaching biology concepts than a textbook (e.g., Allcoat & von Mühlennen, 2018) or whether VR is superior to slideshows at teaching computer science (e.g., Ray & Deb, 2016). However, at absolutely no point in this thesis did any lecturer or educator state that VR was in *competition* with any of these other methods of teaching. Parong and Mayer's (2018) "apples to oranges" (p. 788) comparison aside; no lecturer or students conceptualised VR as being a replacement for lectures, slideshows, or textbooks. Rather, VR's place has always been envisaged as a supplementary one. Again, it is worth noting that this perception is markedly different to how contemporary VR is being marketed in the educational sphere. Indeed, a great deal of research has directly compared "competing" pedagogical methods to discern whether VR should be used or not. However, this experimental application is at odds with how lecturers, teachers, and facilitators foresee VR being applied in their classes.

A far more important consideration is discerning *how* VR should be used, not *if* it should be used. As a result, typical inter-media comparison studies are of limited theoretical or applied value in addressing this central consideration (e.g., VR versus a PowerPoint Presentation). These methods were never conceptualised as being in competition in applied practice (see Study Two and Three), and therefore to be examined as such is a non-sequitur. It is more advisable to focus on *how* VR should be integrated. For example, a novel contribution of Study Six was to examine how different modes of VR presentation influenced learning. Studies Three and Four, as well as previous literature had already justified the use of VR as a means of teaching mental health concepts (Bidaki et al., 2020; DePape et al., 2020; Formosa et al., 2018). Therefore, a media-comparison study would have been of little value. However, Study Six *did* indicate that Experiential VR resulted in increased learning gains compared to a didactic counterpart. These findings will help inform educators, researchers, and content creators of the types of experiences that they should be integrating into their classrooms. From the viewpoint of applied application,

these findings confer far more practical utility than simply addressing whether the technology should or should not be used.

In a similar vein, this thesis has also examined the “*how*” of curriculum integration. As has already been stated, the concerted quest for demonstrating VR’s efficiency over other methods has often left this question unanswered (see, Southgate & Smith, 2017). Most educational VR studies have conceptualised and used the technology as a synchronous classroom activity (e.g., Madden et al., 2018; Ray & Deb, 2016). Only a limited number have made any attempt to encourage access to VR outside of predesignated class times (e.g., Molina-Carmona et al., 2018). However, this thesis has demonstrated that with the correct equipment (i.e., Mobile-VR), VR can also be integrated as an asynchronous method that students can interact with in their own time. Unfortunately, the COVID-19 pandemic meant that the technology could not be examined as a synchronous classroom activity (although, as already mentioned, prior studies have already done this). However, this thesis provides justification for future research to take up this mantle and investigate whether VR is best utilised as part of a structured classroom lesson, or one in which students can access freely. Once again, this approach is not predicated on the “*if*,” but rather the “*how*” of VR integration.

Finally, the supplementary nature of VR has been well substantiated and covered within this thesis. However, as Study One clearly demonstrates, VR has often been studied as a standalone method with no complementary instruction. There were a few exceptions such as combining VR with written material or web-based modules (Smith et al., 2018; Stepan et al., 2017). However, this was not typically the case. Once again, this was not how instructors or students envisaged VR being used. There were a diverse range of opinions and attitudes when discussing VR’s relationship with other instructional methods. For example, some educators remarked that it could be used at the end of a class to complement and summarise didactic content (Study Two), whilst others thought it was best served as an introduction or to facilitate discussion (Study Three). Some students in Study Four thought that VR could supplement lecture material, whilst others in Study Five thought that VR should simply be used to break up module content. Regardless of VR’s role within the curriculum, these findings demonstrate that VR is rarely, if ever

conceptualised as a single, isolated, or standalone method of instruction. Consequently, if researchers are to continue along experimental lines, then such studies should investigate the efficiency of different applied methods. For example, Parong and Mayer (2018) studied whether having students summarise the information contained within the VR experiences at predefined intervals would improve learning. Unfortunately, such research is rare, meaning that once the decision to utilise VR is confirmed, there is a lack of practical guidance on how to use it.

To continue debating whether VR *should* be used or not does little to progress the research out of the *cul-de-sac* it so often finds itself in. This thesis has conclusively demonstrated that VR can be an effective learning tool (Studies One and Six), and there is motivation from both educators and students to use it (Studies Two, Three, Four, and Five). It is now the job of researchers to think beyond the common trope of media comparison and examine *how* VR should be used. Although VR is unlikely to ever replace traditional means of education (despite how it might be marketed), its integration is an inevitability. Therefore, the question of “*how*” is taking ever increasing precedence over the “*if*.”

10.5 Considerations for Applied Practice

From the very inception of this research project, it was deemed essential that this thesis made practical recommendations for applied integration. As covered extensively in this section, a great deal of previous research has sought to justify using VR in the first place (i.e., through media comparison). However, one of the many problems with this continued approach is that it seldom facilitates practical discussions in regards to its eventual applied use. Simply put, once universities have decided to pursue VR as a means of technology aided instruction, then what?

This plea for applied consideration is not merely aimed at educators or instructors. If VR is going to be introduced in education, it will require a concerted effort involving VR designers, technology companies, and policy makers. Based on the findings of this thesis,

the proceeding sections outline some of the most important considerations for applied practice, and how potential impediments can be overcome.

10.5.1 Mobile-VR Provides an Accessible Means of Delivering Material

In late 2021, the Google Cardboard Mobile-VR headset was officially discontinued by the company (Amadeo, 2021). Google cited that it now wished to focus on alternative VR/AR applications, and it would no longer sell or support the product. Despite the continued availability of third-party headsets such as those used in this thesis, this news signals a shift in priorities for technology companies. Fortunately, a range of websites and applications such as YouTube VR still supports the uploading and viewing of 360° content on its platform. This is important as this thesis has clearly demonstrated the crucial role that low-cost and accessible VR hardware has in HE.

The use and application of Mobile-VR was driven by the findings of Study Two. Here, HE lecturers identified a range of barriers and impediments to integrating the technology into their classes. Although lecturers were positive about the impact of the medium to offer novel insights and learning, they stated that the financial cost and their lack of technical knowledge often hindered its use. Consequently, an approach similar to that recommended by Olmos et al. (2018) was implemented. Namely, it was suggested that a “bring your own device” (BYOD) approach could alleviate many of the most common barriers that were originally raised by educators.

Instructors and students now had access to a low-cost and portable headset that required little expertise or training, and worked with their existing technology (i.e., a smartphone). Instructors remarked that the accessibility of Mobile-VR was particularly pertinent due to the COVID-19 pandemic, where students could now access material from home. Students themselves often expressed surprise at just how immersive and engaging they found interacting with the material, citing that they found it enjoyable, intriguing, and a marked change from traditional means of instruction.

There is no doubt that “high-end” VR hardware offers unprecedented immersion and interaction that cannot be fully replicated by Mobile-VR. For instance, more complex VR systems can deliver haptic feedback based on actions performed by the user in the virtual environment (Gibbs et al., 2022). However, in HE, these benefits must be tempered with the acknowledgement that the financial and support costs of purchasing and running high-end systems are beyond the scope of many universities. Mobile-VR offers a tangible, and most importantly, effective means of providing students with 360° content that can supplement their educational needs. Indeed, empirical research has demonstrated that, despite its simplicity, Mobile-VR can still offer an immersive experience (Amin et al., 2016). Therefore, it is prudent that content creators and VR manufacturers realise that there still exists a need for providing financially viable and accessible hardware for general use in HE. In doing so, both lecturers and students will have the opportunity to interact with the technology and benefit from its ability to provide novel insights and experiences.

In practice, what does this mean? If an instructor does not require an experience to contain extended periods of locomotion or environmental interaction, then high-end systems confer little benefit over low-cost Mobile-VR (Amin et al., 2016). From a practical standpoint, apart from a slight increase in graphical fidelity, watching a 360° experience on an Oculus Quest is comparable to a Mobile HMD. Indeed, there were psychology instructors in Study Three who made this very point (see Section 6.5.2.). In addition, students in Studies Four and Five repeatedly remarked that they found the technology engaging and interesting without making pleas for increased sophistication. Therefore, as a supplementary means of instruction, there is nothing wrong with keeping the application of VR simple and cost-effective.

10.5.2 Content Creation Still Hampers VR Implementation

Despite Mobile-VR addressing several barriers to successful integration, there remains a major, unresolved impediment. As Jensen and Konradsen explain, “production of VR simulations is prohibitively expensive, and for instructors this means that they have to use the content that is provided by VR content producers” (p. 1525). This means that in the vast majority of circumstances, lecturers and students will be at the mercy of whatever pre-existing material is available to them. This has two immediate

ramifications. First, despite all advice to the contrary (e.g., Fransson et al., 2020), lecturers may feel the need to structure the lesson around the VR, as opposed to the VR around the lesson. This is likely to be the case if current VR content does not align with predefined learning objectives. The second major issue is that many VR experiences, especially in the field of psychology, may not be a true or accurate reflection of what it is purporting to show. From a practical standpoint, Study Six had content *peer-reviewed* and validated by experts in the field. This would at least be a good starting position for any lecturer wishing to implement this type of content within their classroom. However, VR must reach a point where it is feasible for educators to create bespoke or individualised experiences for their students. Research has suggested that VR creation suites such as Unity are beginning to offer people with a reasonable level of proficiency the opportunity to create content from scratch (Isar, 2018). However, based on the attitudes of lecturers in Study Two, this remains elusive for most given constraints on their time, access to training and support, and levels of self-efficacy. As a result, the problem of bespoke content creation is not one that will disappear any time soon. It is therefore incumbent on educators to utilise and collaborate with people within their own university with the skills to create, deliver, and implement VR. For example, the expertise of a Learning Technologist or similar professional can be consulted to assist with the process.

10.6 Limitations and Future Directions

An essential component of any research project is to be evaluate the methods employed, identify limitations, and suggest how these could be addressed in future research (Theofanidis & Fountouki, 2018). Importantly, this process is not designed to downplay the contribution of this thesis, but rather to reflect on the research experience and critically evaluate the limitations inherent in it (Price & Murnan, 2004).

Throughout this thesis (particularly after the systematic review), the applied and theoretical contribution of continued media comparison studies has been questioned. For instance, comparing educational outcomes using VR and PowerPoints might provide proof-of-concept; but does little to further elucidate why, when, and how VR should be used in an applied context. In an attempt to manoeuvre and cajole the research direction

out of this proverbial *cul-de-sac*, this thesis integrated VR in a variety of real university modules. However, the limiting factors associated with this approach should be acknowledged. Firstly, the number of students who participated in each class was relatively small. Although smaller samples in qualitative studies are typically not a cause for concern (see, Braun & Clarke, 2021c), the negative case analysis in Study Five highlights that dissenting attitudes and perspectives can occur. Consequently, a larger-scale integration (perhaps as part of a bigger class) would have provided more opportunities for these attitudes to come to the fore in an area where student opinion tends to be homogenously positive. Indeed, the lifting of COVID restrictions on educational practice may facilitate this wider application.

A second limitation of this thesis relates to the aforementioned idea of “homogenous positivity” towards VR. Volunteer and convenience sampling, especially within the context of pedagogical studies, has the possibility of being rather self-selecting. Simply put, it is those students who already have a curiosity towards VR or technology that are more likely to participate in the associated studies. Consequently, there are a host of HE students whose attitudes and perceptions towards VR are unaccounted for due to non-participation. For instance, although all students in the Environmental Psychology module (Study Five) were given access to VR material, some students chose not to participate in the data collection aspect. Although non-participation may be due to a variety of extraneous reasons (e.g., not enough time to partake, reticence to take part in an interview), it could also be that they simply are not interested in VR as a pedagogical method. Importantly, negative attitudes and reluctance to engage with the technology are every bit as important to investigate as positive ones (Athens, 2015; Hanson, 2017). This point is illustrated by the findings of Studies Two and Three. Instructors and lecturers identified a variety of barriers, impediments, and frustrations with VR. However, by identifying these, the researcher was able to integrate a range of practical and applied solutions (i.e., using Mobile-VR) to address many of these overarching problems. Addressing this limitation is not a straightforward task, and it cannot be tackled by simply using larger cohorts, bigger classes, or more participants. The nature of applied pedagogical research also means that educators cannot force students to provide module feedback or evaluations that could provide insight into

attitudes towards VR. A more nuanced solution is therefore needed. Future research should not only integrate VR within specific classes, but also within the VLE and management systems used at the institution (e.g., Moodle). Metrics and statistics provided by VLE systems will allow both researchers and educators a comprehensive overview of the amount of interaction with VR material over the course of an entire module (e.g., number of clicks on a VR video, amount of time interacting with VR page). Levels of engagement can then be examined in-light of educational outcomes, exam scores, or other key performance indicators. In addition, VLE forums and discussion boards might provide a degree of qualitative feedback and data. Although this method might not provide the level of detail associated with traditional studies and evaluations, it would provide an overview of VR's influence and effectiveness without students having to participate in the additional tasks associated with study participation. Consequently, data and information relating to an entire cohort can be accounted for, as opposed to only those students who self-select.

As is the case with any extended research project, the ability to adapt and change in response to various intrinsic and extrinsic factors is essential. However, it would be amiss of the researcher not to recognise the constraints and limitations placed upon this project as the result of the COVID-19 pandemic. Many of these were already addressed in the methodology chapter, however, it is worth briefly revisiting these in-light of the findings of this thesis. Namely, this project was generally unable to investigate the attitudes of students towards synchronous integration of VR in a face-to-face context. Indeed, instructors in Studies Two and Three remarked that VR could be applied in smaller classes (e.g., elective fourth-year modules) as a means of supplementing core material. However, the possibility of investigating such application was made impossible due to lockdowns and the restrictions placed on in-person education. Conversely, such restrictions afforded the researcher the opportunity to conduct a completely novel application and investigation of online, asynchronous VR education.

Choosing psychology modules for VR integration was a natural consequence of the researcher's background and knowledge of the subject matter. This provided a convenient gateway to course content and participants, including staff and students.

While limiting the scope to one academic field could hinder the broader applications of this thesis within HE, it is essential to address these limitations directly and explore ways to expand the implications to a broader range of contexts.

Firstly, the qualitative approach of this thesis, often rooted in RTA, was designed to capture the idiosyncratic attitudes of staff and students towards VR. Such a methodological focus on phenomenology must acknowledge that broad generalisability and transferability across domains can be challenging. Indeed, both Braun and Clarke (2021c) and Mays (2000) have already cautioned against making this “quantitative” conceptualisation of generalisability a primary objective in qualitative research. However, it is still important to recognise the extent to which generalisability and transferability can be applied to provide context beyond the limits of this thesis. Indeed, a detailed examination of these issues has already been discussed in Section 3.4.1.1. Ultimately, while contextually grounded in psychology, this research offers insights that extend beyond its immediate domain. Additionally, the applicability of many of the applied suggestions and recommendations, particularly those relating to accessibility, logistics, and integration, are subject-neutral. These practical aspects of VR integration have significance irrespective of the class, module, subject, or desired learning outcomes employed by the facilitator. This cross-disciplinary applicability highlights the complex and nuanced nature of generalisability when considered within the context of qualitative research. Importantly, it requires sensitivity on the part of both the researcher and the reader in carefully extrapolating the relevancy of findings and conclusions to a wide range of contexts and situations.

Secondly, the VR experiences utilised are not exclusively constrained to psychology education. They hold potential as teaching tools across related disciplines as well. For instance, while directly relevant to psychology, an embodied VR experience of mental health conditions could also significantly enhance learning in nursing, social work, counselling, and childcare education. The effectiveness of these experiences in various educational contexts rests on the educators' creativity and adaptability in applying VR tools to meet diverse pedagogical needs (provided that the learning outcomes dictate the decision to employ VR in the first place). Going forward, it is incumbent on researchers

to comprehensively describe the context in which their research is conducted, thus allowing the reader to assess the degree to which these findings are transferable to their own domains. In essence, while this thesis is rooted in a specific context, its findings and recommendations bear implications for broader educational settings. The degree of generalisability, as understood in qualitative research, lies in the potential application and adaptation of these insights across different subject areas within HE.

The final limitation directly relates to one of the key objectives in conducting this research. Namely, this thesis did not want to merely make a theoretical contribution to VR literature. Rather, it was important that this project offered a range of practical and implementable solutions that would help instructors, educators, policy makers, and students more seamlessly integrate technology into the educational sphere. However, qualitative research has seldom been used as a basis for changing policy or affecting decision making (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017). Rather, as Sallee and Flood (2012) found, it is quantitative research that major policy decisions are typically based upon. Consequently, the mainly qualitative approach of this thesis could render it less desirable as a basis for applied change in VR integration. The justification for forgoing a purely quantitative approach has been stated throughout this thesis and does not need to be revisited or reconsidered here. Rather, an essential piece of future work will be to communicate the qualitative findings of this thesis to students, educators, and policy makers in an accessible fashion. The creation of a lay-summary or a practical quick start guide aimed at HE staff would serve as a strong foundation for taking the lessons learned in this thesis and applying them to the classroom. In addition, non-traditional forms of knowledge exchange and research dissemination could serve as a crucial method in increasing awareness of VR's pedagogical utility. For instance, previous research has demonstrated that workshops and interactive seminars that allow users to get "hands-on" with new technology can facilitate an increased receptiveness to integrate such systems (Hennessy et al., 2018; Orozco-Rodríguez et al., 2023). Indeed, these types of proactive demonstration are likely to provide educators with a more informed understanding and perspective of VR compared to traditional scholastic routes of dissemination such as presentations and journal articles.

10.7 Concluding Remarks

As we cast our gaze towards the horizon of VR research within education, the discourse transitions from a binary debate of VR's applicability ("if" it should be used) to a more sophisticated exploration of "how" VR can be most effectively integrated within HE. The commitment of leading technology giants to VR's development sets the stage for its continued evolution and development. However, the trajectory of VR's integration and its sustained impact on education will be shaped by the collective ingenuity of educators, researchers, and policymakers. This necessitates a forward-thinking approach to identifying the optimal VR experiences and integration strategies that align with educational objectives, whether through asynchronous or synchronous modalities, in-person or at a distance.

This thesis not only provides a robust foundation for understanding VR's current and potential impact on education but also charts a course for its future application. It encapsulates VR's unique ability to illuminate complex subjects through immersive experiences, calling for a collaborative effort to harness this technology for educational innovation. This comprehensive investigation into VR's educational utility transcends mere academic exercise, offering concrete methodological advancements and practical recommendations for VR's meaningful integration into classroom practices. Thus, this work not only contributes significantly to the academic discourse on VR in education but also serves as a beacon for future explorations, ensuring VR's role in education is both impactful and enduring.

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12 APPENDICES

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Immersive virtual reality as a pedagogical tool in education: a systematic literature review of quantitative learning outcomes and experimental design

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Abstract The adoption of immersive virtual reality (I-VR) as a pedagogical method in education has challenged the conceptual definition of what constitutes a learning environment. High fidelity graphics and immersive content using head-mounted-displays (HMD) have allowed students to explore complex subjects in a way that traditional teaching methods cannot. Despite this, research focusing on learning outcomes, intervention characteristics, and assessment measures associated with I-VR use has been sparse. To explore this, the current systematic review examined experimental studies published since 2013, where quantitative learning outcomes using HMD based I-VR were compared with less immersive pedagogical methods such as desktop computers and slideshows. A literature search yielded 29 publications that were deemed suitable for inclusion. Included papers were quality assessed using the Medical Education Research Study Quality Instrument (MERSQI). Most studies found a significant advantage of utilising I-VR in education, whilst a smaller number found no significant differences in attainment level regardless of whether I-VR or non-immersive methods were utilised. Only two studies found clear detrimental effects of using I-VR. However, most studies used short interventions, did not examine information retention, and were focused mainly on the teaching of scientific topics such as biology or physics. In addition, the MERSQI

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showed that the methods used to evaluate learning outcomes are often inadequate and this may affect the interpretation of I-VR's utility. The review highlights that a rigorous methodological approach through the identification of appropriate assessment measures, intervention characteristics, and learning outcomes is essential to understanding the potential of I-VR as a pedagogical method.

Keywords Virtual reality · Head mounted displays · Education · Learning · Simulations

Introduction

The increasing financial feasibility of virtual reality (VR) has allowed for educational institutions to incorporate the technology into their teaching. According to research, 96% of universities and 79% of colleges in the UK are now utilising augmented or virtual reality in some capacity (UKAuthority 2019). In addition, the rising power of personal computers and associated hardware has led to a revolution in graphical fidelity, with ever more complex and realistic simulations and virtual worlds (Slater 2018). As Dickey (2005) alludes to, this has both challenged and expanded the very conceptual definition of what is defined as a learning environment. Where once this would have been restricted to classroom teaching or field trips, VR's innate ability to give users a sense of presence and immersion has opened new possibilities in education if implemented appropriately (Häfner et al. 2018).

The use of technology-aided education as a pedagogical method is not a modern phenomenon, and investigations into its utility have been studied for almost half a century. As far back as the 1970s, Ellinger and Frankland (1976) found that the use of early computers to teach economic principles produced comparative learning outcomes with traditional didactic methods such as lectures. However, as Jensen and Konradsen (2018) allude to, it was with the release of the Oculus Rift in 2013 that VR became synonymous with head-mounted-display (HMD) based VR. This had several ramifications. First, HMDs became economically feasible for consumers and educational institutions to acquire *en masse*, due to a significant drop in price (Hodgson et al. 2015). As Olmos et al. (2018) remarks, the economic viability of VR has tackled one of the main entry barriers to adopting the technology. And secondly, academic research into the potential benefits of I-VR in education starts to expand, as well as its applied use in pedagogical settings (Hodgson et al. 2019). One of VR's most important contributions to education is that it has allowed students to repeatedly practice complex and demanding tasks in a safe environment. This is particularly true of procedural tasks such as surgical operations or dental procedures that cannot be carried out for real until a certain level of competency has been achieved (Alaraj et al. 2011; Larsen et al. 2012). Additionally, VR has allowed for students to gain cognitive skills by way of experiential learning, such as exposing them to environments that would be too logistically problematic to visit in reality (Çalışkan 2011). For instance, by using a HMD, Bailenson et al. (2018) were able to expose students to an underwater environment to facilitate learning about climate change. VR has made an important contribution to education in

that it has allowed for students to directly experience environments or situations that are difficult to replicate by using traditional teaching methods such as lectures, slideshows, or 2D videos.

A concise definition of VR's key characteristics is challenging due to the ever-changing nature of the technology. However, Sherman and Craig (2003) proposed that there are a number of constituent elements that must underpin the VR experience, ultimately leading to the life-like perception of the virtual environment. These include the necessity for VR to be immersive, in that the participant's own cognitive faculties produce a sense of being present and involved in the virtual space, often with reduced awareness of what is happening in the real-world around them. Additionally, the virtual space should offer a degree of interactivity, in that the user can manipulate the environment and test variables. This can include interacting with objects, virtual avatars, or even collaborating with other real-life users within the computer-generated space.

Definition of key terms

Due to the multidisciplinary nature of VR research and its pedagogical applications, it is important to define key terms used. VR can broadly be broken down into two main categories: desktop VR (D-VR), and immersive-VR (I-VR). D-VR is typically classified as non-immersive, in that a headset is not used, and the participant will be controlling and manipulating the virtual environment on a computer screen with traditional keyboard and mouse hardware (Lee et al. 2010). On the other hand, I-VR is typically multi-modal in nature by providing a sense of immersion in the environment through 360° visuals by aid of a HMD, auditory stimulation through the use of earphones, and increasingly the proprioception of limbs by way of controllers and tracking (Freina and Ott 2015; Howard-Jones et al. 2015; Murcia-López and Steed 2016). Although there are a range of HMDs on the market, from high-end hardware like the HTC Vive, to viable low-cost options like the Google Cardboard, they all utilise the same core principals of operation (Brown and Green 2016). Typically, a HMD will feature a set of embedded liquid crystal displays (LCD) which will present each eye an image from a slightly different angle. This mimics natural optic function by allowing the wearer to view a stereoscopic image complete with depth perception and a wide field of view. Mobile VR headsets can achieve the same effect using a single display by dividing the screen down the middle and presenting each half to the corresponding eye. Therefore, the current review defines a HMD as a device worn over the head, which provides a stereoscopic computer-generated or 360° video image to the user. This includes tethered (connected to a computer), stand-alone (no computer needed), or mobile VR headsets (mobile/cell phone connected to a HMD).

Previous literature and reviews

There have been a number of systematic reviews that have previously explored the relationship between VR and pedagogical attainment. Lee (1999) reviewed 19 studies from as far back as 1976 and found that 66% of students in simulation groups outperformed those in their respective control groups. However, this review did not

focus exclusively on an educational level or age range, so featured both young kindergarten children, as well as higher education students. As a result, the generalisability of VR's effectiveness as a pedagogical method is difficult to ascertain, with significant differences in age, task difficulty, and applications. Furthermore, all the studies are dated in terms of the technology utilised and feature early D-VR programmes and rudimentary computer simulations. This early technology may be primitive when compared with the high-fidelity graphics and immersive components of contemporary technology. Nevertheless, these early studies do help exemplify that the use of technology in education is not a new concept, and computer-based simulations have long been employed as a way of facilitating learning.

A more recent analysis was undertaken by Merchant et al. (2014), and looked at three specific sub-categories of VR: games, simulations, and virtual worlds. Games give the actor autonomy and freedom to move around the virtual world, testing hypotheses, achieving goals, and eliciting motivation and learning through immersion (Gee 2004). Simulations attempt to recreate a real-world environment that can help facilitate learning by allowing for the testing of variables and resulting outcomes. Finally, virtual worlds can provide an immersive or non-immersive sense of presence in a three-dimensional (3D) world, and the ability to manipulate, interact, or construct objects. Furthermore, virtual worlds can give the opportunity for multiple users to interact with one another within the digital environment (Dickey 2005). The meta-analysis showed that although game-based VR produced the highest learning outcomes, simulations and virtual worlds were also effective at increasing educational attainment. Once again, the limitation of this review is that it did not restrict its analysis to exclusively one domain of education. Although higher education made up the greatest number of studies, research from elementary and middle school were also included in the analysis.

One of the most recent systematic reviews to look exclusively at I-VR through the utilisation of HMDs was carried out by Jensen and Konradson (2018). In their comprehensive search of existing literature published between 2013 and 2017, the review identified 21 quantitative and qualitative papers that focused on both learning outcomes in I-VR, and subjective attitudes and experiences on the part of the user. The review found limited effectiveness of HMD in the acquisition of cognitive, psychomotor, and affective skills when compared with less immersive technologies. However, Jensen and Konradson (2018) did highlight the relatively low quality of studies included as a concern, and this may impede the ability to draw firm conclusions about the educational utility of I-VR.

Rationale for review

There are several fundamental reasons that necessitate an updated assessment of the topic area, such as the increase in relevant published literature, as well as the narrow scope of previous reviews. The last major review looking at I-VR and HMDs as an educational tool was carried out by Jensen and Konradson (2018), with the most recent studies featured in that paper being published in 2016. Since then, there has been a significant increase in relevant published literature, with >70% of the

papers included in the current review being published since 2017, and therefore not included in the previous systematic review. Additionally, unlike previous reviews, the current examination of I-VR's pedagogical utility focuses exclusively on studies where I-VR is directly compared to a less immersive method of learning. As a result, the current paper is able to highlight not only whether I-VR is an effective medium, but also whether it is more effective when compared to alternative methods. Additionally, no other systematic review looking at I-VR and HMDs has had a particular focus on the experimental design, assessment measures, and intervention characteristics of the included studies. The review also addresses the underlying methodology of the included studies, to offer an understanding of how I-VR is being employed in experimental literature. Based upon the findings of previous studies as well as areas yet to be sufficiently explored, this paper has a number of core research questions:

- To assess the subject area, discipline, and learning domain that I-VR has been employed in.
- Understand where I-VR confers an educational benefit in terms of quantitative learning outcomes over non-immersive and traditional teaching methods.
- To examine the experimental design of studies, focusing on how learning outcomes are assessed, and how the I-VR intervention is delivered.
- To inform future experimental and applied practice in the field of pedagogical I-VR application.

Methodology

Search strategy

The current systematic review included peer-reviewed journal articles and conference proceedings that passed all the inclusion criteria detailed. An initial scoping review identified seven databases that could be utilised in a comprehensive literature review, as well as associated keywords and search terms. These included Web of Science (Core Collection), Science Direct, Sage, IEEE Xplore, EBSCO, Taylor & Francis, and Google Scholar. These databases encompass a mixture of general, social science, and technological literature.

Each of the seven databases was searched using a series of keywords based on the following Boolean logic string:

("Virtual Reality" OR "Virtual-Reality" OR "Immersive Virtual Reality" OR "Head Mounted Display" OR "Immersive Simulation") AND (Education OR Training OR Learning OR Teaching)

Due to the scope and parameters of the research objectives, only peer-reviewed literature published between January 2013 and December 2018 was included in the final review. Early access articles due to be published in 2019 were also included if these were found using the database searches. Date criteria was based upon an initial scoping review that found a substantial growth in relevant I-VR literature from 2013 onwards. A major contributing factor was the release of the Oculus Rift

Development Kit 1 (DK-1) in early 2013, which is regarded as one of the first economically viable and high quality HMDs that could be used both within educational institutions, and at home (Lyne 2013).

The literature search across the databases yielded more than 12,000 references from a variety of sources. After the removal of duplicate records, 9,359 unique references were included for the title and abstract screening stage of the review.

Selection and screening

The open and general nature of the search string used led to a large number of references being returned for screening. As Jensen and Konradsen (2018) already alluded to in the last major review, VR research transcends various academic disciplines. The result is a lack of a clear taxonomy of definitions and terms. This means a wide net must be cast to ensure comprehensive capture of relevant material. This review defined I-VR as either a completely computer-generated environment, or the viewing of captured 360° video through the use of a HMD. Studies that utilised surgical or dental simulators and trainers such as the da Vinci Surgical System, were excluded as these represent a separate domain of both technological and pedagogical application. For example, surgical simulation based VR typically combines computer-generated visuals with simulated surgical tools, haptic feedback, and robotic components (Li et al. 2017). This type of technology would therefore not be applicable for general pedagogical application. Additionally, references were excluded if they: (1) focused on using I-VR as a rehabilitation or therapeutic tool; (2) were not in English; or (3) where the full-text was not available.

After title and abstract screening was performed, 197 references remained to be included in the full-text review. Each reference had to pass an inclusion flowchart based on each of the following criteria:

1. The population being sampled was from a high school, further or higher education establishment, or was an adult education student.
2. Population sampled did not have a developmental or neurological condition, nor could VR be used as a rehabilitation tool.
3. Paper described an experimental or quasi-experimental trial with at least one control group.
4. At least one group had to have undergone an educational HMD I-VR experience, and was compared with another group who underwent a non-immersive or traditional pedagogical method of education (e.g. Desktop VR, PowerPoint, traditional lecture).
5. A quantitative and objective learning outcome such as tests scores, completion time, or knowledge retention was used to assess effectiveness.

After full-text screening, 29 references passed all stages and were included in the systematic review. See Fig. 1 for a summary of the selection process by stage.

Inter-rater reliability checks were conducted at the title and abstract screening stage to assess the agreement of included studies. There were four individual

evaluators that assessed the suitability of each reference based upon the inclusion criteria, which yielded an average agreement of 96%. Where any disagreement existed, the paper was discussed among all assessors until a unanimous decision was reached as to its suitability.

Quality assessment tool

To assess the quality of the studies, the *Medical Education Research Study Quality Instrument* (MERSQI) was used (Reed et al. 2007). Although this tool was primarily designed to examine the quality of studies in the field of medical education, it is in practice subject neutral. As the MERSQI assesses not only the quality of experimental design and outcomes measures, but also the assessment instrumentation used, it was viewed as a suitable and comprehensive tool for quality appraisal. In addition, the same instrument was used in a previously peer-reviewed systematic review examining VR, by Jensen and Konradsen (2018).

The MERSQI tool covers six quality assessment domains. These include: study design, sampling, type of data, validity of evaluation instrument, data analysis, and outcomes. Each domain is scored out of three, with a maximum overall score of 18. Unlike Jensen and Konradsen (2018), the current review gave full points in the study design category for experimental trials with participant randomisation, as well as appropriate pre-intervention measures. This decision was made as true randomised control trials featuring random sampling is unrealistic in I-VR pedagogical research, as the participant sample can only be drawn from an educational establishment.

Fig. 1 Stage-by-stage selection process

Results

Quality of studies

The first domain examined for quality was the study design of the papers. There were 20 studies (69%) that featured an experimental design with stated random allocation of participants between control and experimental group. The review featured nine studies (31%) that were quasi-experimental in nature, meaning there was non-random allocation of participants into experimental groups.

Only one of the studies featured participants being studied at more than one institution, with most of the studies included ($N=28$) only sampling from a single establishment. All studies produced response rates of over 75%, which means they were given the highest score in that domain.

In terms of the type of data presented, all included studies featured an objective measure of learning outcomes such as test scores or completion times. No studies used self-assessment on the part of the participant to gauge learning outcomes.

The most pronounced weakness of the studies included in the review was the validity of the evaluation instrument used to assess learning outcomes. This domain pertained to the physical assessment instrumentation such as the quiz, test, or questionnaire that was given to the participant. Only six of the included studies (21%) reported the internal structure sufficiently through dimensionality, measurement invariance, or reliability using the criteria set down by Rios and Wells (2014). In addition, only 10 studies (34%) stated how the content was validated, with the majority ($N=19$) not reporting this information. Only three studies (Kozhevnikov et al. 2013; Makransky et al. 2017; Molina-Carmona et al. 2018) appropriately outlined both the internal structure and validity of evaluation content. The majority of studies ($N=16$) did not report either item.

Of the 29 studies in the current review, 26 scored full marks on the data analysis domain with both an appropriate and sufficiently complex analysis and reporting of the findings. Three studies scored lower than this due to reporting descriptive statistics only (Angulo and de Velasco 2013; Babu et al. 2018; Ray and Deb 2016).

Overall, the average quality score of a study in this systematic review was 12.7 with a range of 10.5–14.5 ($SD=1.0$). This was 1.8 points higher than the review carried out by Jensen and Konradson (2018), which could in part be due to differences in study design criteria which was previously outlined. A full summary of the MERSQI scores for each study can be found in Table 2 in the Appendix.

Subject areas and learning domains

Table 1 provides a summary of all 29 articles that were included in the review. Studies were first categorised by the population that was sampled. Most I-VR studies took place in a higher education establishment (college or university) using undergraduate or postgraduate students ($N=25$). A smaller number of

Table 1 Details of included studies including domain, variables, and summary of main findings

Study (year)	Learning domain	HMD(s) used	Comparison variable(s)	Findings
Harrington et al. (2018)	Cognitive	Samsung Gear VR	2D video	No difference in information retention between both mediums
Yoganathan et al. (2018)	Procedural	Unspecified	2D video Face-to-face training	I-VR produced higher scores in knot tying skills. No difference in completion time
Makransky et al. (2017)	Cognitive	Samsung Gear VR	Desktop VR	Knowledge test score worse when using I-VR. No difference in transfer score
Greenwald et al. (2018)	Cognitive	HTC Vive	2D system	Study found no difference in test scores or number of moves between both mediums. One session was slower in I-VR compared to 2D
Lamb et al. (2018)	Cognitive	HTC Vive	Lecture Serious game Hands-on activity	I-VR produced a better test score than a traditional lecture. No difference between I-VR and educational game or hands-on activity
Webster (2016)	Cognitive	Sony HMZ	Lecture	I-VR produced significantly higher test scores than a lecture
Smith et al. (2018)	Cognitive and procedural	Oculus Rift	Desktop VR Written instructions	No difference in test score or completion time between I-VR and other methods
Ostrander et al. (2018)	Cognitive	HTC Vive	Instructor lesson	In 6 out of 7 lessons, I-VR was no more effective than a lesson delivered by an instructor
Angulo and de Velasco (2013)	Cognitive	Other	3D physical model	Higher appraisal of architectural spaces designed with I-VR than physical model
Stepan et al. (2017)	Cognitive	Oculus Rift	Online textbook	No difference in test score at pre-test, post-test, or 8-week follow-up
Sankaranarayanan et al. (2018)	Cognitive and procedural	Oculus Rift	No I-VR (written material only)	Using I-VR produced higher learning gains in procedural activity and transfer test. There was no difference in MCQ test scores
Fogarty et al. (2017)	Cognitive	Oculus Rift	No I-VR (lectures only)	At pre-intervention the participants performed significantly poorer than the control group. At post-intervention, this difference disappeared showing improvement in cognitive knowledge

Table 1 (continued)

Study (year)	Learning domain	HMD(s) used	Comparison variable(s)	Findings
Rupp et al. (2019)	Cognitive	Google Cardboard Oculus CV1 Oculus DK2	2D video (on phone screen)	Significantly better learning outcomes were demonstrated on test scores when I-VR was used compared to non-immersive condition
Bharathi and Tucker (2015)	Procedural	Oculus Rift	Desktop VR	Functional analysis task was carried out significantly faster in I-VR condition compared to D-VR
Johnston et al. (2018)	Cognitive	Oculus Rift	No I-VR (lectures only)	Those participants who underwent the I-VR experience performed better on final exam question than those who did not use I-VR
Allcoat and von Mühlhelen (2018)	Cognitive	HTC Vive	Textbook 2D Video	Those who used I-VR performed better on a test than 2D control group. The I-VR group performed better on <i>remembering</i> questions than those in the textbook group, but no difference in <i>understanding</i> questions
Kozhevnikov et al. (2013)	Cognitive	nVisor SX60	Desktop VR	Performance in understanding relative motion concepts were significantly higher when participants used I-VR compared to D-VR
Parong and Mayer (2018)	Cognitive	HTC Vive	Slideshow	I-VR was demonstrated to cause significantly poorer results on a cell biology test than those who learned using a traditional PowerPoint
Olmos-Raya et al. (2018)	Cognitive	Samsung Gear VR	Desktop VR	Those participants who learned about geography using I-VR demonstrated significantly higher learning gains and medium term retention than those who used D-VR
Akbulut et al. (2018)	Cognitive	Mobile VR	Lecturers and lab sessions	Test scores were significantly higher in those who used the I-VR platform compared to those who learned through lectures and lab sessions alone
Ray and Deb (2016)	Cognitive	Google Cardboard	Slideshow Lectures	Over the course of 16 sessions, those who learned computer science through I-VR tended to score higher on test scores than those who did not

Table 1 (continued)

Study (year)	Learning domain	HMD(s) used	Comparison variable(s)	Findings
Moro et al. (2017)	Cognitive	Oculus Rift	Desktop VR	I-VR and D-VR were shown to be equally effective modes of learning on an anatomy skill test
Maresky et al. (2019)	Cognitive	Oculus Rift	Independent study	Those who used I-VR to learn about cardiac anatomy scored significantly higher on post-test than a control group who used independent study
Madden et al. (2018)	Cognitive	Oculus Rift	Desktop VR Ball-and-stick method	I-VR was no more effective than D-VR or a traditional model demonstration when learning about astronomy
Liou and Chang (2018)	Cognitive	HTC Vive	Traditional didactic teaching	I-VR was shown to produce significantly higher levels of learning in anatomy and chemistry tests than those who did not use the technology
Molina-Carmona et al. (2018)	Cognitive	Mobile VR	Desktop VR	I-VR was shown to improve the spatial ability of those participants who used it, compared to those that used D-VR
Babu et al. (2018)	Cognitive	HTC Vive	Desktop VR (tablet based)	Although I-VR and D-VR produced similar post-test scores, I-VR was shown to improve retention of knowledge learned
Alhalabi (2016)	Cognitive	Oculus Rift	Traditional methods	I-VR was shown to produce significantly higher attainment in engineering content than traditional educational methods. Furthermore, HMD based I-VR produced better results than a CAVE based system
Gutiérrez-Maldonado et al. (2015)	Affective and cognitive	Oculus Rift DK1	Stereoscopic desktop VR	Both immersive and non-immersive mediums produced similar results in psychiatric interview training

studies used high school pupils ($N=2$), or adult education students ($N=2$) such as those in vocational or work-based programmes.

Each of the included studies were then examined for the topic and subject area they pertained to. This was based upon the nature of the VR experience, participant pool, and intervention. In total, six main subject areas were identified. This included: medicine ($N=4$), science (biology, chemistry, and physics) ($N=13$), social science (human geography) ($N=1$), computer science ($N=2$), engineering and architecture ($N=7$), and safety education ($N=1$). One of the included studies (Molina-Carmona et al. 2018) did not neatly fit into one of the pre-defined categories as it utilised I-VR to teach abstract spatial concept abilities to multimedia engineering students. It was therefore categorised as ‘other’. Figure 2 shows the percentage of papers included by subject area.

In addition to the subject area, the learning outcomes were also categorised into three specific domains based upon the findings of previous systematic reviews, as well as the taxonomy of learning developed by Bloom et al. (1956). The first was *cognitive* which related to studies that intended to teach specific declarative information or knowledge. The second was *procedural* which intends to teach the user how to perform a specific task or learn psychomotor skills that pertain to a certain activity. Finally, the third learning outcome was *affective* skills which can be defined as a growth in areas relating to emotion and attitude. Most of the included studies ($N=24$) concentrated on the cognitive domain, with two studies focusing on purely procedural and psychomotor skills. The remaining studies were a blend of two domains with Sankaranarayanan et al. (2018) and Smith et al. (2018) examining both cognitive and procedural skills, and Gutiérrez-Maldonado et al. (2015) utilising both cognitive knowledge and affective awareness in psychiatric diagnosis training. Figure 3 shows the percentage of studies included by learning domain.

Fig. 2 Percentage of papers per subject area

Studies by learning domain

Fig. 3 Percentage of papers per learning domain

Experimental design

Outcome measures

A thorough understanding of the role of I-VR as a pedagogical practice can only be fully appreciated when consideration is given to the assessment instrumentation and outcome measures used to assess its utility. As previously mentioned, when analysing the quality of the included studies, it was the evaluation instrumentation itself that was shown to have the most pronounced weakness.

To assess the evaluation instruments being employed, the measures were broken down into two broad domains: outcome measures, and assessment instrumentation. Outcome measures can broadly be defined as how learning outcomes were quantified (e.g. by comparing test scores). Assessment instrumentation pertains to the evaluative instrument itself that is used to measure the learning outcomes (e.g. multiple-choice questionnaire, exam style questions). Twenty-seven of the included studies (93%) used test scores to assess learning outcomes, with the majority using this as their sole method. There were four studies that used completion time as a metric of learning outcome, although only one study (Bharathi and Tucker 2015) used this method exclusively. There was one study (Sankaranarayanan et al. 2018) that used the correct order of operation in a procedural task as one of its main outcome measures. There were three papers that utilised other outcome measures that could not be easily categorised. For instance Greenwald et al. (2018) used counting the number of moves needed to complete a task, Webster (2016) used the performance on a virtual jigsaw puzzle, and Angulo and de Velasco (2013) used a mixture of scores and evaluations of an architectural space.

Assessment instrumentation

In terms of the direct assessment instrumentation used to examine outcome measures, there was a heavy reliance on the multiple-choice questionnaire (MCQ). There were eighteen (62%) studies that utilised this method of assessment, with the majority of those using it as their sole evaluation instrument. Only five studies used extended answer questions (long or short form) to probe for a deeper understanding of the educational content, which was usually done in combination MCQs. The studies that included the teaching of procedural skills used marking criteria and checklists to assess whether the correct order was being followed. For instance Yoganathan et al. (2018) had an expert assessor use marking criteria to assess the knot tying skills of students. Similarly, Smith et al. (2018) had evaluators observe students with a decontamination checklist which evaluated performance based upon certain key tasks that were performed.

There were a smaller number of studies that used more novel instrumentation and methods for evaluation, such as the utilisation of labelling and identifying parts of a 3D model (e.g. Babu et al. 2018; Moro et al. 2017; Stepan et al. 2017). Fogarty et al. (2017) probed spatial and conceptual understanding in their assessment instrument by having participants draw shapes based on their understanding of structural engineering principles. Additionally, Alhalabi (2016) used quizzes on both mathematical knowledge, and the appropriate understanding of graphics and charts as an assessment measure for engineering students.

There were three studies (Liou and Chang 2018; Madden et al. 2018; Ray and Deb 2016) where the nature of the assessment instrumentation could not be definitively ascertained from the description.

The majority of studies (62%) utilised the pretest–posttest design by comparing the test scores pre-intervention with those after the I-VR experience. The remainder of the studies tended to assess post-intervention scores only, usually by comparing the difference in learning outcome between I-VR and one or more control group. Less conventional means of post-intervention comparison was sometimes utilised, such as Johnston et al. (2018) comparing the average score on a specific exam question that pertained to an I-VR experience that some student did or did not undertake.

There were four studies that examined the short to medium term retention rate of information and learning through follow-up assessment. This ranged from as soon as 1 day after the initial I-VR experience (Babu et al. 2018), through to 6 months post-intervention (Smith et al. 2018). Olmos-Raya et al. (2018) and Stepan et al. (2017) had follow-up assessments at 1-week and 8-weeks, respectively.

Intervention characteristics

In addition to having appropriate assessment measures, it is also important to examine the nature of the I-VR intervention itself. The most popular HMDs used were the Oculus ($N=13$) and HTC Vive ($N=7$). There were seven studies that used a form of mobile VR headset such as the Google Cardboard or Samsung Gear VR. In one study (Yoganathan et al. 2018) the exact HMD system used could not be

definitively ascertained. Figure 4 provides a breakdown of the HMDs used in the included studies.

Most studies (72%) featured only a single intervention with the I-VR experience, meaning that the student was exposed to the technology just once. There were a few exceptions to this, with Ostrander et al. (2018) having seven individual I-VR experiences in their manufacturing lesson, as well as Ray and Deb (2016) utilising smartphone based I-VR over the course of 16 sessions. Other studies allowed a greater degree of freedom in the number of interventions or times that a student could use I-VR. This was usually a result of time being dedicated to the technology through scheduled classes or lab times (e.g. Akbulut et al. 2018; Alhalabi 2016; Molina-Carmona et al. 2018). Despite this, the I-VR intervention was usually a single and isolated one.

As well as most of the studies featuring a single intervention, the exposure duration was also typically short, ranging from 6 to 30 mins. Generally, the exception to this was when the I-VR exposure lasted as long as it took the participant to complete a specific task, assessment, or procedure within the immersive environment (e.g. Babu et al. 2018; Bharathi and Tucker 2015; Greenwald et al. 2018; Sankaranarayanan et al. 2018). Molina-Carmona et al. (2018) supplemented the limited intervention duration by allowing participants to take the HMD away with them, so they could access the educational content for 2 weeks outside the classroom. However, just as with the number of interventions, exposure duration tended to be short, lasting on average 13 mins for those I-VR experiences that had a set time limit.

Most of the studies (62%) utilised I-VR as the sole method of learning, and did not combine the technology with additional pedagogical practices or materials to encourage learning. Only a limited number of studies (38%) supplemented the I-VR lesson by providing additional aids that were designed to complement the educational experience. For example, Smith et al. (2018) and Stepan et al. (2017) both had participants use web-based modules and textbooks in addition to the I-VR experience before testing them on learning outcomes. A number of the included studies

Fig. 4 HMDs used in studies

also utilised lecture based instruction or scheduled class time to operate in tandem with the I-VR environments (e.g. Akbulut et al. 2018; Fogarty et al. 2017; Johnston et al. 2018; Ray and Deb 2016; Sankaranarayanan et al. 2018).

Theoretical frameworks

A fundamental component of any educational tool or activity is to ground its use in learning theory or educational paradigms. Learning theories can broadly be broken down and defined by proposals regarding how student imbibe, process, and retain the information that they have learned (Pritchard 2017; Schunk 2011). When applied to educational I-VR, these theories should provide a pedagogical framework and foundation as how best to design interventions. Papers were examined for explicit statements regarding the theoretical basis for the study. Those papers that only mentioned theoretical approaches as part of the introduction or literature review were not deemed to have explicitly stated them. The majority of studies ($N=24$) made no mention of a theoretical approach underpinning the intervention. There were two studies that applied a *generative learning* framework (Makransky et al. 2017; Parong and Mayer 2018). This can be defined as an approach where the learner will actively integrate new knowledge with information that is already stored in the brain (Osborne and Wittrock 1985). Webster (2016) employed Mayer's (2009, 2014) *Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning* (CTML). CTML proposes a dual channel approach where visual and auditory information is actively processed, organised, and then stored in the brain. This is contingent on neither channel (visual or auditory) becoming overloaded with information. Smith et al. (2018) used the *NLN Jeffries Simulation Theory* as their theoretical basis. This theory, most commonly employed in nursing education, is where students learn information as part of a simulated experience (Jeffries et al. 2015). For the teaching of vocational skills, Babu et al. (2018) stated that their approach aligned with *situated learning*. Situated learning employs a constructivist approach in that students learn professional skills by actively participating in the experience (Huang et al. 2010).

Learning outcomes

For I-VR to gain wide-spread acceptance as a reliable pedagogical method, it must be shown to confer a tangible benefit in terms of learning outcomes over less immersive or traditional teaching methods.

Cognitive studies

There were twenty-four included studies that fell into the *cognitive* domain and aimed to teach specific declarative information or knowledge through the I-VR environment. The current review found that most studies demonstrated benefits in terms of learning outcomes when using I-VR compared to less immersive methods of learning. A smaller number of studies found no significant advantage regardless

of the pedagogical method being utilised. The results of these cognitive studies have been broken down by subject area.

Science based cognitive studies

The review found that cognitive learning activities requiring a high degree of visualisation and experiential understanding may be best facilitated using immersive technologies. For instance, both Liou and Chang (2018) and Maresky et al. (2019) found that anatomical learning facilitated by complex 3D visualisations of the human body were more conducive to learning in I-VR compared to traditional learning or independent study. Similarly Lamb et al. (2018) used a virtual environment that allowed for the manipulation and movement of strands of DNA, which produced better learning outcomes in content tests than a lecture or a serious educational game. Greater attention and engagement with the I-VR environment as measured with infrared spectroscopy was one of the possible explanations given for the effectiveness of the technology. In a study by Johnston et al. (2018), participants volunteered to take part in a cell biology experience either because they were engaged with the subject matter itself, or wanted supplementary instruction. Johnston et al. (2018) compared the exam scores of those students who volunteered to take part with those who did not. The study found that participants who underwent the I-VR experience scored 5% higher on the related exam question compared to the rest of the assessment. Those who did not undergo the cell biology I-VR experienced scored on average 35% worse on the same question.

The increase in graphical fidelity afforded by I-VR has allowed not only for the creation of complex computer-generated environments, but also the viewing of high resolution 360° video. In one such study, Rupp et al. (2019) had participants watch a six minute 360° video about the International Space Station with either a HMD which created a sense of immersion and presence, or on a mobile screen. The research found that those participants in the HMD condition scored significantly higher in a learning outcome test (MCQ) than those who watched the video in the non-immersive condition.

Although I-VR has been shown to confer a benefit in science education, there is evidence to suggest that not all learning objectives can be learned equally well. For instance, in task devised by Allcoat and von Mühlennen (2018), the researchers found that I-VR conferred a benefit over video or textbook learning when questions required *remembering*, but not ones pertaining to *understanding* of the material. The authors suggest that unfamiliarity and the novelty of the I-VR environments could have contributed to the lack of an obvious benefit in the latter domain. Another study that examined specific question types to understand I-VR's effectiveness was undertaken by Kozhevnikov et al. (2013). In this study, participants learned more conceptual and abstract relative motion concepts using either I-VR or D-VR. The study demonstrated that those in the I-VR condition performed significantly better in the two-dimensional problems than their D-VR counterparts, although there was no significant difference between groups in problems featuring only one spatial dimension.

There were several studies in the domain of science that showed no obvious benefits to using I-VR over traditional pedagogical methods. Two studies (Greenwald

et al. 2018; Moro et al. 2017) compared science learning in I-VR with desktop based VR and 2D videos. Results showed no clear benefit of I-VR based instruction when comparing the difference and significance of learning outcomes between mediums. Similarly, Stepan et al. (2017) found that I-VR was no more effective than online textbooks for the teaching of neuroanatomy. Interestingly, the same study found no difference in information retention rates when the participants were reassessed 8-weeks later. Madden et al. (2018) used I-VR, D-VR, and the traditional ball and stick method to teach astronomy principles pertaining to phases of the moon. The study found that I-VR and D-VR produced comparable test score results, with no significant differences in attainment. However, the authors commented on the encouraging finding that despite being a novel technology to most participants, I-VR still facilitated comparable learning outcomes to more traditional methods.

Despite the majority of studies demonstrating that I-VR learning is more effective or at least on par with traditional pedagogical methods, some studies have shown a detrimental effect of I-VR. Makransky et al. (2017) used a combination of assessment and EEG to find that an I-VR lab simulation produced significantly poorer test scores than a non-immersive alternative. Similarly, during another science experiment, Parong and Mayer (2018) found that students who used I-VR during a biology lesson scored significantly poorer than those who learned using a PowerPoint. Both of these studies cited Mayer's (2009, 2014) Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning as a possible explanation for the poorer performance for I-VR. The researchers postulate that the high-fidelity graphics and animations could have significantly increased cognitive load, which would have detracted from the learning task at hand. It was therefore proposed that a less immersive, yet well designed PowerPoint presentation would facilitate better learning outcomes than a graphically rich I-VR experience.

Engineering and architectural based cognitive studies

I-VR was effective in engineering and architectural education as a tool to visualise key concepts within the discipline. For example, Fogarty et al. (2017) allowed students to volunteer for an I-VR experience who struggled with the comprehension of spatial arrangements in structural engineering. Before the intervention, those students who volunteered to take part scored significantly poorer than their non-intervention counterparts. At post-test, not only did those who underwent the I-VR experience score significantly higher than they did at pre-test, but they also eliminated the significant difference with the non-intervention group. This would suggest that I-VR could serve an important function in supplementing or assisting learning in those students who are struggling to grasp complex problems relating to their discipline. Interestingly, Angulo and de Velasco (2013) used many of these same spatial and visualisation principles in a more applied setting. Their study split students into groups who were tasked with designing an architectural space (a health clinic waiting room), either with the assistance of an I-VR design tool (experimental group) or a physical model (control group). The study found the space that gained the most positive affect was designed by the I-VR group.

Webster (2016) created a graphically rich immersive environment which combined active and passive media with elements of gamification and interactivity to teach corrosion concepts to US army personnel. The study found that although both the I-VR environment and a traditional lecture were effective pedagogical methods for teaching these principles, it was the I-VR condition that produced the highest gain in knowledge acquisition.

There was also some evidence to suggest that I-VR interventions could assist in short-term retention of information in engineering related activities. Babu et al. (2018) found that although participants performed similarly in a mechanical labelling task using either I-VR or a tablet computer immediately post-intervention, the I-VR group had better retention of knowledge when the test was re-administered 1 day later. Furthermore, those participants in the I-VR group were also less likely to wrongly recall information compared to the non-immersive group on the retention test.

Interestingly, Ostrander et al. (2018) examined cognitive learning outcomes over seven separate manufacturing tasks utilising I-VR in one group, and a traditional class-based environment in the other. The study found that in six out of seven tasks, I-VR was no more effective than a traditional class where students could interact with the instructor or the physical models that they were accustomed to.

Medical based cognitive studies

Although papers featuring surgical simulators did not form part of this review, there were several applications of I-VR in the field of general medical education. Harrington et al. (2018) had medical students watch a ten-minute 360° video with slides containing surgical information superimposed over it. This was viewed either on a large television screen, or through a Gear VR headset. The study found no significant differences in knowledge retention scores between those who viewed the information through a HMD, or a traditional television screen. Despite not showing a distinct advantage in cognitive learning outcomes, the authors did suggest that the 360° surgical experience may facilitate a better understanding of how teamwork and interaction takes place within an operating theatre. This type of learning may be more difficult to measure using assessment instrumentation such as the MCQ, but nevertheless it could be that the experiential nature of I-VR may facilitate an understanding of interactions and communications. Smith et al. (2018) used either I-VR or D-VR on a computer to teach students about decontamination protocols. The research found that I-VR was no more effective than D-VR in a MCQ immediately post-intervention, or at 6-weeks follow-up.

Computer science based cognitive studies

Two studies demonstrated a significant advantage in using I-VR to teach computer science information. For instance, Akbulut et al. (2018) found that students who underwent an I-VR experience that focused on software engineering principles scored 12% higher than students who did not undergo I-VR learning. Interestingly, in a study by Ray and Deb (2016) that ran over 16 sessions on microcontrollers in

computing, the I-VR group performance lagged behind that of the control group who used slideshows for the first four sessions. It was only on session number five that the I-VR group outperformed the control group, and this performance enhancement remained relatively stable in the majority of the remaining 11 sessions. In effect, it took the I-VR group some time to *catch up* with the control group, but once they did, they tended to outperform them in the remaining lessons. The authors propose that this may have been due to the novelty of the I-VR equipment which participants took time to become comfortable and competent with.

Other cognitive studies

I-VR was also used by Molina-Carmona et al. (2018) as a means of spatial ability acquisition and visualisation. The study showed that learning outcomes as assessed by a spatial visualisation test were higher among those who undertook the task in an immersive, compared to a non-immersive environment. There was only one study in the field of social science that used I-VR to teach cognitive information. Olmos-Raya et al. (2018) used either I-VR or a tablet-based system to teach high school students about human geography. The research found that I-VR produced higher learning gains on a MCQ than the tablet-based system. Further, those who used I-VR performed better than the non-immersive group on a knowledge retention quiz when administered 1-week later.

Procedural studies

Three of the four studies that attempted to utilise I-VR as a means of teaching procedural skills showed a distinct advantage over less immersive methods. Bharathi and Tucker (2015) found that engineering students were faster in assembling a household appliance in a virtual functional analysis activity in I-VR compared to D-VR. Yoganathan et al. (2018) also found that medical students were more accurate in knot tying practice when using I-VR as a training tool as opposed to a control group who used a standard video. Medical and surgical residents were also studied by Sankaranarayanan et al. (2018) who used I-VR as a teaching tool for emergency fire response in an operating theatre environment. This study found that 70% of those who utilised the I-VR training were able to perform the correct procedure in the correct order. This was 50% higher than the control group who were exposed to a presentation and reading material only and did not experience I-VR.

One of the studies found no significant advantage to using I-VR as a learning tool. Smith et al. (2018) split nursing students into an I-VR group, a D-VR group (desktop PC based), or a written instruction group to learn about appropriate protocols for decontamination. The study found that there was no significant difference in performance between the groups as measured by a decontamination checklist, or the time taken to complete the task. Furthermore, reassessment 6 months later showed that I-VR conferred no advantage in procedural knowledge retention (accuracy and speed) compared to less immersive methods.

Affective studies

Only one of the studies attempted to use I-VR as a pedagogical tool to teach applied behavioural and affective skills. Gutiérrez-Maldonado et al. (2015) used I-VR in the field of diagnostic psychiatry in an attempt to improve interview skills when assessing patients for an eating disorder. Participants were exposed to a series of virtual patient avatars in either the I-VR condition, or a D-VR condition using stereoscopic glasses. Analysis showed that both conditions were equally as effective, and no significant differences were shown in the acquisition of skills between the two groups. Nevertheless, this was a novel study as it traversed the boundaries between traditional cognitive skill acquisition and applied behavioural and affective change.

Discussion and implications

The purpose of this review was to investigate I-VR's effectiveness as a pedagogical method in education, as well as examining the experimental design and characteristics of the included studies. In particular, the review found that the utilisation of I-VR is typically restricted to a small number of subject areas such as science and engineering. Furthermore, a heavy reliance has been placed on the MCQ and test score measures to assess learning outcomes. In addition, I-VR interventions were typically short and isolated, and were not complemented with additional or supplementary learning material. Despite this, most studies did find a significant advantage of using I-VR over less immersive methods of learning. This was the case particularly when the subject area was highly abstract or conceptual, or focused on procedural skills or tasks.

Is the utilisation of I-VR within education restrictive?

The findings of the review suggest a relatively homogenous application of I-VR in terms of both the subject areas represented, as well as the learning domain being taught. Almost 70% of the studies were from the field of science or engineering, with other subjects being marginally represented. It is worth noting, however, that although medical disciplines made up a small proportion of the studies included (14%), this was because most medical applications of I-VR feature surgical simulators and therefore were not part of the current review's inclusion criteria. Most studies utilised I-VR as a way of teaching cognitive skills, with only a handful examining the procedural or affective applications.

The findings of the review raise several issues when trying to assess the general effectiveness of I-VR in education. Similar to the findings of others (e.g. Jensen and Konradsen 2018; Radianti et al. 2020), the arts, humanities, and social sciences were underrepresented in the current review. This makes generalisable conclusions as to the cognitive benefit of the technology in these subjects challenging. One major reason for this under representation may be the lack of I-VR learning content, experiences, and teaching tools. Jensen and Konradsen (2018) highlighted that

instructors are restricted to the material published and produced by VR designers, and this may not necessarily meet the individual needs of the teacher, or the learning outcome trying to be achieved. The skillset needed to produce and create wholly virtual environments that can be rendered and displayed in a HMD is still demanding, despite the release of affordable VR creation suites. Therefore, the bespoke I-VR experiences required to teach social science lessons (or indeed any subject) is completely dependent on an appropriate I-VR tool already existing or having the technical proficiency to create one. A potential solution to the lack of bespoke material could be the examination of the pedagogical effectiveness of HMD 360° video in the classroom, as opposed to computer-generated environments. This content is comparatively easier to create using appropriate video equipment and can be tailored to the individual needs of the instructor or student group. Widespread research that examines the potential of I-VR in a multitude of diverse disciplines and learning domains will continue to be constrained by the availability of the requisite material. That is until such a time where bespoke and individually tailored I-VR experiences become more accessible.

Implications of outcome measures and assessment instrumentation

One of the most striking characteristics of the assessment instrumentation used in the studies was the reliance on the MCQ to assess learning outcomes. Although there have been many debates on the respective advantages and disadvantages of utilising the MCQ, it has generally been considered that it is most appropriate for testing large amounts of surface knowledge over the course of an entire module or syllabus (Excell 2000). As O'Dwyer (2012) points out, the assessment instrumentation encourages comprehensive learning of the entirety of the taught material, as opposed to just specific components. However, since most of the studies featured single interventions of between 6 and 30 mins, doubts are cast on whether MCQs are the most appropriate way to assess learning. Since the MCQ was most commonly administered immediately after the I-VR experience, much of the information may still be stored in short-term memory, and this may not give an accurate reflection of more comprehensive learning or long-term retention.

A second disadvantage associated with the heavy reliance on the MCQ is the limited breadth of knowledge that can be assessed. In Jensen and Konradsen's (2018) systematic review, the researchers found that none of the cognitive studies went beyond teaching *lower level* cognitive skills as defined by Bloom's taxonomy (Bloom et al. 1956). Similar results were found in the current review, with most studies requiring only a knowledge of previously learned material to successfully achieve the desired learning goal. Previous research on pedagogical assessment material (e.g. Ozuru et al. 2013) has suggested that the MCQ cannot assess higher levels of cognitive understanding or conceptual knowledge. Therefore, it may not only be the nature of the I-VR experience itself that restricts the learning of higher level cognitive skills, but also the restrictive nature of the assessment instrumentation that may impede an appropriate demonstration of learning outcomes. The utilisation of short or long form answers could be able to provide a more appropriate

measure of the depth of learning achieved, giving the student an opportunity to demonstrate their conceptual knowledge of a given subject. Furthermore, I-VR research could benefit by expanding the very definition of what constitutes a learning outcome. This could be achieved by not relying exclusively on test score comparisons, but rather examine how I-VR could be used to foster deeper conceptual understanding through experiential learning and subsequent classroom discussions with peers or instructors.

Implication of intervention characteristics for learning outcomes

The current review examined how I-VR is being utilised in experimental and applied settings, and the implications this has for assessing its pedagogical suitability. In most studies, the participant took part in a single I-VR experience that was also short in duration. This presents several key challenges. Most importantly, the novelty of the I-VR technology itself may have impeded the learning experience of the user, especially if they had never used the technology before or were unfamiliar with it. This seemed to be demonstrated by Ray and Deb (2016) who found that in the initial sessions of I-VR learning, performance was on average poorer than those who underwent traditional teaching methods. It was only after the participants began to become familiar with the technology (on session number five) that learning surpassed the control group. Similarly, studies that allowed for extended exposure to I-VR (e.g. Akbulut et al. 2018; Alhalabi 2016; Molina-Carmona et al. 2018), either through free navigation, repeated sessions, or scheduled class time, tended to show an advantage of using I-VR over non-immersive or traditional methods. It is therefore important to address the potentially negative influence that I-VR's novelty as a learning tool may have, especially when outcomes are directly compared to another medium or method. Scepticism for media comparison studies was highlighted in the 1980s by Clark (1983), and then later re-addressed by Parong and Mayer (2018). As Parong and Mayer (2018) put it, the side-by-side comparison of two learning methods is an "apples-to-oranges type of comparison" (p. 788). This "apples-to-oranges" comparison is made starker when considering that I-VR is an unfamiliar technology to most in an educational capacity, and its pedagogical outcomes are being directly compared with familiar methods such as textbooks or lectures. It is important to consider that the novelty of HMDs and I-VR may hinder learning outcomes and classroom application, and it is therefore prudent to ensure that the degree of familiarity with I-VR technology is factored into any direct comparison with other methods. In practice, this could mean that participants require extended familiarisation trials or free navigation before the start of experimental studies as a means of mitigating against potential problems caused by technological novelty.

In addition to the short intervention and exposure time, most studies did not complement I-VR with an additional method of teaching or self-learning. The limited number of studies that did tended to utilise web-based textbooks or modules, as well as lectures and scheduled class time. Encouragingly, those studies that combined or supplemented traditional class-based learning with I-VR (e.g. Akbulut et al. 2018; Fogarty et al. 2017; Johnston et al. 2018; Sankaranarayanan et al. 2018; Yoganathan

et al. 2018) tended to show a learning advantage. This suggests that I-VR may be best employed as form of blended or multi-modal learning to supplement and complement class-based instruction (Garrison and Kanuka 2004). An area for investigation would be to examine I-VR's application longitudinally in a natural classroom environment. The current review contained only a limited number of studies that employed this approach, however, by implementing and studying how I-VR can be adopted and integrated into a module or syllabus, a clearer picture of its capabilities can emerge.

Learning theories ultimately provide a theoretical framework and foundation as how best to design educational interventions (Pritchard 2017; Schunk 2011). However, the review found that few papers explicitly state that any predetermined learning theory was used to advise the characteristics or methods of the study. Similar findings were reported in a systematic review by Radianti et al. (2020) examining I-VR use in higher education exclusively. Radianti et al.'s (2020) review found that in around 70% of the 38 studies included, no learning theory was mentioned as forming the foundation of the VR activity. Several studies have shown that educators regard clear pre-defined intervention characteristics and objectives as essential components of I-VR teaching (Fransson et al. 2020; Lee and Shea 2020). It is therefore essential that future experimental and applied research is based on a sound theoretical basis that can advise how the technology can be appropriately utilised and assessed.

Learning outcomes in I-VR

The current review examined learning outcomes across three domains: cognitive, procedural, and affective. By far the most popular domain was the teaching of cognitive skills and knowledge which made up 83% of the studies in the current review. Around half of those demonstrated a positive effect on learning when using I-VR over less immersive pedagogical methods. Most of the remaining studies showed no significant effect either way, with only a small number of papers exhibiting detrimental results. Researchers have suggested that the increased levels of immersive content that stimulate multisensory engagement can ultimately lead to more effective learning outcomes (Webster 2016). When this is implemented in cognitive learning activities that require a high degree of spatial understanding and visualisation (e.g. Maresky et al. 2019), I-VR can allow the user to gain insights that are difficult to reproduce in reality. This review has already identified scientific subjects such as biology and physics as promising avenues for educational I-VR implementation. However, other scientific disciplines that require abstract or conceptual understanding (e.g. chemistry, mathematics) could also benefit from the visualisation afforded by I-VR.

Studies that utilised I-VR for the teaching of procedural skills and knowledge produced encouraging results, with three of the four studies finding a significantly positive increase in learning (Bharathi and Tucker 2015; Sankaranarayanan et al. 2018; Yoganathan et al. 2018). Interestingly, two of the studies featured a transfer component by having the user first practice the procedure in I-VR, and then use this

form of experiential learning to complete a task in the real world. Yoganathan et al. (2018) had students practice how to tie a surgical knot in I-VR and then complete this task for real in-front of an expert. Sankaranarayanan et al. (2018) had medical students learn how to deal with an operating theatre fire by first practicing the procedure in I-VR, and then applying this knowledge to a mock emergency in a real operating room. Both studies found a positive effect of using I-VR as the training method by demonstrating improved results when performed in a real environment. These are encouraging findings for I-VR's effectiveness in psychomotor and procedural education, as there has been a degree of scepticism over whether I-VR simply produces a "getting good at the game" effect. For instance, Jensen and Konradsen (2018) point out that the honing of procedural skills within I-VR may simply lead to the participant becoming proficient when performing the task virtually, and this may not necessarily transfer to the real world. The current review has identified that the two procedural studies that implemented a transfer task did indeed demonstrate a significant benefit to using I-VR as an initial education method. This demonstrates that virtual training can be a successful precursor to implementation in the real world. This suggests that I-VR could be useful in educating students in dangerous vocational subjects such as electrical engineering without risk to themselves or others. However, this view is based on a small number of studies, and it is therefore important that future procedural tasks utilise a transfer activity to understand the potential scope and parameters surrounding I-VR training and real-world application.

Only one of the studies had a firm focus on the training of affective skills, namely by using I-VR as a way of teaching diagnostic interview techniques in a psychiatric setting (Gutiérrez-Maldonado et al. 2015). Although this study found no clear advantage to using I-VR, other research out with the domain of education has demonstrated promising results in utilising the technology for affective and behavioural change. This included applying the technology successfully in areas such as exposure therapy, anxiety disorder treatment, and empathy elicitation (Botella et al. 2017; Maples-Keller et al. 2017a, b; Schutte and Stilinović 2017). As a result of the strong non-educational body of literature suggesting I-VR can facilitate affective and behavioural change, future research should examine how this can be applied in an educational context, and then transferred to real-world scenarios. For instance, in their psychiatric interview experience, Gutiérrez-Maldonado et al. (2015) had users interact solely with virtual avatars, and did not have the participants demonstrate their learning with a real actor or patient. Therefore, just like with procedural skill acquisition, affective I-VR experiences should seek to understand how virtual learning can then be applied to real situations.

Implications and future practice

The current review has been able to identify a body of experimental and applied research that show the potential benefits of using I-VR in education. It has already been noted that I-VR has traditionally been used to teach low level or fundamental skills and knowledge, and has not necessarily been used to facilitate what Bloom et al. (1956) would consider higher level learning. This would include analysing and

evaluating experience. By expanding the definition of learning outcomes to encompass potential benefits such as an increased depth of understanding or the ability to identify complex themes, pedagogical practice can take advantage of the inherent strength of the medium. These should be comprehensively analysed to investigate learning outcomes that go beyond simple test scores.

The review has also been able to identify areas for improvement in future studies, which would address confounding variables and expand the scope of research. Firstly, as Allcoat and von Mühlenen (2018) suggest, the novelty of I-VR could hamper learning outcomes due to unfamiliarity with the technology. Therefore, it is important to factor in an extended familiarisation or free navigation period that would help alleviate this concern. Additionally, follow-up qualitative analysis such as interviews or focus groups could help explore the phenomenology or direct experience of using I-VR, and highlight concerns relating to unfamiliarity or technological anxiety. The biggest concern relating to the assessment instrumentation was the over reliance on the MCQ (62% of studies used it as the sole method of assessment). Although this method is deemed appropriate for assessing large amounts of surface knowledge, it may not reveal more nuanced forms of learning that extend beyond mere recall of information. Therefore, long form essay questions, oral examinations, or group discussions could be used to facilitate students' ability to present their in-depth understanding and applied knowledge. Future research must base the nature of these interventions on a sound theoretical framework. This would assist in identifying specific learning objectives and methods of assessments. An explicit theoretical approach was commonly lacking in the included studies.

I-VR has already been demonstrated to be an effective tool in non-pedagogical behaviour change, such as treating phobias, mental health conditions, or as a tool for rehabilitation (Botella et al. 2017; Maples-Keller et al. 2018; Ravi et al. 2017). Research should therefore concentrate on I-VR's potential as an acquisition tool for affective skills. There is already a strong body of evidence suggesting I-VR experiences can elicit high levels of empathetic response and perspective taking, and this should be explored within an educational context (Herrera et al. 2018; Shin 2018). For example, Dyer et al. (2018) used I-VR to allow health care students to take the perspective of an older patient with age-related medical conditions, which led to increased empathy. Future studies should investigate whether this perspective taking ability can lead to higher domains of learning, such as evaluating one's actions, applying problem solving skills, or creating new solutions as a direct result of the insights they received from I-VR. This will require researchers and instructors to carefully consider their tools for evaluation and assessment, perhaps incorporating mixed-methods to give a more holistic overview of learning achieved.

Conclusions

The current review found that I-VR conferred a learning benefit in around half of cognitive studies, especially where highly complex or conceptual problems required spatial understanding and visualisation. Although many studies found no significant benefit of using I-VR over less immersive technology, only a small number resulted

in detrimental effects on learning outcomes. However, the homogenous nature of assessment instrumentation, such as an over reliance on the MCQ may have stifled the ability for participants to demonstrate learning outcomes beyond low level cognitive knowledge. Short exposure times and isolated interventions could also pose a problem as the novel nature of the technology could negatively impact the amount of learning able to be imbibed. Encouragingly, most procedural tasks did show a benefit to utilising I-VR, and furthermore, there was evidence that virtual skill acquisition could be transferred successfully to real world problems and scenarios. The ability to repeatedly practice a procedure in a safe environment whilst expending little resources could be one of the most advantageous and intrinsic benefits of I-VR technology. Although affective behavioural change has been widely studied in non-educational applications of I-VR, the domain was underrepresented in the current review, and is an important area for future investigation.

Over the coming years, technological advancement, an increase in creative content, and the possibilities for instructors to create bespoke I-VR experiences will all contribute to I-VR's potential as a teaching tool. It is essential therefore that the implementation of such technology is based on sound theoretical and experimental evidence in order to ensure that the I-VR is utilised correctly, and to its full potential.

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Appendix

See Table 2.

Table 2 MERSQI quality appraisal scores for included studies

Study (year)	Design	Sampling	Type of data	Validity of instrument	Data analysis	Outcomes	Total
Harrington et al. (2018)	3	2	3	1	3	1.5	13.5
Yoganathan et al. (2018)	3	2.5	3	1	3	1.5	14
Makransky et al. (2017)	3	2	3	2	3	1.5	14.5
Greenwald et al. (2018)	2	2	3	0	3	1.5	11.5
Lamb et al. (2018)	3	2	3	0	3	1.5	12.5
Webster (2016)	2	2	3	1	3	1.5	12.5
Smith et al. (2018)	2	2	3	1	3	1.5	12.5
Ostrander et al. (2018)	3	2	3	0	3	1.5	12.5
Angulo and de Velasco (2013)	2	2	3	0	2	1.5	10.5
Stepan et al. (2017)	3	2	3	1	3	1.5	13.5
Sankaranarayanan et al. (2018)	2	2	3	1	3	1.5	12.5
Fogarty et al. (2017)	2	2	3	1	3	1.5	12.5
Rupp et al. (2019)	3	2	3	0	3	1.5	12.5
Bharathi and Tucker (2015)	3	2	3	0	3	1.5	12.5
Johnston et al. (2018)	2	2	3	0	3	1.5	11.5
Allcoat and von Mühlelen (2018)	3	2	3	1	3	1.5	13.5
Kozhevnikov et al. (2013)	3	2	3	2	3	1.5	14.5
Parong and Mayer (2018)	3	2	3	1	3	1.5	13.5
Olmos-Raya et al. (2018)	3	2	3	0	3	1.5	12.5
Akbulut et al. (2018)	2	2	3	0	3	1.5	11.5
Ray and Deb (2016)	3	2	3	0	2	1.5	11.5
Moro et al. (2017)	3	2	3	1	3	1.5	13.5
Maresky et al. (2019)	3	2	3	0	3	1.5	12.5
Madden et al. (2018)	3	2	3	0	3	1.5	12.5
Liou and Chang (2018)	3	2	3	0	3	1.5	12.5
Molina-Carmona et al. (2018)	3	2	3	2	3	1.5	14.5
Babu et al. (2018)	3	2	3	0	2	1.5	11.5
Alhalabi (2016)	2	2	3	0	3	1.5	11.5
Gutiérrez-Maldonado et al. (2015)	3	2	3	0	3	1.5	12.5
Average	2.7	2.0	3.0	0.6	2.9	1.5	12.7

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APPENDIX 2: IMPLEMENTING IMMERSIVE VIRTUAL REALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION: A QUALITATIVE STUDY OF INSTRUCTOR ATTITUDES AND PERSPECTIVES

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Implementing Immersive Virtual Reality

Implementing Immersive Virtual Reality in Higher Education: A Qualitative Study of Instructor Attitudes and Perspectives

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Abstract

The current study aimed to understand the attitudes and perceptions of higher education (HE) instructors who have previously used immersive virtual reality (I-VR) in teaching. This study employed a qualitative design by conducting semi-structured interviews with HE instructors from several disciplines and institutions. Using thematic analysis, five major themes were formulated. These included: (a) applications and benefits; (b) curriculum integration; (c) classroom logistics; (d) barriers to application; and (e) evaluation. Instructors were generally positive about using I-VR as a pedagogical tool, proposing a range of novel applications and uses. However, logistical and technical problems were prominent which made implementation and widescale adoption challenging. The implications of these prominent attitudes are discussed, alongside a range of practical recommendations for applied future practice.

Keywords: Higher Education; Virtual Reality; Attitudes; Qualitative Methods; Thematic Analysis

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Introduction

The use of technology as a pedagogical tool in higher education (HE) is not a new phenomenon. The applications and educational benefits of technology-aided instruction has been studied for more than half a century (Hooper and Rieber, 1995). In addition, research has attempted to identify the various attitudes, constructs, and factors that predict whether these systems will be embraced by users and facilitators (Davis, 1989). Where once desktop-computers and overhead projectors would have been regarded as highly innovative and novel teaching methods, the 'fourth industrial revolution' has heralded a new-age of pedagogical technologies with the potential to change how HE is delivered (Schwab, 2016, p. 11). One such technology that has attracted the interest of educators is Virtual Reality (VR). The multi-disciplinary nature of VR has made a clear and concise definition of its characteristics challenging (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018). However, the virtual world will typically be interactive in that it provides feedback as a result of actions taken by the users, as well as allowing for variables to be tested and manipulated (Sherman and Craig, 2018). VR has generally been broken down into two main categories: non-immersive, and immersive. Non-immersive VR allows the user to interact with a computer generated or virtual environment using a 2D screen, mouse, and keyboard (Lee, Wong and Fung, 2010). Conversely, Immersive Virtual Reality (I-VR) provides multisensory stimulation facilitated by the use of a head-mounted-display (HMD) (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018). The HMD completely immerses the user by surrounding the visual field with information from the virtual environment. In addition, 360° audio, haptic feedback, and limb tracking are commonly employed to increase the sense of presence in the virtual space.

Immersive Virtual Reality Applications in Higher Education

In recent years, the applied use of I-VR in HE has steadily expanded. A major factor is the increased availability of low-cost and accessible HMDs that are still

capable of displaying high-fidelity graphics (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018). A systematic review conducted by Radianti et al. (2020) found that science, engineering, and health-based subjects were the most common disciplines using I-VR as a pedagogical tool in HE. Additional research has also explored the specific educational outcomes that I-VR has been used to teach; the two most common of these being procedural skills and cognitive information (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018).

I-VR can be used in procedural skills training to teach a specific sequence of actions or movements that can then be transferred to real world scenarios (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018). This application of I-VR has most commonly been employed in the context of surgical or dental education (Lungu et al., 2021). The justification for this being that a novice can repeatedly practice dangerous or complex procedures on a virtual patient without risk to themselves or others. This is until a student reaches a certain level of competency where it would be safe for them to be exposed to a real patient. However, the use of I-VR to teach procedural skills has also been employed in HE more generally. For instance, Bharathi and Tucker (2015) developed a virtual engineering laboratory so that functional analysis tasks could be performed using an Oculus Rift HMD. The study demonstrated that students completed the assigned task significantly faster using the HMD than with a non-immersive 2D alternative. Furthermore, a post-experiment questionnaire indicated that students were more satisfied with their learning when using I-VR than the alternative. Procedural learning using I-VR has also been employed in a diverse range of other HE subjects from nursing (e.g. Farra, Smith and Ulrich, 2018) to computer science (Zhou et al., 2018).

I-VR has also been utilised in cognitive learning and attempts to teach theoretical concepts or declarative information, especially when this information is highly abstract or visual. For instance, the technology has been used to help HE

engineering students visualise spatial arrangements through interaction and manipulation using an Oculus Rift HMD (Fogarty, McCormick and El-Tawil, 2018). Similar applications have been employed in biological education by allowing students to visualise strands of DNA (Lamb et al., 2018) or the inside of a microscopic human cell (Johnston et al., 2018). Similar to the principals of procedural learning, virtual fieldtrips or excursions to inaccessible and dangerous locations (e.g. under the ocean) can also be undertaken using the technology (Markowitz et al., 2018). This facilitates the students' ability to construct their own cognitive understanding through experiential learning and perspective taking.

Instructor Attitudes Towards Immersive Virtual Reality

Understanding instructors' attitudes towards educational technology such as I-VR is essential in predicting whether it will be accepted as a teaching tool or not (Hussin, Jaafar and Downe, 2011). This encompasses one of the most fundamental tenets of behavioural psychology; attitudes ultimately influence behaviour (Ajzen and Fishbein, 1974). If researchers and institutions can identify and understand these attitudes, it becomes easier to facilitate I-VR's applied use in the classroom.

The first major barrier to understanding these attitudes is that research examining the perceptions of HE instructors is sparse. Most research has either focused on student attitudes towards I-VR (e.g. DePape et al., 2020) or that of schoolteachers or teachers-in-training (e.g. Cooper et al., 2019; Fransson, Holmberg and Westelius, 2020). Therefore, the degree to which the attitudes of high-school teachers are generalisable to HE institutions is difficult to ascertain. However, there may be common perceptions, barriers, and practicalities that underpin attitudes towards I-VR across educational establishments.

The most fundamental attitudes to understand are those concerned with *how* and *for what* I-VR should be used? Apart from experimental research examining learning outcomes in specific disciplines, little attention has been paid to HE lecturers' perceptions of I-VR application. However, schoolteachers have intimated that highly abstract or conceptual topics such as those taught in physics, mathematics, or geography could benefit from I-VR (Dengel, 2018; Serin, 2020). Chou and Hoisington (2018) extended this idea further by proposing that I-VR could be used for virtual fieldtrips and excursions which would allow students to experience simulated environments; an approach which would be especially practical if the environment was too inaccessible or dangerous to be visited in reality (Cooper et al., 2019). Although these attitudes do not pertain directly to HE, there is no reason to think that these potential applications could not be of benefit to university students also.

Although limited research has examined attitudes towards I-VR and syllabus integration, the general consensus is that its use should be aligned with specific goals and learning objectives. Fransson, Holmberg and Westelius (2020) conducted interviews with schoolteachers in Sweden and found they were adamant that I-VR should not be used as a 'flash-in-the-pan' (p. 3397). Instead it should be used to complement the predefined learning outcomes prescribed within the larger syllabus or module. As one teacher noted, this means constantly assessing I-VR's purpose as a learning tool in the classroom, to ensure it is enhancing learning as opposed to being used as a gimmick. Like any form of technology (e.g. computers, projectors, tablets), HE instructors must ensure that it is the learning outcome itself that dictates whether I-VR is used, and not the other way around (Picciano, 2009). To integrate I-VR in a spurious manner could render its application redundant regardless of whether this is done in a high-school, college, or university environment.

One prominent set of attitudes found among instructors relates to perceived internal and external barriers to I-VR implementation. In a study of HE computing instructors, Alfalah (2018) found that lecturers envisaged problems such as a lack of finance, training, resources, time, and administrative support. The need for professional development services prior to I-VR implementation was also deemed essential. Despite this, instructors were still positive about using I-VR as a pedagogical tool provided the requisite support was in place. Almost identical barriers have been identified by non-HE faculty, such as those in primary school and high school (Chou and Hoisington, 2018; Cooper et al., 2019; Fransson, Holmberg and Westelius, 2020). This would suggest that these barriers are universal and a common concern. As a result, practical solutions and recommendations could help alleviate these concerns across the board as opposed to within just a specific institution. It is therefore important to examine the perspectives and attitudes of instructors who have already implemented the technology in order to inform best practice and ensure I-VR's effectiveness as a pedagogical tool.

Current Study

Problem Statement

It is important to recognise that the literature examining I-VR's educational utility is typically drawn from lab-based studies. This presents problems as educational research conducted in a controlled setting may not account for the many practical issues encountered in a natural classroom environment. As Southgate and Smith (2017) state, classrooms are dynamic and unpredictable in ways that laboratories are not. Therefore, conclusions reached in lab-based I-VR research may not necessarily be ecologically valid. To bridge the gap between experimental and applied research, it is important to understand the attitudes and experiences of those who will ultimately facilitate I-VR's use in the classroom; the instructors.

Theoretical framework

As previously mentioned, research examining the attitudes of HE instructors has often been neglected; where attitudes have been gathered, these tend to come from the HE students undergoing the VR experience itself rather than the facilitator. This poses a concern because, as Alfalah (2018) intimates in the Educational VR System Model, the perceptions of students *and* instructors must operate in tandem to develop an effective I-VR system; the attitudes of one group cannot be considered without the other. Therefore, understanding how HE instructors perceive I-VR is essential for future practice.

Previous research has commonly employed quantitative techniques such as questionnaires to gather instructors' attitudes towards I-VR (e.g. Alfalah, 2018; Serin, 2020). Although this method can be useful, it is often unable to provide the depth of insight that qualitative approaches can. In addition, previous studies have often investigated the attitudes of educators who are not currently using I-VR in teaching, but might in future. This means instructors have limited experience of the practical considerations associated with implementation and adoption. Conversely, participants in the current study all have teaching experience using I-VR in HE, giving them an informed perspective of the technology.

Objectives

By conducting semi-structured interviews with HE instructors across various disciplines, the current study set out to examine several key areas:

- (A) Understand why instructors chose to use I-VR, and how they evaluated the experience.
- (B) Examine the kinds of tasks that I-VR was used for, and how it was integrated into curricula.

- (C) Understand the logistical considerations of implementing I-VR in the classroom.
- (D) Identify the barriers encountered whilst implementing I-VR in teaching.

Design and Methods

Participants

The study recruited lecturers currently employed in a teaching capacity at UK-based HE institutions. All participants were required to have experience of implementing I-VR as a pedagogical tool to deliver teaching to students. In this study, I-VR was defined as the viewing of 360° films or computer-generated imagery via a head-mounted-display (HMD), and implementation was defined as the applied use of the technology with students during lectures, seminars, or workshops. The use of I-VR for surgical or dental training was not included in the study as this represents a highly specialised and niche utilisation of the technology.

In total, seven participants (three male; four female) were included in the study. This sample size has been deemed sufficient for qualitative research employing thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2013; Fugard and Potts, 2015). Participants were drawn from three separate HE institutions in the United Kingdom. They had between 4 – 21 years of total teaching experience ($M = 10.6$; $SD = 6.8$). They had also been using I-VR in an educational capacity for between 1 – 5 years ($M = 2.1$; $SD = 1.2$). Participants were drawn from a range of subjects and faculties including science, health, and creative industries. An overview of participant demographics can be found in Table 1.

Table 1. Participant demographics and overview of VR application

Participant code	Gender	VR teaching experience (years)	Subject discipline(s)	HMD(s) used	Application
P1	Female	5	Psychology	Oculus Rift	VR used for experiential learning and perspective taking to teach psychological theories.
P2	Male	2	Creative industries	Oculus Rift	VR used to provide lecture capture facilitation as well as aiding revision sessions for assessments.
P3	Female	2	Nursing	Oculus Rift and Samsung Gear-VR	Combination of HMDs used to give students an embodied experience of what it is like to be a patient in a hospital.
P4	Female	2	Nursing	Oculus Rift	VR used for experiential learning and simulating sensory differences for first-responders and healthcare staff.
P5	Male	2	Health and life science	Samsung Gear-VR	Mobile-VR used to teach procedural knowledge needed in a healthcare setting.
P6	Male	1	Health and life sciences	Oculus Rift	Oculus Rift was used to teach students cognitive and declarative knowledge as it related to life sciences.
P7	Female	1	Biological sciences	HTC Vive	VR used as a way of visualising bone structures in the human body as part of a biology and physiology module.

Data collection and transcription

A semi-structured interview technique was employed in this study, based on the guidelines set out by Smith and Osborn (2003). This technique used the interview schedule as means of guiding the conversation as opposed to stringently adhering to a specific set of questions. Semi-structured interviews allowed for the researcher to follow-up on insights raised by the participant that were not considered whilst initially devising the interview schedule (Smith and Osborn, 2003). See Appendix for a copy of the associated prompts.

Each interview was conducted by the principal researcher (DH) to ensure continuity of style and approach. These were all conducted in a private room at the participant's own institution, lasting around 60 minutes. The entirety of the interview was recorded using a digital voice recorder. Upon completion recordings were transcribed verbatim by the principal researcher, and then imported to NVivo-12 to assist analysis.

Thematic analysis

Thematic analysis (TA) as set out by Braun and Clarke (2013) was used as the qualitative method of analysis. Due to limited qualitative research examining HE instructors' perceptions of I-VR, TA offers a theoretically flexible approach to data analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2013). An inductive, or bottom-up, approach was undertaken, in that no preconceived coding or thematic framework was used to instruct analysis. Codes were both semantically and latently coded, in that not only was the surface meaning provided by the interviewee noted, but also the researchers' interpretation of underlying concepts or ideas. The principal researcher was responsible for the generation of initial codes and early themes. These were then reviewed by the three co-authors who provided feedback and suggestions on how the codes corresponded to the proposed themes and wider dataset. A final meeting among all four researchers rearranged, split, and

discarded themes until a unanimous decision was reached as to the reliability of the final five overarching themes and associated quotations. Figure 1 provides a step-by-step account of each part of the analysis process.

Figure 1. Step-by-step process for thematic analysis

Findings and Discussion

By employing thematic analysis, five main themes were formulated. These included: (a) applications and benefits; (b) curriculum integration; (c) classroom logistics; (d) barriers to application; and (e) evaluation.

Applications and benefits

The applications and benefits theme concerns the kinds of tasks for which HE instructors used I-VR, as well as the perceived pedagogical benefits afforded by the technology. Instructors identified several domains where they felt the technology could be successfully integrated into their particular subject area.

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Experiential learning, or tasks that required someone to take the embodied perspective of another person were commonly considered to be uniquely suited to I-VR. Instructors remarked that the ability of I-VR to provide a first-hand perspective could increase empathetic response, and eventually lead to demonstrable changes in behaviour. Furthermore, instructors reinforced that this ability could not be replicated by using approaches such as didactic teaching. It is the immersive nature of the I-VR experience itself that elicits a response that can ultimately assist in changing attitude and behaviours. Instructors made several remarks regarding this:

“It gives them a first-person perspective of what is going on, rather than in a traditional lecture where it goes in one ear and out the other. This puts them in a situation where they can relate to what is happening.”

Participant 5.

Many instructors hoped that by allowing their students to embody the lived experience of another, I-VR would elicit an empathetic response. Some instructors even said that their students displayed positive changes in behaviour and their applied practice. For instance, nursing students became more aware of sensory processing differences in their patients as a result of an I-VR experience, and so changed how they interact and convey information. Far from being merely anecdotal, research in the field of psychology has demonstrated the technology's ability to increase empathetic response. For instance, Herrera et al. (2018) found that I-VR could facilitate long-lasting and demonstrable attitude change by undergoing an emotionally salient experience (i.e. homelessness) in I-VR. Therefore, the desire of instructors to use the technology to facilitate affective learning does seem to be consistent with the findings of previous empirical research.

Using I-VR to provide affective learning and first-hand perspective taking was not the only pedagogical application identified by instructors. Several participants used or promoted the technology for cognitive learning purposes. This included applications such as teaching theory, revising material, or visualising abstract or conceptual problems. Instructors felt that I-VR could help solidify theoretical concepts that were first learning in class using traditional teaching methods. As one instructor remarked:

“We would use VR at the end which [...] encapsulated all the theory and hands-on stuff that we done.”

Participant 3.

Hussein and Nätterdal (2015) made a similar observation by proposing that VR could help bridge the gap between acquired theoretical understanding and applied use. An example of this type of application was provided by an instructor in the current study who used I-VR to aid student revision. They would film 360° videos of important seminars, workshops, and group activities that could then be reviewed by students at a later date provided they had access to an HMD. This would allow the student to revise and solidify theoretical concepts learned in class in an immersive manner, and then apply this understanding to examinations, essays, or assessments. Using I-VR as an educational revision tool appears to be a relatively novel application that has rarely been mentioned in previous studies. However, experimental research does suggest that it has the potential to be an effective use of the technology. For instance, Molina-Carmona et al. (2018) found that multimedia engineering students who revised for an examination using I-VR had significantly better learning outcomes than those who used a non-immersive alternative (i.e. a desktop computer).

Curriculum integration

A recurrent theme in the data was that of curriculum integration, or how educators envisage I-VR being used and applied within the syllabus. As Southgate and Smith (2017) previously highlighted, this is a component of pedagogical I-VR research that has been often neglected. The most prominent attitude of participants was that I-VR should be integrated into the curriculum as a form of blended or multimodal learning. As Garrison and Kanuka (2004) note, blended learning combines traditional methods of teaching with technology to achieve a set learning outcome. Technology does not replace existing methods, but rather complements and supplements them. The current study found that instructors would utilise a range of didactic and technological approaches to achieve a set learning outcome in their classes. Instructors were keen to stress that it was important to integrate the I-VR experience into pre-existing methods of teaching.

“Education works that way. We have VLEs; we have online resources; we have Padlet; we have Turning Point. We have all these different technologies, that hopefully enhance the learning experience. VR should be used in that capacity. It should not be a replacement; it should be an enhancement.”

Participant 2.

Instructors also tended to be cautious about integrating I-VR as a stand-alone method of teaching in their curriculum. Although the consensus was that I-VR could be effective when applied properly, it could not be seen as applicable in all scenarios. One participant summed up this attitude succinctly when they noted:

“(VR) is not a panacea, but there is certainly a place for it.”

Participant 1.

One of the implications of I-VR being viewed as a supplementary learning tool was that instructors acknowledged that careful planning had to be undertaken to ensure that the technology was appropriately integrated into the course. As one instructor remarked:

“It’s not a toy. So, for us it has to be integrated into the teaching, it has to mean something. It has to reinforce the session that we use. So, it was very carefully planned.”

Participant 7.

These attitudes are consistent with what Picciano (2009) termed as ‘blending with purpose’ (p. 7). This approach places learning outcomes as the driving force behind the choice of teaching materials used, as opposed to the technology itself dictating the objective. Instructors explicitly stated that to use I-VR without a predefined pedagogical purpose could impair the learning process. This was especially true if the technology was shoehorned into parts of the curriculum where its use was not warranted. Prior research in other institutions have reported similar attitudes. For instance, schoolteachers were vehement that I-VR should only be used for a specific purpose, and as part of a well-structured and designed lesson (Fransson, Holmberg and Westelius, 2020). Simply using the technology because of its novelty, or without a predefined objective could render its use redundant. In practice, this means that the technology should be used only when it can provide a unique perspective on a given topic. As a result, I-VR is not suitable for all subject areas or disciplines, and discretion must be exercised by module coordinators and instructors as to whether its use will confer an educational benefit for their students or not.

Classroom logistics

Classroom logistics refers to how the instructor behaves and organises the I-VR lesson itself. This includes considerations such as the physical space, classroom management, and the need for additional support from members of staff and faculty.

Most instructors referred to the fact that they did not have access to a dedicated I-VR space for teaching and had to manage with normal classrooms or lecture halls. This was often due to stringent room bookings, limited space on city campuses, or as a result of the number of students in the class itself. This could constrain the types of I-VR experiences that instructors could offer to students. For example, if chairs could not be moved, I-VR applications that required locomotion or extended movement were unable to be used. Instead, only experiences that required the student to remain in a seated position could be employed in teaching. As a result of these logistical considerations, a desire for a dedicated I-VR space or lab was almost universal. However, as instructors noted, universities often lack the resources or physical space to provide such a facility. Therefore, it is often the case that instructors had to work within the confines of their physical environment to deliver I-VR teaching.

A second logistical consideration was the number of students typically in each class. Most instructors noted that large class sizes created logistical problems in organising and managing the lesson, as well as often needing to utilise additional staff members to assist. Instructors mentioned that they would often recruit other members of their faculty to be present in the classroom during I-VR lessons. For those who were unable to do this, they often conveyed the attitude that this was indeed a necessity for future practice.

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“I guess what we have learnt is that you need enough people in the room to be able to support them (the students).”

Participant 4.

Instructors also noted that they would need to consider how to manage the classroom appropriately to facilitate both traditional and I-VR learning. For instance, often classes would need to be broken down into multiple sub-groups to accommodate all students and give them a chance to undergo the I-VR experience.

“When we have three groups, all of them can’t use it (VR) at the same time. So, we have to break down the sessions. We have to work out, ‘right, one group can do the VR activity in the morning, the other in the afternoon.’ [...] The set-up time and planning is huge.”

Participant 3.

A common attitude was that I-VR can often be cumbersome to use in an applied setting, and additional staff members and appropriate planning is essential to successful implementation. Instructors therefore must give as much consideration to classroom management and logistics as they do to curriculum integration.

Barriers to application

One of the most common attitudes were the barriers encountered whilst using I-VR. These impaired the ability of the instructor to utilise the technology fully and

are represented in two distinct subthemes based upon the nature and source of the barrier: institutional; or second-order.

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Institutional barriers

Institutional barriers relate to the attitudes and perceptions that instructors had towards their institution's facilitation of I-VR teaching. Instructors were generally not encouraged by the level of financial backing, investment or support they received from their own university. Instructors commonly remarked that although their institution was receptive towards using I-VR in teaching, they seldom made the financial investment needed. This made acquisition of headsets, computers, and software licences challenging.

"If the university want to go down this line then they will need to spend money, and they are not willing to."

Participant 5.

The problem of procuring financial backing for I-VR is not exclusive to the current study and appear to be prevalent among instructors and educators (Chou and Hoisington, 2018; Cooper et al., 2019). Specifically, both the current study and existing literature found that instructors worried about acquiring funds from their institution to purchase HMDs and other necessary equipment.

When instructors were asked why institutions would not financially invest, many said that this was due to scepticism regarding I-VR's longevity and economic feasibility. As one participant remarked:

"People are saying 'it is just a fad.' Therefore, they are not prepared to put any level of investment in [...] for something that may or may not be just a fad."

Participant 2.

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Interestingly, some instructors were understanding of their universities' reticence to make the financial injection necessary. If indeed I-VR fails to have a long-term future as a pedagogical method, universities may fail to see a tangible return on their investment. As one instructor noted, institutions must weigh up the potential risks of making such a large investment.

The most common barrier resulting from a lack of institutional investment was obtaining enough headsets for the entire class. This often meant that HMDs had to be shared and rotated among multiple students, limiting the amount of time each person had with the technology.

"It presents quite a lot of logistical problems for looking at equipment. Trying to get 230 students through the experience of using VR is quite a challenge [...] So our main problem is getting equipment especially when we have only six headsets at the moment."

Participant 3

Additionally, instructors remarked that many applications of I-VR made the presumption that students themselves had access to the technology, which was often not the case. This meant that students commonly could not access I-VR experiences outside of designated class times. One possible solution would be to implement an approach similar to that of Olmos et al. (2018) referred to as bring-your-own-device (BYOD). BYOD involves students using their own smartphones to view I-VR material by attaching them to a mobile-HMD such as the Google Cardboard (Olmos et al., 2018). However, this may cause additional problems such as insurance and liability concerns if a device is broken during classroom use. Additionally, it assumes that all students have a compatible phone that is capable of being inserted into a mobile-VR headset.

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Problems resulting from the institutions' IT and software systems was another common impediment. Ports being blocked by a firewall, poor internet connectivity, and restrictions accessing common VR platforms like Steam and Unity were noted. Even if these problems could be addressed, some educators had serious concerns that most universities do not have the technical infrastructure necessary to adopt I-VR. For instance, one instructor noted that they recorded lectures or seminars on a 360° camera for students to watch. However, a traditional one-hour lecture could generate a file in excess of 50-gigabytes. The instructor noted that no current university platform such as the virtual learning environment (VLE) could accommodate files of that size to be uploaded or shared.

A lack of institutional investment and technological infrastructure are two of the issues raised by instructors in the study. Similar to Alfalah (2018), instructors were also concerned with the lack of an institutional support network and administrative guidance. This often led to instructors having nowhere to turn if they ran into problems using the technology. This led to nearly all participants stating that they were forced to use their "own initiative" when implementing I-VR into their teaching. This often consisted of trying various approaches to I-VR teaching to see what worked best. Based on these findings, it seems prudent to suggest that a centralised support network is an essential component of efficient I-VR implementation. A pooling together of knowledge from across the university, even in an informal manner, could give instructors the support and guidance they need to facilitate the technology in their classrooms.

Regardless of the institutional barriers encountered, nearly all instructors agreed that it would take a shift in educational policy to accommodate I-VR in HE. This means that faculty, institutions, government, and third-parties will all need to

interact to provide the conditions necessary for widespread adoption of the technology. For instance, barriers related to technical infrastructure cannot be solved by the institution alone and will require input and guidance from others to find efficient solutions.

Second-order barriers

Ertmer (1999) defined second-order barriers as those that are intrinsic to the individual themselves such as beliefs around self-efficacy and technological confidence. It is well established that these internal factors can influence the behavioural intention to use and adopt technology such as I-VR (Davis, 1989).

Although instructors noted that I-VR was a novel teaching method, they often remarked that their own lack of technical skills or proficiency was a barrier to upscaling or utilisation. Surprisingly, many of the instructors interviewed confessed to not being technically savvy themselves but enjoyed using I-VR regardless. Statements like "I'm not technical" and "I'm a complete novice" occurred frequently. Several studies have identified a lack of self-efficacy and technical skills as being a source of apprehension among schoolteachers and HE instructors (Alfalah, 2018; Fransson, Holmberg and Westelius, 2020). Therefore, appropriate institutional support and training is essential to give instructors the skills and knowledge necessary to implement I-VR effectively. Fortunately, as Lee and Shea (2020) demonstrate, it does not take long for individuals to develop the skills required when quality training is offered.

Self-efficacy and a lack of technological confidence was also cited as a reason for sub-optimal VR experiences being used in the classroom. Instructors remarked that they did not know where to find bespoke material that was specifically relevant to their lesson. As a result, a few instructors attempted to create their own-tailor made I-VR experiences. Unfortunately, a lack of confidence and

proficiency using 360° cameras, editing software, creation suites, and HMDs meant that this was extremely challenging. It is therefore important to note that a lack of self-efficacy does not merely impact on the ability to use HMDs, but rather extends to the quality of I-VR experiences that are able to be offered to students. As a result, a holistic approach to professional development is needed to cover all aspects of training necessary to implement I-VR. This should include both the technical and pedagogical skills necessary to apply the technology.

Evaluation

Instructors emphasised the importance of evaluating the I-VR teaching in their institution. Nearly all instructors interviewed thought it was important to gather feedback on the students' experience of I-VR learning through formal (e.g. questionnaires) or informal means (e.g. verbal feedback). The outcome of the evaluative process was important in deciding whether I-VR teaching was worth continuing to pursue. Students generally enjoyed using the technology which created excitement, heightened motivation, and resulted in the achievement of set learning outcomes. As one instructor noted, this influenced the decision to continue using I-VR:

“We would love for it to continue because it has been evaluated so well. It just added a different vibe to the room. They were excited. They were looking forward to it.”

Participant 1.

These attitudes are similar to a number of other studies that have investigated how instructors perceive student engagement (Serin, 2020; Lee and Shea, 2020). Encouragingly, when students themselves are asked to self-report their level of enjoyment whilst using I-VR, they commonly express similar attitudes (e.g. Fogarty, McCormick and El-Tawil, 2018) with Heafner (2004) also

concluding that anecdotal and empirical research has found that motivation and engagement through technology can have a positive impact on student attainment. Similarly, in the present study, instructors were keen to emphasise that their evaluation showed tangible benefits to student learning. In one case, students were able to apply what they learned as a result of I-VR to a real healthcare setting:

“For those students who went out to practice recently having used VR, the provisional feedback has been that they have been able to implement things already. Seeing the results, it has definitely been worth it.”

Participant 3.

Although students enjoyed I-VR sessions, instructors did witness some trepidation on the part of the user. Sometimes students were self-conscious using the I-VR equipment in front of their peers. This was often the result of their physical actions (e.g. arm movements) in VR being without context to an outside observer. This sometimes led to embarrassment and a failure to interact fully with the technology, especially in front of large classes. A potential solution was to display what the user saw in VR onto a screen so that everyone else could watch it. This would mean that the observer could witness what the user was doing, providing a point of reference for their physical movements. Additionally, smaller class sizes or the ability to use the HMD privately could help alleviate some of the anxiety associated with I-VR use.

Instructors also raised concerns that some students reported cybersickness, or the inability to use I-VR due to medical conditions. This is a common problem that has been identified already as a barrier towards educational integration of HMDs and associated technology (Jensen and Konradsen, 2018; Southgate and

Smith, 2017). It is imperative that future practice factors in these considerations and makes alternative methods of learning available for students who cannot partake in I-VR.

Conclusion

Using a qualitative methodology, the current study set-out to understand the attitudes and experience of HE instructors towards I-VR. Instructors proposed a range of benefits and novel applications for I-VR teaching such as embodied experience and perspective taking. Furthermore, instructors expressed that I-VR teaching was evaluated well by the students who participated. However practical barriers relating to financial backing, institutional support, and self-efficacy were common. This impacted how effectively the technology could be implemented in their respective subjects or departments. Universities will therefore need to invest both financially in the technology as well as in staff training and support to help alleviate some of the most important obstacles. Ultimately, it will be this response that will dictate whether I-VR has a long-term future in HE.

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